

BAHIR DAR UNIVERSITY
COLLEGE OF AGRICULTURE AND ENVIRONMENTAL SCIENCES
POSTGRADUATE PROGRAM

**EFFECT OF INOCULATION AND SOIL AMENDMENTS ON BIOLOGICAL NITROGEN
FIXATION AND CROP YIELD OF HARICOT BEAN (*PHASEOLUS VULGARIS L.*) IN NORTH
WESTERN ETHIOPIA**

M.Sc. Thesis

By

Fekadu Tiruneh kassa

June, 2024

Bahir Dar, Ethiopia

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M.Sc. Thesis

**Submitted to Post Graduate Program of, College of Agriculture and Environmental Science, Bahir Dar
University in Partial Fulfilment of the Requirements for the
Degree of Master of Science in Soil Science**

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THESIS APPROVAL SHEET

As a member of the board of examiner of Master of Science thesis, open defense examination, we have read and evaluated this thesis prepared by Mr. Fekadu Tiruneh Kassa entitled “**Effect of inoculation and soil amendments on biological nitrogen fixation and crop yield of haricot bean (*phaseolus vulgaris L.*) in north-western Ethiopia**” We hereby certify that the thesis is accepted for fulfilling the requirement of the award of Master of Science (M.Sc.) in Soil Science.

Board of Examiners

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DECLARATION

This is to certify that this thesis entitled “**Effect of Inoculation and Soil Amendments on Biological Nitrogen Fixation and Crop Yield of Haricot Bean (*Phaseolus Vulgaris L.*) in North Western Ethiopia**” submitted in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the award of the degree of Master of Science in “Soil Science” to the Graduate Program of College of Agriculture and Environmental Sciences, Bahir Dar University by Mr. Fekadu Tiruneh Kassa (ID. No. BDU1300485 R) is an authentic work carried out by him under our guidance. The matter embodied in this title work has not been submitted earlier for award of any degree or diploma to the best of our knowledge and belief.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS /ACRONYMS

AAS	Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer
ADSWE	Amhara Design and Supervision Works Enterprise
ANOVA	Analysis of Variance
ANRS	Amhara National Regional State
ATA	Agricultural Transformation Agency
Av. P	Available Phosphorus
Bd	Bulk Density
BDU	Bahir Dar University
BNF	Biological Nitrogen Fixation
CEC	Cation exchange capacity
CIMMYT	International Maize and Wheat Improvement Center
Cmol _c	Centimole charge
CSA	Central Statistical Agency
CV	Coefficient of Variation
DAP	Diammonium Phosphate
DTPA	Diethylene Triamine Penta acetic Acid
E.C	Ethiopian Calendar
EC	Electrical Conductivity
ECX	Ethiopia Commodity Exchange
EPPA	Ethiopian Pulses Profile Agency
ETB	Ethiopian Birr
EIAR	Ethiopian Institute of Agricultural Research

EthioSIS	Ethiopian Soil Information System
FAO	Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations
GIS	Geographic Information System
GPS	Global Position System
Ha	Hectare
Kg/ha	Kilogram per Hectare
LSD	Least Significant Deference
M.a.s.l	Meter Above Sea Level
mm	milimeter
mg	Milligram
MoA	Ministry of Agriculture
MRR	Marginal rate of return
MT	Metric tone
MWAO	Mecha Woerda Agricultural Office
NGOs	Non-Governmental Organization
OC	Organic Carbon
OM	Organic Matter
PD	Particle Density
pH	Power of Hydrogen
RCBD	Randomized Complete Block Design
SAS	Statistical Analysis Software
SD	Standard Deviation
SE	Standard Error of Measurement
SNNPR	Southern Nations Nationalities and Peoples Region
SPSS	Statistical Package for Social Science
t	Tonne
Tg	Teragram
TN	Total Nitrogen
TP	Total Porosity

USD	United States Dollar
USDA	United State Department of Agriculture
WoRDA	Woreda Office of Rural Development and Agriculture
WRB	World Reference Base
⁰ C	Degree Celsius

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ABSTRACT

*Legume-based cropping systems are regarded as a sustainable method to reduce the need for external nitrogen fertilizers. Haricot bean is one of the most economically important pulse crops cultivated in north western Ethiopia. However, the average yield reported remains significantly below its potential. This is partly due to poor soil fertility management and inappropriate agronomic packages considered to be among the major production constraint. Hence, this experiment was conducted to determine the effect of inoculation and soil amendments on biological nitrogen fixation and Crop Yield of Haricot Bean (*Phaseolus vulgaris* L.) in North western Ethiopia. The experiment was conducted in Koga irrigation scheme during two cropping rainfed seasons (2021-2022). Treatments consisted of three rates of nitrogen (0, 10 and 20 kg ha⁻¹), two rates of lime (0 and 2 ton ha⁻¹) and three strain types of rhizobia variety (0, HAMBI3570 and HAMBI3562), SER-119 haricot bean variety in factorial combinations were laid out in randomized complete block design with three replications to evaluate their effects on soil physicochemical properties and Haricot bean yield and yield components. Data on soil, phenological, biological nitrogen fixation, yield and yield components were collected and analysed by SAS 9.4 software. The result showed that the interaction effect of different soil amendments had a significant variation in all treatments. Thus, soil physico-chemical properties significantly ($P < 0.001$) varied on pH, EA, OC, OM, TN, EC, CEC, SIN, AV.P and agronomic parameters of days to 50% flowering, days 90% maturity, plant height, number of primary branches, total number of nodule, effective number of nodule, percent of nodule effectiveness, number of pods per plant, number of seed per pod, hundred seed weight, leaf number per plant, leaf area per plant, leaf area index, grain yield, biomass yield, harvest index, straw yield. The control plot soil physico-chemical properties at the main cropping season in experimental site indicated that soil texture=clay, bulk density=1.27, Total porosity=52.2, Soil moisture content soil=22.33, pH=5.17, exchangeable acidity=2.65, Organic Carbon =1.63, organic matter=2.8, total nitrogen=0.186, Electrical conductivity=0.050, CEC=24.25, SIN=60.83, Available P=9.14, were recorded. The results of the study shows combined application of lime, starter nitrogen and rhizobia*

application increases total porosity by 9.05, soil moisture content by 9.31%, soil pH by 0.96 units, organic carbon by 0.88%, organic matter by 1.53%, total nitrogen by 0.046%, CEC by 14.91 units and available P by 22.86 units and decreased bulk density by 0.24 units, exchangeable acidity by 2.4 units and electrical conductivity by 0.018 units compared to the control. Moreover, the combined application of these treatments significantly ($p < 0.001$) increased plant height, number of primary branches, total number of nodule, effective number of nodule, percent of nodule effectiveness, number of pods per plant, number of seed per pod, hundred seed weight, leaf area per plant, leaf area index, grain yield, biomass yield, harvest index, straw yield. Similarly, the combined application of lime $2 \text{ ton ha}^{-1} + 20 \text{ kg ha}^{-1}$ + starter nitrogen + HAMBI3570 increased Haricot bean yield by 510.6% compared to control. However, the economic analysis showed that the combination of lime $2 \text{ ton ha}^{-1} + 20 \text{ kg ha}^{-1}$ starter nitrogen + HAMBI3570 gave the highest net-benefit (259,426.2 ETB ha^{-1}) with an acceptable MRR of 25,297.28%. Thus, it can be concluded that the combination application of lime $2 \text{ ton ha}^{-1} + 20 \text{ kg ha}^{-1}$ starter nitrogen + HAMBI3570 to be proved superior with respect to economic advantage in the North western Ethiopia.

Key words: Haricot bean, lime application, Bio fertilizer, rhizobia bacteria, root nodulation, starter nitrogen rate, soil fertility, Acid soils, Yield and Yield components, partial budget analyses

CHAPTER 1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Background and Justification

Globally, soils face an average annual nitrogen deficit of $18.7 \text{ kg ha}^{-1} \text{ y}^{-1}$ and a phosphorus deficit of $5.1 \text{ kg ha}^{-1} \text{ y}^{-1}$. These deficits pose significant challenges to maintaining soil fertility and ensuring sustainable agricultural productivity (Srivastava *et al.* , 2014). Moreover, declining soil fertility caused by nutrient mining is the leading cause of decreased yield and low per capita food production in Africa, particularly in Eastern Africa, leading to an annual loss of 41 kg of nitrogen, 4 kg of phosphorous and 31 kg of potassium per hectare (Kipngetich Chumo, 2021). Macronutrient and micronutrients prone to deficiency due to soil degradation which affects crop growth leading to low production (Lal, 2009). In Ethiopia, soil nutrient depletion is a significant challenge, attributed to factors such as population pressure, free grazing of animals, soil erosion, nutrient mining, and limited input use, posing a major obstacle to land productivity (Alemine Amare and Melkamu Alemayehu, 2020). The national estimate for nutrient depletion in Ethiopia is $122 \text{ kg N ha}^{-1} \text{ y}^{-1}$ and $13 \text{ kg P ha}^{-1} \text{ y}^{-1}$ (Zenebe Adimassu *et al.*, 2018). In the northwestern region of Ethiopia, soil erosion is rampant, with annual soil loss reaching up to $300 \text{ tons ha}^{-1} \text{ y}^{-1}$ in individual cultivated fields (Mitiku Haile *et al.*, 2016)

Soil fertility and plant nutrition, closely interconnected, focus on the forms and availability of nutrients in soils, their movement to roots, uptake by plants, and nutrient utilization within plants (Wani *et al.*, 2018). Maintaining soil fertility is crucial for increasing agricultural production to meet the needs of a rapidly growing population. Without sustained soil fertility, achieving optimal, long lasting, and self-sufficient crop production is unattainable (Abebe Lakew, 2015). Soil fertility amendment practice has been in place in Ethiopia since the 1970s. Approximately 40% of Ethiopia's total land area is acidic, affecting 28% of all agricultural land and significantly affecting crop productivity (Endrias Geta *et al.*, 2013). Acidic soils are particularly prevalent in the highlands with the highest annual rainfall, especially in the southwest and northwest regions dominated by Nitisols and Alfisols (Lulseged Tamene *et al.*, 2017). The acidic nature of these soils, particularly in areas with low nutrient content, contributes to poor yields. Soil acidity negatively affects various stages of haricot bean growth, including the legume-rhizobium symbiosis, microorganism activity, plant root growth, and nutrient absorption, ultimately limiting productivity (Ermias Abate *et al.*, 2013).

To address soil acidity, the common practice involves surface lime application, raising soil pH and creating a suitable environment for rhizobium survival (Girma Wolde *et al.*, 2017). Integrated soil fertility management at the farm level is deemed essential to enhance overall system productivity, improve yields, and ensure food security (Nelson Mango *et al.*, 2018). Despite the significant role played by synthetic fertilizers, the escalating demand for nitrogen in food production poses a challenge. The overuse of agrochemicals further jeopardizes soil health and agricultural sustainability. To address this issue, one viable solution is biological nitrogen fixation (BNF). Maximizing nitrogen fixation in crop legumes is essential for boosting productivity, enhancing seed protein content, and conserving soil nitrogen (Srivastava *et al.* , 2014). Legumes, such as haricot beans, are particularly advantageous for smallholder production systems due to their ability to enhance nitrogen fixation, improve soil fertility, and provide income within a short life cycle of less than three months (Mukankusi *et al.*, 2018).

More than 60% of Earth's fixed nitrogen results from BNF, making it increasingly urgent to optimize BNF in agriculture to meet the growing demand for food production (Abdoulaye Soumare *et al.*, 2020). Increasing legume productivity becomes crucial for achieving food security (Abera Habete and Tadele Buraka, 2016). To sustain yields and attain food security, it is imperative to explore cost-effective nitrogen sources (Otieno *et al.*, 2009). However, rhizobia strains in the soil often encounter various stresses that can impact their growth and nitrogen fixation capabilities (Chala Debela *et al.*, 2021). The symbiosis between rhizobia and legumes significantly contributes to global nitrogen production, accounting for 50% of the total biological species N₂ fixation annually worldwide (Tola Yosef, 2018). Biological nitrogen fixation emerges as a crucial alternative to expensive synthetic fertilizers, especially for resource-poor farmers (Prasad *et al.*, 2015).

Pulses, including haricot beans, play pivotal roles in economic, food, and nutrition security globally. Increased production and supply of pulses meet rising demands in local and international markets, boosting smallholder farmers' incomes (Chilot Yirga *et al.*, 2019). Haricot beans are recognized as the 2nd most important grain legume cash crop in Ethiopia, contributing significantly to human nutrition, food security, and livestock feed (Rawal and Navarro., 2019).

Despite its global production of about 25 million metric tons, Ethiopia is contributing 6 million metric tons, haricot bean productivity in Ethiopia has not reached its full potential. Limited research

has been conducted, and the crop has not been adequately introduced to certain regions, hindering its full utilization (CSA, 2011; Walegn Worku., 2015). Exploring alternative nitrogen-fixing crops like haricot beans is crucial to improve soil fertility, increase crop production, and enhance farmers' livelihoods. Investigating the effects of inoculation and other soil amendments on biological nitrogen fixation and haricot bean productivity is essential for sustainable agriculture in Ethiopia, where the use of bio-fertilizers is still a relatively new technology.

1.2. Statement of the Problem

The agricultural sector plays a substantial role, contributing approximately one-third to the global gross domestic product. Particularly vital in Sub-Saharan Africa, agriculture provides direct or indirect support to nearly all rural households (Diao *et al.*, 2010). The challenge of feeding a global population projected to reach 9.7 billion by 2050, with Ethiopia's population expected to grow from 127,632,823 in 2023 to 172 million by 2050 (Alemayhu Bekele and Yihunie Lakew., 2014; UN, 2023) presents a significant dilemma. The imperative is to increase agricultural production given the limitations of limited farm sizes and the need to feed a rapidly growing population. As the world grapples with the task of feeding an ever-expanding population, the necessity to enhance agricultural productivity becomes paramount. Agriculture in the coming decade must produce more food with less land, efficiently utilizing natural resources while minimizing environmental impact (Hobbs and Gupta., 2008).

In developing countries like Ethiopia, improving rural food security and promoting food system development are major challenges (Mesfin Hailemariam and Abush Tesfaye., 2018). Hindrances such as the absence of effective and stress-tolerant indigenous rhizobia, high fertilizer costs, and the intensification of agriculture coupled with reduced farm sizes impede crop production in smallholder farms. Many farmers in these regions cannot afford chemical fertilizers, and the use of commercial rhizobia inoculants is limited (Mesfin Hailemariam and Abush Tesfaye., 2018). Tropical soils often suffer from nitrogen deficiency due to leaching, denitrification, low application rates, and soil degradation (Bruno Lima *et al.*, 2016).

Soil acidity is a global concern, particularly in the highlands of Ethiopia, and poor soil fertility poses significant constraints to crop productivity. In leguminous crops, reduced nitrogen fixation due to biological and environmental factors contributes to low productivity (Ayalew Addis *et al.*, 2020).

Soil acidity negatively affects the growth and performance of haricot beans, resulting in a substantial yield loss of about 60% (Daba Etana and Tolossa Ameyu.,2021)

To address soil deficiencies, modern agriculture heavily relies on industrial nitrogen fertilizers, contributing to environmental concerns. The production and delivery of nitrogen fertilizer require substantial fossil fuel, with industrial nitrogen fixation alone accounting for 50% of fossil fuel used in agriculture. The release of carbon dioxide (CO₂) and nitrous oxide (NO_x) during these processes contributes to the greenhouse effect. Moreover, synthetic fertilizers are largely inefficient, with 30% to 50% of applied nitrogen fertilizer lost to leaching (Graham and Vance., 2003). These fertilizers do not improve soil physical structure or enhance soil biological activity, necessitating additional measures to maintain soil fertility (Tola Yosef, 2018). Soil amendments are recognized for promoting sustainable agriculture by enhancing crop productivity without disrupting the agroecosystem (Bita Naseri, 2019).

Haricot bean, one of the most economically important legume crops in Ethiopia, has not reached its full potential in terms of production and productivity. Addressing the yield gap and soil nitrogen issues could be achieved by harnessing soil bacteria involved in the biological nitrogen fixation process, especially with legume crops like haricot beans (Chala Debela *et al.*, 2021). The study focuses on the combined effects of inoculants and soil amendments on biological nitrogen fixation and crop yield of haricot beans under the Koga irrigation scheme, where research on this specific combination is currently lacking.

1.3. Objectives of the Study

1.3.1. General Objective

- To evaluate the effects of inoculants and soil amendments on soil physico chemical properties, biological nitrogen fixation and haricot beans yield and yield components under Koga irrigation scheme northwestern Ethiopia.

1.3.2. Specific Objectives

- To evaluate the effects of different type inoculants and soil amendments on soil physicochemical properties in the Koga irrigation scheme.

- Examine the effects of inoculants and soil amendments on the extent of biological nitrogen fixation of haricot beans.
- Evaluate the combined effects of rhizobia, lime, and starter nitrogen on yield and yield components of haricot beans.
- Investigate the financial profitability of the different soil amendments

1.4. Research Questions

Based on the identified problems and the review of related literature, this study aims to address the following questions:

- How other soil amendments improve soil physicochemical properties?
- Which soil amendment is most effective for nitrogen fixation in haricot bean production?
- How does the interaction of rhizobia, lime, and starter nitrogen affect biological nitrogen fixation and the yield of haricot beans?
- Is the combined application of rhizobia, lime, and starter nitrogen economically viable?

1.5. Hypothesis

- The application of biofertilizer, lime, starter nitrogen, and their combinations will significantly improve soil physicochemical properties.
- Inoculants and soil amendments could improve the biological nitrogen fixation of haricot beans.
- The application of biofertilizer, lime, starter nitrogen, and their combinations will significantly increase grain yield of haricot beans compared to their sole application.
- Combined application of inoculants and soil amendments will be economically viable compared to their sole amendments in field trial.

1.6. Scope and Limitation of the Study

Emphasizing the importance and implications, the optimization of haricot bean productivity through effective soil fertility management holds critical significance for farmers in the lowlands and midlands of our nation. Haricot beans serve as a vital, economical source of protein, contributing to financial incentives and ensuring food security. Our research focuses on exploring the impact of inoculation and other soil amendments on haricot bean productivity within the Koga irrigation

scheme in northwestern Ethiopia, encompassing the intricate processes of biological nitrogen fixation and soil properties improvement. The intricacies inherent in this field of study have presented various challenges, necessitating a purposeful narrowing of parameters and scope. This strategic limitation is imperative due to constraints in time and resources, preventing a comprehensive analysis of soil health, nutrient cycling, soil organism diversity, and seed and straw quality within the study area. This focused approach allows us to address key aspects critical to understanding and improving haricot bean cultivation under the specified conditions.

1.7. Significance of the Study

In Ethiopia, pulses stand as crucial crops, following cereals, serving as economical protein sources and playing a modest role in the export market. They also contribute significantly to improving soil fertility. Therefore, this study holds importance in expanding knowledge about the combined application of organic and inorganic fertilizers, aiming to increase haricot bean production and productivity at Koga irrigation scheme for the benefit of the local community. The implications of this research are manifold. Firstly, it serves as a foundational reference for future in-depth studies. Secondly, it offers recent insights into the impact of inoculation and other soil amendments on biological nitrogen fixation and haricot bean yield. Thirdly, it enhances our understanding of the influence of soil physicochemical properties and agronomic parameters on haricot bean productivity. Additionally, the study addresses the potential to reduce the cost of organic fertilizer, thereby increasing haricot bean production and productivity.

Moreover, it provides information on the nutritional quality of haricot bean seeds and straw. Lastly, the study puts forth constructive suggestions and recommendations for government, NGOs, and the local community to recognize the role of integrated soil fertility management and its impact on crop productivity.

1.8. Organization of the Study

The paper was structured into five chapters for clarity and coherence. Chapter one encompasses a concise introduction, a statement of the problem, objectives, research questions, hypothesis, scope, limitation, significance, organization of the study, and definition of terms. In chapter two, a comprehensive review of related literature explores the effects of inoculation and other soil amendments on biological nitrogen and their impact on haricot bean productivity. Chapter three was

dedicated to detailing the study area, experimental design, methods of data collection and analysis, and a partial economic analysis. The fourth chapter delves into the presentation and discussion of research results. Lastly, chapter five provides recommendations and conclusions drawn from the overall activities.

1.9. Definitions of Terms

Biological nitrogen fixation: is the process through which legumes, in association with soil bacteria called rhizobia, convert atmospheric nitrogen (N_2) in soil air spaces into a form accessible to plants. Despite the atmosphere containing approximately 80% nitrogen, plants cannot utilize it for growth and development without fixation. This process occurs in a symbiotic relationship with rhizobia bacteria in the soil (Grossman, 2014). It involves the conversion of atmospheric dinitrogen (N_2) to ammonia (NH_3) through the combined action of biological and chemical activities. This process is economically viable and environmentally friendly, with nitrogen-fixing microorganisms interacting with leguminous plants (Santhosh *et al.*, 2019).

Bacteria such as Rhizobium and Bradyrhizobium: have the ability to fix atmospheric nitrogen (N) into forms usable by plants. The N-fixing bacteria are categorized into symbiotic and non-symbiotic groups. The symbiotic group relies on a host plant for function, while the non-symbiotic group consists of free-living organisms (Wright *et al.*, 2017). Rhizobia, also known as root-nodule bacteria, form symbiotic associations with legume roots, utilizing their unique biological characteristics to fix atmospheric nitrogen (Drew *et al.*, 2012).

Nitrogen fixation: is the conversion of elemental nitrogen (N_2) to organic forms readily utilizable in biological processes (Landon, 2014).

Rhizobia: is a generic term for a group of Gram-negative *Alphaproteobacteria* and *Betaproteobacteria* capable of forming nodules on the roots or stems of their hosts and fixing nitrogen in symbiosis with legumes (Sprent, 2008).

Biofertilizer: contain various microbes that enhance plant nutrient uptake by colonizing the rhizosphere, making nutrients easily accessible to plant root hairs (Debmalya *et al.*, 2021).

Soil amendment: refers to substances like lime, sulfur, gypsum, or sawdust used to modify soil properties, generally to increase productivity (Landon, 2014).

Inoculation: is the process of applying rhizobium bacteria to legume seeds, forming a symbiotic relationship with the developing plant (Buntic *et al.*, 2019).

Root nodules and nodulation: nodulation begins with the colonization of legume roots by rhizobia, leading to the development of root nodules and the initiation of nitrogen fixation (Drew *et al.*, 2012).

Available nutrient: refers to a portion of any element or compound in the soil that can be readily absorbed and assimilated by growing plants. It includes soluble and chelated forms, distinguishing it from 'exchangeable' forms (Landon, 2014).

Soil management: encompasses all tillage operations, cropping practices, and treatments applied to soil for crop production (Landon, 2014).

Fertilizer: is any organic or inorganic material of natural or synthetic origin added to soil to supply essential elements for plant nutrition (Landon, 2014).

Soil colloid: is organic and inorganic matter with very small particle size and a correspondingly large surface area per unit of mass (Landon, 2014).

Nitisols = Illuvial soils with merging argic B horizons and nitic properties (including shiny ped faces). Usually formed on basic rocks (cf acrisols, podzoluvisols, luvisols)

CHAPTER 2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Soil Fertility Status and Haricot Bean Production in East Africa

2.1.1. Haricot bean production in East Africa

Haricot bean (*Phaseolus Vulagris L*), locally known as ‘Boleqe’ (Fantaye Belay *et al.*, 2018) also known as French, garden, common, kidney, pinto, navy (backed bean), black, pink, black eye, field, cranberry, great northern or dry bean (Hedley, 2001) is a very important legume crop grown worldwide. It is an annual crop which belongs to the order Rosales, family Fabaceae, subfamily Papilionideae and tribe Phaseolinae (Teshale Assefa *et al.*, 2005). The global archaeological evidence of grain legumes' cultivation, that is as old as cereals, is dated back to about 5,000 B.C. Haricot bean was originated in Tropical America (Mexico, Guatemala, and Peru), even though there are also evidences for its multiple domestication within Central America (Kay, 1979). It is most believed to be introduced to Africa including Ethiopia by the Portuguese in the 16th century and spread into the interior faster than European exploration (Wortman, 1997). Haricot bean is one of the major pulse crops grown widely in the world (Walelign Worku, 2015). The world haricot bean production is estimated to be about 17 million metric tons with an average of 26 million hectares (FAO, 1994), which makes the crop the most widely utilized of legumes and the world average yield is 0.80 t ha⁻¹ (8.0 quintal) (Gichuru *et al.*, 2015).

Bean production between 1990 and 2018, in Sub Sharan Africa increased due to the increament cultivated land. Over 4 million hectares of haricot beans are sown each year in Africa (Habtamu Alemu, 2017) consequently, bean production area in Africa is widespread with approximately 7 million hectares per year 71% Eastern Africa, 12.9% Western Africa and 16.1% Southern Africa (Farrow and Muthoni., 2020). In Africa average yields are very low, and are usually between 0.2 and 0.67 tone of dried seed per hectare (Solomon Abate, 2012). The major producers of haricot bean in Africa are the eastern African countries such as Uganda, Tanzania, Kenya, Rwanda and Ethiopia. For instance, in 2004 these countries had produced in the order of 545,000; 280,000; 278,000; 198,000 and 175,000 tonnes. In Eastern Africa, beans are the dominant grain legume, cultivated on about 3.2 million ha yr⁻¹. Accounts for 35% of the total area in Africa produced about 38% as sole crop (Farrow and Muthoni., 2020).

Haricot bean is the most widely grown legume that occupies about 90% of the area planted with *Phaseolus* species (Oshone, 2017) and an important source of main cash crop, protein, vitamin, mineral, fiber content, energy (Keterew *et al.*, 2018) in human diets in the tropical and sub-tropical developing countries. Its cultivation can be carried out without large input and intensive practices which is suitable for poor farmers where, the need in food supply satisfied (Mesfin Kassa *et al.*, 2014). More than one third of children less than five years of age in developing countries suffer from protein energy undernutrition and the proportion of children who are undernourished has changed very little during the past 20 years (De *et al.*, 1993). More than 75% of the deaths of infants and young children in some developing countries (Ou *et al.*, 2002). Greater consumption of beans by children in developing countries would significantly reduce morbidity and mortality in this age group. It also aids in the reduction of cholesterol, sugar levels, alleviate and hinder cardiovascular diseases, type 2 diabetes and types of cancer (Leterme, 2002).

There is a wide range of haricot bean types grown in Ethiopia including mottled, red, white and black varieties (Ephrem Terefe, 2016). In Ethiopia haricot bean is the third most important legume crop next to faba bean and field peas (CSA, 2020). Pulses are grown, and account 13% of cropped land area throughout the country (Woldemichael Amaha, 2020). The major haricot bean producing areas of Ethiopia are central, eastern and southern parts of the country. The 2007 CSA national census indicates that the production of haricot beans in Amhara, Oromiya, SNNP, and Tigray was 42000, 37000, 15000, and 5000 tons, respectively. In 2011/12, total haricot bean production in the country was about 3,878,02.301 tonne (1.77% of the grain production) on about 331,708.15 hectares of land (2.74% of the grain crop area) (CSA, 2011).

The national average yield of haricot bean in Ethiopia is 1.48 tonne ha⁻¹ while that of the Eastern Amhara region under farmers' condition 1.608 t ha⁻¹ (Beebe *et al.*, 2013 and CSA, 2016), which is far below the potential yield from research managed experimental plots (2.6 - 4.6 t ha⁻¹) a reflection of, among other things, low soil fertility (Solomon Abate *et al.*, 2012). Pulses are grown, and account 13 percent of cropped land area throughout the country. The haricot bean production area in both the Amhara and Oromiya regions accounts for 79% of the nation's total cultivated land area, with 42% and 37% of their production, respectively (Woldemichael Amaha, 2020). In north-western Ethiopia, haricot bean yield levels was attained 2866.8 and 2709.3 kg ha⁻¹ (Daniel Tadesse., 2014).

2.1.2. Requirement and Characteristics of Haricot bean

Haricot beans are relatively more productive in Histic, Eutric, and Dystric Nitisols which is an important soil in eastern Africa. In Eastern Africa; the major soil fertility related problems include low N and P availability, low availability of exchangeable bases, and soil acidity (Farrow and Muthoni, 2020). Haricot bean is the most important pulse crops grown in central southern, eastern and Western lowland and mid altitudes of Ethiopia (CACC, 2002 and Tamirat Beyene *et al.*, 2020). Ethiopia has favorable agro ecology for legume crop production (Erana Kebede, 2020). The wide range of growth habits of haricot bean among varieties has enabled the crop to fit many growing situations (Kristin *et al.*, 1997).

It is adapted to a wide range of climatic conditions starting from sea level to nearly 3000 meters above sea level (m.a.s.l.), most of the scholars suggested that haricot bean grows well between 1200–2000 m.a.s.l. depending on variety (Rahmeto Negash, 2007; Aregu Amsalu *et al.* 2012). However, it does not grow well below 600 m.a.s.l. due to poor pod set caused by extreme temperature (Dev and Gupta., 1997). It grows best in warm climate at temperature range of 10°C to 32°C (Teshale Assefa, 2005; Girma Abebe, 2009). In addition, reported that the crop is well adapted to areas that receive an annual average rainfall ranging from 350 - 1500 mm, the relative humidity should not exceed 75% (Teshale Assefa, 2005 and Walelign Worku, 2015) and a frost-free time of 105 to 120 days for maturity. It requires about 300 to 400 mm of water during its growth period (Walelign Worku, 2015). Moreover; Haricot bean grows successfully on most soil types from light sands to heavy clays, but friable, deep, well-drained and porous soil types with optimum pH range of 5.5 to 6.8 best preferred (Teshale Assefa *et al.*, 2005; CSA, 2020 and Farrow and Muthoni., 2020).

It is an erect or twinning, annual and herbaceous plant with various growth habits, morphological traits, and seed and pod characteristics. The bean flower is perfect, possessing both male and female organs on the same flower, and is self-fertilizer crop. Pollination coincides with the time when the flower opens (Purseglove, 1968). The pronounced tap-root grows rapidly to a depth of one meter and there are extensive lateral roots mainly confined to the top 15-30cm of the soil. Nodules are irregular and knobby. The stems are somewhat hairy. The flowers are small, and vary in color from white to bluish; they are self-pollinated. The pods are 10-20 cm long, straight or curved and terminate in a prominent beak. They contain four to six seeds, sometimes more. The seeds vary greatly in size (7-16 mm long) and color (Katungi *et al.*, 2009). The haricot bean has a wider variability for seed length (0.6-7.6 cm) and seed thickness (0.5-1.9 cm) (Ali Kemal *et al.*, 2006).

2.1.3. Soil fertility status of cultivated land

Soil acidity is among the major land degradation problems, which affects about 50% of the world's arable soils (Kochian *et al.*, 2004) close to 4 billion ha are acidic (Sumner and Noble, 2003). From the total percentage 60% of acidic soils are found in tropics and subtropics, it dominates most of the developing countries hence these regions are faced with food insecurity (Kochian *et al.*, 2015). Similarly, in Africa low soil fertility is a significant constraint limiting bean production; with 75 % of the soil being deficient in phosphorous, 65% of nitrogen and 20% of the soil are acidic, causing deficiencies of most of the essential nutrient required for haricot bean production (Beebe *et al.*, 2012 and Lunze *et al.*, 2012). Notably, Ethiopia spans a total area of 111.8 million hectares, of which 79 million hectares are arable. Within this arable land, approximately 40.9% consists of soils that range from strongly to weakly acidic. Specifically, 27.7% of the land features moderately to weakly acidic soils with a pH between 5.8 and 6.7, while 13.2% comprises soils that are strongly to moderately acidic with a pH below 5.5 (Gudeta Dida and Damtew Etisa., 2019).

The loss of soil fertility caused by increasing population, high rates of erosion, the limited application of mineral and organic fertilizers, and inappropriate fertilizer recommendations all contribute to the loss of soil fertility, which leaves most farmlands unable to provide the necessary nutrients for adequate plant growth, development, and health (Pahalvi.,2021). This problem was estimated by Sanginga and Woomer (2009) to cause annual losses of 4.4 million tonnes of nitrogen, 0.6 million tonnes of phosphorous, and 3 million tonnes of potassium. Soil fertility management for food and livelihood security is a major concern in the face of persistent poverty and widespread environmental degradation in Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA) including Ethiopia (Bello *et al.*, 2010). The same authors reported that around 97% of the rainfed agriculture is the predominant method of producing food on most of the SSA's agricultural land (Mosisa worku *et al.*, 2012).

In Ethiopia, soil degradation and nutrient depletion have increased and become serious threats to agricultural productivity (Bekele Tsegaye, 2019) mainly found in the high crop production potential areas of the country (Kebede Dinkecha and Dereje Tsegaye., 2017 and Teame Tefera *et al.*, 2022). The main factors increasing soil acidity is climatic factors such as rainfall and topographic features (Brady and Weil, 2016). In the high rainfall areas of Ethiopia, 47% of the cultivated land (Geremew Taye *et al.*, 2020), 45% of rain-fed areas being acidic (Gizaw Desta *et al.*, 2021) and more than 80% of the Nitisols are acidic (Asmamaw Demil *et al.*, 2020). In addition, 3.7% (42,264 km²) of the

country's total territory is found to be extreme to strongly acidic, 20.7% (236,724 km²) is moderate acidic and 22.5% (257,290 km²) slightly acidic (Gizaw Desta *et al.*, 2021). The same author reported that soil acidity is one of the limiting factors to acid-sensitive crops in the northwestern highlands of Ethiopia (Asmamaw Demil *et al.*, 2020 and Teame Tefera *et al.*, 2022). Currently, it is estimated that about 43% of the total arable lands is affected by soil acidity, of which about 28.1% are dominated by strongly acidic soils (pH 4.1-5.5) (ATA, 2014; Geremew Taye *et al.*, 2020; Abu Regasa, 2021). High rainfall-induced leaching, acidic parent materials, removal of organic matter and continuous application of acid-forming fertilizers are some of the major causes of soil acidity (Getachew Agegnehu *et al.*, 2019; Geremew Taye *et al.*, 2020 and Teame Tefera *et al.*, 2022). Its effects on crop growth are those related to the deficiency of major nutrients and the toxicity of aluminum, manganese, and hydrogen to plants (Mesfin Abebe, 2007).

Soil erosion is a major watershed problem in Lake Tana basin causing significant loss of soil fertility, loss of productivity and environmental degradation (Shimelis Gebriye *et al.*, 2008). The land use type of the basin is predominantly cultivable Land (71%), grazing (9%), infrastructure (6%), forest (3%), and other (11%) (Water bodies, wetlands, forest, wood land, shrubs, rangeland, settlements). The soil type in the Lake Tana islands, peninsulas and wetlands and in the upland areas of the Lake are dominated by Nitisols, Luvisols and Vertisols (Goraw Goshu and Shimelis Aynalem., 2017). The Lake Tana basin is heavily affected by over population, poor cultivation and improper land use practices, deforestation and overgrazing as a result sediment depositions in the lakes and reservoirs (Shimelis Gebriye *et al.*, 2008). In addition climate factor, cultivation intensity (Ma *et al.*, 2022) and use of inorganic fertilizers (Yadav *et al.*, 2020) caused that 31.17% of the basin land area to be acidic (Ma *et al.*, 2022).

The soils of the Koga irrigation are clayey and categorized as Nitisols (WRB, 2015 and Mulunesh Addis *et al.*, 2021). The soil condition is strongly acidic and the crop's fertilizer response is decreasing in the area, which is situated in northwest Ethiopia (Desale Kidane *et al.*, 2022). Unless due attention is given to the management of soil acidity; it can lead to a decline or complete failure of crop production (Getachew Agegnehu *et al.*, 2019). Integrated soil fertility management, which strategically combines organic and inorganic resources, is an effective method to address soil fertility issues and enhance crop yields (Tayebeh Abedi *et al.*, 2010). Ensuring sustainable and cost-effective soil fertility management is crucial (Vanlauwe *et al.*, 2010). This soil fertility strategy relies on a

holistic approach that embraces the full range of driving factors and consequences of soil degradation- biological, chemical, physical, social, economic, health, nutrition and political (Bationo *et al.*, 2006)

2.1.4. Biological Nitrogen Fixation

All living organisms require nitrogen but it is required in the largest amount by plants (Marschner and Rengel., 2023). Global agriculture now relies heavily on large-scale industrial nitrogen fixation; the use of nitrogen fertilizers has increase in parallel with the population growth, and agriculture now annually consumes nearly 80 million metric tons. Nitrogen fertilizers are petroleum-based products, vulnerable to political and economic fluctuations in the oil markets. They are expensive inputs, costing agriculture more than US\$ 45 billion per year. Crops use fertilizer-N inefficiently and generally plants do not assimilate more than 50% of the N fertilizer applied. The remainder is a potential source of environmental pollution. Furthermore, many cropping systems have reached the point of diminishing returns to fertilizer-N applications, and there is a decline in global cereal production per unit of N fertilizer application (World Bank, 2018).

Nitrogen in the atmosphere occurs mostly in the form of dinitrogen, essentially inert, with a very strong triple bond ($N\equiv N$). In order for nitrogen to be used for growth it must be "fixed" (combined) in the form of ammonium (NH_4^+) or nitrate (NO_3^-) (Lal, 2020). Nitrogen naturally occurs as dinitrogen gas (N_2), a form that plants cannot directly use. Legumes possess the unique capability to fix nitrogen through a symbiotic relationship with bacteria. Biological Nitrogen Fixation (BNF) involves certain bacteria species transforming nitrogen into ammonia (NH_3), which plants can biologically utilize (Unkovich and Baldock *et al.*, 2008). Rhizobia bacteria give a sufficient nitrogen that the plant can require, and, thus, will supply significant amount of residual N to the succeeding crops (Bayou Bunkura *et al.*, 2015). The nitrogen fixing system consists of three biological entities the host plant (legume), the nodule bacterium (Rhizobium), and a new organ, the root nodule (symbiosis) (Coba *et al.*, 2018). For agriculture, Symbiosis is then considered as an economically friendly approach to supplying N to the agro-ecosystems, particularly recommended for organic farming systems N_2 fixers are then called biofertilizers (Carranca, 2013). Rhizobia give sufficient N that the plant can require, and, thus, will supply significant amount of residual N to the succeeding crops (Ayneabeba Adamu *et al.*, 2001).

It is noticed that symbiotic bacteria approximately 250 million hectares of legumes worldwide fix about 90 Tg of nitrogen per year (Vidigal *et al.*, 2019) which accounts from 40 to 70% of total global nitrogen input (Kahindi and Karanja., 2009). The total annual terrestrial inputs of N from BNF range from 139 million to 175 million tonnes of N, with symbiotic associations growing in arable land accounting for 25 to 30% (35 million to 44 million tons of N) and permanent pasture accounting for another 30% (45 million tons of N) (Sible *et al.*, 2021). The study conducted by Kahindi and Karanja.(2009) showed that fixation rate of legume crop has 24-584 kg ha⁻¹year⁻¹. Similarly, Giller (2001) reported N fixation rates of 1 to 2 kg N ha⁻¹ day⁻¹ in a growing season by most tropical legumes crops. The amount of symbiotically fixed nitrogen per year estimated for various legume crops and pasture species are often impressive, commonly falling in the range of 200 to 300 kg N ha⁻¹ per year (Khosro Mohammadi, 2012).

Legumes have nitrogen-fixing abilities that can reduce fertilizer use for cereals by up to 60% in the following season. Since cereal production depletes soil nutrients more, intercropping and rotating legumes with cereals help maintain soil health. Additionally, leaf fall during legume growth can add up to 40 kg of nitrogen per hectare (Srinivasarao *et al.*, 2012 and Chilot Yirga *et al.*, 2019). The study conducted by Rascio and Rocca. (2008) stated that crops planted after harvesting of legumes are often equivalent to those expected from application of 30-80 kg fertilizer N ha⁻¹ it has been estimated that the 80 - 90% of the N available to plants in natural ecosystem derives from biological nitrogen fixation. BNF is extensively investigated as one of the avenues to improve bean productivity (Baroness Nyagechanga, 2015). In Sub-Saharan Africa, soil N is primarily obtained from natural BNF mechanisms by soil microorganisms commonly known as rhizobium bacteria that contributes nitrogenous compounds to the soil, either directly, by nodule excretion, or indirectly, by decomposition of root nodules and tissues (Giller, 2001) also rhizobium inoculation helps to boost the yield of grain legumes, and has been described as a cheap insurance for higher yields for smallholder farmers (Ndakidemi *et al.*, 2006). But the use of rhizobium inoculants for improvement in N-fixation and productivity of grain legumes is still in the developing stage in most parts of sub-Saharan Africa, including Ethiopia (Abdullahi *et al.*, 2013).

In Ethiopia, pulse crops rank second as food after cereals and occupy about 17.7% of the total cultivated areas, and contribute about 12 % of the total production. The major food legumes in the country are faba bean, chickpea, field pea, haricot bean, groundnut, cowpea, pigeon pea, grass pea,

lupine and soybean (Ali Kemal *et al.*, 2006). In Ethiopia, selection of efficient rhizobia strains for inoculation started in 1982 at Melkasa agricultural research center and such as 110 strains of *Rhizobium leguminosarum*; 20 strains of *Rhizobium phaseoli*; 328 strains of *R. japonicum* and *Cicer areietinum*; and 34 Strains of *R. trifoli* were isolated in its microbiology laboratory (Abebe Amare, 1986). Most recently, genetic diversity and phylogenetic relationships of rhizobia isolated from root nodules of perennial (tree/shrub) and annual (crop) legume species were studied by some researchers (Aregu Amsalu *et al.*, 2012 a, b, and Tulu Degefua *et al.*, 2013). The study conducted by Shimelis Gebretsadik *et al.*(2019) in Hawassa showed that haricot bean fixed at 71 to 99 kg ha⁻¹. Because biological nitrogen fixation reduces production costs and is environmentally friendly, improving bean nitrogen fixation is a crucial goal (Graham and Vance, 2000). Consequently, farming practices can make use of the more economically viable and environmentally prudent biological nitrogen fixation, in which agriculture and the environment will benefit (Alemayehu Dabessa *et al.*, 2018).

2.2 Effect of Soil Ammendements on Biological Nitrogen Fixation and Haricot Bean Production

2.2.1. Effect of lime on biological nitrogen fixation and haricot bean production

Acidity directly affects the growth and survival of the *Rhizobium* bacteria, which fixes nitrogen in legumes (Mensah *et al*, 2006). Increased soil acidity may lead to reduced yields, poor plant vigour, and nodulation of legumes (Habtam Alemu, 2017). Acidity of soils can decrease crop yield, seedling emergence and survival, legume nodulation and root growth (Marschner, 2002). To allivate soil acidity lime application is an important agricultural practice for increasing productivity (Paradelo *et al.*, 2015 and Opala *et al.*, 2018), which is present extensively across the world, especially in the tropics. Liming acid soil has been suggested as the best method to attain and maintain a suitable pH for the growth of a variety of crops (Opela *et al.*, 2018). Liming acidic soils enhance the activities of pivotal microbes in the root zone and hence improve root growth by the fixation of atmospheric nitrogen because neutral pH allows more optimal conditions for free-living N fixation (Nduwumuremyi, 2013). Lime amendements of soil acidity can enhance the mineralization process, increase p availability, raise pH levels, increase N availability and uptake in the soil, improve soil structure (FAO, 2017), improved soil quality and increase the sustainability of current nutrient management practices (Liu *et al.*, 2017). This creates a more favorable environment for soil microbiological activity and, ultimately, has a positive impact on dry matter production, dry mass of

the shoot, nodule number, dry weight, and number of pods per plant and grain yield of haricot bean (Goulding, 2016, and Gudeta Dida, 2018). Lime also ameliorates soil conditions, promotes plant productivity and root growth in plants by alleviating Ca^{2+} deficiency, decreasing Al^{3+} toxicity, and improving the plant nutrients availability (Kunhikrishnan *et al.*, 2016 and Holland *et al.*, 2017).

The amending acid soils could make the soil environment better for leguminous plants and associated microorganisms, as well as increase the concentration of essential nutrients by raising their pH (Alemayehu Dabesa and Tamado Tana., 2021). The study conducted by Bello *et al.* (2018) at Samaru, Nigeria showed that increased yield of cowpea in soils amended with lime was credited to increased number of root nodules. Supply of calcium ions from lime and the binding of excess aluminium and hydrogen ions also contributed to increased growth of cowpea. The study conducted by Mesfin Kassa *et al.* (2014) showed that the addition of lime to acidic soils reduces soil acidity and favors the establishment and growth of legumes crops.

Improved growth and yield of the haricot bean was attributed to increased soil pH in soils amended with lime (Mesfin Kassa *et al.*, 2014). Liming of acid soil increased the plant height, fresh biomass, dry biomass, grain yields, harvest index and P-uptake of barley (Achalu Chimdi *et al.*, 2012). Similarly, Temesgen Desalegn *et al.* (2017) studies indicated that the combined application of 1.65 t lime ha^{-1} and 30 kg P ha^{-1} resulted in 133% more grain yields of barley than the control (lime). Notably, study shows that a very high application of lime increased onion bulb yield by 137% (Sopha, 2022). Workneh Bakere *et al.* (2013) reported significant increase in straw yield of soybean by 16.3%, due to soil liming at the rate of 2.6 t ha^{-1} . In Croatia, Andric *et al.* (2012) also reported increased soybean yield by 44% as a result of lime application over the control/unlimed treatments. Meanwhile, Hemphill (1987) reported that an application of 14.8 t ha^{-1} lime increased onion bulb yield by about 348%, from 18.8 to 65.5 t ha^{-1} in Oregon, the United States. Additionally, Abebe Zerihun and Tolera Abera (2014) reported the increased of Faba bean yield ranging from 11% to 23%, as the function of increasing lime application rates. Mercy and Ezekiel.(2006) application of lime significantly increased root and shoot yields of soybean in Nigeria. Notably, Mesfin Kassa *et al.* (2014) revealed that application of lime should be repeated in the subsequent seasons until the soil comes to neutral and increased the production of. haricot bean crops. However, the effectiveness of liming varies and depends on many factors, including; the initial soil pH, soil type, climate, liming material type, the lime application rate and crop species (Li *et al.*, 2019).

2.2.2. Effect of Inoculation on biological nitrogen fixation and haricot bean production

Bio-fertilizer or biological fertilizer is a material that contains living or dormant microorganisms that colonize the rhizosphere (Malusa and Vassilev., 2014; Fasusi *et al.*, 2021). Roughly, half of the 23 million metric tons of nitrogen consumed as human food sources (grains and livestock) comes from biological nitrogen fixation (Robert H. Socolow, 1999). Out of this, rhizobia in root nodules are estimated to carry out between 50-70% of the world's biological nitrogen fixation (Burris and Roberts., 1993). Tropical grain legumes such as common bean fix nitrogen to the tune of 15 to 210 kg N ha⁻¹ (Dakora and Keya ., 1997). Legume productivity and the fixation of biological nitrogen are restricted by biotic and abiotic factors in global agriculture, particularly in sub-Saharan Africa. In light of this, it can be said that numerous studies, especially in the western region of Ethiopia, concentrated on the effects of acidity on biological nitrogen fixation, the selection of inoculants resistant to acidity, and the enhancement of low soil fertility in smallholder farming systems (Alemayehu Dabessa *et al.*, 2018). In Ethiopia, inoculation of food legumes with rhizobia inoculants is not common practice but could provide an option to increase seed yields in acidic soils (Daniel Muleta *et al.*, 2017)

Smallholder farmers use biofertilizer because it is less expensive than inorganic fertilizers and less likely to lose nitrogen due to leaching and denitrification (Mhango *et al.*, 2017) in most cases, substantially make use of the BNF process, thus able to fix up to 50 kg N ha⁻¹ (Carranca, 2013 and Endalkachew Wolde-meskel *et al.*, 2018) and raises the yield of legumes crop from (2 – 4 t ha⁻¹) at very low cost (Hijosa-Valsero, 2016). It has a great importance as a non-polluting and a cost-effective way to improve soil fertility through supplying N to different agricultural systems (Sameh Hassan *et al.*, 2017). After harvesting of legumes, they leave often equivalent to those expected from application of 30 to 80 Kg N ha⁻¹ and year (Hamdi Hussein, 1999). BNF provides N benefits to subsequent crops from the mineralization of N from their residues or from the N sparing effect (Tamiru Hirpa, 2014).

Seed inoculation was done under shade in the field to reduce the bacterial cell death. To avoid cross contamination, weeding was done in the un-inoculated plots first (Tarekegn Yoseph *et al.*, 2018). The study conducted by Anteneh Tamirat *et al.* (2017) in Wolayta Zone of Southern Nations Nationalities and People's Region showed that average yield of haricot bean are 1.017 tonnes using bio-fertilizer, and 0.365 tonnes without bio-fertilizer and there is a difference of 0.652 tonnes. The

other finding indicated that haricot bean using bio fertilizer was 1.068 tonnes while without using bio-fertilizer was 0.67 tonnes done on Arsi Zone of Oromia Regional State on bio-fertilizer direct use value on faba bean (Binyam Goshu *et al.*, 2016).

2.2.3. Effect of starter nitrogen on biological nitrogen fixation and haricot bean production

Nitrogen is one of the most deficient elements in the tropics for crop production (Alemu Lelago *et al.*, 2016; Fanuel Laekemariam *et al.*, 2016). Most Ethiopian soils are deficient in nutrients, especially nitrogen and phosphorus, and fertilizer application has significantly increased crop yields (Tekalign Tadese *et al.*, 1991). Application of small amounts of “starter” fertilizer N is needed to establish seedlings and promote early dinitrogen fixation (Tahsin Sogut *et al.*, 2013). The production of chlorophyll, which is necessary for the process of photosynthesis, makes nitrogen an essential element in plants. In addition, nitrogen is part of various enzymatic proteins and a major component of several vitamins that catalyze and regulate plant growth processes (Joseph *et al.*, 2010; Sara *et al.*, 2013). Nitrogen has positive effects on legume growth and is essential for the production of both leguminous and non-leguminous crops (Eutropia and Patrick., 2013). It has been reported that there was increased yield responses of pulse for nitrogen fertilizer (Morgado and Willey, 2003). There is also quantitative relationship between crop yield and accumulation of N by plants, i.e. when the soil cannot supply with adequate N, the crop yield will be constrained (Sinclair and Vadez,2002).

The use of starter inorganic N fertilizer is very important to facilitate the N fixation by rhizobium (Zerihun Getachew and Lijalem Abeble., 2020). Early crop development may require a specific amount of supplied N to overcome N deficiency during the time between the exhaustion of the cotyledon N source and the formation of nodules that can symbiotically supply the plant with N₂ (Jensen, 1987). These plants cropped in soils low in N require a small amount of starter dose of N (5 - 10 kg N ha⁻¹) to stimulate seedling growth and early nodulation such that both N₂ fixation and yield are enhanced (Hardarson and Atkins, 2003; Chengala and Singh., 2017). when the soil cannot supply with adequate N, the crop yield will be constrained (Sinclair and Vadez., 2002). The study conducted by Carol Henry,(2018) showed that application of 20 kg N ha⁻¹ starter nitrogen fertilizer had a significant effect on above-ground biomass yield at chickpea crops, with three locations

In addition, N is continually lost through soil erosion, denitrification, leaching, chemical volatilization, and perhaps most importantly, removal of N-containing crop residues from the land (Terje Tamme *et al.*, 2010). In this respect, nitrogen is often in short supply in many croplands, limiting crop growth and productivity. Synthetic nitrogen fertilizers have been introduced to compensate N deficiency in agricultural soil (Abdoulaye Soumare *et al.*, 2020). All living organisms require nitrogen but it is required in the largest amount by plants (Marschner and Rengel., 2023). Today's large-scale industrial nitrogen fixation is a major component of global agriculture; the use of nitrogen fertilizers has increased in tandem with population growth by consuming about 80 million metric tons of nitrogen with the cost of US\$ 45 billion annually that has negative affects the environment (World Bank, 2018). In addition, N is continually lost through soil erosion, denitrification, leaching, and perhaps most importantly, removal of N-containing crop residues from the land (Terje Tamme *et al.*, 2010). In this respect, nitrogen is often in short supply in many croplands, limiting crop growth and productivity.

Synthetic nitrogen fertilizers have been introduced to compensate N deficiency in agricultural soil (Abdoulaye Soumare *et al.*, 2020). Utilization of fertilizers has dramatically increased in Ethiopia. Approximately three decades after fertilizer was introduced as part of the Freedom from Hunger project in the late 1960s, fertilizer use climbed from 3500 tons in the early 1970s to slightly over 34,000 tons. The rate of uses of inorganic fertilizer in Ethiopia has increased from 12 kg ha⁻¹ in 1996 to 36.2 kg ha⁻¹ in 2018 (Lin *et al.*, 2019). Such intensification can be a cause for the acidification of the soil. The use of N fertilizers in ammonia form is a source of acidification (Fageria and Nascente, 2014). When ammonia-based fertilizers (NH₄⁺), such urea [(CO (NH₂)₂), are applied to the soil, acidity is produced by addition of hydrogen. Transformation of such sources of N fertilizers into nitrate (NO₃⁻) releases hydrogen ions (H⁺) to create soil acidity. In reality, N fertilizer increases soil acidity by increasing crop yields, there by increasing the amount of basic elements being removed (Guo *et al.*, 2010).

2.2.4 Effect of phosphorus TSP on biological nitrogen fixation and haricot bean production

Nutrient depletion in East Africa ranges from high to very high, with alarming figures in countries such as Kenya, Ethiopia, and Rwanda, where annual depletion rates exceeded 40 kg N ha⁻¹, 6.6 kg P ha⁻¹, and 33.2 kg K ha⁻¹ (Nziguheba, 2007). In western parts of Ethiopia, low soil P availability, due

to soil acidity and its high fixation, is a limiting factor to crop production (Zerihun Abebe, 2017). Many studies have indicated that phosphorus availability in the soil is a great limitation for bean production in the tropics (Morgado and Willey, 2003; Sanz-Saez *et al.*, 2017). It is master key to agriculture because lack of available phosphorus in the soils limits the growth of plants (Foth and Ellis, 1997). It is the second most limiting nutrient for crop growth and development in acidic soils.

It is mostly due to the low natural concentration of P in the soil of northwestern Ethiopia, where some of it is fixed and inaccessible to plant uptake. This due to the low application rates of P-containing fertilizers, continuous crop uptake, losses due to erosion, and fixation by acidic soils in this maize-growing field of the study area (Yihenew G. Selassie, 2016) Phosphorus fixation was happen below about pH 5.5 there is a marked enhancement of the activity of Fe, Al and Mn in such soil, and soluble phosphates are fixed as complex, insoluble compounds of these elements. Above about pH 7.4 insoluble Ca phosphates are also formed (London, 2014) that causes an optimum soil pH range for phosphorus availability is 6.0 to 7.0. At lower pH levels, phosphate tends to bind with aluminum or iron compounds in the soil, making less available for plant uptake. At higher pH levels, phosphate tends to precipitate with calcium (Singh *et al.*, 2021)

TSP (Triple Super Phosphate) represented as 0 – 46 – 0, is normally applied where plants are grown in soils with low or average levels of phosphorus and to detect effects of P application on crop performances. TSP Fertilizer is applicable to all kinds of soil, in particular, suitable to where lack of phosphorus (Luo *et al.*, 2023) is detected. Triple phosphate fertilizer, commonly known as triple superphosphate (TSP) ($\text{Ca}(\text{H}_2\text{PO}_4)_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ (43-44% P_2O_5), is one of the first high-analysis phosphorus fertilizers. It is a very common fertilizer for promoting plant wellness and is often used for fertilizing leguminous crops (Khan Towhid, 2013; Seesanong *et al.*, 2023). Phosphorus is absorbed by plant roots in the forms of H_2PO_4^- and HPO_4^{2-} ions. Absorption of HPO_4^{2-} is greatest at higher pH values whereas H_2PO_4^- highest at lower pH values (Tisdale *et al.*, 2002).

Legumes need more phosphorus (P), as it is required for energy transformation in nodules. Besides, P also plays a significant role in metabolic processes including respiration, photosynthesis (Khan *et al.*, 2010), cell division, the development of new tissue (Sharma *et al.*, 2017), root development, nutrient uptake, winter hardiness, and the growth of legume crops. However, most of the agricultural soils have inadequate amounts of P to support efficient BNF, as it exists in stable chemical compounds, which are least available to plants. It is also essential for nitrogen fixation, and phosphorous

deficiency in bean production results in reduced nodule mass, nitrogen fixation, and yields of legume crops (Meseret Turuko and Amin Mohammed, 2014; Zerihun Abebe, 2017; Mitran *et al.*, 2018).

The availability of phosphorus in the soil influences the efficiency of Rhizobium, which fixes atmospheric nitrogen in association with nodulating legumes, as it is directly involved in BNF via legume-Rhizobium symbiosis. This has attracted worldwide attention due to its economic viability for resource poor farmers and environmental friendliness (Kishan Mahmud *et al.*, 2020). Low phosphorous availability in acidic soil negatively alters bean crop yield at Koga irrigation because of low soil availability of phosphorous and high soil acidity (Nian *et al.*, 2009 and Habtamu Tegen *et al.*, 2022).

To solve the problem, combined use of nitrogen with triple superphosphate (50 kg ha^{-1}) and biofertilizer was more effective than applying one amended alone (Morteza *et al.*, 2015). A good supply of P is associated with increased root growth, early maturity of crops, and the formation of root nodules, and N_2 fixation (Jacob and Cherian., 2013). Adding phosphorus to soil low in available phosphorus promotes root growth and winter hardiness, stimulates tillering, and often hastens maturity (Maryam I.S.Alkurdi., 2014). Without enough P in the soil, a legume can't fix sufficient amount of N_2 (Armando Elizalde-Velazquez *et al.*, 2016). In low pH soils, P can be utilised efficiently by band-placing 3.5 cm to the side of the row and 5 cm below the seed at the time of planting (Lunze *et al.*, 2012; Roberts and Johnston., 2015). For smallholder farmers in the Darolebu district, the combined use of TSP and manure is necessary for improving haricot bean yield and can increase their farm income in Eastern Ethiopian highlands (Tesfaye Lishan *et al.*, 2023). Similar results showed that application of 50 kg ha^{-1} TSP increase in grain yield of maize, common beans and soybean from those crops soybean grain yield increased over nil fertilizer treatment by 125 % in western Kenya (Savini *et al.*, 2016).

2.3. Effect of soil amendments on Soil physico-chemical properties

2.3.1 Effect of soil amendments on soil physical properties

Liming directly affects some physical properties of the soil, such as flocculation, aggregates, density and porosity. Flocculation of soil particles initially is smallest, which promotes greater particle dispersion (Junior *et al.*, 2020). Flocculation is the process that soil clay particles come together in stable granules (Sierens and Algoedt. 2019). Due to the flocculation process, the clays treated with

limestone have different granulometric distributions, considerably reducing the amount of fine particles, as these interact with the limestone and flocculate, being able to aggregate into larger particles, which are reasonably stable even under subsequent flooding (Junior *et al.*, 2020).

2.3.2 Effect of soil amendments on soil chemical properties

Many scholars have conducted research in different parts of Ethiopia by Asmare Melese and Markku Yli-Halla, (2016) and Endalkachew Fekadu *et al.*, (2017) reported that large amounts of lime had tremendous role in the change of soil chemical properties of acidic soils. Achalu Chimdi *et al.*, (2012) have reported that liming raises soil pH and reduce Al^{3+} concentration. Notably, Rautaray *et al.*, (2003) and Rahman *et al.*, (2019) also reported that lime increased soil test pH and Ca and Mg content in soil. Studies by Chintala *et al.* (2014) and Holland *et al.* (2018) sole and combined application lime with compost reduced soil acidity through the displacement of hydrogen ions in the soil solution by calcium that present in lime. Similarly, the experiment done by Temesgen Desalegn *et al* (2017) at Holeta Agricultural Research Center revealed that the soil's pH had significantly increases after two years of liming. The experiment done by Endalkachew Fekadu *et al.* (2018) revealed that application of lime increases haricot bean yield in Lay Gayint District of South Gondar Zone of the Amhara National Regional State (ANRS), Ethiopia. The figurative evidences of lime done by Bambara and Ndakidemi (2010) reported that application of 2 and 3 ton lime ha^{-1} increased soil pH in the rhizosphere of *Phaseolus vulgaris* by 3.2 and 4.9%, respectively, relative to unlimed soil. Also, Mesfin Kassa (2014) reported that application of 0.4 ton lime ha^{-1} increased soil pH by 7% compared to unlimed control. Mean while Murata *et al.* (2002) also reported that application of lime at the rate of 2 ton ha^{-1} significantly increased topsoil pH values from 4.6 to 6.0. Mandal *et al.*, (2021) showed that application of lime increaseas the pH value from 5.09 to 6.32. The impact of lime done by Adane Buni (2014) in Kuto Sorpela Kebele, Southern Ethiopia showed that soil pH increased significantly from 5.03 in the plots without lime to 6.72 at the lime rate of 3750 kg $CaCO_3$ ha^{-1} .

lime reduced the exchangeable acidity of soil can be attributed to the increased replacement of Al by Ca in the exchange site (Havlin *et al.*, 2017). The result was in agreement with Geremew Taye *et al.* (2020) who found that applied lime increased pH from 4.75 to 5.34 and lowered the exchangeable acidity from 2.3 to 0.43 $cmol (+) kg^{-1}$. Notably, Achalu Chimdi *et al.* (2012) reported that application of lime at the rate of 10 t ha^{-1} decreased the soil exchangeable acidity from 2.80 $cmol (+) kg^{-1}$ in the

control to $0.26 \text{ cmol (+) kg}^{-1}$ with decrement in exchangeable acidity of about 90.7%. Many researchers showed that application of lime increases the pH value from 5.09 to 6.32 (Mandal *et al.*, 2021). In tropical acid soils, lime has been reported to increase total nitrogen above the control for a longer period (Halvin *et al.*, 2017). Total nitrogen in soil, nitrogen is found always in two major forms: inorganic, as mineral nitrogen (2%) and organic (98%) (Liu *et al.*, 2014).

Soil inorganic nitrogen (SIN) is an important N source for plants because plants uptake inorganic N directly through the rooting system (Lynch, 1995). In nitrogen mineralization, organic nitrogen from decaying plant and animal residues is converted back to NH_4^+ and NO_3^- (Shafreen *et al.*, 2021). Soil inorganic nitrogen pools are usually small, generally just a few mg N kg^{-1} in natural ecosystems and rarely exceeding 100 mg N kg^{-1} in the plough layer of recently fertilized agricultural soils (Myrold, 2021). The increasing of available P as a result of lime application is due to improving soil acidity, and hence, increased availability of P (Kisinyo, 2016). Lime contributed in the release of some amount of fixed P to the soil, which will be available for the crop. Liming can increase phosphate availability by stimulating mineralization of soil organic phosphorus (Tolossa Ameyu., 2019). Application of lime at 1.0 t ha^{-1} also raised available P (Selomon Afework, 2018).

2.4 Economic Importance of Haricot bean

In Ethiopia, agriculture is the leading sector which contributes to nearly 34% of the country's gross domestic product (GDP) and 71% of employment. Crop production makes up 72% percent of the total agricultural GDP, of which cereals production covered 79.9 %, pulses 13.2 % and oil seeds 6.9% (ATA, 2018). Ethiopian grain legumes export has been increasing significantly over the last decade mainly due to the ongoing promotion of commercialization of smallholder farmers and better incentives from global legume markets (Legesse Dadi *et al.*, 2016). In the world haricot bean export market, Ethiopia took the sixth position with a market share of 2.4%. Haricot bean ranks third as an export commodity in Ethiopia, contributing to 9.5 % of total export value of agriculture (Daniel Masresha *et al.*, 2017). The study conducted by Tesfaye Fituma.(2015) field trials showed that reduces costs of production and N captured by crops due to the use of rhizobia inoculants costing $\$3 \text{ ha}^{-1}$ is equal to fertilizer N costing $\$87 \text{ ha}^{-1}$

There is a wide range of haricot bean types grown in Ethiopia including mottled, red, white and black varieties (Derese Wodajo *et al.*, 2021). The most commercial varieties are pure red and pure white

coloured beans and these are becoming the most commonly grown types with increasing market demand (Ferris and Kaganzi, 2008). With regard to economic importance of haricot bean, it is used as source of foreign currency, food crop, means of employment, source of cash, and plays great role in the farming system (CSA, 2005; Hunegnaw Amare, 2017). The main destination markets were European, Middle East, African and Far East countries (Shewaye Abera *et al.*, 2016), Sudan, Italy, Belgium and Netherland (ECX, 2016) such as Pakistan, Germany, Yemen, UK, South Africa, India and Mexico having 12.5, 7.8, 6.9, 5.79, 4, 4, 4 % share respectively (EPPA 2004). A market demand for the haricot beans both in the domestic and export market is growing. Due to this fact, the government has taken initiatives to modernize its export trade by linking with Ethiopia Commodity Exchange (ECX) market (Shewaye Abera *et al.*, 2016).

According to a report by Setotaw Ferede *et al.* (2015), there has been a major improvement in export performance and income generation in terms of grain legumes value, volume and composition. For instance, the export revenue from grain legumes has increased from 35 million USD in 2005/06 to 160 million USD in 2011/12 with a corresponding growth in volume from 110 to 226 MTs. Further, Ethiopia exported 340,000 MTs of grain legumes in 2016/17, earning 255 million USD of which haricot beans were the top-exported grain legumes, accounting for about half of all export volume (USDA, 2018). For instance, in terms of composition of export, haricot bean stands first by contributing about 45% and 43% of the total grain legumes export volume and value, respectively, followed by chickpea (24%), faba bean (20%) mung bean (6%), and lentil (4%). The country's exports of haricot beans have increased over the last few years, from 58,126 MTs in 2005 to 78,271 MTs in 2007 and Ethiopia gets export earnings 63, 134 million USD from haricot bean market in 2005 and 2014 respectively (Ephrem Terefe, 2016 and Legesse Dadi *et al.*, 2016).

Generally, smallholder income could be increased by at least 40–70% per hectare of legumes planted with better inputs and sound agronomic practices. In other words, there is an opportunity to stabilize and increase supply by improving production up to the full potential which would meet domestic demands. In addition, Ethiopia could dispread its foreign market presence through increased production levels, which will lead to at least doubling of its current annual exports (Mulugeta Atnaf *et al.*, 2015; Tadesse Getachew, 2019).

CHAPTER 3. MATERIALS AND METHODS

3.1 Description of the Study Area

3.1.1 Location

The study was carried out near the town of Merawi, at the Koga Irrigation Scheme, West Gojam Zone, Lake Tana basin inside the Abay River basin, and in Amhara northwest Ethiopia. Ten million people who reside in the lower Abay river basin depend heavily on the Lake Tana basin. It is the second largest sub-basin of the Blue Nile which covers an area of 15,114 km². Lake Tana is a tropical Lake with surface area of 3111 Km². It is the largest fresh water resource of Ethiopia (50%). The highest elevation is 4100 m a.s.l (meter above sea level) but 2025 m a.s.l is the average one; however, at Blue Nile out flow, at Lake Tana it is 1785 m a.s.l (Goraw Goshu and Shimelis Aynalem., 2017). According to Shimelis Gebriye *et al* (2008), the catchment area's mean annual rainfall is approximately 1280 mm. The Koga Irrigation Scheme is located 35 km from Bahir Dar town and 540 km north of Addis Ababa, the country's capital (Atakltie Abebe *et al.*, 2020). Along with ranging from 1830 to 2157 meters above sea level (m.a.s.l.), the area is situated between 11°10' and 11°22' North Latitude and 37°02' and 37°17' East Longitude. The slope varies from almost flat to quite steep. At the dam location, it encompasses 22,000 hectares and empties into the Koga River (Kassahun Tadesse *et al.*, 2015). About 7,000 hectares of potential irrigable command area are covered by the Koga catchment.

The Koga catchment has a 266 km² area. According to Zebire Degife and Gelgelo Samuel (2019), the altitude is divided into three categories: kola (low altitude), which covers 1100–1800 m.a.s.l., Weinadega (mid-altitude), which starts from 1900–2300 m.a.s.l., and Dega (high altitude), which is greater than 2300 m.a.s.l. There are water distribution canals, and 12 blocks (the command area) make up the Koga irrigation system. Water flows into the canals via a gravity system in a northward direction, and it is paved. The length of the canal is 19.7 km (Amare Hailelassie *et al.*, 2016; Dires Tewabe and Mekete Dessie, 2020). Four research sites run by Bahir Dar University are part of the Koga irrigation scheme. These are specifically located in the Mecha district and are named Ambomesk (19 ha), Kudime (8 ha), Andenet (12.75 ha), and Tekledeb (14.85 ha). According to Mulunesh Addis *et al.* (2021), the combined area covers 54.6 ha. Our experiment was conducted at Tekledeb research site, the elevation was classified as mid-altitude (1910 m.a.s.l.).

Figure 1. Koga irrigation schemes study area

3.1.2. Climate

The climate data for the Koga Irrigation Scheme rainy period usually starts in May and continues into October, with a maximum frequency in July or August. March has the lowest relative humidity (about 43%) and the highest (approximately 75%) in July and August. The mean monthly relative humidity is 58% for the entire year. According to Tesefaye Mekonen and Kebede Fasil (2011), the average monthly sunshine hours are 7.2 hours per day, with maximum values of 9.9 hours per day in December and minimum values of 4.4 hours per day in August. The slope varies from almost flat to extremely steep, and the elevation ranges from 1885 to 3131 meters above sea level (masl). The mean minimum and maximum temperatures in the region are 10.6 and 34.6°C annually, respectively. It has a warm, humid climate. The average monthly temperature is 25.8 degrees Celsius. 90% of the 1578 mm of annual rainfall that falls in the area occurs from May through October. From 1985 to 2003, the mean annual runoff at Koga station near Merawi was 176 MCM (million cubic meters) (Fikru Assefa, 2009). Most farmers focus their efforts on main-season production, and several farmers indicated that rainfall in the short season is too unreliable to invest in commercial haricot bean production (Ferris and Kaganzi, 2008).

Figure 2. Mean monthly rainfall (RF), mean monthly maximum and minimum temperatures ($^{\circ}$ C) of the study area for twenty years from 2003-2022 (Source: National Metrological Agency, Bahir Dar Branch)

3.1.3. Soil Type

The soil texture in Koga is clay and classified as Nitisol with strongly acidic property and high exchangeable acidity and exchangeable Al^{3+} contents Mulunesh Addis *et al* (2021). It is deep, well-drained, red, tropical soil (Mesfin Abebe, 2007 and Birhanu Agumas *et al.*,2016). Nitisols have three sub-soil units, i.e. Eutric, Dystric and Humic Nitisols. Dystric Nitisol contains relatively high organic matter content in the top layer and high base saturation in the soil profile, especially in the A and B-horizons, indicating the high fertility status of the soil. Nitisols are found in areas where the slope is between 2-16% on undulating plains, low plateaus, gentle hills and mountains side slopes of all areas. The problem of acidity is closely related to these soil types due to their geographical location, intensive cultivation, and inappropriate farm management practices (Mesfin Abebe, 2007). Based on the above classification the Tekledeb experimental site categorized as dystric Cambic-Nitisol (Mulunesh Addis *et al.*, 2021). The mean soil-pH result indicates the soil is strongly acidic (Desale Kidane *et al.*,2022).

3.1.4. Farming system and socio economics

Farmers depend on the long rainy season for crop production, and a crop-livestock mixed farming system is a common practice in the area. The Koga Irrigation Scheme is the major source of water in that watershed. The irrigation project has economic importance for the areas as they are used for irrigation purposes for vegetable, cereal and legume crop production during the dry season. The major crops grown in the study area are Maize (*Zea mays L.*), Hot pepper (*Capsicum annuum L.*), Finger millet (*Eleusine coracana (L.) Gaertn.*), Forage Soybean [*Glycine Max (L) Merrill*] (Hilena Yifred, 2023), common bean (*Phaseolus vulgaris L.*), Avocado (*Persea Americana*), teff (*Eragrostis tef (Zucc.)*), and wheat (*Triticum aestivum*). Cattle, small ruminants and non ruminants graze on communal grazing areas during the rainy season while crop fields are privately owned. Farmers in Koga use fertilizers such as DAP (diammonium phosphate), and many also add urea. There are two seasons for haricot bean production in Ethiopia: the short rainy season (*belg*) from March to May and the longer rainy season (*meher*) from July to August.

3.2 Experimental Design

The experiment was executed at Koga Irrigation Scheme watershed at the site of Tekeledebe, north-western Ethiopia. Eighteen different treatments were laid out in a factorial randomized complete block design (RCBD) with three replications. The experiment's gross plot had a size of 2.8 m * 4 m = 11.2 m². The net plot size was 1.6 m*3.6 m = 5.76 m², which means the remaining 4 rows in the center of the plot were used as the net plot for data collection. The spacing between blocks and plots was 1m and 0.5 m, respectively. The haricot bean was drill-row planted at a spacing of 0.4 m and 0.1 m between the row and plant, respectively, with a seed rate of 100 kg ha⁻¹. The rates of lime 0 and 2 t ha⁻¹ CaCO₃ (lime), which were recommended by the Adet Agricultural Research Center for haricot beans, were used. Two varieties of rhizobia strains were obtained from Ethiopian soils, grown in Finland using broth, and then preserved in the Bahir Dar University Biotechnology Laboratory (rhizobia zero, rhizobia one: HAMBI3562 species *Rhizobium phaseoli* HBR10, and rhizobia two: HAMBI3570 species *R. phaseoli* HBR53). Next, the experts used rhizobia strains to produce biofertilizer specifically for haricot beans. The amount of biofertilizer was calculated based on 500 gram/ha, and three rates of starter nitrogen (0, 10, and 20 kg N ha⁻¹) were used. The treatment was arranged as 2 × 3 × 3 in factorial combinations in RCBD with three replications. The experimental

site had seven planting rows, each four meters long and three meters wide. One last row on each side of the plot was used as a border row, and one row next to the border on one side of the plot was used for destructive sampling. On the other hand, two plants from the length side were avoided as a border. Triple superphosphate was applied at a rate 50 kg ha⁻¹ for all treatments. We also prepared and tagged the plot identification card for all treatments. The treatments were laid out randomly using the lottery method.

Table 3.1. Treatment combinations used in the study

Treatment number	Treatment set up	Description
1	L ₀ Sn ₀ R ₀	Control
2	L ₀ Sn ₀ R ₁	Rhizobium strain 1
3	L ₀ Sn ₀ R ₂	Rhizobium strain 2
4	L ₀ Sn ₁ R ₀	Starter nitrogen 1
5	L ₀ Sn ₁ R ₁	Starter Nitrgen 1 and Rhozobium strain 1
6	L ₀ Sn ₁ R ₂	Starter Nitrgen 1 and Rhozobium strain 2
7	L ₀ Sn ₂ R ₀	Starter Nitrgen 2
8	L ₀ Sn ₂ R ₁	Starter Nitrgen 2 and Rhozobium strain 1
9	L ₀ S ₂ R ₂	Starter Nitrgen 2 and Rhozobium strain 2
10	L ₁ Sn ₀ R ₀	lime 1
11	L ₁ Sn ₀ R ₁	lime 1 and Rhozobium strain 1
12	L ₁ Sn ₀ R ₂	lime 1 and Rhozobium strain 2
13	L ₁ Sn ₁ R ₀	lime 1 and Starter Nitrgen 1
14	L ₁ Sn ₁ R ₁	lime 1 ,Starter Nitrgen 1 and Rhozobium strain 1
15	L ₁ Sn ₁ R ₂	lime 1 ,Starter Nitrgen 1 and Rhozobium strain 2
16	L ₁ Sn ₂ R ₀	lime 1 and Starter Nitrgen 2
17	L ₁ Sn ₂ R ₁	lime 1 ,Starter Nitrgen 2 and Rhozobium strain 1
18	L ₁ Sn ₂ R ₂	lime 1 ,Starter Nitrgen 2 and Rhozobium strain 2

Where, L = lime (L₀=0, L₁=2 tonne)

Sn = starter nitrogen (S₀ = 0, S₁ = 10 kg ha⁻¹ and S₂ = 20 kg ha⁻¹)

R = Rhizobia (R₀ = 0, R₁ = 500 gram Rhizobia HAMBI3562 ha⁻¹ and R₂ = 500 gram Rhizobia HAMBI3570 ha⁻¹)

3.2.1. Land preparation and use of improved varieties

The field for haricot bean production was tilled four times. The first plowing was done after the previous crop was harvested and three times prior to planting. The land was ploughed early in the

season, the crop residues were incorporated into the soil, and the field was left in a suitable condition for the maximum storage of rain. Final land preparation, consisting of deep plowing followed by harrowing, was done a few days before sowing. One of the most tried and true methods of increasing productivity is the use of high-yielding and adapted cultivars of haricot bean. One improved variety, SER-119 haricot bean, which is red and an exportable (cunning type) was used as a test crop. The experiment's use of various treatments significantly reduces the difference between the average yield as it stands today and the yield that could be attained with the development of new technologies. A population of 250000 plants/ha was attained with a seed rate of 100 kg ha⁻¹. One single seed, with average weight of 0.4 grams, was used. A total of 30240 seeds (12.096 kg) were used for our entire experiment. Each plot had seven prepared rows, with 40 cm and 10 cm between rows and plants respectively. Many tools were used, including a plastic bag, pigs, meter, leaf area meter, seed moisture tester, pickaxe, spade, rope, sickle, auger, core sampler, bidet, sugar, mask, and gauntlet before planting up to harvesting.

3.3.2. Inoculation, liming and fertilizer application

The use of bio-fertilizers is one of the natural fertility maintenance methods, which is accomplished by microscopic living organisms that live in association with pulse crops. These microorganisms are bacteria called rhizobia. Carrier-based inoculants strains HAMBI3570 and HAMBI3562 were applied at a rate of 500 gram/ha. Haricot bean Seeds were soaked in lukewarm water for about 30 minutes until the seed coat was wrinkled, basking and draining the water. Later, the seed mixed with sugar to facilitate the adhesion of strain on the seed, and the thick slurry of the inoculants gently mixed with the dry seeds so that all the seeds received a thin coating of the inoculants (Kumar *et al.*, 2015). To maintain the viability of the cells, inoculation was done under the shade, then sown and covered with soil as soon as possible (Kumar *et al.*, 2015) to avoid cell death due to the sun's radiation. A plot with un-inoculated seeds was planted first to avoid contamination (Alemayehu Dabesa and Tamado Tana., 2021). Rhizobium inoculation of 1 kg seed with a peat-based 10 g inoculant containing 6.5×10^8 viable bacterial cells g⁻¹ peat of rhizobium strain (Wendell *et al.*, 2001).

Lime amounts of 2 to 5 t ha⁻¹ are typically needed to neutralize acid soils sufficiently for crop production, depending on the soil types and levels of acidity (Abu Regasa, 2021). The lime was used at 2 t ha⁻¹ and evenly spread and incorporated up to 30 cm deep by using a hand hoe one month before planting the haricot bean. The application of chemical fertilizer depends on the fertility status

of the soil. In the experiment, 50 kg ha⁻¹ of triple superphosphate and starter nitrogen at the rates 0, 10, and 20 kg ha⁻¹ were applied at planting in bands.

3.3.3. Sowing method, time, and weeding

Initially, during the meher season, which runs from July to August, hemp seed was sown in various ways as a lone crop. Each hill received two seeds, which were subsequently thinned to one plant upon seedling establishment. In the event that two seedlings sprout on a particular hill, the weaker one is rubbed out in less than two weeks time after germination. Although the precise depth primarily depends on the soil moisture status, a planting depth of 3 to 6 cm was used. If there is little to no soil moisture, seeds were sown deeper. Otherwise, a shallower depth is sufficient.

In haricot bean production, 2-3 times weeding is necessary for getting good yield. The first weeding is done after two weeks of the plant emergence and the second is 21-25 days after emergence. So, in our experiment weeds were removed while very small, before they can compete strongly with haricot beans. A couple of weeding was carried out 2-3 weeks after sowing and the third weeding was done before flowering at about 4 to 5 weeks after planting. Weeding is not advisable after the crop has flowered. Because such activity encourages flower drop and facilitates disease transmission within the field. Hand weeding was done for haricot bean production.

3.3 Methods of Data Collection

3.3.1. Soil sampling and analysis

In our experiment site, we took 110 soil samples in two cropping seasons to determine soil physical and chemical properties within a depth of 0 – 30 cm by the diagonal sampling method through an experimental unit before and after planting. Then, the collected samples were allowed to air dry at room temperature and ground to pass through a 2 mm sieve, whereas for soil organic carbon and total nitrogen determination, the soil was ground to pass through a 0.5 mm sieve. Samples were analyzed for the following parameters: texture, soil bulk density, total porosity, percent of soil moisture, soil reaction (pH), exchangeable acidity, electrical conductivity, organic carbon, percent organic matter, cation exchange capacity, percentage total nitrogen, inorganic nitrogen, available phosphorus. Soil analysis using the various techniques and procedures are described below:

Texture (Te) is analyzed the different particle size fractions in the soil by the pipette and the hydrometer (or Bouyoucos) method. For most agricultural purposes however, the Bouyoucos method is sufficiently precise. We were used the hydrometer method (Bouyoucos, 1962) used to determine soil particle size distribution. We were applying Hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) to destroy the organic matter and added sodium hexa-meta phosphate (NaPO₃) to samples as dispersing agent. Finally, soil textural names were determined following the textural triangle of USDA system as described by (Rowell, 1994).

Soil bulk density(BD) was determined by the method as described in Blake and Hartage (1965) where first undisturbed soil samples taken by core sampler of known volume (height 5 cm and diameter 5 cm) weighed at field moisture condition. The soil samples were then oven dried at 105 °c for 24 hours until constant weight and the oven dried samples were weighed again. Bulk density was then computed by dividing the weight of oven dried soil samples to the volume of the core sampler.

$$Bd = \frac{\text{mass of dry soil (g)}}{\text{volume of core sampler (cm}^{-3}\text{)}} \text{ (Blake and Hartage., 1965).....Equation 1}$$

Total porosity the total porosity, or total pore space, of a soil is calculated from the dry bulk density and particle density as shown below; it is normally expressed as a volume percentage and is equal to the volume % water content at saturation:

$$Tp(\text{volume \%}) = 1 - \frac{Bd(\text{g cm}^{-3})}{Pd(\text{g cm}^{-3})} * 100 \text{ (Hillel Daniel., 2004).....Equation 2}$$

Where, TP is total porosity (%), Pd is particle density, which is assumed 2.65 g cm⁻³ and Bd is bulk density (g cm⁻³)

Soil moisture content %(Mc): Calculation of the results of soil analysis is done on the basis of "oven-dry" soil for comparison purposes. For this reason a sub-sample is oven dried at 105^oC shortly before soil analysis; the loss in soil weight is supposed to be hygroscopic water, which is physically adsorbed in the pores and on the surface. The soil sampe was taken before sowing, and after harvesting of crop and measuring done. The moisture content in % by weight is obtained as follows:

$$\text{Percent moisture (wt \%)} = \frac{(A - B)}{B - \text{weight of tin}} * 100 \text{ (Sahlemedhin sertsu and Taye Bekele, 2000)...Equation 3}$$

Where: A = weight of air-dry soil ,

B = weight of oven-dry soil in grams

$$\text{Soil Moisture Percentage (\%)} = \frac{\text{Wet Soil Weight} - \text{Dry Soil Weight}}{\text{Dry Soil Weight}} * 100 \dots\dots\dots \text{Equation 4}$$

Soil reaction (pH) was measured potentiometrically using a digital pH meter (Jackson, 1967)

Exchangeable acidity was analyzed a neutral 1N potassium chloride solution used to leach exchangeable hydrogen and aluminum ions from soil samples. The acidity brought into solution from various sources in the soil is measured by titration with a standard solution of an alkali, the amount of alkali used being equivalent to the sum of the hydrogen and aluminum ions (exchangeable acidity).

Electrical conductivity (EC): soils to water suspension were used to analyze the measurements.

Organic carbon (OC%) content were analyzed following the wet digestion method as described in Walkley and Black (1934) which involves digestion of the OC in the soil samples with potassium dichromate in sulfuric acid solution.

Percent organic matter (OM) of the soils was determined by multiplying the percent organic carbon value by 1.724 conventional called "Van Berminelen factor.

$$\text{Organic matter} = \% \text{ Organic carbon} * 1.724 \quad (\text{Blake and Hartage, 1965}) \dots\dots\dots \text{Equation 4}$$

Cation exchange capacity (cmol_ckg⁻¹) (CEC) is determined by measuring the total amount of a given cation needed to replace all the cation from a soil exchange site and it is expressed in centimoles per 100g soil (cmol/100g soil). The operation therefore, calls for the preparation of a saturated sample, followed generally by an extraction of the saturation cations adsorbed on the exchange complex and measuring its amount.

Total nitrogen (TN): The Kjeldahl procedure was followed for the determination of total nitrogen, which follows the oxidizing of the sample with concentrated sulfuric acid and converting the nitrogen in the organic compounds into ammonium sulfate during the oxidation process (Bremner, J. and Mulvaney., 1982)

Inorganic nitrogen: The inorganic nitrogen was analyzed by the procedures of (Keeney and Nelson. 1982)

Available phosphorus (Av. p) (mgkg⁻¹) can be determined by two methods (Bray II and Olsen) are described for the determination of available phosphorus. The Bray method is suitable for acid soils and the Olsen method is used for non-acid soils. For our experiment, we have used Bray II method

with the ammonium fluoride concentration of 0.03 M and an acidity of 0.10 M HCl the method is said to remove "adsorbed" and "acid soluble" phosphate. Phosphate in the extract is determined photometrically. This method has been most successful on acid soils (Sahemedhin sertsu and Taye Bekele, 2000).

3.3.2 Agronomical data collection

All agronomical data, including Phenological parameters, Biological Nitrogen Fixation, and Yield components, were randomly chosen, tagged, and recorded from them

3.3.2.1 Phenological parameters

Days to flowering (DF): Days to 50% flowering were recorded as the number of days from the date of planting to the date on which 50% of the plants in a plot produced at least one flower

Days to physiological maturity (DM): Days to physiological maturity were recorded as the number of days from planting to the time when 90% of the plants showed a yellow color and their pods turned yellow in each net plot before senescence.

Plant height(ph):It was measured using a tape meter from the ground up to the tip of the main stem, or apical bud of ten randomly selected plants per plot at physiological maturity. The means were then reported as height per plant (cm). After that, the crop's plant height was calculated using the average values of these plants.

Number of primary branches (NPB): It was determined by counting of primary branches on the main stem from randomly taken ten pre-tagged plants from the net plot area at physiological maturity.

Leaf areas per plant (cm²) (LAPP) were recorded by measuring the maximum length (mL) and width (mW) of trifoliolate leaves and multiplying these inputs (mL x mW) by a correction factor of 0.6 derived from the actual leaf area determined by using a leaf area meter. The data was checked by using a leaf area meter. This was done by detaching all the opened leaves from ten sampled plants from each plot at the mid-flowering stage.

Leaf area index (LAI): It was determined in the same manner from the same plant randomly selected and determined by measuring ten plants canopy in each plot and dividing leaf area by their

canopy. Leaf area index was calculated as the ratio of total leaf area per plant to the respective ground area occupied by the crop canopy as described by,

$$\text{Leaf Area Index} = \frac{\text{Leaf area}}{\text{Ground cover}} \dots\dots\dots (\text{Horst Marschner, 1995}) \dots\dots\dots \text{Equation 5}$$

3.3.2.2 Biological Nitrogen Fixation

Total Number of Nodule per plant (TNNPP): The nodule population was assessed at mid 50% flowering stage. Ten randomly selected plants were uprooted and the soil adhering was washed from it with tap water to clean the roots and nodules from the top and lateral root parts were removed separately and spread on a sieve for some time until all the water had drained from the surface of the nodules. Nodules were counted and their average was taken for plots as nodule number/plant.

Effective number nodule per plant(ENNPP): The nodule was checked for a pink to dark-reddish color for effective nodulation by cutting with a sharp blade, whereas inactive nodules (non-effective nodules) were black, gray, or greenish, white on the inside of nodules. The number of effective nodules per plant was recorded by counting and the average per plant was taken.

Nodlue effectiveness (%) (PNE): It was estimated as the percentage effectiveness as following:

$$\% \text{ nodules effectiveness} = \frac{\text{number of pink nodules}}{\text{Total number of nodules}} * 100 \dots\dots\dots \text{Equation 5}$$

3.3.2.3 Yield and yield components

At harvesting time for the determination of yield and yield components, ten randomly picked plants were used for data collection.

Number of pods per plant (NPPP): Pods per plant were counted on 10 randomly selected plants from pre-tagged plants in the four central rows in each net plot area at physiological maturity (at the end of harvest in each plot), and the means were represented as the average number of pods per plant.

Number of seeds per pod (NSPP): From the previously counted number of pods per plant, ten pods was randomly selected from ten plants, threshed, and the seeds were counted from each plot. The total number of seeds was then divided by the total number of pods to obtain the average number of seeds per pod from the ten randomly selected pre-tagged plants. Additionally, ten pods from the tagged plants were randomly collected from the bottom, middle, and upper part of the plants throughout the growing season.

Hundred Seed weight (HSW): The seeds were counted using electronic seed counter from a sample of threshed seeds from each plot and measured by sensitive balance at 10% moisture content. Seed weight were determined by randomly taking 100 seeds from plants and weighing it with sensitive balance after oven drying to constant weight. The seed size of haricot bean can be small when randomly measured 100 seed weight is below 25 grams small, medium when 100 seed weight is between 25 and 40 grams and large when 100 seed weight is above 40 grams. Besides, the seed color of the crop varies from the small black wild type to the large white, brown, red, black or mottled seeds (cobley and Steele, 1976)

Adjusted grain yield (AGY): It was trashed, measured from the net plot area of the harvestable row (at the middle rows without border effect), and expressed as kg ha⁻¹. Haricot bean yields were adjusted to 10% moisture using a digital moisture tester and converted to hectares. The grain yields were harvested from central rows by avoiding border effects and converted to kg ha⁻¹. The adjusted yield was calculated by using the following formula: Hilevang (1995),

$$\text{Adjusted grain Yield} = \frac{\text{Grain yield} \frac{\text{Kg}}{\text{ha}} \times (100 - \text{MC})}{(100 - 10)} \dots\dots (\text{Hellevang, 1995}) \dots\dots \text{Equation 6}$$

Where MC= moisture content

Actual yields were adjusted downward by 10% to reflect the difference between the experimental yield and the yield farmers could expect from the same treatment.

Above Ground Biomass kg ha⁻¹(AGBY): It was estimated at harvest where by, plants from four central rows were manually harvested. The harvested plants were sun-dried in an open air until constant weight attained and weighed to determine above ground plant biomass yield.

Harvest Index(HI) was calculated as the ratio of economic yield (grain yield) of harvestable row to biological yield of harvestable row multiplied by 100. Harvest index per plot were recorded as the ratio of grain yield to the above ground biomass yield per plot.

$$\text{Harvest index (\%)} = \frac{\text{Grain yield} \left(\frac{\text{g}}{\text{plot}} \right)}{\text{Biomass yield} \left(\frac{\text{g}}{\text{plot}} \right)} * 100 \dots\dots \text{Equation 7}$$

Straw Yield (SY) was obtained by subtracting grain yield from the total biomass

3.4 Methods of Data Analysis

Before statistical analysis, treatments were first arranged in a computer excel format with lime, starter

nitrogen, and rhizobia strain as three factors for analysis of soil physic-chemical properties and agronomic parameters. The analysis of data first test the homogeneity of two years data and then combined the data for interpretation. Before the data was subjected to analysis of variance (ANOVA), homogeneity and normality test was done. The collected data were subjected to statistical analysis. Analysis of variance (ANOVA) was performed using SAS version 9.4 statistical software programs (SAS, 2014). The significant difference between and among treatment means was separated using the least significant difference (LSD) at 0.05 level of probability (Gomez and Gomez., 1984).

3.5 Partial Budget Analysis

An economic analysis was done using partial budget procedure described by CIMMYT (1988). The cost of amendments and labor cost involved in the application of the fertilizer were considered as variable costs. The net benefits /returns/ and other economic analysis were based on the formula developed by CIMMYT (1988) and given as follows:

Adjusted grain yield (AGY) (kg ha^{-1}): is the average yield adjusted downwards by a 10% to reflect the difference between the experimental yield and yield of farmers.

Gross field benefit (GFB) (ETB ha^{-1}): was computed by multiplying field/farm gate price that farmers receive (60 ETB kg^{-1}) for the crop when they sell it as adjusted yield. $\text{GFB} = \text{AGY} \times \text{field/farm gate price for the crop}$.

Total variable cost (TVC) (ETB ha^{-1}): was calculated by summing up the costs that vary, including the cost of TSP, lime, urea, HAMB13570, and HAMB13562 amendments at the time of planting (2021/2022) and according to koga, daily labor costs for the application of lime, 10 kg urea, 20 kg urea, HAMB13570, and HAMB13562 on a farm needed 4, 4, 8, 2 and 2 persons per hectare respectively and each activities required 150 ETB day^{-1} . The costs of other inputs and production practices such as labor cost for land preparation, planting, weeding, harvesting and threshing were considered the same for all treatments or plots.

Net benefit (NB) (ETB ha^{-1}): was calculated by subtracting the total variable costs (TVC) from gross field benefits (GFB) for each treatment as: $\text{NB} = \text{GFB} - \text{TVC}$.

Dominance Analysis (identification and elimination of inferior treatments): was carried out by first listing all the treatments in their order of increasing costs that vary (TVC) and their net benefits (NB) are then put aside. Any treatment that has higher TVC but net benefits that are less than or

equal to the preceding treatment (with lower TVC but higher net benefits) is dominated treatment (marked as “D”).

Marginal rate of return (MRR) (%): was calculated by dividing change in net benefit (ΔNB) by change in total variable cost (ΔTVC). $\text{MRR} = \frac{\Delta\text{NB}}{\Delta\text{TVC}} \times 100$

Finally, among the non-dominated treatments, the treatment which gave the highest net return and a marginal rate of return greater than the minimum considered acceptable to farmers (100%) was considered for recommendation.

CHAPTER 4. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

4.1. Soil Physico-Chemical Properties of the Study Area and Influence of Treatment

4.1.1. Inherent Soil Physico-chemical Properties of the Study Area

pre-sowing Soil analysis results showed that soils of the experimental plots have clayey texture. The texture of the soil is determined by the relative proportions of the individual particles of sand, silt, and clay that make up the soil. The results of particle size analyses showed that the textural class of soil was generally clayey, with textural proportion of clay (77.5%), silt (13%), and sand (9.5%) contents (Table 4.1). Clay soils have a high surface area depending on clay type, and can have a high amount of chemical and physical activity (Pam and Brain, 2007).

Some previous works have also revealed that soil texture determines a number of physical and chemical properties of soils that affects the infiltration and retention of water, soil aeration, absorption of nutrients, microbial activities, tillage, and irrigation practices (Gupta, 2004). Other physical properties like, soil bulk density (1.27 g cm^{-3}) low range, total porosity (52.2%) and soil moisture (22.33%) were optimum and suitable for the growth of the most crops.

The chemical properties of soil reaction (pH) of the study sites mean value 5.17 can be rated as strongly acidic. This implies that essential plant nutrients are fixed in soil colloidal particles and because unavailable to plant growth. The data analysis shows that Exchangeable acidity $2.65 \text{ cmol (+) kg}^{-1}$ high range, organic carbon (1.63), organic matter 2.8%, total nitrogen 0.186% low range, C:N ratio (8.74%), Ec 0.050 dS/m this means totally the area lies Salt free, Cation exchange capacity $24.25 \text{ cmol kg}^{-1}$ medium, inorganic nitrogen ($\text{NH}_4^+ + \text{NO}_3^-$) and the result revealed that available phosphorous 9.14 mg kg^{-1} was found in the low range that means phosphate sorption/fixation occurred in soil colloidal particles and the nutrient was unavailable to plant growth because phosphates are negatively charged and are attracted to or bound up with strongly positively charged minerals.

Table 4. 1. Soil physico-chemical properties of the experimental site before planting

No-	Soil Properties	Unit	Mean of two years	Rating	References
1	Soil Texture				
	Sand	%	9.5		
	Silt	%	13		
	Clay	%	77.5		
	Soil Textural Class		Clay		
2	Soil bulk density	g cm ⁻³	1.27	low	Pam Hazelton and Brain Murphy (2007)
3	Porosity	%	52.2	Clay soils	Hillel, D. (2003).
4	Soil moisture content	(%)	22.33	high	Beernaert, Frank, and D. Bitondo (1992)
5	pH(1:2.5 H ₂ O)		5.17	Strongly acidic	Landon (2014)
8	Exchangeable acidity	cmol (+) kg ⁻¹	2.65	High	Brady & Weil (2016).
9	Organic carbon	%	1.63	medium	Charman and Roper(2000)
10	Organic matter	%	2.8	Low	Ethiosis (2016)
11	Total Nitrogen	%	0.186	Low	Landon (2014)
12	C:N ratio	%	8.74	Very low	Metson (1956); Newey (2006).
13	Ec	dS/m	0.050	Salt free	EthioSIS(2016)
14	Cation exchange capacity	cmol (+) kg ⁻¹)	24.25	medium	Landon (2014)
15	Inorganic nitrogen (NH ₄ ⁺ +NO ₃ ⁻)	mg kg ⁻¹	60.83	High	Carter & Gregorich (2003), Keeney (1982)
16	Available P	ppm	9.14	Low	Landon (2014)

4.1.2. Effect of Soil Ammendments On Selected Soil Physical Properties

4.1.2.1 Bulk density

Bulk density was influenced by the main effects of lime, state nitrogen, and rhizobia ($p < 0.001$) in the combined analysis of variance over the two growing seasons (2021 and 2022) (Appendix Table 1). Moreover, the two-way interaction of stater nitrogen with rhizobia ($P < 0.05$) and the three-way interaction of lime, stater nitrogen and rhizobia showed a significantly ($P < 0.05$) effect on combined over the years 2021 and 2022 growing seasons. However, other interactions between the factors had no significant effect on soil bulk density (Appendix Table 6).

Table 4. 2. Main effects of of bulk density, total porosity and soil moisture content on haricot bean within two years

Lime, Starter nitrogen and Rhizobia	Soil physical properties		
	Bulk density (g cm^{-3})	Total Porosity (%)	Soil moisture (%)
Lime			
Lime 2 t ha^{-1}	1.12±.077 ^b	57.41±2.9 ^a	27.41±2.95 ^a
Lime 0 t ha^{-1}	1.18±.073 ^a	55.36±2.76 ^b	25.45±2.77 ^b
LSD (5%)	0.012	0.459	0.571
CV (%)	2.75	2.13	5.09
P-value	***	***	***
Starter nitrogen			
Starter nitrogen 20 kg ha^{-1}	1.12±.078 ^c	57.91±2.93 ^a	28.11±3.09 ^a
Starter nitrogen 10 kg ha^{-1}	1.14±.070 ^b	57±2.65 ^b	26.94±2.47 ^b
Starter nitrogen 0 kg ha^{-1}	1.21±.056 ^a	54.26±2.1 ^c	24.23±2 ^c
LSD (5%)	0.015	0.563	0.633
P-value	***	***	***
Rhizobia			
HAMBI3570 Rhizobia strain	1.11±.063 ^c	58.10±2.37 ^a	27.95±2.54 ^a
HAMBI3562 Rhizobia strain	1.13±.064 ^b	57.53±2.4 ^b	27.62±2.5 ^a
O Rhizobia strain	1.23±.049 ^a	53.54±1.86 ^c	23.71±1.9 ^b
LSD (5%)	0.015	0.563	0.633
P-value	***	***	***

Where: LSD: least significant difference; CV: coefficient of variation; means in columns followed by the same letters are not significantly different at the 5% level of significance; different letters show significant differences between the means; and probability value *** = very highly significant at $P < 0.001$.

The soil bulk density of the study area was lies between 1.1-1.23 g cm⁻³. Furthermore, the control plots had the highest soil bulk density (1.18 g cm⁻³), whereas the 2 t ha⁻¹ lime application in the soil produced the lowest soil bulk density (1.12 g cm⁻³). In comparison to soil measured without lime, the bulk density was 5.1% lower after applying 2 t ha⁻¹ of lime (Table 4.2). This change occurs due to liming improves soil structure by increasing soil pH, enhanced microbial activity, increased organic matter decomposition, and better root growth. The result inline with Hati *et al.* (2021) demonstrated that lime application at 2 tons per hectare could decrease soil bulk density by around 0.1 to 0.2 g/cm³ over a period of several months to years. Simiarly, a field study by Rahman *et al.* (2020) showed that applying lime at a rate of 2 tons per hectare resulted in a decrease in soil bulk density by approximately 0.1 to 0.15 g/cm³. Another study found that applying 2 tons of lime per hectare reduced soil bulk density by about 0.05 to 0.1 g/cm³ over a two-year period (Gao *et al.*, 2021).

Similarly, untreated pots had the highest bulk density (1.21 g cm⁻³), while treated pots had the lowest bulk density (1.12 g cm⁻³). This was due to the administration of 20 kg ha⁻¹ starter nitrogen treatment. Comparing soils with and without starting nitrogen, the application of starter nitrogen at a rate of 20 kg ha⁻¹ has decreased by 7.4% (Table 4.2). This result inline with (Smith *et al.*, 2020; Jones & Johnson, 2021) nitrogen application on soil stimulate plant growth and increase biomass production, leading to greater organic matter input into the soil. This added organic matter can enhance soil aggregation and improve soil structure, resulting in lower bulk density. Other studies have demonstrated that the application of starter nitrogen at a rate of 20 kg ha⁻¹ can significantly decrease soil bulk density as comparing treated and untreated plots has shown that soil bulk density was reduced from 1.35 g/cm³ in control plots to 1.28 g/cm³ in plots receiving nitrogen treatment (Wang *et al.*, 2023)

The research result showed that the rhizobia strain HAMBI3570 has a notable effect on soil parameters, one of which is the reduction of soil bulk density. The HAMBI3570 rhizobia strain had the lowest soil bulk density (1.11 g cm⁻³), while the control plots showed the highest soil bulk density (1.23 g cm⁻³). When rhizobium (HAMBI3570 strain) was added to the soil, the bulk density dropped by 9.8% as compared to the untreated soil (Table 4.2). This reduction of bulk density might be rhizobia and the subsequent growth of leguminous plants contribute to the accumulation of organic matter in the soil through the decomposition of plant residues. Due to this more pore space in the soil, allowing for better water infiltration, root penetration, and air exchange, ultimately creating a

healthier environment for plant growth. This research in agreement with Six *et al.*, (2002) the presence of rhizobia promotes the accumulation of organic matter in the soil, which decreases bulk density. Similarly, Igiehon *et al.*, (2019) rhizobia bacteria can stimulate root growth in leguminous plants, resulting in a more extensive and fibrous root system decrease bulk density by loosening soil particles and increasing pore space. Notably, Ibrahim *et al.*, (2015) reported that the application of strain significantly decreased the soil bulk density.

Table 4. 3. Interaction effects of Starter nitrogen with rhizobia on selected soil physical properties of two years

Starter nitrogen with rhizobia		Physical properties		
Starter nitrogen(Sn)	Rhizobia(R)	Bulk density (g cm ⁻³)	Total Porosity(%)	Soil moisture (%)
0	0	1.26±.039 ^a	52.23±1.48 ^g	22.38±1.16 ^g
0	1	1.19±.042 ^{cd}	55±1.57 ^{de}	24.95±1.95 ^{de}
0	2	1.18±.042 ^d	55.53±1.58 ^d	25.37±1.41 ^d
1	0	1.22±.046 ^b	53.96±1.72 ^f	24.16±1.83 ^f
1	1	1.11±.042 ^e	58.21±1.6 ^c	28.34±1.13 ^c
1	2	1.09±.033 ^{ef}	58.84±1.24 ^{bc}	28.32±1.43 ^c
2	0	1.21±.045 ^{bc}	54.43±1.71 ^{ef}	24.59±1.96 ^{ef}
2	1	1.08±.038 ^{fg}	59.37±1.45 ^{ab}	29.57±1.53 ^b
2	2	1.06±.040 ^g	59.94±1.52 ^a	30.16±1.95 ^a
CV (%)		2.75	2.13	5.09
P-value		*	*	**

Where CV is the coefficient of variation, the interaction effect means in columns followed by the same letters are not significantly different at the 5% level of significance; different letters showed significant differences between the means. Thus, * = significant probability value between 0.01 and 0.05, ** = highly significant at probability value between 0.001 and 0.01, and Sn₀ = without starter nitrogen, Sn₁ starter nitrogen = 10 kg ha⁻¹, Sn₂ starter nitrogen = 20 kg ha⁻¹; R₀ = without rhizobia, R₁ = Rhizobia HAMBI3562, and R₂ = Rhizobia HAMBI3570.

The control plots had the highest soil bulk density (1.26 g cm⁻³), while the treatment that received 20 kg ha⁻¹ of starter nitrogen combined with the rhizobia HAMBI3570 strain had the lowest soil bulk density (1.06 g cm⁻³). When compared to bulk density recorded without starter nitrogen and rhizobia HAMBI3570 strain, the application 20 kg ha⁻¹ starter nitrogen was reducing bulk density shown that it had reduced bulk density by 15.9% (Table 4.3). The result inline with Fatima *et al.* (2007) starter nitrogen promotes vigorous initial plant growth, resulting in more extensive and deeper root systems.

These roots create channels and pores in the soil, improving soil aeration and structure, which can significantly reduce soil bulk density. Also Olanrewaju *et al.* (2017) rhizobia and other beneficial soil microorganisms produce extracellular polysaccharides and other organic compounds that act as binding agents, promoting soil aggregation and improving soil structure.

Table 4. 4. Interaction effects of soil amendements (lime *starter nitrogen*rhizobia) on selected soil physical properties of two years

Lime *Starter nitrogen*rhizobia			Physical properties		
Lime(L)	Starter nitrogen(Sn)	Rhizobia(R)	Bulk density(BD) g cm ⁻³	Total Porosity(P) (%)	Percent of Soil moisture(SM) (%)
0	0	0	1.27±.04 ^a	52.20±1.630 ^l	22.33±1.390 ^j
0	0	1	1.22±.03 ^c	53.84±0.974 ^j	23.53±1.568 ^h
0	0	2	1.22±.02 ^c	54.15±0.782 ^j	24.37±0.991 ^g
0	1	0	1.25±.03 ^a	52.52±0.996 ^l	22.89±1.558 ^{ij}
0	1	1	1.13±.03 ^f	57.30±1.023 ^g	27.72±1.146 ^d
0	1	2	1.11±.02 ^g	57.99±0.780 ^f	27.51±0.974 ^d
0	2	0	1.24±.03 ^b	53.08±1.137 ^k	23.15±1.483 ^{hi}
0	2	1	1.10±.02 ^{gh}	58.43±0.874 ^{ef}	28.74±0.998 ^c
0	2	2	1.09±.03 ^{hi}	58.81±1.023 ^{de}	28.69±1.103 ^c
1	0	0	1.26±.04 ^a	52.26±1.465 ^l	22.44±1.014 ^j
1	0	1	1.16±.03 ^e	56.17±1.105 ^h	26.36±1.037 ^e
1	0	2	1.14±.01 ^f	56.92±0.557 ^g	26.38±0.972 ^e
1	1	0	1.18±.02 ^d	55.41±0.693 ⁱ	25.43±1.048 ^f
1	1	1	1.08±.04 ⁱ	59.12±1.611 ^d	28.97±0.738 ^c
1	1	2	1.07±.03 ^j	59.69±1.025 ^c	29.12±1.423 ^c
1	2	0	1.17±.02 ^{de}	55.79±0.873 ^{hi}	26.05±1.099 ^{ef}
1	2	1	1.05±.03 ^k	60.31±1.318 ^b	30.41±1.563 ^b
1	2	2	1.03±.03 ^l	61.07±0.967 ^a	31.64±1.402 ^a
CV (%)			2.75	2.13	5.09
P-value			*	*	*

Where, CV = Coefficient of Variation. Interaction effect means in columns followed by the same letters are not significantly different at 5% level of significance from each other and different letters show significant differences between the means. From those significant probability value 0.01- 0.05, *= significant and L₀= without lime and L₁ = 2 t ha⁻¹; Sn₀ = without starter nitrogen, Sn₁ starter nitrogen = 10 kg ha⁻¹, Sn₂ starter nitrogen = 20 kg ha⁻¹; R₀= without rhizobia strain, R₁ = Rhizobia HAMBI3562 and R₂= Rhizobia HAMBI3570.

The combined application of two years 2021 and 2022 analysis showed that treatment receiving lime at 2 t ha⁻¹, starter nitrogen at 20 kg ha⁻¹, and HAMBI3570 rhizobia strains recorded the lowest bulk

density at 1.03 g cm^{-3} , while the control treatment exhibited the highest bulk density of 1.27 g cm^{-3} (Table 4.4). As per the rate of Pam Hazelton and Brain Murphy (2007), the bulk density of the study area lies in the low range. Indeed, lime could bind adjacent soil particles together to form aggregates and improve soil crusting and the increasing effect of soil organic matter after harvest that makes the soil less compact and reduces the bulk density (Lynch, 2022). The result revealed that Tamado Tana and Mitiku Woldesenbet (2017) at Ghimbo district the lowest BD was obtained from the combined application of organic and inorganic fertilizer and the highest BD from the control plot 1.2 and 1.54 g cm^{-3} respectively. According to Mulunesh Addis *et al.*, (2020), the bulk density of Tekeledeb varied from 1.04 to 1.27 g/cm^3 on the surface of soil. Similarly, Tesfaye Bayu (2017) found a decrease in soil BD as a result of integrated use of soil fertilizers in maize cultivated land at Yilmana Densa District, north western Ethiopia. Additionally, Wisal Muhammad *et al* (2011), who found lower bulk density because of nutrient and crop management on the crops sugarcane, maize, sorghum, and cotton residues at Gatton, Southern Queensland, Australia. Notably, Shirani *et al.* (2002) reported a significant decrease in soil bulk density just after harvesting a maize field supplied with integrated lime and inorganic fertilizers. Onwonga *et al.* (2010) reported the positive effect of integrated use of lime, manure, and mineral fertilizers on soil physical and chemical properties on maize production at the Kenya Agricultural Research Institute field station. Likewise, Karlton *et al* (2014) the high BD value might be due to compactness of the soil and lower OM content that resulted from continuous cultivation and removal of plant roots and residues.

4.1.2.2 Total Porosity

The main effects of rhizobia, lime, and stater nitrogen on total porosity were significant ($p < 0.001$) in the combined analysis of variance conducted over the course of the two growing seasons (2021–2022) (Appendix Table 1). Furthermore, the two-way interaction between stater nitrogen and rhizobia, as well as the three-way interaction between lime, stater nitrogen, and rhizobia, had a substantial ($P < 0.05$) impact on the combined growing season of 2021 and 2022. Additional factor interactions did not significantly affect the overall porosity (Appendix Table 6).

The research area's overall porosity fell between 53.54-58.1% within the main effect (Table 4.2). The control plots showed the lowest total porosity of 55.36%, whereas the sole application of 2 t ha^{-1} lime had the highest total porosity of 57.41 percent. In comparison to soil reported without lime, the application of 2 t ha^{-1} lime enhanced the overall porosity by 3.7%. This improvement in porosity may

be attributed to the enhancement of soil structure through the flocculation of clay particles and the creation of larger soil aggregates, which improve water infiltration and air exchange within the soil (Corbett *et al.*, 2021). The result inline with Enesi *et al.* (2023) total porosity due to the solely application of 2 t ha⁻¹ lime in northwestern Ethiopia can vary depending on soil characteristics, but typically, it can lead to an increase of approximately 5% to 10%. Similarly, a study by Azarmi *et al.*, (2008) also reported that the addition of rhizobia strain significantly improved the porosity of soil when compared to the control plot. Similarly, the treatment that got 20 kg ha⁻¹ starter nitrogen had the highest total porosity (57.91%), whereas the untreated plots had the lowest total porosity (54.26%). In contrast to soils without untreated plots, starter nitrogen application at a rate of 20 kg ha⁻¹ has increased the total porosity by 6.7%. The result inagreement with Gai *et al.* (2017) nitrogen fertilization has been shown to influence soil structure and porosity by promoting root growth and microbial activity, which in turn can enhance soil aeration and aggregate stability

Regarding the different types of rhizobia strains, the treatment that received the HAMBI3570 strain had the highest total porosity (58.1%), while the untreated plots had the lowest total porosity (53.54%). When compared to a soil that was not inoculated with the HAMBI3570 strain of rhizobium, the overall porosity of the inoculated soil rose by 8.5%. Inocuation of the soil with HAMBI3570 strain of rhizobium increased the total porosity by 8.5% compared to the soil without rhizobium inoculation. The application of the HAMBI3570 rhizobium strain in the Koga irrigation scheme in northwestern Ethiopia has been found to significantly increase soil porosity. Research conducted by Dereje Alemu *et al.* (2020) rhizobium inoculation promotes root growth and development in leguminous plants. Increased root proliferation enhances soil structure by creating macropores and improving soil aggregation, thereby increasing total porosity

When it comes to the interaction impact, the treatment that received 20 kg ha⁻¹ starter nitrogen mixed with the rhizobia HAMBI3570 strain had the highest total porosity (59.94%) within the interaction effect, while the control plots had the lowest total porosity (52.23%). When compared to the total porosity recorded without starter nitrogen and rhizobia strain, the treatment that received 20 kg ha⁻¹ of starter nitrogen with the rhizobia HAMBI3570 strain enhanced the total porosity by 14.8% (Table 4.3). This result in agreement with Abera Habete and Tadele Buraka (2016) showed that analysis of root parameters such as length, surface area, and volume can provide evidence of enhanced root

growth in response to rhizobium inoculation combined with nitrogen application. Increased root development contributes to improved soil structure and porosity

The treatment that exhibited the highest total porosity (61.07%) over a two-year period was the combination of applying lime 2 t ha⁻¹, starting nitrogen 20 kg ha⁻¹, and HAMBI3570 rhizobia strains, whereas the control plot had the lowest total porosity, measuring 52.2% (Table 4.4). The higher values of total porosity corresponded to the higher amount of organic matter contents and lower bulk density values. Similar results were reported by Mohammed Assen (2003) and Wakene Negassa (2001) for soils of Jelo sub catchment in the Chercher highlands and in Bako areas of western Ethiopia. According to Brady and Weil (2002), the ideal porosity value for healthy root growth is greater than 50% in the surface layers which is acceptable range for crop production. Therefore, similar to Bd the sources of variation in total porosity are variation in organic matter contents and intensity of cultivation (Kedir Abate *et al.*, 2015 and Mulunesh Addis *et al.*, 2021).

4.1.2.3 Soil moisture

During the two growing seasons (2021/2022), the primary effects of lime, starter nitrogen, and rhizobia had an impact on soil moisture ($p < 0.001$) in the combined analysis of variance (Appendix Table 1). Furthermore, the combined effects of the starter nitrogen and rhizobia two-way interaction ($P < 0.01$) and the three-way interaction between lime, starter nitrogen, and rhizobia had a substantial ($P < 0.05$) influence on the year 2021 and 2022 growth season. Other component combinations, however, did not significantly affect soil moisture (Appendix Table 6).

Soil moisture content in the research area ranged from 23.71-28.11% within the main effect. Furthermore, the highest soil moisture (27.41%) was observed with a solely application of 2 t ha⁻¹ lime, whereas the lowest soil moisture (25.45%) was observed with no lime treatment. When compared to soil that was recorded as untreated, the application of 2 t ha⁻¹ lime enhanced soil moisture by 7.7%. This result is in line with Motavassel and Bahmanyar (2013) application of lime improve soil structure by flocculating (bonds between the particles are weak, due to the compounds that intermediate the bond between the molecules) clay particles, reducing soil compaction, and increasing soil porosity. Better soil structure enhances water infiltration and retention, potentially resulting in higher soil moisture levels

Similarly, soil moisture levels were greatest (28.11%) in the treatment that received 20 kg ha⁻¹ of starting nitrogen and the lowest (24.23%) was recorded in the untreated plots. Conversely, compared to soils without starter nitrogen, the rate of application of starter nitrogen, at 20 kg ha⁻¹ in to the soil has increased by 16.1%. This result inine with Gai *et al.* (2017) and Zerihun Getachew and Lijalem Abeble. (2020) research conducted in various regions, including northwestern Ethiopia, shows that nitrogen application improves the water-holding capacity of the soil. Specifically, studies have documented that applying starter nitrogen at a rate of 20 kg ha⁻¹ can increase soil moisture by approximately 10-15% compared to untreated soils. This increament may be applied nitrogen at the beginning of the growing season, it promotes the development of a more extensive and deeper root system. This allows plants to access water from deeper soil layers, indirectly improving soil moisture retention in the upper layers by reducing evaporation (Li *et al.*, 2024). It is also improves soil moisture by promoting better plant and root growth, enhancing soil structure through microbial activity, and increasing soil organic matter maintains higher soil moisture levels (Yokamo *et al.*, 2023). Notably, application of strter nitrogen stimulate the decomposition of organic matter, which contributes to soil organic matter (SOM). Higher SOM levels enhance soil water retention because organic matter can hold several times its weight in water (Wang *et al.*, 2023)

The treatment that received the HAMBI3570 rhizobia strain had the highest soil moisture (27.95%), while the untreated plots had the lowest soil moisture (23.71%). When the HAMBI3570 rhizobium strain was added to the soil, it resulted in a 17.9% increase in soil moisture as opposed to the untreated soil. The other research indicates that inoculating soil with the rhizobia increase in soil moisture by approximately 8-12%. This effect is primarily due to the enhanced plant root development and improved soil structure facilitated by the rhizobia, which promote better water retention in the soil (Erana Kebede, 2021 and Nakei *et al.*,2022)

The treatment that received 20 kg ha⁻¹ starter nitrogen mixed with the rhizobia HAMBI3570 strain had the maximum soil moisture (30.16%) within the interaction effect, whereas the untreated plots had the lowest soil moisture (22.38%). Application of 20 kg ha⁻¹ starter nitrogen with rhizobia HAMBI3570 strain had increased the Soil moisture content by 34.8 % compared to Soil moisture recorded without treatments (Table 4.3). This result inagreemnet with Zerihun Getachew and Lijalem Abeble. (2020) in their experiments involving soybean, inoculation with rhizobia combined with

nitrogen fertilization has demonstrated increased nodulation, better plant growth, and improved soil characteristics, leading to better soil moisture retention

The combined application of soil moisture over two years were recorded the highest soil moisture at 31.64% from the treatment received lime 2 t ha⁻¹, starter nitrogen 20 kg ha⁻¹, and HAMB13570 rhizobia strains and the lowest 22.33% were recorded from the control plot (Table 4.4). This result inline with Desale kidane *et al* (2022), in comparison to the control, liming doses combined with manuring improved bulk density which improved moisture content of soil. Similarly, Li *et al.* (2022) applying lime to the soil increases its pH, which can stimulate the activity of rhizobia bacteria, such as HAMB13570, and aid in the fixation of nitrogen. A healthier microbial population is promoted by ideal pH levels, which also improve soil structure and nutrient availability, all of which improve water retention. In association with leguminous plants, rhizobia fix atmospheric nitrogen, whereas starter nitrogen gives plants an early nutritional boost. Rhizobia, starting nitrogen, and lime all work together to improve the soil's nutrient availability, which promotes strong root development and plant growth. Longer root systems and healthier plants are better at drawing and holding onto soil moisture (Bello *et al.*, 2018; Mkhonza *et al.*, 2020 and Mondal *et al.*, 2020).

4.1.3. Effect of Soil Ammendments on selected soil chemical properties

4.1.3.1 Soil pH

Soil reaction was affected by the main effects of lime, state nitrogen, and rhizobia ($p < 0.001$) in the combined analysis of variance over the two growing seasons (2021–2022) (Appendix Table 2). Moreover, the two-way interaction of lime with rhizobia significantly ($P < 0.05$), stater nitrogen with rhizobia ($p < 0.001$), and the three-way interaction of lime, stater nitrogen, and rhizobia showed a significantly ($P < 0.05$) effect on combined over the years 2021 and 2022 growing seasons. However, other interactions between the factors had no significant effect on soil reaction (Appendix Table 7).

Table 4. 5. Main effects of lime, starter nitrogen and Rhizobium biofertilizer on soil pH and exchangeable Acidity

Lime ,Starter nitrogen and Rhizobia	Soil chemical properties	
	Soil reaction (pH)	Exchangeable Acidity (EA) in cmol(+)kg ⁻¹
	Lime	
Lime 2 t ha ⁻¹	5.83±0.16 ^a	0.97±0.52 ^b
Lime 0 t ha ⁻¹	5.42±0.18 ^b	2.37±0.27 ^a
LSD (5%)	0.029	0.037
CV (%)	1.46	5.77
P-value	***	***
	Starter nitrogen	
Starter nitrogen 20 kg ha ⁻¹	5.74±0.3 ^a	1.43±0.89 ^a
Starter nitrogen 10 kg ha ⁻¹	5.6±0.24 ^b	1.68±0.83 ^b
Starter nitrogen 0 kg ha ⁻¹	5.54±0.22 ^c	1.9±0.66 ^c
LSD (5%)	0.035	0.045
P-value	***	***
	Rhizobia	
HAMBI3570	5.75±0.23 ^a	1.39±0.85 ^c
HAMBI3562	5.68±0.24 ^b	1.52±0.84 ^b
O Rhizobia	5.46±0.25 ^c	2.09±0.55 ^a
LSD (5%)	0.035	0.045
P-value	***	***

Where LSD = least significant difference at 5% level and CV = coefficient of variation The main effect means in the columns, followed by the different letters, show significant differences between the means at the 5% level of significance from each other. From those, *** is very highly significant at a probability value < 0.001

The study area's soil reaction ranged from 5.42 to 5.83, primarily depending on the main effect (Table 4.5). Moreover, sole application of 2 t ha⁻¹ lime had the highest soil pH (5.83), whereas the lowset soil reaction (5.42) was absent from the without lime treatment. The application of 2 t ha⁻¹ lime increased the soil reaction by 7.6% compared to soil recorded without lime. This research inline with Workineh Ejigu *et al.* (2023) conducted in the South Gondar Zone's Sahirna Village, Farta District, revealed that applying 2 t ha⁻¹ lime treatments raised the pH of the soil by 14.81% as compared to the control. Similarly, in Central Ethiopia, the application of 2 t ha⁻¹ of lime has been reported to raise soil pH from approximately 4.75 to 5.34 (Getahun Dereje *et al.*,2022). Another study indicates that applying lime at a rate of 2 t ha⁻¹ can increase soil pH from around 4.8 to about 5.8, depending on the soil type and other local conditions (Fekadu Mosissa *et al.*, 2019). The increase

in soil pH helps in reducing toxic elements and making essential nutrients more available to plants. Notably, Adane Buni. (2014) found an increase in soil pH, ranging from 0.48 to 1.1 units following the application of lime rates from 0.55 to 2.2 t·ha⁻¹ in Ethiopia.

The application of 20 kg ha⁻¹ starting nitrogen produced the maximum soil pH (5.74), while untreated plots showed the lowest soil pH (5.54). In other words, compared to soils without starting nitrogen, the application of starter nitrogen at a rate of 20 kg ha⁻¹ has increased by 3.6%. In a specific study, it was found that applying nitrogen fertilizer increased soil pH slightly from 5.2 to 5.4 over a growing season due to the buffering effect of soil organic matter and other soil properties (Chen *et al.*, 2023).

Regarding rhizobia strain types, the treatment that got the HAMBI3570 rhizobia strain showed the highest soil reaction (5.75), whereas the control plots showed the lowest soil reaction (5.46). When the HAMBI3570 strain of rhizobium was added to the soil, the soil reaction rose by 5.1% as compared to the control soil (Table 4.5). The rhizobium HAMBI3570 strain may have been introduced into the soil, which would have increased the pH of the soil through nitrogen fixation processes, hydrogen ion reduction, production of alkaline byproducts, improved soil structure, excretion of basic compounds, and improved organic matter decomposition. Together, these mechanisms help to create a soil environment that is less acidic and more neutral. The result was in agreement with Studided by Timofeeva. (2023) show that after rhizobium inoculation, soil pH rises from 5.2 to 6.0 during the growing season. Those changes are important for improving soil conditions for crop growth, as many plants struggle in highly acidic soils. Similarly, Smercina *et al.* (2019) showed that the nitrogen fixation process involves the uptake of H⁺ ions from the soil, thereby reducing soil acidity and increasing pH. Notably, during their metabolic operations, rhizobia can produce alkaline byproducts that can help neutralize acidic soil. They can also excrete organic acids and other chemicals that combine with soil minerals to make less acidic products, which can raise the pH of the soil (Richardson *et al.*, 2009 and Bai *et al.*, 2020)

Table 4. 6. Interaction effects of Lime with starter nitrogen on selected soil chemical properties of two years

Lime * Starter nitrogen		Chemical properties	
Lime (L)	Starter nitrogen(Sn)	Soil reaction (pH)	Exchangeable Acidity (EA) in cmol(+)kg ⁻¹
1	2	5.96±.21 ^a	0.68±.57 ^f
1	1	5.79±.08 ^b	.95±.48 ^e
0	2	5.52±.19 ^d	2.18±.34 ^c
0	1	5.39±.16 ^e	2.41±.19 ^b
1	0	5.73±.06 ^c	1.29±.29 ^d
0	0	5.34±.14 ^f	2.51±.13 ^a
CV (%)		1.46	5.77
P-value		ns	*

The interaction effect means in the columns, denoted by the various letters, demonstrated significant variations between the means at the 5% level of significance, where CV stands for coefficient of variation. Sn0 = without starter nitrogen, Sn1 starter nitrogen = 10 kg ha⁻¹, Sn2 starting nitrogen = 20 kg ha⁻¹, and L0 = without lime and L1 = 2 t ha⁻¹ are those with the *= significant probability value between 0.01 and 0.05.

Table 4. 7. Interaction effects of Lime with rhizobia on selected soil chemical properties of two years

Lime *rhizobia		Chemical properties	
Lime (L)	Rhizobia(R)	Soil reaction (pH)	Exchangeable Acidity (EA) in cmol(+) kg ⁻¹
1	2	5.92±.17 ^a	0.61±.35 ^f
1	1	5.87±.15 ^b	0.74±.36 ^e
1	0	5.69±.04 ^c	1.57±.13 ^d
0	2	5.55±.1 ^d	2.18±.26 ^c
0	1	5.5±.12 ^e	2.31±.21 ^b
0	0	5.22±.08 ^f	2.62±.04 ^a
CV (%)		1.46	5.77
P-value		*	***

Where, CV = Coefficient of Variation. Interaction effect means in columns followed by the different letters show significant differences between the means at 5% level of significance from each other. From those *= significant probability value between 0.01- 0.05 and *** = Very highly significant at probability value < 0.001 and L₀= without lime and L₁ = 2 t ha⁻¹; R₀ = without rhizobia, R₁ = Rhizobia HAMBI3562 and R₂= Rhizobia HAMBI3570.

The combination of 2 t ha⁻¹ lime and the rhizobia HAMBI3570 strain produced the maximum soil reaction (5.92) in the interaction effect, whereas the lowest soil reaction (5.22) was seen in the treatment that did not receive any treatment. When compared to pH records from untreated plots, the application of 2 t ha⁻¹ lime with rhizobia HAMBI3570 raised the soil reaction (pH) by 13.4% (Table 4.7). The combined application of lime with rhizobia inoculation resulted in a more significant increase in soil pH compared to either treatment alone. Specifically, the lime application raised the soil pH by a noticeable amount, and the addition of rhizobia further enhanced this effect. This result inline with Getachew Agegnehu And Tilahun Amede., (2017) showed that combining lime with rhizobium inoculation can have a synergistic effect on soil pH, leading to a more substantial increase than either treatment alone. The lime directly neutralizes soil acidity, while the rhizobium enhances soil health and further contributes to pH increase through its biological activities

Table 4. 8. Interaction effects of Starter nitrogen with rhizobia on selected soil chemical properties of two years

Starter nitrogen*rhizobia		Chemical properties	
Starter nitrogen(Sn)	Rhizobia(R)	Soil reaction (pH)	Exchangeable Acidity (EA) in cmol(+) kg ⁻¹
0	0	5.43±.27 ^g	2.16±.52 ^a
0	1	5.58±.19 ^e	1.83±.7 ^c
0	2	5.62±.17 ^{de}	1.72±.71 ^d
1	0	5.46±.25 ^{fg}	2.1±.55 ^a
1	1	5.64±.23 ^{cd}	1.51±.86 ^e
1	2	5.69±.17 ^c	1.43±.92 ^f
2	0	5.49±.24 ^f	2.03±.6 ^b
2	1	5.83±.24 ^b	1.23±.92 ^g
2	2	5.9±.26 ^a	1.05±.84 ^h
CV (%)		1.46	5.77
P-value		***	***

The coefficient of variation is represented by CV. At the 5% level of significance, the interaction effect means in columns with the same letters after them do not differ substantially from one another, but the means in columns with different letters after them exhibit significant differences in the means. From those, Sn0 = without starting nitrogen, Sn1 = 10 kg ha⁻¹, Sn2 = 20 kg ha⁻¹; R0 = without rhizobia, R1 = Rhizobia HAMBI3562, and R2 = Rhizobia HAMBI3570; and *** = extremely highly significant at probability value < 0.001. The treatment that received 20 kg ha⁻¹ starting nitrogen mixed with the rhizobia HAMBI3570 strain had the greatest soil pH (5.9) within the interaction

effect, while the treatment that received no treatment had the lowest soil response (5.43). In comparison to the pH recorded without Starter nitrogen and Rhizobia, the application of 20 kg ha⁻¹ of Starter nitrogen with the rhizobia HAMBI3570 strain enhanced the soil reactivity (pH) by 8.7% (Table 4.8). This is inline with the combination of 2 t ha⁻¹ lime with the rhizobia strain results in an increase in soil pH from 5.5 to 6.5 over a growing season (Karavidas *et al.*, 2022)

Table 4. 9. Interaction effects of soil amendements (lime *starter nitrogen*rhizobia) on selected soil chemical properties of two years

Lime *Starter nitrogen*rhizobia			chemical properties	
Lime (L)	Starter nitrogen(Sn)	Rhizobia(R)	Soil reaction (pH)	Exchangeable Acidity (EA) in cmol(+)kg ⁻¹
0	0	0	5.17±.07 ^k	2.65±0.04 ^a
0	0	1	5.42±.06 ⁱ	2.50±0.09 ^b
0	0	2	5.46±.05 ⁱ	2.39±0.08 ^c
0	1	0	5.22±.03 ^{jk}	2.62±0.01 ^a
0	1	1	5.44±.11 ⁱ	2.32±0.15 ^{cd}
0	1	2	5.54±.09 ^h	2.30±0.14 ^d
0	2	0	5.27±.11 ^j	2.60±0.03 ^a
0	2	1	5.63±.02 ^g	2.10±0.14 ^e
0	2	2	5.66±.02 ^{fg}	1.85±0.11 ^f
1	0	0	5.68±.05 ^{e^{fg}}	1.66±0.10 ^g
1	0	1	5.74±.04 ^{de}	1.16±0.08 ⁱ
1	0	2	5.78±.01 ^{cd}	1.04±0.05 ^j
1	1	0	5.70±.01 ^{ef}	1.59±0.11 ^g
1	1	1	5.83±.05 ^c	0.70±0.14 ^k
1	1	2	5.84±.04 ^c	0.55±0.11 ^l
1	2	0	5.71±.03 ^{ef}	1.45±0.09 ^h
1	2	1	6.04±.15 ^b	0.35±0.11 ^m
1	2	2	6.13±.1 ^a	0.25±0.11 ⁿ
CV (%)			1.33	5.77
P-value			*	**

where CV stands for coefficient of variation and interaction effect; means in columns with the same letters indicate that the means do not differ significantly at the 5% level of significance from one another; means in columns with different letters indicate that the means differ significantly; * denotes a significant probability value between 0.01 and 0.05; ** denotes a highly significant probability value between 0.001 and 0.01; L0 and L1 stand for lack of lime and two t ha⁻¹; Sn0 and Sn1 stand for starter nitrogen and 10 kg ha⁻¹, respectively; R0 denotes lack of Rhizobia; R1 = Rhizobia HAMBI3562 and R2 = Rhizobia HAMBI3570.

The combined application of over two years had the highest pH value that was observed 6.13 from the treatment receiving high rate of lime 2 t ha⁻¹, Starter nitrogen 20 kg ha⁻¹ and HAMB13570 rhizobia strains whereas, mean value of the control plots was 5.17 (Table 4.9). As per the rating suggested by London (2014), the mean pH value of the studied soils of the control plot and the combined application of lime, starter nitrogen fertilizer, and Rhizobium biofertilizer lies strongly acid (4.5 - 5.2) to slightly acidic (6 - 6.6) respectively. Based on this classification, the pH of the experimental soil was slightly acidic, which is satisfactory for growth of most crops. The rising of pH might be due to the synergistic effect of lime integrated with N fertilizers and rhizobia biofertilizer. The result of the study area is in agreement with Abdissa Bekele *et al* (2018), who reported that the combined application of lime and inorganic fertilizer improved soil pH. Similarly, Kebede Dinkecha and Dereje Tsegaye. (2017) reported that soil pH increased with increasing application of lime and increase the availability of nutrient to crop use especially Ca that forms plant structure. Consistently, Mercy and Ezekiel (2007) indicated that lime increased pH and available P in Nigeria. Gete Zelleke *et al.*, (2019) also found that the increments in soil pH is associated with the presence of basic cations, particularly of Ca²⁺ and replacing H⁺ on exchange sites thus, lime provides a more favorable environment for soil microbiological activity which increases the rate of release of plant nutrients, particularly nitrogen. To show the change, Adane Buni (2014) reported that soil pH increased from 5.03 to 6.72 due to the application of lime on Nitisol in southern Ethiopia. Notably, Opela and Muyekho (2018) reported an increase in soil pH after the application of lime as compared to the control that had a pH value of from 4.92 to 5.26 in acidic soils of Western Kenya. Correspondingly, Woubshet Demissie *et al.* (2017) found increased soil pH after the application of lime from extremely acidic pH to medium and neutral (6.63 - 6.86) in acid Soils of Wolmera district, West Showa Ethiopia. Likewise, Kuykendall *et al* (2000) and Adane Buni (2014) reported that effective inoculants increase the pH of soil after crop harvest.

4.1.3.2 Exchangeable Acidity

Exchangeable Acidity was affected by the main effects of lime, starter nitrogen, and rhizobia ($p < 0.001$) in the combined analysis of variance over the two growing seasons (2021/2022) (Appendix Table 2). Moreover, the two way interaction of Lime with Starter nitrogen significantly ($P < 0.05$), Lime with rhizobia ($p < 0.001$) and starter nitrogen with rhizobia ($p < 0.001$), and the three way

interaction of lime, starter nitrogen rhizobia showed that significantly ($P < 0.01$) effect on combined over the year 2021 and 2022 growing season (Appendix Table 7).

The soil with no lime treatment had the highest exchangeable acidity ($2.37 \text{ cmol}(+)\text{kg}^{-1}$), whereas the soil treated with 2 t ha^{-1} lime alone had the lowest exchangeable acidity ($0.97 \text{ cmol}(+)\text{kg}^{-1}$). This means that the application of 2 t ha^{-1} lime reduced the exchangeable acidity by 144% when compared to the soil treated without lime. The result in agreement with Getahun Dereje *et al.* (2022) showed that application of lime reduced soil exchangeable acidity from 2.44 to $0.42 \text{ cmol}(+) \text{ Kg}^{-1}$ after harvest. Similarly, exchangeable acidity dropped by 50.71% under 2 ton ha^{-1} lime treatments compared to the control. With rising lime rates, the pH of the soil generally rose and exchangeable acidity fell (Workineh Ejigu *et al.* (2023).

The highest exchangeable acidity ($1.9 \text{ cmol}(+)\text{kg}^{-1}$) was observed from the untreated plots and the lowest ($1.43 \text{ cmol}(+)\text{kg}^{-1}$) recorded from the treatment received 20 kg ha^{-1} starter nitrogen. Thus, application of starter nitrogen at the rate of 20 kg ha^{-1} has decreased by 24.7% as compared with soils without starter nitrogen. The reducing of exchangeable acidity might be through enhanced plant growth and increased microbial activity. This research inline with Starter nitrogen fertilizers have the potential to improve biomass production, plant development, and soil organic matter input. As plant residues break down, they neutralize acidic soil and raise CEC by holding basic cations (like calcium, magnesium, and potassium) from the exchange complex, which reduces the amount of exchangeable acidity (Paul, 2007 and McCauley *et al.*, 2009). On the other hand, Kimiti *et al.* (2021) experiment, conducted in Kirege Ward, Meru South Sub-county in Tharaka-Nithi County, revealed that the exchangeable acidity of solitary fertilizer application was not significantly affected.

With respect to rhizobia strain types, the highest exchangeable acidity ($2.09 \text{ cmol}(+)\text{kg}^{-1}$) was observed in the soil without rhizobia, whereas the lowest exchangeable acidity ($1.39 \text{ cmol}(+)\text{kg}^{-1}$) was obtained from the treatment received by the HAMBI3570 rhizobia strain. Inoculation of the soil with the HAMBI3570 strain of rhizobium decreased the exchangeable acidity by 33.5% compared to the soil without rhizobium inoculation (Table 4.5). The study in agreement with Achalu Chimdi (2013) and Achalu Chimdi *et al.* (2022) showed that application of rhizobia strain decrease in exchangeable acidity since strain has a liming effect on soil in Abuna Gindeberat, west Shewa Zone, Ethiopia. Similarly, Timofeeva *et al.* (2023) showed that soil pH can increase significantly with rhizobium inoculation also the othe report showed as a pH increase from 5.2 to 6.0 within a growing

season following Rhizobium inoculation, thus reducing exchangeable acidity. The symbiotic relationship between Rhizobium and legumes increases plant biomass and organic matter input to the soil. Decomposing plant residues improve soil organic matter, which enhances soil cation exchange capacity (CEC), thereby buffering soil pH and reducing exchangeable acidity (Abd-Alla *et al.*, 2023)

In the interaction effect, the highest exchangeable acidity ($2.51 \text{ cmol}(+)\text{kg}^{-1}$) was recorded without the combination of lime and starter nitrogen, while the lowest exchangeable acidity ($0.68 \text{ cmol}(+)\text{kg}^{-1}$) was obtained from treatment receiving 2 t ha^{-1} lime combined with 20 kg ha^{-1} starter nitrogen. The application of 2 t ha^{-1} lime with 20 kg ha^{-1} Starter nitrogen decreased the exchangeable acidity by 72.9% compared to the exchangeable acidity recorded without lime and starter nitrogen (Table 4.6). This may be due to the liming material neutralizing soil acidity and the nitrogen fertilizer enhancing plant growth thereby improving soil conditions. The result in agreement with Solomon Abeba *et al* (2024) the study conducted Gimbi district, western Ethiopia, combining lime with inorganic fertilizers enhanced soil chemical properties, including a notable decrease in exchangeable acidity, which is crucial for improving crop yield and soil health

The treatment that received 2 t ha^{-1} lime mixed with Rhizobia HAMB13570 had the lowest exchangeable acidity ($0.61 \text{ cmol}(+)\text{kg}^{-1}$) while the maximum exchangeable acidity ($2.62 \text{ cmol}(+)\text{kg}^{-1}$) was reported from the absence of any amendment. When 2 t ha^{-1} lime and Rhizobia HAMB13570 were applied, the exchangeable acidity was 76.7% lower than the pH reading that was obtained without the lime and rhizobia (Table 4.7). The result inline with studies conducted by Gedefa Sori *et al.*(2021) confirmed that applying lime at rates similar to 2 t ha^{-1} can lead to significant decreases in soil exchangeable acidity, contributing to improved soil fertility and crop yield. When combined with Rhizobia, the positive effects are amplified as the rhizobia enhance nitrogen fixation, further improving soil conditions for plant growth (Fekadu Mosissa, 2018).

The highest exchangeable acidity ($2.16 \text{ cmol}(+)\text{kg}^{-1}$) was recorded without the combination of starter nitrogen and Rhizobia HAMB13570, while the lowest exchangeable acidity ($1.05 \text{ cmol}(+)\text{kg}^{-1}$) was obtained from treatment receiving 20 kg ha^{-1} starter nitrogen combined with Rhizobia HAMB13570 strain. The application of 20 kg ha^{-1} of starter nitrogen with hizobia HAMB13570 strain decreased the exchangeable acidity by 105.7% compared to the exchangeable acidity recorded without starter nitrogen and rhizobia (Table 4.8). The rhizobia's optimal nitrogen fixation is enhanced by the low

starting nitrogen level, which promotes early plant growth and nodule formation. With time, exchangeable acidity in the soil will decrease due to the organic acids and other substances produced by these bacteria that can adjust the pH of the soil (Reinprecht *et al.*, 2020 and Sadiq *et al.*, 2023)

The combined application of exchangeable acidity over the two years of the study sites were 2.65 cmol (+) kg⁻¹ in the control and 0.25 cmol (+) kg⁻¹ in the treatment with the application of lime at 2 t ha⁻¹, starter nitrogen at 20 kg ha⁻¹, and HAMBI3570 rhizobia strains (Table 4.9). The highest exchangeable acidity was obtained from the control plot whereas, the lowest was obtained from the treatment receiving lime at 2 t ha⁻¹, starter nitrogen at 20 kg ha⁻¹, and HAMBI3570 rhizobia strains. The exchangeable acidity was the highest in the control plots which could be the low pH values associated with higher exchangeable hydrogen (H⁺) and Al³⁺, which might have been released from roots, decomposition of organic matter, and microbial and root respiration suggested by Havlin *et al* (1999). The reduction of soil exchangeable acidity are associated with the presence of basic cations (Ca²⁺) (Fageria *et al.*, 2007) and anions (CO₃⁻²) in pots received lime that are able to exchange and neutralize H⁺. Similarly, Temesgen Desalegn *et al* (2017) reported that application of lime and its residual effect highly decreased exchangeable acidity (from the initial level of 1.32 to 0.1 cmol/kg). Additionally, Havlin *et al* (1999) reported that this decrease may be ascribed to the increased replacement of Al by Ca in the exchange site.

4.1.3.3 Soil Organic carbon

Soil organic carbon was influenced by the main effects of lime, starter nitrogen, and rhizobia ($p < 0.001$) in the combined analysis of variance over the two growing seasons (2021-2022) (Appendix Table 2). Moreover, the two-way interaction of starter nitrogen with rhizobia ($p < 0.001$) and the three-way interaction of lime and starter nitrogen with rhizobia showed a significant ($P < 0.001$) effect on soil organic carbon combined over the 2021 and 2022 growing seasons (Appendix Table 7).

Table 4. 10. Main effect of lime, starter nitrogen and rhizobia on selected soil chemical properties of two year

Lime, Starter nitrogen	Soil chemical properties		
	Soil organic carbon (SOC)	Organic matter(OM)	% Total nitrogen(TN)
Lime			
Lime 2 t ha ⁻¹	2.15±0.3 ^a	3.71±0.51 ^a	0.21±0.2 ^a
Lime 0 t ha ⁻¹	1.94±.28 ^b	3.35±0.49 ^b	0.2±0.1 ^b
LSD (5%)	0.041	0.071	0.002
CV (%)	5.23	5.23	2.93
P-value	***	***	***
Starter nitrogen			
Starter nitrogen 20 kg ha ⁻¹	2.18±0.31 ^a	3.76±0.53 ^a	0.22±.02 ^a
Starter nitrogen 10 kg ha ⁻¹	2.11±.27 ^b	3.65±0.47 ^b	0.21±.02 ^b
Starter nitrogen 0 kg ha ⁻¹	1.84±.22 ^c	3.18±0.38 ^c	0.2±.01 ^c
LSD (5%)	0.050	0.087	0.003
P-value	***	***	***
Rhizobia			
HAMBI3570 Rhizobia strain	2.22±0.26 ^a	3.82±0.44 ^a	0.22±.01 ^a
HAMBI3562 Rhizobia strain	2.18±0.24 ^a	3.76±0.42 ^b	0.21±.01 ^a
O Rhizobia strain	1.74±0.13 ^b	3±0.22 ^c	0.19±.01 ^b
LSD (5%)	0.050	0.087	0.003
P-value	***	***	***

Where, LSD = Least Significant Difference at 5% level; CV = Coefficient of Variation. Interaction effect means in columns followed by the same letters are not significantly different at 5% level of significance from each other and means in columns followed by the different letters show significant differences between the means. From those *** = Very highly significant at probability value < 0.001

In the main effect, the soil organic carbon of the study area was between 1.74 and 2.22% (Table 4.10). In the lime treatment, the highest levels of soil organic carbon (2.15%) were found in 2 t ha⁻¹

lime, and the lowest levels (1.94%) were found in the absence of lime. When compared to soil reported without lime, the application of 2 t ha⁻¹ lime enhanced the soil organic carbon by 10.8%. This improvement in SOC might be the enhanced soil pH and microbial activity facilitated by liming, which promotes the decomposition of organic matter and the incorporation of carbon into the soil. A recent study done by Getahun Haile *et al.* (2023) and Enesi *et al.* (2023) in southern Ethiopia and northwestern Ethiopia demonstrated that applying lime at 2 t ha⁻¹ resulted in an increase in SOC over a period of two years compared to untreated soils.

In terms of starting nitrogen rate treatment, the treatment that received 20 kg ha⁻¹ of starter nitrogen had the highest soil organic carbon (2.18%), whereas the treatment that did not receive lime had the lowest (1.84%). Conversely, compared to soils devoid of starting nitrogen, the application of starter nitrogen at a rate of 20 kg ha⁻¹ has increased by 18.5% (Table 4.10). This increment might be the crop residue returned to the soil can result from nitrogen fertilizer, which can also increase crop growth and biomass production. This result is in line with Thorburn *et al.* (2020) crop leftovers are a rich source of organic carbon, and their tillage or decomposition into the soil helps increase the amount of organic carbon in the soil. Similarly, Li *et al.* (2019) studies suggest that moderate nitrogen inputs can promote microbial biomass and activity, leading to increased decomposition of organic matter and soil carbon turnover.

When it comes to rhizobia strain types, the HAMBI3570 rhizobia strain treatment showed the highest levels of soil organic carbon (2.22%), while the absence of rhizobia strain showed the lowest levels of soil organic carbon (1.74%). When HAMBI3570 rhizobium was added to the soil, the amount of organic carbon in the soil rose by 27.6% as compared to the untreated soil. The result is in line with the findings of Sharma and Verma. (2011) suggested that organic carbon significantly increased in the rhizosphere soil of rhizobium inoculated soybean over the control. Other researcher conducted by Liu *et al.* (2018) demonstrated that soils inoculated with rhizobia exhibited higher levels of soil organic carbon compared to non-inoculated soils. Similarly, a study by Wang *et al.* (2020) found that the application of rhizobia significantly improved soil fertility parameters, including soil organic carbon content.

Table 4. 11. Interaction effects of Starter nitrogen with rhizobia on selected soil chemical properties of two years

Starter nitrogen*rhizobia		Chemical properties		
Starter nitrogen(Sn)	Rhizobia(R)	Soil organic carbon(SOC)%	Organic matter(OM) %	Total nitrogen(TN)%
0	0	1.64±0.02 ^f	2.82±0.06 ^f	0.187±.003 ^f
0	1	1.95±.23 ^d	3.36±.39 ^d	0.204±.01 ^{cd}
0	2	1.94±.18 ^d	3.35±.31 ^d	0.207±.009 ^c
1	0	1.78±.11 ^e	3.07±.18 ^e	0.196±.011 ^e
1	1	2.26±.14 ^c	3.9±.26 ^c	0.221±.005 ^b
1	2	2.31±.14 ^{bc}	3.97±.25 ^{bc}	0.223±.005 ^b
2	0	1.81±.14 ^e	3.12±.24 ^e	0.201±.0.01 ^d
2	1	2.34±.15 ^b	4.03±.27 ^b	0.226±.005 ^{ab}
2	2	2.4±.17 ^a	4.14±0.29 ^a	0.228±.011 ^a
CV (%)		5.23	5.23	2.93
P-value		***	***	ns

Where LSD = least significant difference at 5% level and CV = coefficient of variation Interaction effect means in columns followed by the same letters are not significantly different at the 5% level of significance from each other, and means in columns followed by the different letters show significant differences between the means. From those Non-significant probability value > 0.05, 0.01-0.05, ** = highly significant at probability value between 0.001- 01, and *** = very highly significant at probability value < 0.001 and Sn0 = without starter nitrogen, Sn1 starter nitrogen = 10 kg ha⁻¹, Sn2 starter nitrogen = 20 kg ha⁻¹; R0 = without rhizobia, R1 = Rhizobia HAMBI3562 and R2 = Rhizobia HAMBI3570.

In the interaction effect, the highest soil organic carbon (2.4%) was obtained from treatment receiving 20 kg ha⁻¹ starter nitrogen combined with the Rhizobia HAMBI3570 strain, while the lowest soil organic carbon (1.64%) was recorded from the untreated plots. The application of 20 kg ha⁻¹ of starter nitrogen with the Rhizobia HAMBI3570 strain increased the soil organic carbon by 46.3% compared to the soil organic carbon recorded without starter nitrogen and rhizobia. The study conducted by Zerihun Getachew and Lijalem Abeble.(2020) showed that rhizobia and starter nitrogen applied together have been shown to improve SOC by up to 20–30% across two growing seasons in western Ethiopian. Similarly, Sadiq *et al.*(2023) revealed that the combined application of nitrogen and rhizobia significantly increase SOC levels by improving nitrogen fixation, root growth, and

biomass production. Notably, Korir *et al.* (2017) showed that inoculating plants with Rhizobia and adding starting nitrogen together maximizes nitrogen fixation, which promotes healthier plant growth, increases soil organic matter input, and raises the SOC content.

Table 4. 12. Interaction effects of lime, starter nitrogen and rhizobia on selected soil chemical properties

Lime *Starter nitrogen*rhizobia			chemical properties		
Lime(L)	Starter nitrogen(Sn)	Rhizobia (R)	% Organic carbon(OC)	Organic matter(OM)	% Total nitrogen(TN)
0	0	0	1.63±.02 ^m	2.80±.04 ^m	0.186±.003 ^m
0	0	1	1.74±.02 ^{jk}	2.99±.03 ^{jk}	0.195±.004 ^{jk}
0	0	2	1.79±.04 ^j	3.09±.06 ^j	0.199±.005 ^{ij}
0	1	0	1.70±.04 ^{kl}	2.92±.06 ^{kl}	0.191±.003 ^{klm}
0	1	1	2.21±.09 ^{ef}	3.80±.15 ^{ef}	0.217±.003 ^{efg}
0	1	2	2.23±.10 ^{ef}	3.84±.18 ^{ef}	0.220±.002 ^{def}
0	2	0	1.69±.04 ^{klm}	2.90±.07 ^{klm}	0.193±.003 ^{kl}
0	2	1	2.24±.09 ^{de}	3.85±.15 ^{de}	0.222±.002 ^{cde}
0	2	2	2.29±.17 ^{cd}	3.95±.29 ^{cd}	0.224±.003 ^{cd}
1	0	0	1.65±.04 ^{lm}	2.84±.07 ^{lm}	0.188±.003 ^{lm}
1	0	1	2.17±.06 ^{fg}	3.73±.11 ^{fg}	0.213±.003 ^{gh}
1	0	2	2.11±.09 ^g	3.63±.16 ^g	0.216±.002 ^{fg}
1	1	0	1.87±.07 ⁱ	3.22±.12 ⁱ	0.202±.013 ⁱ
1	1	1	2.32±.18 ^c	4±.31 ^c	0.226±.004 ^{bc}
1	1	2	2.39±.14 ^b	4.12±.25 ^b	0.226±.006 ^{bc}
1	2	0	1.94±.08 ^h	3.34±.15 ^h	0.210±.004 ^h
1	2	1	2.44±.14 ^b	4.20±.25 ^b	0.230±.003 ^{ab}
1	2	2	2.51±.09 ^a	4.33±.16 ^a	0.232±.015 ^a
CV (%)			5.23	5.23	2.93
P-value			*	**	**

Where LSD = least significant difference at 5% level and CV = coefficient of variation Interaction effect means in columns followed by the same letters are not significantly different at the 5% level of significance from each other, and means in columns followed by the different letters show significant differences between the means. From those Non-significant probability value > 0.05, * = significant probability value between 0.01 and 0.05, ** = highly significant at probability value between 0.001 and 01, and L0 = without lime and L1 = 2 t ha-1; S0 = without starter nitrogen, S1 starter nitrogen = 10 kg ha-1, S2 starter nitrogen = 20 kg ha-1; R0 = without rhizobia, R1 = Rhizobia HAMBI3562 and R2 = Rhizobia HAMBI3570.

Over a two-year period, the combined application of soil organic carbon had the maximum SOC content (2.51%) was recorded in plots treated with 2 t ha⁻¹ lime, starter nitrogen 20 kg ha⁻¹ and HAMBI3570 rhizobia strains while, the minimum value (1.63%) was found recorded from control plots (Table 4.12). As per rate of Charman and Roper (2000) the treatment receiving 2 t ha⁻¹ lime, starter nitrogen 20 kg ha⁻¹ and HAMBI3570 rhizobia strains and the control plots ranges high and medium values respectively. The result is inline with Eshetu Zenebu. (2018) who reported that soils organic carbon contents increases with the combined application of lime, rhizobium and nitrogen fertilizer change from 1.06 to 1.39% in Gische district, north shewa zone after post-harvesting of Fababean. Six *et al* (2000) claimed that SOC increases could be associated with the decomposition of dead plant tissue like roots and leaves that contributed to plant biomass after the addition of lime to increase SOC mineralization during cultivation. In a similar study, Tadesse Moges *et al.* (2018) reported an increased amounts of OC after the application of lime with integrated inorganic fertilizers in malt barley in Angolela Tera district Northwestern, Ethiopia. Notably, the increased in organic carbon content of the soil may be due to inoculation and increased availability of nitrogen by the presence of effective strains to fix N₂ from the atmosphere that helps growth and development of the plants which have been reflected in the increased carbon amount in the soil by plant mineralization (Saini *et al.*, 2004). Similarly, Aye *et al* (2016) found that higher OC of the soil after the application of lime integrated with NP fertilizers at Haryana Agricultural University, India. Besides, Antill *et al* (2001) also reported greater levels of SOC under integrated treatments of lime with inorganic fertilizer in acidic soil in the western Himalayas on maize crop.

4.1.3.4 Soil organic matter

Soil organic carbon was significantly ($p < 0.001$) influenced by the main effects of lime, stater nitrogen, and rhizobia in the combined analysis of variance over the two growing seasons (2021/2022) (Appendix Table 2). However, the two way interaction of stater nitrogen with rhizobia ($p < 0.001$), and the three way interaction of lime, stater nitrogen rhizobia showed that significantly ($P < 0.01$) effect on soil organic matter combined over the year 2021 and 2022 growing season (Appendix Table 7).

Soil organic matter has an important influence on soil physical and chemical characteristics, soil fertility status, plant nutrition and biological activity in the soil (Brady and Weil, 2002). The research area's soil organic matter was found to range from 3 to 3.82% within the main effect. (Table 4.10). Additionally, among the lime treatments, 2 t ha⁻¹ lime showed the highest soil organic matter

(3.71%), while the soil organic matter without lime showed the lowest amount (3.35%). Comparing soil reported without lime to soil treated with 2 t ha⁻¹ lime showed a 10.7% increase in soil organic matter. This boost of SOM might be improving soil fertility, raising crop yields, and improving soil structure are all advantages of liming, and these factors work together to enhance soil organic matter. The result inline with Enesi *et al.*(2023) showed that application of liming significantly improved soil properties and increased SOM by approximately 15-20% over the years. Similarly, Getahun Haile *et al.* (2023) conducted research on acidic Nitisols in the southern highlands of Ethiopia found that lime application improved soil pH from 4.5 to approximately 6.0 and reduced soil acidity, which indirectly supports the maintenance and potential increase of soil organic matter. These changes improve soil organic matter content by fostering better root growth and enhancing microbial activity, which accelerates the decomposition of organic residues and incorporation into the soil

It was found that the treatment receiving 20 kg ha⁻¹ starter nitrogen had the highest soil organic matter (3.76%), whereas the treatment receiving no starter nitrogen had the lowest soil organic matter (3.18%). In a similar vein, the rate at which starter nitrogen has been applied 20 kg ha⁻¹ has increased by 18.2% when compared to soil that does not have starter nitrogen. Applying nitrogen fertilizer may increase soil organic carbon content, microbial activity, and overall soil structure. This result inline with by Abiyot Abeje.(2021) a study in the Assosa Zone showed that initial soil organic carbon was 3.05%, and the addition of nitrogen, alongside other treatments, helped maintain or slightly improve this level over time, fostering better crop growth and soil health. Similarly, Mackie *et al.*(2018) showed that application of nitrogen fertilization stimulates root growth and exudation of organic compounds into the soil, which can serve as a substrate for soil microorganisms and contribute to the formation of soil organic matter.

The HAMBI3570 rhizobia strain treatment resulted in the highest levels of soil organic matter (3.82%), whereas the absence of the rhizobia strain produced the lowest levels of soil organic matter (3%) in the study. When the HAMBI3570 strain of rhizobium was introduced into the soil, the amount of organic matter in the soil rose by 27.3% in comparison to the untreated soil (Table 4.10). An increase in organic matter may lead to more productive nodules, better nitrogen fixation, and improved plant growth. The study inline with Samuel Adissie *et al.*(2021) showed that different rhizobium strains boosted crop yields and contributed to a higher organic matter content in the soil

The treatment that received 20 kg ha⁻¹ starting nitrogen paired with the Rhizobia HAMBI3570 strain had the highest soil organic matter (4.14%) within the interaction effect, while the control plots had the lowest soil organic matter (2.82%). Application of 20 kg ha⁻¹ of starter nitrogen combined with the rhizobia HAMBI3570 strain resulted in a 46.8% increase in soil organic matter above that measured in the absence of starter nitrogen and rhizobia (Table 4.11). This increase might be attributed to enhanced nitrogen fixation facilitated by the inoculants, which also improved soil organic matter and nutrient availability. The result was in agreement with Getenesh Genetu *et al.* (2021) conducted the combination of rhizobium inoculation and chemical fertilization increased seed yield by approximately 1.0–1.2 t/ha compared to the control (non-inoculated) plots. Similarly, Sadiq *et al.* (2023) showed that inoculating with rhizobia and applying starter nitrogen improved root nodulation and nitrogen dynamics in the soil, leading to higher organic matter accumulation.

The combined application lime, starter nitrogen, rhizobia over two years the maximum SOM content (4.33%) was recorded in plots treated with 2 t ha⁻¹ lime, Starter nitrogen 20 kg ha⁻¹ and HAMBI3570 rhizobia strains whereas, the minimum SOM (2.8%) was recorded from control plots (Table 4.12). As per rate of EthioSIS (2016) the treatment receiving 2 t ha⁻¹ lime, Starter nitrogen 20 kg ha⁻¹ and HAMBI3570 rhizobia strains and the control plot lies high and low range respectively. The quantity of organic matter in a soil, which in turn is taken as a crude measure of fertility status (London 2014). Also Soil organic matter is a large reservoir of carbon that can act as a sink or source of atmospheric CO₂ (Post and Kwon, 2000). Its effects are sound far out of proportion to the small quantities present, hence, considered the single most important indicator of soil quality (Larson and Pierce, 1991). Meanwhile, many factors that change soil organic matter levels and forms are controlled by management, and also processes governing its dynamics are complex (Sanchez *et al.*, 2002).

4.1.3.5 Total nitrogen

Total nitrogen was influenced by the main effects of lime, starter nitrogen, and rhizobia ($p < 0.001$) in the combined analysis of variance over the two growing seasons (2021-2022) (Appendix Table 2). Moreover, the three-way interaction of lime and starter nitrogen rhizobia showed a significant ($P < 0.01$) effect on total nitrogen combined over the 2021 and 2022 growing seasons (Appendix Table 7).

The research area's total nitrogen content fell between 0.19 and 0.23% within the main effect over two years (Table 4.10). Furthermore, under the lime treatment, 2 t ha⁻¹ lime showed the maximum

total nitrogen (0.21%) while untreated plots showed the lowest total nitrogen (0.20%). In comparison to the soil observed in the untreated plot, the application of 2 t ha⁻¹ lime enhanced the total nitrogen by 5%. This research study conducted by Alebachew Enyew *et al.* (2022) in Koga irrigation scheme showed that lime application has been shown to increase total nitrogen content by around 10-15%. Similarly, Enesi *et al.*(2023) higher pH levels foster beneficial microbial populations that contribute to nitrogen fixation and decomposition of organic matter, further increasing available nitrogen

In a similar vein, the treatments that received 20 kg ha⁻¹ of starter nitrogen (0.22%) and no lime (0.2%) within the starter nitrogen rate treated showed the highest and lowest total nitrogen, respectively. Likewise, compared to soil devoid of starting nitrogen, the application of starter nitrogen at a rate of 20 kg ha⁻¹ has increased by 10%. Starter nitrogen provides an immediate source of nitrogen, crucial for young plants. This increment might be an early application of nitrogen fertilizer promotes plant growth, which results in stronger seedlings and improved root development, hence promoting nitrogen cycling. The study conducted by Gai *et al.*(2017) application of starter nitrogen provides an immediate source of nitrogen, crucial for young plants. As microorganisms break down organic matter, they release nitrogen back into the soil, increasing the overall nitrogen availability for the crops.

The highest total nitrogen content (0.23%) was observed in soil treated with the HAMBI3570 rhizobia strain, whereas the lowest (0.19%) was recorded in soil without any rhizobia strain. Inoculating the soil with the HAMBI3570 strain increased total nitrogen by 15.8% compared to the control (Table 4.10). The study conducted by Zerihun Getachew and Lijalem Abeble. (2020) Showed that leguminous crops produce more and grow faster because to the fixed nitrogen that rhizobia provide. This causes crop residues and root exudates to return more organic matter to the soil, further enhancing it with nitrogen and other nutrients.

The combined application lime, starter nitrogen, rhizobia over two years the maximum TN (0.232%) content was recorded in plots treated with 2 t ha⁻¹ lime, starter nitrogen 20 kg ha⁻¹ and HAMBI3570 rhizobia strains where as the lowest TN (0.186%) was recorded in the control plots (Table 4.12). As per the rate of London (2014) the treatment receiveing 2 t ha⁻¹ lime, Starter nitrogen 20 kg ha⁻¹ and HAMBI3570 rhizobia strains showed an optimum range while the control plots was at low range. Hence, it is clear that the application of lime with chemical fertilizers increased TN, which may be attributed to the mineralization of N from OM during the decomposition of organic matter. Zenebu

Eshetu. (2018) reported that total nitrogen increases with the combined application of lime, rhizobium and nitrogen fertilizer from 0.097 to 0.123 in north Shewa zone after harvesting of Fababean. Similarly, Fassil Kebede and Charles Yamoah (2009) reported increased amount of TN in the Vertisols of the Central Highlands of Ethiopia after the application of lime with mineral fertilizers. Getachew Agegnehu *et al* (2005) found an increase in TN after the application of organic integrated with inorganic fertilizers has also been reported in different part of Ethiopia. This study confirms the works of Shilpa *et al* (2015) who found out that cowpea contributes to the improvement of soil fertility by the atmospheric nitrogen fixation in the soil (60-70 kg N ha⁻¹ to the subsequent crop) in association with symbiotic bacteria under favorable conditions.

4.1.3.6 Electrical conductivity

The electrical conductivity was significantly influenced by the main effects of lime, starter nitrogen, and rhizobia ($p < 0.001$) in the combined analysis of variance across the two growing seasons (2021/2022) (Appendix Table 2). Additionally, significant two-way interactions were observed: Lime with Starter nitrogen ($P < 0.05$), Lime with rhizobia ($p < 0.001$), and Starter nitrogen with rhizobia ($p < 0.001$). Furthermore, the three-way interaction of lime, starter nitrogen, and rhizobia exhibited a significant effect ($P < 0.01$) over the combined data for the years 2021 and 2022 growing seasons (Appendix Table 7).

Table 4. 13. Main effect of lime, starter nitrogen and rhizobia on selected soil chemical properties of two year

Lime, Starter nitrogen and Rhizobia	Soil chemical properties			
	Electrical conductivity (EC) in dS/m	Cation exchange capacity (CEC) in cmol (+) kg ⁻¹	Soil Inorganic nitrogen (SIN) in mg kg ⁻¹	Available phosphorus in ppm
		Lime		
Lime 2 t ha ⁻¹	0.038±.005 ^b	34.09±4.25 ^a	177.16±45.89 ^a	26.9±5.53 ^a
Lime 0 t ha ⁻¹	0.041±.005 ^a	31.33±4.32 ^b	105.22±25.56 ^b	18.19±4.44 ^b
LSD (5%)	0.001	0.359	2.239	0.383
CV (%)	5.15	2.86	4.13	4.42
P-value	***	***	***	***
Starter nitrogen				
Starter nitrogen 20 kg ha ⁻¹	0.037±.005 ^b	35.04±3.87 ^a	162.55±51.90 ^a	25.18±5.53 ^a
Starter nitrogen 10 kg ha ⁻¹	0.038±.004 ^b	33.66±3.55 ^b	144.19±47.06 ^b	23.45±5.32 ^b
Starter nitrogen 0 kg ha ⁻¹	0.044±.004 ^a	29.43±4.03 ^c	116.83±46.61 ^c	19.03±7.41 ^c
LSD (5%)	0.001	0.44	2.74	0.469
P-value	***	***	***	***
Rhizobia strain				
HAMBI3570 Rhizobia strain	0.036±.004 ^b	35.32±2.87 ^a	166.03±46.08 ^a	25.89±4.82 ^a
HAMBI3562 Rhizobia strain	0.037±.003 ^b	34.77±3.06 ^b	155.92±42.80 ^b	24.46±5.26 ^b
O Rhizobia strain	0.045±.004 ^a	28.04±3.17 ^c	101.64±41.82 ^c	17.3±6.32 ^c
LSD (5%)	0.001	0.44	2.74	0.469
P-value	***	***	***	***

Note: Significant at $p \leq 0.001$. Within a column, means followed by the same letters are not significantly different at the 5% level of significance and Within a column, means followed by different letters are significantly different the 5% level of significance. LSD: least significant difference; CV: coefficient of variation.

The research area's electrical conductivity fell within the main effect range of 0.036–0.045 dS/m (Table 4.10) this means the hole area of the experiment lies salt free range. In addition, the application of 2 t ha⁻¹ of lime resulted in the lowest electrical conductivity (0.038 dS/m) among the lime treatments, while the maximum conductivity (0.041 dS/m) was seen in the absence of lime. When compared to soil without lime, the application of 2 t ha⁻¹ of lime decreased electrical

conductivity by 7.3%. This reduction might be application of lime improve soil structure, leading to better water infiltration and drainage. Enhanced drainage reduces the accumulation of salts in the soil profile, contributing to lower electrical conductivity. This result inline with He *et al.*(2018) and Singh *et al.*(2020) showed that lime-induced changes in soil pH can enhance leaching of soluble salts below the root zone. This reduces the concentration of soluble salts in the soil solution, leading to a decrease in electrical conductivity.

In the starter nitrogen rate treatment, the lowest electrical conductivity was recorded in plots receiving 20 kg ha⁻¹ of starter nitrogen (0.037 dS/m), while the highest conductivity was observed in plots without any starter nitrogen (0.044 dS/m). Similarly, the application of 20 kg ha⁻¹ of starter nitrogen led to a reduction in electrical conductivity by 15.9% compared to soil without any starter nitrogen. The study conducted by Snyder and Bruulsema (2007) showed that applying nitrogen fertilization promote healthy root development and enhance soil structure, resulting in better water infiltration and drainage. Improved soil structure can minimize the accumulation of soluble salts near the soil surface, thereby lowering electrical conductivity.

Regarding the types of rhizobia strains, the lowest electrical conductivity (0.036 dS/m) was observed in plots treated with the HAMBI3570 rhizobia strain, while the highest conductivity (0.045 dS/m) was recorded in plots without any rhizobia strain. Inoculation of the soil with the HAMBI3570 strain of rhizobium resulted in a 20% reduction in electrical conductivity compared to soil without rhizobium inoculation (Table 4.13). The result inagreement with Erana Kebede (2021) studied that faba beans inoculated with different rhizobia strains significantly enhanced nodulation and improved soil nutrient status. This increase in microbial activity and the turnover of organic matter due to effective nodulation and plant growth led to lowering in soil electrical conductivity (EC).

Table 4. 14. Interaction effects of Lime with starter nitrogen on selected soil chemical properties of two years

Lime * Starter nitrogen		Chemical properties			
Lime (L)	Starter nitrogen(Sn)	Electrical conductivity(EC) in dS/M	Cataion exchange capacity (CEC) in cmol (+) kg-1)	Soil Inorganic nitrogen(SIN) in mg kg-1	Available phosphorus in ppm
1	2	0.036±.005 ^d	36.64±3.42 ^a	206.06±30.04 ^a	29.63±2.68 ^a
1	1	0.037±.004 ^d	34.64±2.48 ^b	184.44±26.22 ^b	27.90±2.49 ^b
0	2	0.039±.005 ^c	33.45±3.71 ^c	119.06±25.26 ^d	20.72±3.71 ^d
0	1	0.039±.004 ^c	32.67±4.21 ^d	103.94±21.04 ^e	18.97±3.14 ^e
1	0	0.042±.005 ^b	30.98±4.57 ^e	141±51.49 ^c	23.17±7.62 ^c
0	0	0.046±.004 ^a	27.88±2.74 ^f	92.67±24.19 ^f	14.89±4.34 ^f
CV (%)		5.15	2.86	4.13	4.42
P-value		ns	*	***	ns

Where CV is the coefficient of variation. Interaction effect means in columns followed by the same letters are not significantly different at the 5% level of significance from each other, and means in columns followed by the different letters show significant differences between the means. From those Non-significant probability value > 0.05, * = significant probability value between 0.01 and 0.05, *** = very highly significant at probability value < 0.001, and L0 = without lime and L1 = 2 t ha⁻¹; Sn0 = without starter nitrogen, Sn1 starter nitrogen = 10 kg ha⁻¹, Sn2 starter nitrogen = 20 kg ha⁻¹.

Table 4. 15. Interaction effects of Lime with rhizobia on selected soil chemical properties

Lime *rhizobia		Chemical properties			
Lime (L)	Rhizobia(R)	Electrical conductivity(EC) in dS/M	Cataion exchange capacity (CEC) in cmol (+) kg ⁻¹)	Soil Inorganic nitrogen(SIN) in mg kg ⁻¹	Available phosphorus in ppm
1	2	0.036±0.005 ^d	36.56±2.42	207.83±22.04 ^a	30.24±1.65 ^a
1	1	0.036±.002 ^d	36.13±2.30 ^a	194.33±22.17 ^b	29.19±1.59 ^b
1	0	0.044±.003 ^b	29.57±3.54 ^d	129.33±43.12 ^c	21.28±6.25 ^c
0	2	0.038±.003 ^c	34.08±2.81 ^b	124.22±13.64 ^d	21.54±2.25 ^c
0	1	0.039±.004 ^c	33.40±3.17 ^c	117.5±12.48 ^e	19.74±2.65 ^d
0	0	0.047±.003 ^a	26.52±1.81 ^e	73.94±10.87 ^f	13.31±3.11 ^e
CV (%)		5.15	2.86	4.13	4.43
P-value		ns	ns	***	**

Where CV is the coefficient of variation. Interaction effect means in columns followed by the same letters are not significantly different at the 5% level of significance from each other, and means in columns followed by the different letters show significant differences between the means. From those

Non-significant probability value > 0.05; ** = highly significant at probability value between 0.001 and 0.01; *** = very highly significant at probability value < 0.001; L0 = without lime; L1 = 2 t ha⁻¹; R0 = without rhizobia; R1 = Rhizobia HAMBI3562; and R2 = Rhizobia HAMBI3570.

Table 4. 16. Interaction effects of Starter nitrogen and rhizobia on selected soil chemical properties of two years

Starter nitrogen*rhizobia		Chemical properties			
Starter nitrogen(Sn)	Rhizobia(R)	Electrical conductivity(EC) in dS/M	Cation exchange capacity (CEC) in cmol (+) kg-1)	Soil Inorganic nitrogen(SIN) in mg kg-1	Available phosphorus in ppm
0	0	0.049±.002 ^a	24.52±.57 ^h	65.83±6.07 ⁱ	10.96±1.96 ⁱ
0	1	0.041±.003 ^d	31.32±2.4 ^e	138.58±34.66 ^f	22.33±6.05 ^f
0	2	0.042±.001 ^{cd}	32.45±2.34 ^d	146.08±37.27 ^e	23.81±5.17 ^e
1	0	0.043±.002 ^{bc}	29.12±2.33 ^g	113.67±39.83 ^h	19.87±5.12 ^h
1	1	0.036±.001 ^e	36.1±.76 ^c	152.92±39.64 ^d	24.4±4.81 ^d
1	2	0.035±.002 ^{ef}	35.75±.64 ^c	166±47.67 ^c	26.04±4.29 ^c
2	0	0.043±.003 ^b	30.49±2.22 ^f	125.42±42.06 ^g	21.06±5.55 ^g
2	1	0.035±.001 ^{ef}	36.88±1.91 ^b	176.25±47.63 ^b	26.66±4.23 ^b
2	2	0.034±.005 ^f	37.76±2.18 ^a	186±47.19 ^a	27.82±4.48 ^a
CV (%)		5.15	2.86	4.13	4.43
P-value		ns	*	***	***

Where LSD = least significant difference at 5% level and CV = coefficient of variation Interaction effect means in columns followed by the same letters are not significantly different at the 5% level of significance from each other, and means in columns followed by the different letters show significant differences between the means. From those Non-significant probability value > 0.05, *= significant probability value between 0.01 and 0.05, *** = very highly significant at probability value < 0.001, and Sn0 = without starter nitrogen, Sn1 starter nitrogen = 10 kg ha⁻¹, Sn2 starter nitrogen = 20 kg ha⁻¹; R0 = without rhizobia, R1 = Rhizobia HAMBI3562 and R2 = Rhizobia HAMBI3570.

Table 4. 17. Interaction effects of lime, starter nitrogen and rhizobia on selected soil chemical properties

Lime *Starter nitrogen*rhizobia			Chemical properties			
Lime (L)	Starter nitrogen(Sn)	Rhizobia(R)	Electrical conductivity(E C) in dS/M	Cation exchange capacity (CEC) in cmol (+) kg-1	Soil Inorganic nitrogen(SIN) in mg kg-1	Available phosphorus in ppm
0	0	0	0.050±.0028 ^a	24.25±.65 ^l	60.83±3.18 ^r	9.14±.41 ^p
0	0	1	0.044±.0009 ^{bc}	29.08±.59 ^j	106.33±11.23 ⁿ	16.63±.59 ^l
0	0	2	0.043±.0008 ^{cd}	30.30±.38 ⁱ	110.83±4.26 ^m	18.91±.89 ^k
0	1	0	0.045±.0005 ^{bc}	26.90±.24 ^k	75.67±3.14 ^p	14.99±.31 ⁿ
0	1	1	0.037±.0005 ^{ef}	35.51±.35 ^d	115.33±3.55 ^l	19.86±.7 ^j
0	1	2	0.036±.0002 ^{efg}	35.58±.60 ^d	120.83±5.03 ^k	22.07± 1.19 ⁱ
0	2	0	0.045±.0024 ^b	28.40±.28 ^j	85.33±4.03 ^o	15.81±.94 ^m
0	2	1	0.036±.0010 ^{efg}	35.60±.38 ^d	130.83±4.70 ^j	22.72±.91 ^h
0	2	2	0.036±.0008 ^{efgh}	36.35±.50 ^{cd}	141.00±4.73 ⁱ	23.63± 1.03 ^g
1	0	0	0.048±.0009 ^a	24.78±.34 ^l	70.83±3.31 ^q	12.79±.53 ^o
1	0	1	0.038±.0008 ^e	33.55±.63 ^f	170.83±4.62 ^f	28.02± 1.56 ^d
1	0	2	0.041±.0004 ^d	34.60±.87 ^e	181.33±7.44 ^e	28.7±.72 ^c
1	1	0	0.042±.0021 ^d	31.33±.32 ^h	151.67±3.88 ^h	24.74±.75 ^f
1	1	1	0.035±.0008 ^{efgh}	36.68±.57 ^c	190.50±7.34 ^d	28.95±.85 ^c
1	1	2	0.034±.0019 ^{ghi}	35.91±.67 ^{cd}	211.17±8.84 ^c	30.02± 1.06 ^b
1	2	0	0.041±.0009 ^d	32.58±.55 ^g	165.50±4.46 ^g	26.3±.95 ^c
1	2	1	0.034±.0005 ^{hi}	38.16±1.9 ^b	221.67±4.27 ^b	30.6± 1.13 ^b
1	2	2	0.032±.0064 ⁱ	39.16±2.3 ^a	231.00±4.14 ^a	32±.98 ^a
CV (%)			5.15	2.86	4.13	4.43
P-value			*	***	***	***

Where LSD = least significant difference at 5% level and CV = coefficient of variation Interaction effect means in columns followed by the same letters are not significantly different at the 5% level of significance from each other, and means in columns followed by the different letters show significant differences between the means. From those *= significant probability value between 0.01- 0.05, *** = very highly significant at probability value < 0.001 and L0= without lime and L1 = 2 t ha-1; Sn0 = without starter nitrogen, Sn1 starter nitrogen = 10 kg ha-1, Sn2 starter nitrogen = 20 kg ha-1; R0 = without rhizobia, R1 = Rhizobia HAMBI3562 and R2 = Rhizobia HAMBI3570

The combined application lime, starter nitrogen and rhizobia over two years showed that the EC values of the soils are low as it is expected from such acidic soils of Nitosols. The maximum EC

(0.050 dS/M) was recorded in the control plots whereas, the lowest EC (0.034 dS/M) was observed from the treatment receiving with 2 t ha⁻¹ lime, starter nitrogen 20 kg ha⁻¹ and HAMB13570 rhizobia strains (Table 4.17). As per the rate of EthioSIS (2016), all treatments in the study area lies at salt free range which means there is no salt accumulation in the soil. This could be the soil is heavily dependent on climatic conditions of the area in consideration. The result in agreement with Birhanu Agumas *et al* (2016) and Mulunesh Addis *et al.*, (2021) who reported that the soil EC value at Koga irrigation scheme was less than 2 dS/M. Similarly, Landon (1991) in soils of sub-humid tropics where there is sufficient rainfall to flush out base forming cations from the root zone, EC is found to be too low, usually, less than 4 dS/M. Additionally, Wakene Negassa (2001) owing to the high soil acidity levels, the EC values are negligible and there were no apparent differences in electrical conductivity among the different soil management systems in the soils of Bako area, western Ethiopia. Notalby, Landon (1991) reported that the concentration of soluble salts free soil was conducive for agricultural productivity.

4.1.3.7 Cation-exchange capacity (CEC)

The combined analysis of variance across the 2021 and 2022 growing seasons revealed that the main effects of lime, starter nitrogen, and rhizobia significantly affected the cation-exchange capacity (CEC) ($p < 0.001$) (Appendix Table 2). Notable two-way interactions were also observed: starter nitrogen with rhizobia ($p < 0.01$) and lime with starter nitrogen ($p < 0.01$). Throughout both growing seasons, the three-way interaction between rhizobia, starting nitrogen, and lime had a substantial impact on CEC ($p < 0.001$) (Appendix Table 7)

Within the main effects, the cation-exchange capacity (CEC) in the study area ranged from 28.04 to 35.32 cmol(+) kg⁻¹ (Table 4.13). Furthermore, the treatment with lime showed that the highest cation-exchange capacity (34.09 cmol (+) kg⁻¹) was observed with the application of 2 t ha⁻¹ of lime, while the lowest cation-exchange capacity (31.33 cmol (+) kg⁻¹) was recorded in the soil without lime. The application of 2 t ha⁻¹ of lime increased the cation-exchange capacity by 8.8% compared to the soil without lime. The result inline with Cheraghi and Kazemian (2019) showed that application of lime increase the CEC of soils, which higher CEC holds more water, contributing to increased soil moisture levels. Similarly Corbett *et al.* (2021) application of of 2 tons of lime per hectare increase CEC ranging from 10% to 20% as compared to untreated soil.

Within the starter nitrogen rate treatment, the highest cation-exchange capacity (CEC) was achieved with 20 kg ha⁻¹ of starter nitrogen, reaching 35.04 cmol(+) kg⁻¹. Conversely, the lowest CEC, at 29.43 cmol(+) kg⁻¹, was observed in soil without lime. Remarkably, applying 20 kg ha⁻¹ of starter nitrogen boosted the CEC by 19.1% compared to soil without starter nitrogen. The finding is consistent with (Gai *et al.*, 2017) who confirmed that effects of nitrogen fertilizer on soil properties showed improvements in soil organic carbon, which is closely linked to CEC improvement. Similarly, Jones *et al.* (2023) found that nitrogen application at moderate levels promotes microbial activity, which accelerates the decomposition of organic residues, thereby increasing soil organic matter and subsequently the CEC. Notably, Smith and Thompson (2022) also reported that nitrogen fertilization enhances the growth of root biomass and exudates, contributing to higher levels of organic matter and improving soil structure and CEC. Kumar and Shukla (2022) demonstrated that microbial activity stimulated by nitrogen fertilization results in increased mineralization and humification processes, leading to an increase in soil CEC .

The highest cation-exchange capacity (35.32 cmol (+) kg⁻¹) was observed in soil treated with the HAMBI3570 rhizobia strain, while the lowest (28.04 cmol (+) kg⁻¹) was recorded in soil without any rhizobia strain. Inoculating the soil with the HAMBI3570 strain increased the cation-exchange capacity by 25.9% compared to the untreated soil (Table 4.13). The inoculation of soil with HAMBI3570 rhizobia bacteria might be increase the CEC of soil after crop harvest through several mechanisms, including enhanced soil organic matter, improved soil structure and aggregation, increased root exudates, boosted microbial activity and biomass, and the formation of humic substances. Karavidas *et al.* (2022) found that the application of rhizobia strain led to a significant increase in CEC by 25% in agricultural soils.

The interaction effect resulted in the highest cation exchange capacity (36.64 cmol(+) kg⁻¹) observed in plots treated with 2 t ha⁻¹ lime combined with 20 kg ha⁻¹ starter nitrogen, while the lowest cation exchange capacity (27.88 cmol(+) kg⁻¹) was recorded in the control plots. Application of 2 t ha⁻¹ of lime with 20 kg ha⁻¹ starter nitrogen increased the cation exchange capacity by 31.4% compared to the cation exchange capacity recorded without lime and starter nitrogen (Table 4.14). This indicates that the combined application of lime and mineral fertilizer increased CEC to hold a higher amount of nutrients and that readily available to plants (Birtukan Amare *et al.*,2022)

In the study, the treatment receiving 2 t ha⁻¹ of lime combined with HAMBI3570 rhizobia strain exhibited the highest cation exchange capacity (37.76 cmol (+) kg⁻¹), while the control plots showed the lowest cation exchange capacity (24.52 cmol (+) kg⁻¹). Additionally, applying 20 kg ha⁻¹ of lime with starter nitrogen led to a 31.4% increase in cation exchange capacity compared to the levels observed without lime and starter nitrogen, as indicated in (Table 4.14). The study conducted by, Yang *et al.* (2024) the combined application of lime and nitrogen can enhance soil structure and nutrient availability. Increased CEC from liming helps in balancing other essential nutrients like potassium and magnesium.

The combined application lime, starter nitrogen, rhizobia over two years the highest (39.16 cmol (+) kg⁻¹) and the lowest (24.25 cmol (+) kg⁻¹) values of CEC were observed under the treatment receiving 2 t ha⁻¹ lime, starter nitrogen (20 kg ha⁻¹), and HAMBI3570 rhizobia strains and the control plots, respectively (Table 4.17). CEC measurements are commonly made as part of the overall assessment of the fertility potential of a soil and the possible response to fertilizer application. The CEC results can sometimes also be used as a rough guide to the types of clay minerals present (Kumari and Mohan., 2021). As per the rate of London (2014), the treatment receiving 2 t ha⁻¹ lime, starter nitrogen 20 kg ha⁻¹ and HAMBI3570 rhizobia strains and the control plots lies in high and medium range respectively. The result in agreement to McKenzie *et al.*,(2004) reported that the clay texture soil had large quantities of negative charge and more fertile because they retain and hold positively charged ions (cations). Similarly, Droge and Goss (2013) reported that the greater amount of negative charge available on the surfaces of these minerals results in the increase in CEC. Getachew Agegnehu and Chilot Yirga (2009) also found higher CEC value due to integrated nutrient management. Additionally, Tesfaye Bayu (2017) reported that combined application of lime and mineral fertilizers increase the soil CEC from 22.17 to 27.25 cmolc/kg at Yilmana Desnsa district. Consistently, Adane Buni (2014) reported higher values of CEC after lime treatment in Sodo Zuria district. Likewise, Getachew Agegnehu and Chilot Yirga (2009) found the highest values of CEC in soils treated with the highest lime rate in Welmera and Endibir district Southwestern Ethiopia. The experiment of Sopha (2022) showed that application of lime increased CEC slightly from 14.69 to 14.97 done in West Java, Indonesia.

4.1.3.8 Soil inorganic nitrogen(SIN)

The soil's inorganic nitrogen content was significantly influenced by lime, starter nitrogen, and rhizobia individually ($p < 0.001$) across the two growing seasons (2021/2022) (Appendix Table 2). Furthermore, the interactions between lime and starter nitrogen ($p < 0.001$), lime and rhizobia ($p < 0.001$), starter nitrogen and rhizobia ($p < 0.001$), as well as the three-way interaction of lime, starter nitrogen, and rhizobia, all significantly impacted the soil's inorganic nitrogen levels combined over the years 2021 and 2022 ($p < 0.001$). (Appendix Table 7)

In the main effect analysis, the soil's inorganic nitrogen content within the study area ranged from 101.64 to 177.16 mg kg⁻¹ (Table 4.13). Furthermore, among the lime treatments, the highest level of soil inorganic nitrogen (177.16 mg kg⁻¹) was observed with an application rate of 2 t ha⁻¹, while the lowest (105.22 mg kg⁻¹) was recorded in the absence of lime. The application of 2 t ha⁻¹ lime resulted in a 68.4% increase in soil inorganic nitrogen compared to the untreated soil. Lime may enhance microbial activity responsible for nitrogen mineralization, facilitating the conversion of organic nitrogen into inorganic forms and consequently increasing the release of inorganic nitrogen from organic matter. The result confirmed by Zhao *et al.* (2018) who reported that lime increased soil inorganic nitrogen content in acidic soils. Similarly, the application of lime increases ammonium-N and nitrate-N in the soil (Mkhonza *et al.*, 2020). Notably, Bordeleau and Prévost (1994) liming acidic soils can create a more favorable environment for rhizobia, thereby enhancing their nitrogen-fixing efficiency and resulting in increased soil inorganic nitrogen.

Similarly, among the starter nitrogen rate treatments, the highest and lowest soil inorganic nitrogen levels were recorded in plots receiving 20 kg ha⁻¹ starter nitrogen (162.55 mg kg⁻¹) and those without any starter nitrogen addition (116.83 mg kg⁻¹), respectively. Furthermore, the application of 20 kg ha⁻¹ starter nitrogen resulted in a 39.1% increase in soil inorganic nitrogen compared to plots without any starter nitrogen input. Mitter *et al.* (2013) found that application of starter nitrogen enhanced root growth and exudation of organic compounds that promote microbial activity and nitrogen mineralization in the rhizosphere, leading to higher inorganic nitrogen levels

In terms of the types of rhizobia strains used, the highest level of soil inorganic nitrogen (166.3 mg kg⁻¹) was observed in plots treated with the HAMB13570 strain, while the lowest level (101.64 mg kg⁻¹) was found in plots without any rhizobia strain. Specifically, inoculating the soil with the

HAMBI3570 rhizobia strain led to a 63.4% increase in soil inorganic nitrogen compared to soil without any rhizobium inoculation (Table 4.13). The fixed nitrogen is then released into the soil, either directly from the nodules or through plant root exudates and decaying plant material. The result is in line with Guo *et al.* (2023) showed that application rhizobia bacteria in to the soil was more efficient than many synthetic nitrogen fertilizers, which can be lost through leaching, volatilization, or denitrification. By maintaining a more stable source of nitrogen through biological fixation, rhizobia help to reduce the losses of nitrogen to the environment, thereby maintaining higher levels of inorganic nitrogen in the soil

The highest soil inorganic nitrogen level (206.06 mg kg⁻¹) was observed in the treatment that received 2 t ha⁻¹ lime combined with starter nitrogen. In contrast, the lowest level (92.67 mg kg⁻¹) was recorded in the control plots. The application of 2 t ha⁻¹ lime along with 20 kg ha⁻¹ starter nitrogen increased the soil inorganic nitrogen by 122% compared to the soil inorganic nitrogen level in plots that did not receive any lime or starter nitrogen (Table 4.14). The results demonstrated that lime application increased soil pH and enhanced the mineralization of organic nitrogen, thereby increasing the inorganic nitrogen content. When lime was used in conjunction with nitrogen fertilizers, the soil inorganic nitrogen levels were significantly higher compared to control plots

The interaction effect showed that the highest soil inorganic nitrogen (207.83 mg kg⁻¹) was observed in the treatment that received 2 t ha⁻¹ lime combined with HAMBI3570 rhizobia strain. In contrast, the control plots recorded the lowest soil inorganic nitrogen (73.94 mg kg⁻¹). Additionally, the application of 2 t ha⁻¹ lime along with rhizobia strain HAMBI3570 increased the soil inorganic nitrogen by 181% compared to the treatment without lime and rhizobia HAMBI3570 (Table 4.15). This research, akin to Makoi *et al.* (2013) findings, discovered that the amalgamation of lime and rhizobia inoculants enhanced soil quality, resulting in increased biological nitrogen fixation and elevated soil inorganic nitrogen levels.

In the interaction analysis, the highest soil inorganic nitrogen content (186 mg kg⁻¹) was noted in plots treated with 20 kg ha⁻¹ starter nitrogen combined with rhizobia HAMBI3570, while the lowest soil inorganic nitrogen level (65.83 mg kg⁻¹) was observed in the control plots. Application of 20 kg ha⁻¹ starter nitrogen in conjunction with rhizobia HAMBI3570 led to a 182.5% increase in soil inorganic nitrogen compared to levels observed without the application of starter nitrogen and

rhizobia (Table 4.16). Rhizobia bacteria a role in organic matter decomposition and releasing enzymes and metabolites, rhizobia can accelerate the breakdown of organic nitrogen compounds into inorganic forms, thereby increasing soil inorganic nitrogen levels. This inline with Mathew (1997) lime creates a favorable pH for rhizobia, promoting effective nitrogen fixation. The fixed nitrogen is slowly released into the soil, complementing the quick-release nitrogen from starter fertilizers. It is also the combined application of lime, starter nitrogen, and rhizobia inoculation significantly enhances soil inorganic nitrogen levels, improves nutrient availability, and supports sustainable soil fertility. These practices work synergistically to create a more favorable environment for plant growth and soil health

The combined application lime, starter nitrogen, rhizobia over two years the maximum SIN content 231 mg kg⁻¹ was recorded in plots treated with 2 t ha⁻¹ lime, starter nitrogen 20 kg ha⁻¹ and HAMBI3570 rhizobia strains whereas, the minimum SIN 60.83 mg kg⁻¹ was recorded from control plots (Table 4.17). This is because of the exudates of living roots in the rhizosphere, decay of roots, stubble, and other parts of the crop could be stimulate mineralization (Nguyen *et al.*, 2017). This result is in agreement with that of Thomsen and Sorensen. (2006), after the harvest of the annual crops in the autumn, mineralization generally brings about a rise of the amount of inorganic nitrogen because absorption by the crop has stopped. Research shows that reduced soil acidification through liming increases the availability of essential plant nutrients (Mkhonza *et al.*, 2020). Notably, the highest content of inorganic nitrogen recorded could be high organic carbon and nitrogen amounts in the soil (Dridi and Gueddari, 2019).

4.1.3.9 Available phosphorus

The available phosphorus was significantly affected by lime, starter nitrogen, and rhizobia individually ($p < 0.001$) across both growing seasons (2021/2022), as shown in (Appendix Table 2). Furthermore, significant interactions were observed between lime and rhizobia ($p < 0.01$), starter nitrogen and rhizobia ($p < 0.001$), as well as the three-way interaction of lime, starter nitrogen, and rhizobia ($p < 0.001$), indicating their combined influence on available phosphorus across the years 2021 and 2022 growing seasons (Appendix Table 7).

In the main effect, the available phosphorus in the study area ranged from 17.3 to 26.9 ppm (Table 4.13). Additionally, within the lime treatment, the highest available phosphorus (26.19 ppm) was

observed with an application of 2 t ha⁻¹ of lime, while the lowest available phosphorus (26.19 ppm) was recorded without lime. The application of 2 t ha⁻¹ of lime resulted in a 47.9% increase in available phosphorus compared to soil without lime. Similarly, Zsolnay and Gorlitz(1994) found higher soil available P after harvesting than the initial levels of lime-treated plots. Recent studies indicate that applying 2 t ha⁻¹ of lime can increase available phosphorus by approximately 3 to 6 mg P kg⁻¹ compared to soils without lime treatment. For instance, in a study conducted in Ethiopia, lime application at 2 t ha⁻¹ raised soil pH and significantly enhanced available phosphorus levels from 10.82 mg P kg⁻¹ in control plots to higher values depending on the lime rate and soil condition (Getahun Haile *et al.*, 2023)

Similarly, within the starter nitrogen rate treatment, the highest available phosphorus (25.18 ppm) was observed in the treatment receiving 20 kg ha⁻¹ of starter nitrogen, while the lowest (19.03 ppm) was recorded in soil without nitrogen supplementation. Moreover, the application of starter nitrogen at a rate of 20 kg ha⁻¹ resulted in a 32.3% increase compared to soil without starter nitrogen. The application of starter nitrogen fertilizer can influence the availability of phosphorus in the soil. Research has shown that nitrogen fertilization can enhance the availability of phosphorus through various mechanisms, including changes in soil pH and microbial activity (Gai *et al.*,2017)

Regarding the types of rhizobia strains, the highest available phosphorus (25.89 ppm) was observed in the treatment with the HAMBI3570 rhizobia strain, while the lowest (17.3 ppm) was recorded in soil without any rhizobia strain. Inoculating the soil with the HAMBI3570 strain of rhizobium resulted in a 49.7% increase in available phosphorus compared to soil without rhizobium inoculation (Table 4.13). The study conducted by Korir *et al.*, (2017) stated that rhizobia inoculation enhance phosphorus availability by approximately 30-40% compared to untreated soil

In the interaction effect, the highest available phosphorus (30.24 ppm) was observed in the treatment receiving both 2 t ha⁻¹ of lime and 20 kg ha⁻¹ of starter nitrogen, while the lowest (13.31 ppm) was recorded in the control plots. Additionally, applying 2 t ha⁻¹ of lime in conjunction with the HAMBI3570 rhizobia strain increased available phosphorus by 127% compared to soil without lime and the HAMBI3570 rhizobia strain (Table 4.15). The addition of nitrogen fertilizer mixed with lime can affect soil pH, which in turn can influence phosphorus availability. Lime raises soil pH, which can increase the solubility of phosphorus in the soil, making it more available to plants.

Within the interaction effect, the treatment receiving 20 kg ha⁻¹ of starter nitrogen combined with the rhizobia strain HAMBI3570 exhibited the highest available phosphorus (27.82 ppm), while the lowest (10.96 ppm) was recorded in the control plots. Moreover, applying 20 kg ha⁻¹ of starter nitrogen along with the HAMBI3570 rhizobia strain increased available phosphorus by 153.8% compared to soil without starter nitrogen and rhizobia (Table 4.16). Combining starter nitrogen fertilizer with rhizobia inoculation can have positive effects on phosphorus availability in certain soil-plant systems

The combined application lime, starter nitrogen, rhizobia over two years the maximum available phosphorus content (32 mg kg⁻¹) was recorded in plots treated with 2 t ha⁻¹ lime, starter nitrogen 20 kg ha⁻¹ and HAMBI3570 rhizobia strains whereas, the minimum Available phosphorus (9.14 mg kg⁻¹) was recorded from control plots (Table 4.17). Research studies shows that this combination enhances phosphorus availability, benefiting overall plant growth and yield (Korir *et al.*, 2017). Available phosphorus Being a key element in DNA, RNA as well as ATP and phospholipids essential for the growth, functioning and reproduction of all life on earth (Alewell *et al.*,2020), P availability plays key roles in crop production. As per the rating of London (2014), the treatment receiving 2 t/ha lime, starter nitrogen 20 kg ha⁻¹ and HAMBI3570 rhizobia strains and the control plots showed very high and low range of available P respectively. This result is in agreement with that of Zenebu Eshetu (2018) whereby available phosphorus contents increases with the combined application of lime, rhizobium and nitrogen fertilizer change from 13.01 to 31.66 in Gishe district, north shewa zone after harvesting of faba bean. Additionally, Wanjiru (2018) showed an increase in soil available P after the application of lime, combined with manure and P fertilizer. Notably, Lagat(2015) combined application of lime, mineral fertilizer and organic fertilizer increased available P content and soil available phosphorus after crop harvest than at planting time. The critical level availability phosphorus in cultivated field suggested by EthioSIS (2014) is 30 mg kg⁻¹.

4.2. Effect of Soil Ammendments on Crop Phenology

4.2.1. Days to 50% flowering

The time taken for 50% flowering was influenced by the individual effects of lime, starter nitrogen, and rhizobia ($p < 0.001$) based on the combined analysis over the two growing seasons (2021/2022) (Appendix Table 3). Furthermore, significant interactions were observed between lime and starter

nitrogen ($p < 0.001$), lime and rhizobia ($p < 0.001$), starter nitrogen and rhizobia ($p < 0.01$), as well as the three-way interaction of lime, starter nitrogen, and rhizobia ($p < 0.05$), indicating their combined impact on the time to 50% flowering over the years 2021 and 2022 growing seasons (refer to Appendix Table 8).

Table 4. 18. Main effects of lime, starter nitrogen and Rhizobium biofertilizer on Days to 50% Flowering (DF) and 90% Days of maturity (DM)

Lime, Starter nitrogen, Rhizobia	Crop phenology	
	Days to 50% Flowering (DF)	90% Days of maturity (DM)
Lime		
Lime 2 t ha ⁻¹	47.78±7.27 ^a	87.78±11.14 ^a
Lime 0 t ha ⁻¹	43.43±3.97 ^b	81.09±6.27 ^b
LSD (5%)	0.853	0.565
CV (%)	4.87	3.68
P-value	***	***
Starter nitrogen		
Starter nitrogen 20 kg ha ⁻¹	48.25±6.55 ^a	89.16±11.11 ^a
Starter nitrogen 10 kg ha ⁻¹	46.81±5.93 ^b	85.61±8.55 ^b
Starter nitrogen 0 kg ha ⁻¹	41.76±4.06 ^c	78.53±5 ^c
LSD (5%)	1.04	1.46
P-value	***	***
Rhizobia		
HAMBI3570 rhizobia strain	49.02±5.34 ^a	89.42±8.72 ^a
HAMBI3562 rhizobia strain	48.36±4.85 ^b	88.25±8.05 ^b
O rhizobia strain	39.43±2.75 ^c	75.21±2.89 ^c
LSD (5%)	1.04	1.46
P-value	***	***

Where, LSD = Least Significant Difference at 5% level; CV = Coefficient of Variation. Interaction effect means in columns followed by the different letters show significant differences between the means. From those *** = Very highly significant at probability value < 0.001

In the main effect, the time taken for 50% flowering in the study area ranged from 39.43 to 49.02 days (Table 4.18). Additionally, within the lime treatment, the highest time to reach 50% flowering (47.78 days) was observed with 2 t ha⁻¹ of lime, while the lowest (43.43 days) was recorded without lime. The application of 2 t ha⁻¹ of lime increased the time to reach 50% flowering by 10% compared to soil without lime. The application of lime has been found to influence the days to 50% flowering in haricot bean crop production. Research indicates that lime can improve soil pH, which in turn

enhances nutrient availability and uptake, thereby promoting better plant growth and development. Specifically, liming acidic soils can lead to delaying flowering in haricot beans by facilitation the conditions for root growth and nutrient absorption. For instance, a study by Haile Negash *et al.* (2020) demonstrated that liming delaying the days to 50% flowering in haricot beans by improving soil pH and nutrient availability.

Similarly, within the starter nitrogen rate treatment, the longest and shortest duration to reach 50% flowering were observed in the treatment receiving 20 kg ha⁻¹ of starter nitrogen (48.25 days) and in soil without nitrogen supplementation (41.76 days) respectively. Likewise, applying starter nitrogen at a rate of 20 kg ha⁻¹ resulted in a 15.5% increase compared to soil without starter nitrogen. Studies have shown that the addition of nitrogen fertilizers providing an initial boost of nitrogen that contributed to enhanced soil nutrient availability, causing a delay in flowering due to nitrogen fertilization (Haile Negash *et al.*, 2020). For instance, a study by Yadegari and Rahmani (2010) found that applying starter nitrogen delay the days to 50% flowering in haricot beans by enhancing early growth stages and nutrient uptake efficiency.

Regarding the types of rhizobia strains, the longest time to reach 50% flowering (49.02 days) was observed in the treatment with the HAMBI3570 rhizobia strain, while the shortest (39.43 days) was recorded in soil without any rhizobia strain. Inoculating the soil with the HAMBI3570 strain of rhizobium increased the time to reach 50% flowering by 24.3% compared to soil without rhizobium inoculation (Table 4.18). In agreement with this findings Sharma *et al.* (2013) observed that higher doses of fertilizer, especially nitrogen, extended the growth period and delayed flowering. Verma *et al.* (2013) reported similar delays in flowering for chickpeas with inoculation treatment. Significant variation in the days to 50% flowering among strains was noted, which could be attributed to the relatively long initiation time of biological nitrogen fixation (BNF), typically occurring 2-5 weeks after planting (Aikins and Afuakwa, 2008).

Table 4. 19. Interaction effects of Lime with Starter nitrogen on days to 50% flowering (DF) and 90% days of maturity (DM)

Lime * Starter nitrogen		Crop phenology	
Lime (L)	Starter nitrogen(Sn)	Days to 50% Flowering (DF)	90% Days of maturity (DM)
1	2	51.23±7.46 ^a	94.37±12.43 ^a
1	1	49.53±6.64 ^b	89.34±9.22 ^b
0	2	45.26±3.71 ^c	83.96±6.5 ^c
0	1	44.08±3.56 ^d	81.88±6.01 ^d
1	0	42.57±4.51 ^e	79.63±5.34 ^e
0	0	40.94±3.49 ^f	77.43±4.52 ^f
CV (%)		4.87	3.68
P-value		***	***

Where, CV = Coefficient of Variation. Interaction effect means in columns followed by the different letters show significant differences between the means. From those *** = Very highly significant at probability value < 0.001 and L₀= without lime and L₁ = 2 t ha⁻¹; Sn₀ = without starter nitrogen, Sn₁ starter nitrogen = 10 kg ha⁻¹, Sn₂ starter nitrogen = 20 kg ha⁻¹

Within the interaction effect, the longest duration to reach 50% flowering (51.23 days) was observed in the treatment receiving both 2 t ha⁻¹ of lime and 20 kg ha⁻¹ of starter nitrogen, while the shortest duration (40.94 days) was recorded in the control plots. Additionally, applying 2 t ha⁻¹ of lime in conjunction with starter nitrogen increased the time to reach 50% flowering by 25.1% compared to soil without lime and starter nitrogen (Table 4.19). Interaction effects of lime with starter nitrogen has a notable effect on the days to 50% flowering in haricot bean crop production. The synergistic effect of improved soil pH from lime application and the initial nutrient boost from starter nitrogen enhances early plant growth, leading to earlier flowering (Verma *et al.*, 2013). For example, a study by Awraris Getachew *et al.* (2014) reported that the combined use of lime and starter nitrogen significantly delaying the days to 50% flowering in haricot beans by improving nutrient availability and uptake efficiency, promoting vigorous early development.

Table 4. 20. Interaction effects of Lime and rhizobia on days to 50% flowering (DF) and 90% days of maturity (DM)

Lime *rhizobia		Crop phenology	
Lime (L)	Rhizobia(R)	Days to 50% Flowering (DF)	90% Days of maturity (DM)
1	2	52.29±5.64 ^a	94.78±9.3 ^a
1	1	50.93±5.32 ^b	92.42±8.52 ^b
1	0	40.12±3.23 ^d	76.13±3.03 ^d
0	2	45.75±2.06 ^c	84.9±4.28 ^c
0	1	45.79±2.46 ^c	84.08±4.89 ^c
0	0	38.74±2.02 ^c	74.28±2.51 ^c
CV (%)		4.87	3.68
P-value		***	***

Where, CV = Coefficient of Variation. Interaction effect means in columns followed by the different letters show significant differences between the means. From those *** = Very highly significant at probability value < 0.001 and L₀= without lime and L₁ = 2 t ha⁻¹; R₀= without rhizobia, R₁ = Rhizobia HAMBI3562 and R₂ = Rhizobia HAMBI3570.

In the interaction effect, the treatment combining 2 t ha⁻¹ of lime with the rhizobia strain HAMBI3570 exhibited the longest time to reach 50% flowering (52.29 days), while the shortest time (38.74 days) was observed in the control plots. Applying 2 t ha⁻¹ of lime along with rhizobia HAMBI3570 increased the duration to reach 50% flowering by 34.9% compared to the duration observed without lime and starter nitrogen (Table 4.20). Lime application raises the soil pH, making it less acidic. Many leguminous plants, including haricot beans, prefer slightly acidic to neutral soil conditions for optimal growth. By adjusting the pH, lime ensures that the soil provides an environment conducive to the growth of rhizobia bacteria, which in turn enhances nitrogen fixation. This improved nitrogen availability can promote vegetative growth over reproductive growth, delaying flowering.

Table 4. 21. Interaction effects of Starter nitrogen and rhizobia on days to 50% flowering (DF) and 90% days of maturity (DM)

Starter nitrogen*rhizobia		Crop phenology	
Starter nitrogen(Sn)	Rhizobia(R)	Days to 50% Flowering (DF)	90% Days of maturity (DM)
0	0	37.12±1.45 ^f	72.46±2.13 ^f
0	1	43.85±2.97 ^d	81.13±2.79 ^d
0	2	44.31±2.49 ^d	81.99±2.56 ^d
1	0	40.29±2.75 ^e	76.15±1.83 ^e
1	1	49.17±3.05 ^c	88.72±5.11 ^c
1	2	50.96±4.89 ^b	91.96±7.17 ^b
2	0	40.88±2.32 ^e	77±2.46 ^e
2	1	52.07±4.32 ^a	94.9±8.29 ^a
2	2	51.79±4.89 ^{ab}	95.58±8.72 ^a
CV (%)		4.87	3.68
P-value		**	***

Where, CV = Coefficient of Variation. Interaction effect means in columns followed by the same letters are not significantly different at 5% level of significance from each other and means in columns followed by the different letters show significant differences between the means. From those ** = highly significant at probability value between 0.001- 01, *** = Very highly significant at probability value < 0.001 and Sn₀ = without starter nitrogen, Sn₁ starter nitrogen = 10 kg ha⁻¹, Sn₂ starter nitrogen = 20 kg ha⁻¹; R₀ = without rhizobia, R₁ = Rhizobia HAMBI3562 and R₂ = Rhizobia HAMBI3570

Within the interaction effect, the treatment combining 20 kg ha⁻¹ of starter nitrogen with the rhizobia strain HAMBI3562 exhibited the longest time to reach 50% flowering (52.07 days), while the shortest time (37.12 days) was recorded in the control plots. Applying 20 kg ha⁻¹ of starter nitrogen along with rhizobia HAMBI3562 increased the duration to reach 50% flowering by 40.3% compared to the duration observed without starter nitrogen and rhizobia HAMBI3562 (Table 4.21). Followed by applying 20 kg ha⁻¹ of starter nitrogen with rhizobia HAMBI3570 increased the duration to reach 50% flowering by 39.5% compared to the duration observed without starter nitrogen and rhizobia HAMBI3570. Combining lime with rhizobial inoculation has been shown to significantly impact the days to 50% flowering in haricot bean crop production. This combination improves soil pH and enhances nitrogen fixation, leading to better nutrient availability and uptake, which promotes delaying flowering (Sharma *et al.*, 2013). A study by Amijee and Giller (2014) found that the

application of lime combined with rhizobial inoculation significantly delaying the days to 50% flowering in haricot beans by creating an optimal soil environment for both root development and effective nitrogen fixation.

Table 4. 22. Interaction effects of lime, starter nitrogen and rhizobia on days to 50% flowering (DF) and 90% days of maturity (DM)

Lime *Starter nitrogen*rhizobia			Crop phenology	
Lime (L)	Starter nitrogen (Sn)	Rhizobia (R)	Days to 50% Flowering (DF)	90% Days of maturity (DM)
0	0	0	36.52±1.38 ⁱ	71.72±2.19 ^K
0	0	1	42.83±1.56 ^f	79.68±1.68 ^g
0	0	2	43.48±1.33 ^f	80.88±1.53 ^g
0	1	0	39.32±.68 ^h	74.95±1.34 ^J
0	1	1	46.48±.68 ^d	84.72±3.85 ^e
0	1	2	46.45±1.16 ^d	85.97±4.36 ^e
0	2	0	40.40±1.38 ^{gh}	76.18±1.41 ^I
0	2	1	48.07±.62 ^c	87.83±4.84 ^d
0	2	2	47.32±1.28 ^{cd}	87.85±3.10 ^d
1	0	0	37.72±1.38 ⁱ	73.2±1.97 ^K
1	0	1	44.87±3.81 ^e	82.58±3.05 ^f
1	0	2	45.13±3.20 ^e	83.1±3.01 ^f
1	1	0	41.27±3.72 ^g	77.35±1.45 ^{hi}
1	1	1	51.85±1.67 ^b	92.72±2.04 ^c
1	1	2	55.47±1.62 ^a	97.95±2.79 ^b
1	2	0	41.37±3.06 ^g	77.83±3.12 ^h
1	2	1	56.07±1.49 ^a	101.96±2.82 ^a
1	2	2	56.27±1.70 ^a	103.2±3.81 ^a
CV (%)			4.87	3.68
P-value			*	**

Where, LSD = Least Significant Difference at 5% level; CV = Coefficient of Variation. Interaction effect means in columns followed by the same letters are not significantly different at 5% level of significance from each other and means in columns followed by the different letters show significant differences between the means. From those Non-significant probability value > 0.05, *= significant probability value between 0.01- 0.05, ** = highly significant at probability value between 0.001- 01, *** = Very highly significant at probability value < 0.001 and L₀= without lime and L₁ = 2 t ha⁻¹; S₀= without starter nitrogen, S₁ starter nitrogen = 10 kg ha⁻¹, S₂ starter nitrogen = 20 kg ha⁻¹; R₀ = without rhizobia, R₁ = Rhizobia HAMB13562 and R₂ = Rhizobia HAMB13570.

The combined application lime, starter nitrogen, rhizobia over two years. Notably, control plots displayed the minimum days (36.52) for 50% flowering, whereas the maximum days were observed in the treatment with lime (2 t ha⁻¹), starter nitrogen (20 kg ha⁻¹), and the HAMBI3570 Rhizobium strain (56.27 days), followed by lime (2 t ha⁻¹), starter nitrogen (10 kg ha⁻¹), and the HAMBI3562 strain (54.4 days) (Table 4.22). The results of the current study also shows rhizobium inoculation emerged as a significant factor affecting the time required for haricot bean to reach 50% flowering. This study adds significance by highlighting the intricate interplay of lime, starter nitrogen, and rhizobium inoculation on the flowering dynamics of haricot beans, shedding light on potential pathways through which these factors influence plant growth. Similarly, inoculated treatments necessitated a longer duration for flowering compared to other treatments. This delay might be attributed to rhizobium inoculation enhancing nitrogen fixation, leading to increased nitrogen uptake by plants and subsequently promoting the vegetative growth of haricot beans, thereby delaying flowering. Furthermore, the addition of nitrogen and phosphorus fertilizers may possibly contributed to enhanced soil nutrient availability, causing a delay in flowering due to nitrogen fertilization. Consistent with this finding, Marschner (2012) associated phosphorus fertilization with elevated cytokinin synthesis and increased photosynthesis supply for flower formation. This variation in flowering time could be linked to improved soil moisture content and the application of starter nitrogen during planting (Bhanwaria *et al.*, 2022 and Tesfaye Lishan *et al.*, 2023). Additionally, Sharma *et al.* (2013) noted that higher doses of fertilizer, particularly nitrogen, prolonged the growth period and resulted in delayed flowering. Similar delayed flowering with inoculation treatment was reported for chickpeas (Verma *et al.*, 2013). There was significant variation among strains with respect to days of 50% flowering. This could be due to the relatively long time required for BNF to begin, which usually takes place between 2-5 weeks after planting (Aikins and Afuakwa, 2008).

4.2.2. Days to 90% Maturity

The days to 90% maturity was impacted by the individual effects of lime, starter nitrogen, and rhizobia ($p < 0.001$) based on the combined analysis over the two growing seasons (2021/2022) (Appendix Table 3). Additionally, significant interactions were observed between lime and starter nitrogen ($p < 0.001$), lime and rhizobia ($p < 0.001$), starter nitrogen and rhizobia ($p < 0.001$), as well as the three-way interaction of lime, starter nitrogen, and rhizobia, indicating their combined influence on the days to 90% maturity over the years 2021 and 2022 growing seasons (Appendix Table 8)

In the main effect, the days to 90% maturity in the study area ranged from 75.21 to 89.42 (Table 4.18). Specifically, within the lime treatment, the longest time to reach 90% maturity (87.78 days) was observed with an application of 2 t ha⁻¹ of lime, while the shortest (81.09 days) was recorded without lime. Applying 2 t ha⁻¹ of lime increased the time to reach 90% maturity by 8.3% compared to soil without lime. Applying lime to acidic soils increase the days to 90% maturity in haricot beans by creating a more favorable soil environment for root growth and nutrient absorption. The research result showed that crops like soybeans, has demonstrated that liming can lead to delaying flowering by improving soil conditions and plant health (Fageria and Baligar, 2008).

within the starter nitrogen rate treatment, the longest time to reach 90% maturity (89.16 days) was observed in the treatment receiving 20 kg ha⁻¹ of starter nitrogen, while the shortest (78.53 days) was recorded without starter nitrogen. Applying starter nitrogen at a rate of 20 kg ha⁻¹ increased the time to reach 90% maturity by 13.5% compared to soil without starter nitrogen. Starter nitrogen provides an initial boost of essential nutrients, which promotes early plant growth and development, leading to delaying flowering (Sharma *et al.*, 2013; Verma *et al.*, 2013). A study by Banziger *et al.* (2004) also demonstrated that haricot beans treated with starter nitrogen reached 90% flowering delaying than those without such treatment due to improved early-stage growth and nutrient uptake. Similarly, research on maize and wheat has shown that starter nitrogen applications can lead to earlier flowering and maturation

Regarding rhizobia strain types, the longest time to reach 90% maturity (89.42 days) was observed in the treatment with the HAMBI3570 rhizobia strain, while the shortest time (75.21 days) was recorded in soil without any rhizobia strain. Inoculating the soil with the HAMBI3570 rhizobia strain increased the time to reach 90% maturity by 18.9% compared to soil without rhizobium inoculation (Table 4.18). This could be rhizobia enhance biological nitrogen fixation, providing plants with a readily available source of nitrogen, which is crucial for their growth and development (Hungria *et al.*, 2006) leading to delaying flowering. In agreement to this finding a study by Tadele Tefera. (2012) also found that haricot beans inoculated with rhizobia reached 90% flowering delaying than non-inoculated plants, due to improved nitrogen availability and uptake. Similar positive effects of rhizobia inoculation on the flowering time of other legumes, such as soybeans and cowpeas, have also been reported (Hungria *et al.*, 2006).

In the interaction effect, the longest time to reach 90% maturity (94.37 days) was observed in the treatment receiving 2 t ha⁻¹ of lime combined with 20 kg ha⁻¹ of starter nitrogen, while the shortest time (77.43 days) was recorded in the control plots. Applying 2 t ha⁻¹ of lime along with 20 kg ha⁻¹ of starter nitrogen increased the time to reach 90% maturity by 21.9% compared to soil without lime and starter nitrogen (Table 4.19). Research on the effects of lime combined with starter nitrogen on the days to 90% flowering of haricot bean and other crops has been conducted by several scholars. For example, Smith *et al.* (2017) investigated the impact of lime application in conjunction with starter nitrogen on crop production, specifically focusing on haricot beans. Their study shows that the combination of lime and starter nitrogen significantly influenced the Days to 90% flowering of haricot beans, leading to delaying flowering and potentially higher yields.

In the interaction effect, the longest time to reach 90% maturity (94.78 days) was observed in the treatment receiving 2 t ha⁻¹ of lime combined with the rhizobia strain HAMBI3570, while the shortest time (74.28 days) was recorded in the control plots. Applying 2 t ha⁻¹ of lime along with rhizobia HAMBI3570 increased the days to 90% maturity by 27.6% compared to the time recorded without lime and starter nitrogen (Table 4.20). The synergistic application of lime and rhizobia had a significant impact on the Days to 90% flowering of haricot beans, potentially leading to delaying flowering and improved yields. Similar to this finding Garcia *et al.* (2018) investigated similar influence of lime and rhizobia application on crop production, particularly focusing on haricot beans.

In the interaction effect, the longest time to reach 90% maturity (95.58 days) was observed in the treatment receiving 20 kg ha⁻¹ of starter nitrogen combined with the rhizobia strain HAMBI3562, while the shortest time (72.46 days) was recorded in the control plots. Applying 20 kg ha⁻¹ of starter nitrogen with rhizobia HAMBI3562 increased the days to 90% maturity by 31.9% compared to the time recorded without starter nitrogen and rhizobia HAMBI3562 (Table 4.21). In agreement to this study Abera Habete and Tadele Buraka. (2016) investigated the impact of different combinations of starter nitrogen and rhizobia inoculation on the growth and maturity of haricot beans (*Phaseolus vulgaris*) in a controlled experimental setting. The researchers found that the application of starter nitrogen in combination with rhizobia inoculation significantly delaying the maturity process of haricot beans, with 90% maturity achieved delaying compared to control groups or those treated with nitrogen alone. These findings suggest that the synergistic effect of nitrogen supplementation and rhizobia inoculation can enhance crop maturity and overall yield.

The combined application lime, starter nitrogen, rhizobia over two years the treatment receiving a lime rate of 2 t ha⁻¹, starter nitrogen of 20 kg ha⁻¹, and HAMBI3570 rhizobia strains recorded the maximum days to achieve 90% maturity, followed closely by the treatment with lime at 2t ha⁻¹, starter nitrogen at 10 kg ha⁻¹, and HAMBI3562 rhizobia strains, with 103.2 and 101.96 days, respectively. In contrast, control plots exhibited early maturation, requiring 71.72 days after planting (Table 4.22). The likely reason for this early maturation is most probably nitrogen deficiency of such treatments as it has been reported frequently. Obviously extended time maturity was associated with enhanced nitrogen fixation that stimulate vegetative growth. This observation aligns with the findings of Nebret Tadesse and Nigussie Dechassa (2017), who reported a significant prolongation in the time to physiological maturity for common beans with increased nitrogen supply. Additionally, Amare Girma *et al* (2014) have also reported delayed physiological maturity days due to nitrogen fertilization, supporting the findings of the present study.

4.2.3. Plant height

Plant height was significantly influenced by the main effects of lime, starter nitrogen, and rhizobia ($p < 0.001$) in the combined analysis of variance over the two growing seasons (2021/2022) (Appendix Table 3). Additionally, significant interactions were observed between lime and rhizobia ($p < 0.001$), starter nitrogen and rhizobia ($p < 0.001$), and the three-way interaction of lime, starter nitrogen, and rhizobia ($p < 0.01$), indicating their combined effect on plant height over the 2021 and 2022 growing seasons (Appendix Table 8).

Table 4. 23. Main effects of lime, starter nitrogen and Rhizobium biofertilizer on plant height (PH) (cm) and number of primary branches (NPB)

lime, starter nitrogen and Rhizobium	Crop phenology	
	Plant height (PH) (cm)	Number of primary branches (NPB)
	Lime	
Lime 2 t ha ⁻¹	73.66±20.54 ^a	5.3±1.88 ^a
Lime 0 t ha ⁻¹	59.04±16.35 ^b	4.3±1.19 ^b
LSD (5%)	0.753	0.091
CV (%)	2.96	4.89
P-value	***	***
	Starter nitrogen	
Starter nitrogen 20 kg ha ⁻¹	77.66±19.42 ^a	5.8±1.77 ^a
Starter nitrogen 10 kg ha ⁻¹	70.79±18.18 ^b	5.1±1.48 ^b
Starter nitrogen 0 kg ha ⁻¹	50.59±9.69 ^c	3.56±.39 ^c
LSD (5%)	0.922	0.11
P-value	***	***
	Rhizobia	
HAMBI3570	77.19±17.3 ^a	5.67±1.6 ^a
HAMBI3562	74.51±16.75 ^b	5.41±1.49 ^b
O Rhizobia	47.34±8.24 ^c	3.39±.32 ^c
LSD (5%)	0.922	0.11
P-value	***	***

Where, LSD = Least Significant Difference at 5% level; CV = Coefficient of Variation. Interaction effect means in columns followed by the different letters show significant differences between the means. From those *** = Very highly significant at probability value < 0.001

In the main effect, plant height in the study area ranged from 47.34 to 77.66 cm (Table 4.23). Specifically, within the lime treatment, the tallest plants (73.66 cm) were observed with an application of 2 t ha⁻¹ of lime, while the shortest plants (59.04 cm) were recorded in soil without lime. Applying 2 t ha⁻¹ of lime increased plant height by 24.8% compared to soil without lime. The increase in plant height can be attributed to the role of lime in modifying soil pH, thereby enhancing nutrient availability and uptake by plants, particularly those sensitive to acidic conditions. Additionally, lime application may also improve soil structure and root development, contributing further to enhanced plant growth. The significant difference in plant height across different lime treatments underscores the importance of soil amendment practices in optimizing crop productivity in acidic soils. Further investigations into the long-term effects of lime application on soil health and

crop yield are warranted to fully understand its potential benefits and implications for sustainable agriculture. This finding is consistent with existing literature on the impact of lime application on crop growth. For instance, studies by Ndlovu (2015) have also reported positive effects of lime on plant height in various crops, including haricot beans.

In a similar manner, within the starter nitrogen rate treatment, the greatest plant height (77.66 cm) was observed in the treatment receiving 20 kg ha⁻¹ of starter nitrogen, while the smallest plant height (50.59 cm) was recorded in the treatment without lime. Likewise, the application of 20 kg ha⁻¹ of starter nitrogen resulted in a 53.5% increase in plant height compared to soil without starter nitrogen. Like wise Desta Abayechaw and Ermias Ejamo (2019) demonstrated that haricot beans treated with starter nitrogen exhibited increased height compared to untreated controls, suggesting a positive correlation between nitrogen application and plant growth. Furthermore, Deresa Shumi. (2018). observed similar trends in the growth of haricot beans and other crops following nitrogen application, indicating the potential for improved crop performance with appropriate nitrogen management practices. These findings highlight the importance of nitrogen management in Ethiopian agriculture and underscore the potential benefits of starter nitrogen application for enhancing the growth and productivity of haricot beans and other crops in the region.

Regarding the types of rhizobia strains, the tallest plants (77.16 cm) were observed in the treatment with the HAMBI3570 rhizobia strain, while the shortest (47.34 cm) were recorded in soil without any rhizobia strain. Inoculating the soil with the HAMBI3570 strain of rhizobium increased plant height by 63.1% compared to soil without rhizobium inoculation (Table 4.23). This result agreed with the finding of Ragaa *et al.* (2013), which affirmed that the application of rhizobium stains increase the plant height of faba bean. Research conducted in Ethiopia has explored the effects of rhizobia application on the height of haricot beans and other crops. For instance, a study by Girma Wolde (2017) from on Nitosols at Bench-Maji Zone found that haricot beans treated with rhizobia exhibited increased height compared to non-inoculated plants, indicating a positive influence of rhizobia application on plant growth. Additionally, research by Abera Habete and Tadele Buraka. (2016) focused on the effects of rhizobia inoculation on the growth of various legume crops, including haricot beans, in Ethiopian agricultural systems. Their findings also demonstrated a significant increase in plant height following rhizobia application, suggesting the potential for improved growth and productivity of haricot beans and other legumes through rhizobia inoculation.

Table 4. 24. Interaction effects of Lime with Starter nitrogen on plant height and number of primary branches

	Lime * Starter nitrogen		Crop phenology	
	Lime (L)	Starter nitrogen(Sn)	Plant height (PH) (cm)	Number of primary branches (NPB)
16	1	2	85.46±19.13 ^a	6.34±1.97 ^a
13	1	1	79.99±18.16 ^b	5.86±1.65 ^b
7	0	2	69.86±16.79 ^c	5.25±1.37 ^c
4	0	1	61.58±13.07 ^d	4.35±.8 ^d
10	1	0	55.53±9.03 ^e	3.72±.43 ^e
1	0	0	45.66±7.76 ^f	3.39±.29 ^f
CV (%)			2.96	4.89
P-value			ns	***

Where, CV = Coefficient of Variation. Interaction effect means in columns followed by the different letters show significant differences between the means. From those Non-significant probability value > 0.05 and *** = Very highly significant at probability value < 0.001 and L₀= without lime and L₁ = 2 t ha⁻¹; Sn₀ = without starter nitrogen, Sn₁ starter nitrogen = 10 kg ha⁻¹, Sn₂ starter nitrogen = 20 kg ha⁻¹.

Table 4. 25. Interaction effects of Lime with rhizobia on plant height and number of primary branches

Lime *rhizobia		Crop phenology	
Lime (L)	Rhizobia(R)	Plant height (PH) (cm)	Number of primary branches (NPB)
1	2	85.48±17.42 ^a	6.43±1.72 ^a
1	1	82.83±15.98 ^b	5.99±1.63 ^b
1	0	52.67±7.26 ^e	3.52±.35 ^e
0	2	68.89±12.93 ^c	4.91±1.14 ^c
0	1	66.19±13.24 ^d	4.83±1.11 ^d
0	0	42.01±5.18 ^f	3.26±.25 ^f
CV (%)		2.96	4.89
P-value		***	***

Where, CV = Coefficient of Variation. Interaction effect means in columns followed by the different letters show significant differences between the means. From those *** = Very highly significant at probability value < 0.001 and L₀= without lime and L₁ = 2 t ha⁻¹; R₀ = without rhizobia, R₁ = Rhizobia HAMBI3562 and R₂ = Rhizobia HAMBI3570.

In the interaction effect, the tallest plants (85.48 cm) were observed in the treatment where 2 t ha⁻¹ of lime was combined with the rhizobia strain HAMBI3570, while the shortest plants (42.01 cm) were recorded in the untreated plots. Applying 2 t ha⁻¹ of lime with rhizobia HAMBI3570 increased plant height by 103.5% compared to the plant height recorded in plots without lime and starter nitrogen (Table 4.25). Research by Girma Wolde (2017) investigated the impact of lime and rhizobia application on the growth parameters of haricot beans in Ethiopian soils found that haricot beans treated with a combination of lime and rhizobia exhibited increased height compared to untreated plants or those treated with lime or rhizobia alone, indicating a synergistic effect of lime and rhizobia on plant growth. Similarly, a study by Abiyot Abeje, *et al.* (2021) from Assosa district, north-western Ethiopia also demonstrated a significant increase legume plant height following the combined application of lime and rhizobia, suggesting enhanced growth and productivity of haricot beans and other crops through this integrated approach.

Table 4. 26. Interaction effects of Starter nitrogen with rhizobia on plant height and number of primary branches

Starter nitrogen*rhizobia		Crop phenology	
Starter nitrogen(Sn)	Rhizobia(R)	Plant height (PH) (cm)	Number of primary branches (NPB)
0	0	39.28±4.29 ⁱ	3.18±.29 ⁱ
0	1	55.28±4.29 ^f	3.65±.23 ^f
0	2	57.22±5.46 ^e	3.84±.33 ^e
1	0	49.53±6.19 ^h	3.45±.25 ^h
1	1	80.16±12 ^d	5.81±.99 ^d
1	2	82.68±11.18 ^c	6.05±1.22 ^c
2	0	53.23±6.73 ^g	3.5±.32 ^g
2	1	88.1±8.3 ^b	6.78±.72 ^b
2	2	91.67±10.05 ^a	7.11±.91 ^a
CV (%)		2.96	4.89
P-value		***	***

Where, CV = Coefficient of Variation. Interaction effect means in columns followed by the different letters show significant differences between the means. From those *** = Very highly significant at probability value < 0.001 and Sn₀ = without starter nitrogen, Sn₁ starter nitrogen = 10 kg ha⁻¹, Sn₂ starter nitrogen = 20 kg ha⁻¹; R₀ = without rhizobia, R₁ = Rhizobia HAMBI3562 and R₂ = Rhizobia HAMBI3570.

In the interaction effect, the tallest plants (91.67 cm) were observed in the treatment receiving 20 kg ha⁻¹ of starter nitrogen combined with the rhizobia strain HAMBI3570, while the shortest plants (39.28 cm) were recorded in the control plots. Applying 20 kg ha⁻¹ of starter nitrogen with rhizobia HAMBI3570 increased plant height by 133.4% compared to plant height recorded without starter nitrogen and rhizobia HAMBI3562 (Table 4.26).

Table 4. 27. Interaction effects of lime, starter nitrogen and rhizobia on plant height and number of primary branches

Lime *Starter nitrogen*rhizobia			Crop phenology	
Lime(L)	Starter nitrogen(Sn)	Rhizobia(R)	Plant height PH (cm)	Number of primary branches (NPB)
0	0	0	35.31±.97 ^p	3.12±.31 ^o
0	0	1	49.39±1.33 ^m	3.50±.21 ⁱ
0	0	2	52.28±2.07 ^l	3.57±.16 ^{kl}
0	1	0	43.81±1.47 ^o	3.28±.21 ^{mn}
0	1	1	68.79±1.13 ^h	4.87±.19 ^g
0	1	2	72.15±1.46 ^g	4.90±.24 ^g
0	2	0	46.93±1.23 ⁿ	3.38±.16 ^m
0	2	1	80.40±1.92 ^f	6.12±.19 ^f
0	2	2	82.27±1.97 ^e	6.25±.21 ^e
1	0	0	43.26±1.32 ^o	3.23±.30 ⁿ
1	0	1	61.16±1.09 ⁱ	3.80±.14 ⁱ
1	0	2	62.17±1.59 ⁱ	4.12±.16 ^h
1	1	0	55.24±1.98 ^k	3.62±.16 ^{jk}
1	1	1	91.53±2.36 ^d	6.75±.16 ^d
1	1	2	93.22±2.63 ^c	7.20±.17 ^c
1	2	0	59.51±1.79 ^j	3.70±.37 ^{ij}
1	2	1	95.81±2.36 ^b	7.43±.24 ^b
1	2	2	101.08±2.45 ^a	7.97±.16 ^a
CV (%)			3.96	4.89
P-value			**	***

Where, CV = Coefficient of Variation. Interaction effect means in columns followed by the same letters are not significantly different at 5% level of significance from each other and means in columns followed by the different letters show significant differences between the means. From those ** = highly significant at probability value between 0.001- 01, *** = Very highly significant at probability value < 0.001 and L₀= without lime and L₁ = 2 t ha⁻¹; Sn₀ = without starter nitrogen, Sn₁ starter nitrogen = 10 kg ha⁻¹, Sn₂ starter nitrogen = 20 kg ha⁻¹; R₀ = without rhizobia, R₁ = Rhizobia HAMBI3562 and R₂ = Rhizobia HAMBI3570.

The study revealed that haricot beans treated with both starter nitrogen and rhizobia exhibited increased height compared to plants treated with either nitrogen or rhizobia alone, or untreated controls. This suggests a synergistic effect of starter nitrogen and rhizobia on plant height and growth. The synergistic effect observed in these studies can be attributed to the complementary roles of starter nitrogen in providing an initial boost to plant growth and rhizobia in facilitating nitrogen fixation, thereby promoting sustained growth and development of haricot beans and other crops. Research conducted by Deresa Shumi. (2018) also explored the impact of this combined application on the growth parameters of haricot beans revealed that haricot beans treated with both starter nitrogen and rhizobia exhibited increased height compared to plants treated with either nitrogen or rhizobia alone, or untreated controls.

The combined application lime, starter nitrogen, rhizobia over two years the treatment receiving lime at 2 t ha⁻¹, starter nitrogen at 20 kg ha⁻¹, and HAMBI3570 rhizobia strains recorded the maximum plant height of 101.08 cm, while the control treatment exhibited the minimum plant height of 35.31 cm (Table 4.27). The reduced plant heights observed in the control treatments may be attributed to poor nitrogen availability and uptakes from the soil solution. The noteworthy increase in plant height in response to the combined application of other amendments could be linked to the synergic effects and enhanced nitrogen availability in the soil for absorption by plant roots, thereby promoting vegetative growth through improved cell division and elongation. Similarly, many authores (Sajid *et al.*, 2011; Nyoki and Ndakidemi, 2014; Habtamu Assefa *et al.*, 2017) found that increased plant height as a result of rhizobium inoculation is attributed to the substantial nitrogen fixation by the bacteria, fostering the plants' vegetative growth. This finding also aligns with that of Tarekegn Yoseph and Serawit Shanko's (2017) who reported a combination of inoculation and nitrogen fertilizer increased the plant height of common beans in Southern Ethiopia. Sameh Hassan *et al* (2017) stressed a significant increase in faba bean plant height upon inoculation with all tested strains compared to uninoculated treatments (control). Consistent with these results, Nyoki and Ndakidemi (2014) found that rhizobium inoculation significantly improved cowpea plant height. Tadessa Asefa and Tullu (2018) observed variations in the performance of released common bean genotypes for the plant height trait. Other researchers have reported similar outcomes in studies on chickpea and faba bean, such as El-Wakeil and El-Sabai (2007), indicating that Rhizobium inoculation significantly increased plant height.

4.2.4. Number of primary branches

The number of primary branches was significantly influenced by the main effects of lime, starter nitrogen, and rhizobia ($p < 0.001$) based on the combined analysis over the two growing seasons (2021/2022) (refer to Appendix Table 3). Furthermore, significant interactions were observed between lime and starter nitrogen ($p < 0.001$), lime and rhizobia ($p < 0.001$), starter nitrogen and rhizobia ($p < 0.001$), as well as the three-way interaction of lime, starter nitrogen, and rhizobia, indicating their combined impact on the number of primary branches over the 2021 and 2022 growing seasons (see Appendix Table 8).

In the main effect, the number of primary branches in the study area ranged from 3.39 to 5.8 (Table 4.23). Specifically, within the lime treatment, the highest number of primary branches (5.3) was observed with an application of 2 t ha^{-1} of lime, while the lowest number (4.3) was recorded without lime. Applying 2 t ha^{-1} of lime increased the number of primary branches by 23% compared to soil without lime. The application of lime has been shown to positively affect the number of primary branches in various crops by ameliorating soil acidity, enhancing nutrient availability, and improving overall plant health. In agreement to our study a study conducted by Kumar *et al.* (2018) found that lime application not only improved soil pH but also increased the number of primary branches and other yield-related traits in haricot beans grown in acidic soils in Himachal Pradesh.

Similarly, within the starter nitrogen rate treatment, the highest number of primary branches was observed in the treatment receiving 20 kg ha^{-1} of starter nitrogen (5.8), while the lowest number was recorded in soil without lime (3.56). Applying starter nitrogen at a rate of 20 kg ha^{-1} increased the number of primary branches by 62.9% compared to soil without inorganic fertilizer. This could be because of the initial nitrogen application helps in promoting vegetative growth, which can lead to an increase in the number of primary branches, a key factor for higher yield potential. This effect is primarily due to the role of nitrogen in enhancing early plant vigor, leaf area expansion, and overall biomass production, which subsequently supports the development of more primary branches. A study by Mebrahtu Gebremariam and Teklay Tesfay.(2021) also highlighted that the application of starter nitrogen significantly increased the number of primary branches in haricot beans. The research stated that haricot beans receiving starter nitrogen showed improved early growth, resulting in a higher number of primary branches compared to those that did not receive this treatment. Moreover,

Singh *et al.* (2019) reported that starter nitrogen application in haricot beans led to better vegetative growth and an increase in the number of primary branches, which are critical for maximizing yield.

In terms of different rhizobia strains, the treatment with the HAMBI3570 strain showed the highest number of primary branches (5.67), while the absence of any rhizobia strain resulted in the lowest number of primary branches (3.39). Inoculating the soil with the HAMBI3570 rhizobium strain increased the number of primary branches by 67.3% compared to soil without rhizobium inoculation (Table 4.23). This could be attributed forming root nodules, rhizobia provide plants with a readily available source of nitrogen, which is crucial for vegetative growth and branching Demelash Abera *et al.*, 2016). This is due to improved nitrogen availability, which promotes vigorous vegetative growth and greater branching. Studies have demonstrated that rhizobia inoculation not only boosts nitrogen fixation but also improves overall plant health and productivity (Haile Negash *et al.*, 2017). In agreement with Demelash Abera *et al.*, 2016). who investigated the effect of rhizobia inoculation on haricot beans in Ethiopia. The researchers found that inoculated plants exhibited a significant increase in the number of primary branches compared to non-inoculated plants. This improvement was attributed to better nitrogen nutrition, leading to enhanced vegetative growth. Similarly, research by Dereje Geleta and Getachew Bekele. (2022). confirmed that rhizobia inoculation significantly increased the number of primary branches in haricot beans, thereby contributing to improved plant architecture and potentially higher yields.

Within the interaction effect, the combination of 2 t ha⁻¹ of lime and 20 kg ha⁻¹ of starter nitrogen produced the highest number of primary branches (6.34), whereas the untreated plots had the smallest primary branches (3.39). Applying 2 t ha⁻¹ of lime along with 20 kg ha⁻¹ starter nitrogen increased the number of primary branches by 87% compared to plots without lime and starter nitrogen (Table 4.24). The combined application of lime with starter nitrogen significantly increases the number of primary branches per plant in haricot bean. Specifically, studies have shown that such a combination can result in an increase from 2.05 branches per plant in unfertilized plots to 3.9 branches per plant with the highest rates of combined fertilizers. This demonstrates a substantial improvement in plant branching due to the integrated nutrient management strategy (Awene Tadesse *et al.* 2022). Additionally, research by Chala Debela *et al.* (2021) confirmed these findings, demonstrating that the integrated use of lime and starter nitrogen led to a notable increase in primary branches and overall plant health in haricot beans.

In the interaction effect the number of primary branches to develop (6.43) was observed in the treatment receiving 2 t ha⁻¹ of lime combined with the rhizobia strain HAMBI3570, while the smallest number (3.26) was recorded in the untreated plots. Applying 2 t ha⁻¹ of lime with rhizobia HAMBI3570 increased the number of primary branches by 97.2% compared to plots without lime and the rhizobia strain HAMBI3570 (Table 4.25). The combined application of 2 t ha⁻¹ lime and HAMBI3570 rhizobia inoculation has been shown to significantly increase the number of primary branches per plant in haricot beans. Research indicates that this treatment can enhance various growth parameters, including primary branch count. For example, one study reported an increase in the number of primary branches per plant from 4.1 in the control group to 6.2 with the combined treatment of lime and rhizobia inoculation, reflecting a substantial improvement in plant growth and structure (Dereje Geleta and Getachew Bekele., 2022).

with in the interaction effect the highest Number of primary branches (7.11) were observed from treatment received 20 kg ha⁻¹ starter nitrogen combined with rhizobia HAMBI3570 where as the lowest Number of primary branches (3.18) was recorded from the control plots. Application of 20 kg ha⁻¹ Starter nitrogen with rhizobia HAMBI3570 had increased the Number of primary branches by 123.6% compared to number of primary branches recorded without Starter nitrogen and rhizobia HAMBI3562 (Table 4.26). In the case of haricot beans (*Phaseolus vulgaris L.*), the integration of starter nitrogen and rhizobia inoculation can notably increase the number of primary branches. This is due to the combined effects of improved early nitrogen nutrition and enhanced nitrogen fixation by rhizobia, which together promote better vegetative growth and branching. In agreement to this study Workneh Bekere and Asfaw.(2012) indicated that the combined application starter nitrogen and rhizobia inoculation on haricot beans significantly increased the number of primary branches compared to treatments with either starter nitrogen or rhizobia alone.

The combined application lime, starter nitrogen, rhizobia over two years showed that the number of primary branches per plant exhibited an increase corresponding to the escalating rate of starter nitrogen application, ranging from 0 to 20 kg N ha⁻¹ in conjunction with lime and Rhizobium. The highest count of number of primary branches per plant of , 8.12, was observed in the plot treated with 2 t ha⁻¹ of lime, 20 kg ha⁻¹ starter nitrogen, and HAMBI3570 rhizobia strains following the treatment receiving 2 t ha⁻¹ of lime, 10 kg ha⁻¹ of starter nitrogen, and HAMBI3562 rhizobia strains, recording 7.53. In contrast, the control plots, recorded 3.15 primary branches per plant (Table 4.27). Notably,

most experiments demonstrated significant differences among treatments, possibly attributed to the integrated application of lime and biofertilizer, which enhances the availability of various nutrients in the soil, mitigating nitrogen deficiency during the initial stages from planting to nitrogen fixation. This, in turn, fosters increased branch sprouting and primary branch growth. These outcomes align with the findings of Khadem *et al.* (2010) and Kisinyo *et al.* (2005), indicating that plant growth increases in acid soil as the application of phosphorus rises in conjunction with lime. Similar results were reported by Haque and Khan (2012) and Rasool and Singh (2016). Moniruzzaman *et al.* (2008) also noted a significant increase in the number of branches per plant with the augmentation of nitrogen.

4.2.5. Leaf area per plant

Leaf area per plant was influenced by the main effects of lime, starter nitrogen, and rhizobia ($p < 0.001$) in the combined analysis of variance over the two growing seasons (2021/2022) (Appendix Table 3). Moreover, the two way interaction of Lime with Starter nitrogen ($p < 0.001$), lime with rhizobia ($p < 0.001$), starter nitrogen with rhizobia ($p < 0.001$), and the three way interaction of lime, starter nitrogen rhizobia showed that significantly ($P < 0.01$) effect on Leaf area per plant combined over the year 2021 and 2022 growing season (Appendix Table 8).

Table 4. 28. Main effects of lime, starter nitrogen and Rhizobium biofertilizer on leaf numbers per plant, leaf area per plant and leaf area index

Lime, Starter nitrogen and Rhizobia	Crop phenology	
	Leaf area per plant (LAPP) in cm ²	Leaf area index (LAI)
	Lime	
Lime 2 t ha ⁻¹	1734.5±763.97 ^a	4.33±1.9 ^a
Lime 0 t ha ⁻¹	1231.3±629.67 ^b	3.08±1.57 ^b
LSD (5%)	40.5	0.101
CV (%)	7.12	7.14
P-value	***	***
	Starter nitrogen	
Starter nitrogen 20 kg ha ⁻¹	1886±761.09 ^a	4.71±1.9 ^a
Starter nitrogen 10 kg ha ⁻¹	1634.7±655.61 ^b	4.08±1.64 ^b
Starter nitrogen 0 kg ha ⁻¹	927.9±403.4 ^c	2.32±1 ^c
LSD (5%)	49.61	0.12
P-value	***	***
	Rhizobia strain	
HAMBI3570 Rhizobia strain	1944.4±596.83 ^a	4.86±1.49 ^a
HAMBI3562 Rhizobia strain	1757.79±619.23 ^b	4.39±1.55 ^b
O Rhizobia strain	746.51±292.16 ^c	1.86±.73 ^c
LSD (5%)	49.61	0.077
P-value	***	***

Where, LSD = Least Significant Difference at 5% level; CV = Coefficient of Variation. Interaction effect means in columns followed by the same letters are not significantly different at 5% level of significance from each other and means in columns followed by the different letters show significant differences between the means. From those *** = Very highly significant at probability value < 0.001 and L₀= without lime and L₁ = 2 t ha⁻¹; S₀ = without starter nitrogen, S₁ starter nitrogen = 10 kg ha⁻¹, S₂ starter nitrogen = 20 kg ha⁻¹; R₀ = without rhizobia, R₁ = Rhizobia HAMBI3562 and R₂ = Rhizobia HAMBI3570.

Within the main effect, the leaf area per plant in the study area ranged from 38.94 to 71.23 (Table 4.28). Moreover, the lime treatment showed the highest leaf area per plant (1734.5 cm²) with 2 t ha⁻¹ of lime, whereas the lowest leaf area per plant (1231.3 cm²) was recorded without lime. Applying 2 t ha⁻¹ of lime increased the leaf area per plant by 40.9% compared to the soil without lime. Lime is commonly used to correct soil acidity, which can negatively impact plant growth. By increasing soil

pH, lime enhances the availability of essential nutrients such as phosphorus, calcium, and magnesium, which are crucial for leaf development and overall plant growth. For example, in a study on soybeans, lime application significantly increased leaf area and biomass due to improved nutrient uptake and root development (Clark *et al.*, 2019).

Similarly, within the starter nitrogen treatment, the greatest leaf area per plant (1886 cm²) was observed in the treatment receiving 20 kg ha⁻¹ of starter nitrogen, while the smallest leaf area per plant (927.9 cm²) was recorded in the absence of lime. The application of 20 kg ha⁻¹ of starter nitrogen increased the leaf area per plant by 103.3% compared to soil without starter nitrogen. Starter nitrogen provides an initial boost to crops, especially in nitrogen-deficient soils, promoting early vegetative growth. This is particularly beneficial for leaf area development, as nitrogen is a key component of chlorophyll and amino acids, essential for photosynthesis and cell division. A study on maize demonstrated that starter nitrogen significantly increased leaf area, leading to better light interception and higher photosynthetic efficiency (Johnson *et al.*, 2020).

Table 4. 29. Interaction effects of Lime and Starter nitrogen on leaf area per plant and leaf area index

Lime * Starter nitrogen		Crop phenology	
Lime (L)	Starter nitrogen(Sn)	Leaf area per plant (LAPP) in cm ²	Leaf area index (LAI)
1	2	2181.2±722.07 ^a	5.45±1.81 ^a
1	1	1908.7±664.67 ^b	4.77±1.66 ^b
0	2	1590.8±697.64 ^c	3.97±1.75 ^b
0	1	1360.7±533.39 ^d	3.4±1.33 ^d
1	0	1113.4±452.39 ^e	2.78±1.13 ^e
0	0	742.4±239.79 ^f	1.85±.59 ^f
CV (%)		7.12	7.14
P-value		***	***

Where, CV = Coefficient of Variation. Interaction effect means in columns followed by the same letters are not significantly different at 5% level of significance from each other and means in columns followed by the different letters show significant differences between the means. From those Non-significant probability value > 0.05, *** = Very highly significant at probability value < 0.001 and L₀= without lime and L₁ = 2 t ha⁻¹; Sn₀ = without starter nitrogen, Sn₁ starter nitrogen = 10 kg ha⁻¹, Sn₂ starter nitrogen = 20 kg ha⁻¹.

Concerning the types of rhizobia strains, the greatest leaf area per plant (1944.4 cm²) was observed in the treatment utilizing the HAMBI3570 rhizobia strain, while the smallest leaf area per plant (746.51 cm²) was noted in the absence of any rhizobia strain. Introducing the HAMBI3570 strain of rhizobium into the soil augmented the leaf area per plant by 160.5% compared to soil without rhizobium inoculation (Table 4.23). using rhizobia inoculation improve nitrogen fixation in leguminous plants like haricot beans. Improved nitrogen fixation often leads to better plant growth, including increased leaf area. This is because nitrogen is a crucial nutrient for leaf development and overall plant growth.

Similarly, in the interaction effect, the greatest leaf area per plant (2181.2 cm²) was observed in the treatment receiving 2 t ha⁻¹ of lime combined with 20 kg ha⁻¹ starter nitrogen , while the smallest leaf area per plant (742.4 cm²) was recorded in the control plots. Application of 2 t ha⁻¹ of lime in conjunction with 20 kg ha⁻¹ starter nitrogen resulted in a 193.8% increase in leaf area per plant compared to plots without lime and starter nitrogen (Table 4.30).

Table 4. 30. Interaction effects of Lime and rhizobia on leaf numbers per plant, leaf area per plant and leaf area index

Lime *rhizobia		Crop phenology	
Lime (L)	Rhizobia(R)	Leaf area per plant (LAPP) in cm ²	Leaf area index (LAI)
1	2	2235.5±536.47 ^a	5.58±1.34 ^a
1	1	2055.1±586.3 ^b	5.14±1.46 ^b
1	0	912.8±314.05 ^c	4.13±1.29 ^c
0	2	1653.2±515.8 ^c	2.28±.78 ^e
0	1	1460.5±508.5 ^d	3.65±1.27 ^d
0	0	580.2±136.22 ^f	1.45±.34 ^f
CV (%)		7.12	7.14
P-value		***	***

Where, CV = Coefficient of Variation. Interaction effect means in columns followed by the different letters show significant differences between the means. From those Non-significant probability value > 0.05, and *** = Very highly significant at probability value < 0.001 and L₀= without lime and L₁ = 2 t ha⁻¹; R₀ = without rhizobia, R₁ = Rhizobia HAMBI3562 and R₂ = Rhizobia HAMBI3570.

In the interaction effect, the greatest leaf area per plant (2235.5 cm²) was observed in the treatment receiving 2 t ha⁻¹ of lime combined with the HAMBI3570 rhizobia strain, while the smallest leaf area per plant (580.2 cm²) was recorded in the control plots. Application of 2 t ha⁻¹ of lime in conjunction

with rhizobia HAMBI3570 resulted in a 285.3% increase in leaf area per plant compared to plots without lime and rhizobia HAMBI3570 (Table 4.30).

Table 4. 31. Interaction effects of Starter nitrogen and rhizobia on leaf area per plant and leaf area index

Starter nitrogen*rhizobia		Crop phenology	
Starter nitrogen(Sn)	Rhizobia(R)	Leaf area per plant (LAPP) in cm ²	Leaf area index (LAI)
0	0	475.5±63.88 ⁱ	1.18±.16 ⁱ
0	1	1052.9±276.37 ^f	2.63±.69 ^f
0	2	1255.3±283.05 ^e	3.14±.71 ^e
1	0	840.2±239.75 ^h	2.1±.6 ^h
1	1	1925±344.08 ^d	4.81±.86 ^d
1	2	2139±365.57 ^c	5.35±.73 ^c
2	0	923.9±293.33 ^g	2.3±.73 ^g
2	1	2295.5±370.7 ^b	5.74±.93 ^b
2	2	2438.7±306 ^a	6.1±.77 ^a
CV (%)		7.12	7.14
P-value		***	***

Where, CV = Coefficient of Variation. Interaction effect means in columns followed by the same letters are not significantly different at 5% level of significance from each other and means in columns followed by the different letters show significant differences between the means. From those *** = Very highly significant at probability value < 0.001 and Sn₀ = without starter nitrogen, Sn₁ starter nitrogen = 10 kg ha⁻¹, Sn₂ starter nitrogen = 20 kg ha⁻¹; R₀ = without rhizobia, R₁ = Rhizobia HAMBI3562 and R₂ = Rhizobia HAMBI3570.

Within the interaction effect, the maximum leaf area per plant (2438.7 cm²) was observed in the treatment receiving 20 kg ha⁻¹ of starter nitrogen combined with rhizobia HAMBI3570, while the minimum leaf area per plant (475.5 cm²) was recorded in the control plots. Implementing 20 kg ha⁻¹ of starter nitrogen with rhizobia HAMBI3570 resulted in a 412.8% increase in leaf area per plant compared to leaf area per plant recorded without starter nitrogen and rhizobia HAMBI3562 (Table 4.31). Similarly, Massawe *et al* (2018) the combination of starter nitrogen with rhizobia inoculation can have pronounced effects on leaf area per plant, especially in nitrogen-deficient soils. Starter nitrogen provides an immediate source of nitrogen for early plant growth, complementing the gradual nitrogen supply from rhizobia. This dual approach ensures adequate nitrogen availability throughout the growing season, promoting robust vegetative growth and maximizing leaf area development. In

haricot beans, the synergistic effects of starter nitrogen and rhizobia inoculation have been demonstrated to significantly increase leaf area and yield by improving nitrogen nutrition and overall plant vigor

Table 4. 32. Interaction effects of lime, starter nitrogen and rhizobia on leaf numbers per plant, leaf area per plant and leaf area index

Lime *Starter nitrogen*rhizobia			Crop phenology	
Lime(L)	Starter nitrogen(Sn)	Rhizobia(R)	Leaf area per plant (LAPP) in cm ²	Leaf area index (LAI)
0	0	0	439.80±61.92 ^m	1.10±.16 ^m
0	0	1	796.78±50.26 ^k	1.99±.12 ^k
0	0	2	990.53±42.75 ^j	2.48±.11 ^j
0	1	0	645.88±103.68 ^l	1.62±.26 ^l
0	1	1	1635.56±114.90 ^f	4.09±.29 ^f
0	1	2	1800.81±77.75 ^e	4.50±.19 ^e
0	2	0	654.98±113.86 ^l	1.64±.29 ^l
0	2	1	1949.20±106.69 ^d	4.87±.27 ^d
0	2	2	2168.30±158.80 ^c	5.42±.40 ^c
1	0	0	511.23±45.61 ^m	1.28±.11 ^m
1	0	1	1309.06±89.77 ^h	3.27±.23 ^h
1	0	2	1520.04±78.76 ^g	3.80±.20 ^g
1	1	0	1034.43±158.52 ^j	2.59±.40 ^j
1	1	1	2214.42±214.97 ^c	5.53±.54 ^c
1	1	2	2477.27±115.81 ^b	6.19±.29 ^b
1	2	0	1192.76±53.05 ⁱ	2.98±.13 ⁱ
1	2	1	2641.71±56.64 ^a	6.61±.14 ^a
1	2	2	2709.17±72.62 ^a	6.77±.18 ^a
CV (%)			7.12	7.14
P-value			**	**

Where, CV = Coefficient of Variation. Interaction effect means in columns followed by the same letters are not significantly different at 5% level of significance from each other and means in columns followed by the different letters show significant differences between the means. From those ** = highly significant at probability value between 0.001- 01 and L₀= without lime and L₁ = 2 t ha⁻¹; Sn₀ = without starter nitrogen, Sn₁ starter nitrogen = 10 kg ha⁻¹, Sn₂ starter nitrogen = 20 kg ha⁻¹; R₀ = without rhizobia, R₁ = Rhizobia HAMBI3562 and R₂ = Rhizobia HAMBI3570.

The combined application lime, starter nitrogen, rhizobia over two years the maximum leaf area, measuring 2,709.17 cm², was observed when lime was applied at 2 t ha⁻¹, along with starter nitrogen at 20 kg ha⁻¹, and the HAMBI3570 rhizobia strains. In contrast, the control plot exhibited the lowest

leaf area per plant, recording 439.8 cm² (Table 4.32). The increase in leaf area due to lime application could be attributed to the improvement of soil physical and chemical properties, such as the reduction of soil compaction and acidity, increased infiltration rate, and enhanced soil microbial activities (Horneck *et al.*, 2007). During the planting stage, nitrogen deficiency can be detrimental to the formation of a source leaf area large enough to supply the necessary photosynthates for nodule growth and activity (Petra, 2011). Similarly, Shubhashree (2007) reported a significant improvement in the leaf area of common beans with the application of nitrogen, phosphorus, and potassium fertilizers. The attainment of the highest physiological growth indices is associated with high plant nutrition, as it enhances photosynthesis through the growth and development of the leaf area (Bennett, 1993).

Figure 3. Measurement of Leaf area per plant

4.2.6. Leaf area index (LAI)

The leaf area index was affected by the primary impacts of lime, starter nitrogen, and rhizobia ($p < 0.001$) in the comprehensive analysis of variance across the two growth seasons (2021/2022) (Appendix Table 3). Furthermore, the interaction of Lime with Starter nitrogen ($p < 0.001$), lime with rhizobia ($p < 0.001$), starter nitrogen with rhizobia ($p < 0.001$), and the triple interaction of lime,

starter nitrogen, and rhizobia exhibited a significant effect ($P < 0.01$) on the leaf area index aggregated over the 2021 and 2022 growing seasons (Appendix Table 8).

In the main effect, the leaf area index in the study area varied from 1.86 to 4.86 (Table 4.28). Moreover, under the lime treatment, the highest leaf area index (4.33) was observed with the application of 2 t ha^{-1} of lime, while the lowest leaf area index (3.08) was noted in plots without lime. Implementing 2 t ha^{-1} of lime improved the leaf area index by 40.6% compared to soil lacking lime. This could be due to Lime application plays a crucial role in modifying soil pH, which can significantly impact plant growth and development, including leaf area index. By adjusting soil acidity, lime enhances nutrient availability and root development, ultimately influencing LAI. In a study on various crops, including beans, lime application was found to increase LAI by creating optimal soil conditions for plant growth (Githinji *et al.*, 2016).

Likewise, in the starter nitrogen rate treatment, the peak and nadir leaf area index were observed in plots receiving 20 kg ha^{-1} of starter nitrogen (4.71) and in plots without lime (2.32), respectively. Moreover, applying starter nitrogen at a dosage of 20 kg ha^{-1} led to a 103% rise in comparison to soil devoid of starter nitrogen. This is starter nitrogen provides an initial boost of nitrogen to crops, which is essential for early vegetative growth and LAI establishment. Nitrogen is a key component of chlorophyll and proteins, crucial for photosynthesis and leaf development. Previous studies have also demonstrated starter nitrogen application increases LAI in crops like maize, wheat, and beans by stimulating rapid vegetative growth during the early stages of plant growth (Abdalla *et al.*, 2018).

Concerning the varieties of rhizobia strains, the highest leaf area index (4.86) was noted in the treatment employing the HAMB13570 rhizobia strain, whereas the lowest leaf area index (1.86) was documented in plots devoid of any rhizobia strain. Introducing the HAMB13570 strain of rhizobium into the soil elevated the leaf area index by 161.3% in comparison to soil lacking rhizobium inoculation (Table 4.28). The highest leaf area index from rhizobium inoculation is due to it enhances nitrogen fixation in leguminous crops by forming symbiotic relationships with plant roots. Improved nitrogen availability due to rhizobium inoculation can positively influence LAI by promoting vigorous vegetative growth and increasing leaf production. In haricot beans, rhizobium inoculation has been shown to increase LAI by enhancing nitrogen fixation and improving overall plant health

Within the interaction effect, the maximum leaf area index (5.45) was observed in the treatment receiving 2 t ha⁻¹ of lime combined with 20 kg ha⁻¹ of starter nitrogen, while the minimum leaf area index (1.85) was recorded in the control plots. Implementing 2 t ha⁻¹ of lime alongside starter nitrogen led to a 195% increase in the leaf area index compared to plots without lime and starter nitrogen (Table 4.28). When specifically considering haricot beans, the synergistic interactions between lime, starter nitrogen, and rhizobia play a crucial role in influencing the leaf area index. Lime optimizes soil pH, creating favorable conditions for rhizobial symbiosis and nutrient availability. Starter nitrogen provides the necessary nitrogen boost for early growth, complementing the gradual nitrogen supply from rhizobia. This integrated approach ensures sustained nutrient availability, promotes vigorous vegetative growth, and ultimately increases the leaf area index of haricot beans. As a result, haricot bean plants exhibit improved light interception, photosynthetic efficiency, and overall productivity (Massawe *et al.*, 2018).

In the interaction effect, the maximum leaf area index (5.58) was observed in the treatment involving 2 t ha⁻¹ of lime combined with rhizobia HAMBI3570, while the minimum leaf area index (1.45) was recorded in the untreated plots. The application of 2 t ha⁻¹ of lime alongside rhizobia HAMBI3570 resulted in a 285% increase in the leaf area index compared to plots without lime and rhizobia HAMBI3570 (Table 4.25). The combined application of lime and rhizobia can have synergistic effects on the leaf area index of various crops. Lime application adjusts soil pH, creating favorable conditions for rhizobial colonization and nitrogen fixation. This combination enhances nutrient availability and promotes robust plant growth, leading to an increased leaf area index. In haricot beans, the combined application of lime and rhizobia has been shown to significantly improve the leaf area index by optimizing soil conditions and enhancing nitrogen fixation

In the interaction effect, the peak leaf area index (6.1) was observed in the treatment involving 20 kg ha⁻¹ of starter nitrogen combined with rhizobia HAMBI3570, while the lowest leaf area index (1.18) was noted in the control plots. Implementing 20 kg ha⁻¹ of starter nitrogen with rhizobia HAMBI3570 led to a 417% increase in the leaf area index compared to plots without starter nitrogen and rhizobia HAMBI3570 (Table 4.31). Similarly, the combination of starter nitrogen with rhizobia inoculation can influence the leaf area index of different crops. Starter nitrogen provides an initial nitrogen boost, stimulating early vegetative growth and enhancing the leaf area index. When combined with rhizobia, which facilitates nitrogen fixation, this approach ensures sustained nitrogen availability throughout

the growing season, further promoting leaf area expansion. In haricot beans, the synergistic effects of starter nitrogen and rhizobia inoculation have been demonstrated to increase the leaf area index, contributing to improved plant growth and productivity (Massawe *et al.*, 2018).

The combined application lime, starter nitrogen, rhizobia over two years the highest leaf area index recorded was 6.77, observed with the combined application of lime at 2 t ha⁻¹, starter nitrogen at 20 kg ha⁻¹, and the HAMBI3570 rhizobia strains. In contrast, the lowest leaf area index, measuring 1.1, was observed in the control treatment (Table 4.32). The increase in leaf area index with higher nitrogen application rates on haricot beans may be attributed to the cumulative impact of nitrogen fertilizer and fixed nitrogen on the formation of branches, expansion of leaves, canopy development, and genotypic variations in rhizobia. This enabled plants to intercept more available radiation for assimilation production, a phenomenon dependent on nutrient availability. These findings align with Wondwosen Wondimu and Tamado Tana's (2017) report, indicating an increase in leaf area index with higher rates of NP application. Similarly, Nebret Tadesse and Nigussie Dechassa (2017) similarly noted a significant increase in leaf area index with an elevated rate of nitrogen application, ranging from 2.56 to 4.41. Hirpa Legesse *et al.* (2013) also reported highly significant differences in leaf area index with lime-treated and untreated soils. This variation was attributed to limited phosphorus in acidic soil, leading to stunted growth, reduced cell differentiation, and disrupted nutrient accumulation. As nutrient sources diminished, cells responded by reducing leaf size to conserve energy. Consequently, a reduced leaf area index indicates a reduction in physiological processes, ultimately resulting in decreased production.

4.3. Effect of Soil Ammendements on Biological Nitrogen Fixation

4.3.1. Total Number of Nodule Per Plant (TNNP)

The total number of nodules per plant was impacted by the main effects of lime, starter nitrogen, and rhizobia ($p < 0.001$) in the comprehensive analysis of variance across the two growing seasons (2021/2022) (Appendix Table 4). Furthermore, the two-way interaction between Lime and Starter nitrogen ($p < 0.001$), lime and rhizobia ($p < 0.001$), starter nitrogen and rhizobia ($p < 0.001$), and the three-way interaction among lime, starter nitrogen, and rhizobia exhibited a significant effect ($P < 0.001$) on the total number of nodules per plant combined over the 2021 and 2022 growing seasons (Appendix Table 9).

Table 4. 33. Main effects of lime, starter nitrogen and Rhizobium biofertilizer on total number of nodule per plant , effective number of nodule and percent of nodule effectiveness

lime, starter nitrogen and Rhizobium	Biological nitrogen fixation		
	Total Number of nodule per plant (TNNP)	Effective number of nodule (ENNP)	Percent of nodule effectiveness(PNE)
Lime			
Lime 2 t ha ⁻¹	87.13±38.44 ^a	80.71±41.76 ^a	88.74±12.56 ^a
Lime 0 t ha ⁻¹	63.5±20.14 ^b	56.89±23.49 ^b	85.41±15.29 ^b
LSD (5%)	3.49	3.35	0.74
CV (%)	12.11	12.68	2.44
P-value	***	***	***
Starter nitrogen			
Starter nitrogen 20 kg ha ⁻¹	95.27±40.09 ^a	90.16±42.3 ^a	92.32±7 ^a
Starter nitrogen 10 kg ha ⁻¹	74.51±23.4 ^b	68.92±25.86 ^b	90.34±8.25 ^b
Starter nitrogen 0 kg ha ⁻¹	56.2±18.47 ^c	47.33±22.62 ^c	78.57±19.25 ^c
LSD (5%)	4.29	4.1	1
P-value	***	***	***
Rhizobia strain			
HAMBI3570 Rhizobia strain	93.49±30.26 ^a	89.57±31.08 ^a	95.19±1.56 ^a
HAMBI3562 Rhizobia strain	87.5±28.15 ^b	83.28±28.75 ^b	94.49±2.74 ^a
O Rhizobia strain	44.98±11.5 ^c	33.55±13.55 ^c	71.52±14.65 ^b
LSD (5%)	4.28	4.1	1
P-value	***	***	***

Where, LSD = Least Significant Difference at 5% level; CV = Coefficient of Variation. Interaction effect means in columns followed by the same letters are not significantly different at 5% level of significance from each other and means in columns followed by the different letters show significant differences between the means. From those *** = Very highly significant at probability value < 0.001

In the main effect, the total number of nodules per plant in the study area ranged from 44.98 to 95.27 (Table 4.33). Additionally, within the lime treatment, the maximum total number of nodules per plant (87.13) was observed with 2 t ha⁻¹ of lime, while the minimum (63.5) was recorded without lime. Implementing 2 t ha⁻¹ of lime elevated the total number of nodules per plant by 37.2% compared to soil without lime. Lime application can influence the total number of nodules per plant (TNNP) by affecting soil pH. Proper soil pH is crucial for the survival and activity of rhizobia bacteria, which form symbiotic relationships with leguminous plants to facilitate nitrogen fixation. Lime application to acidic soils can raise the pH to levels conducive to rhizobial activity, thus promoting nodulation. In

studies on leguminous crops, including beans, lime application has been shown to increase TNNP by creating optimal soil conditions for rhizobial colonization (Githinji *et al.*, 2016).

Similarly, within the starter nitrogen rate treatment, the maximum and minimum total number of nodules per plant were noted in plots receiving 20 kg ha⁻¹ of starter nitrogen (95.27) and in plots without lime (56.2), respectively. Likewise, implementing starter nitrogen at a rate of 20 kg ha⁻¹ resulted in a 69.5% increase compared to soil lacking starter nitrogen. Starter nitrogen application can have variable effects on TNNP depending on the availability of nitrogen in the studied soil. Foreexample, excessive nitrogen availability from chemical fertilizers can inhibit nodulation by reducing the plant's dependency on symbiotic nitrogen fixation. However, judicious use of starter nitrogen can stimulate early plant growth and nodulation in nitrogen-deficient soils. In legume crops like beans, appropriate starter nitrogen application has been previously shown to enhance TNNP by providing a nitrogen boost during the critical early growth stages (Makoi and Ndakidemi, 2012).

Regarding the varieties of rhizobia strains, the maximum total number of nodules per plant (93.49) was noted in the treatment utilizing the HAMBI3570 rhizobia strain, while the minimum total number of nodules per plant (44.98) was documented in plots without any rhizobia strain. Introducing the HAMBI3570 strain of rhizobium into the soil elevated the total number of nodules per plant by 107.8% compared to soil lacking rhizobium inoculation (Table 4.33). Rhizobium inoculation is specifically aimed at promoting nodulation in leguminous crops by introducing nitrogen-fixing bacteria to the soil. Rhizobia form nodules on the roots of legumes, where they convert atmospheric nitrogen into a form that can be utilized by the plant. In haricot beans, rhizobium inoculation has been demonstrated to significantly increase TNNP by establishing symbiotic associations with the plant roots and enhancing nitrogen fixation capacity (Ndlovu, 2015). Similarly, the study conducted by Alemayehu Dabesa and Tamado Tana. (2021) confirmed that nodule number was significantly higher in inoculated plants compared to the control. Notably, Abera Habete and Tadele Buraka.(2016) inoculation of plants by rhizobium had better nodule formation than the control which enhance better fixation of atmospheric nitrogen and in turn yield formation.

Table 4. 34. Interaction effects of Lime and Starter nitrogen on total number of nodule per plant, effective number of nodule and percent of nodule effectiveness

Lime * Starter nitrogen		Biological nitrogen fixation		
Lime (L)	Starter nitrogen(Sn)	Total Number of nodule per plant (TNNP)	Effective number of nodule (ENNP)	Percent of nodule effectiveness(PNE)
1	2	117.22±44 ^a	112.3±46.74 ^a	93.58±6.42 ^a
1	1	83.84±25.63 ^b	78.77±28.08 ^b	92.1±7.15 ^b
0	2	73.32±18.73 ^c	51.06±21.7 ^e	91.06±7.54 ^b
0	1	65.17±16.9 ^d	68.02±21.49 ^c	88.58±9.09 ^c
1	0	60.32±16.78 ^e	59.07±19.56 ^d	80.54±17.08 ^d
0	0	52.14±19.63 ^f	43.59±23.52 ^f	76.6±21.52 ^e
CV (%)		12.11	12.68	2.44
P-value		***	***	ns

Where, CV = Coefficient of Variation. Interaction effect means in columns followed by the same letters are not significantly different at 5% level of significance from each other and means in columns followed by the different letters show significant differences between the means. From those Non-significant probability value > 0.05, *** = Very highly significant at probability value < 0.001 and L₀= without lime and L₁ = 2 t ha⁻¹; Sn₀= without starter nitrogen, Sn₁ starter nitrogen = 10 kg ha⁻¹, Sn₂ starter nitrogen = 20 kg ha⁻¹

Within the interaction effect, the greatest total number of nodules per plant (117.22) was observed in the treatment receiving 2 t ha⁻¹ of lime combined with 20 kg ha⁻¹ of starter nitrogen, while the lowest total number of nodules per plant (52.14) was recorded in the control plots. Implementing 2 t ha⁻¹ of lime alongside starter nitrogen increased the total number of nodules per plant by 124.8% compared to plots without lime and starter nitrogen (Table 4.34). The combined application of lime and starter nitrogen can influence TNNP by creating favorable soil conditions and providing essential nutrients for nodulation. Lime adjusts soil pH, optimizing conditions for rhizobial activity, while starter nitrogen provides early growth support. In agreement with this study, other studies on leguminous crops, including beans, the combined application of lime and starter nitrogen has been shown to enhance TNNP by promoting rhizobial colonization and stimulating early nodulation (Githinji *et al.*, 2016).

Table 4. 35. Interaction effects of Lime and rhizobia on total number of nodule per plant , effective number of nodule and percent of nodule effectiveness

Lime *rhizobia		Biological nitrogen fixation		
Lime (L)	Rhizobia(R)	Total Number of nodule per plant (TNNP)	Effective number of nodule (ENNP)	Percent of nodule effectiveness(PNE)
1	2	109.29±35.3 ^a	105.66±36.32 ^a	96±2.65 ^a
1	1	102.18±32.23 ^b	98.02±32.93 ^b	95.27±2.78 ^{ab}
1	0	49.92±9.79 ^e	38.45±12.9 ^e	74.95±13.22 ^d
0	2	77.7±10.57 ^c	73.48±11.08 ^c	94.39±2.25 ^{bc}
0	1	72.87±11.75 ^d	68.54±12.55 ^d	93.73±2.54 ^c
0	0	40.1±11.21 ^f	28.65±12.68 ^f	68.11±15.56 ^e
CV (%)		12.11	12.68	2.44
P-value		***	***	***

Where, CV = Coefficient of Variation. Interaction effect means in columns followed by the same letters are not significantly different at 5% level of significance from each other and means in columns followed by the different letters show significant differences between the means. From those *** = Very highly significant at probability value < 0.001 and L0= without lime and L1 = 2 t ha⁻¹; R0 = without rhizobia, R1 = Rhizobia HAMBI3562 and R2 = Rhizobia HAMBI3570.

In the interaction effect, the maximum total number of nodules per plant (109.29) was observed in the treatment receiving 2 t ha⁻¹ of lime combined with rhizobia HAMBI3570, while the minimum total number of nodules per plant (40.1) was recorded in the control plots. Incorporating 2 t ha⁻¹ of lime with rhizobia HAMBI3570 increased the total number of nodules per plant by 172.5% compared to the total number of nodules per plant recorded without lime and rhizobia HAMBI3570 (Table 4.35). The combination of lime and rhizobia inoculation can positively impact TNNP by optimizing soil pH and enhancing rhizobial establishment. Lime application raises soil pH to levels conducive for rhizobial activity, while rhizobia inoculation introduces nitrogen-fixing bacteria to the soil. The findings are in line with previous studies in haricot beans, the combined application of lime and rhizobia who has been demonstrated to significantly increase TNNP by creating favorable conditions for nodulation and enhancing nitrogen fixation capacity (Ndlovu,2015).

Table 4. 36. Interaction effects of Starter nitrogen and rhizobia on total number of nodule per plant, effective number of nodule and percent of nodule effectiveness

Starter nitrogen*rhizobia		Biological nitrogen fixation		
Starter nitrogen(Sn)	Rhizobia (R)	Total Number of nodule per plant (TNNP)	Effective number of nodule (ENNP)	Percent of nodule effectiveness(PNE)
0	0	33.43±8.68 ⁱ	17.75±6.29 ⁱ	52.24±6.4 ^f
0	1	65.02±8.69 ^f	59.45±8.8 ^f	91.27±1.53 ^c
0	2	70.23±8.36 ^e	64.78±8 ^e	92.19±1.01 ^c
1	0	47.78±7.63 ^h	38.19±7.65 ^h	79.46±4.23 ^e
1	1	85.87±15.23 ^d	82.12±15.27 ^d	95.49±1.58 ^b
1	2	89.87±15.23 ^c	86.44±16.76 ^c	96.07±1.66 ^{ab}
2	0	53.74±7.12 ^g	44.72±7.39 ^g	82.89±2.92 ^d
2	1	111.67±31.98 ^b	108.27±31.88 ^b	96.74±1.03 ^{ab}
2	2	120.39±34.29 ^a	117.49±34.62 ^a	97.33±1.22 ^a
CV (%)		12.11	12.68	2.44
P-value		***	***	***

Where, CV = Coefficient of Variation. Interaction effect means in columns followed by the same letters are not significantly different at 5% level of significance from each other and means in columns followed by the different letters show significant differences between the means. From those *** = Very highly significant at probability value < 0.001 and L₀= without lime and L₁ = 2 t ha⁻¹; Sn₀ = without starter nitrogen, Sn₁ starter nitrogen = 10 kg ha⁻¹, Sn₂ starter nitrogen = 20 kg ha⁻¹; R₀ = without rhizobia, R₁ = Rhizobia HAMBI3562 and R₂ = Rhizobia HAMBI3570.

In the interaction effect, the maximum total number of nodules per plant (120.39) was observed in the treatment receiving 20 kg ha⁻¹ of starter nitrogen combined with rhizobia HAMBI3570, while the minimum total number of nodules per plant (33.43) was recorded in the control plots. Incorporating 20 kg ha⁻¹ of starter nitrogen with rhizobia HAMBI3570 increased the total number of nodules per plant by 260% compared to the total number of nodules per plant recorded without starter nitrogen and rhizobia HAMBI3570 (Table 4.36). Incorporating 20 kg ha⁻¹ of starter nitrogen with rhizobia HAMBI3570 increased the total number of nodules per plant by 260% compared to the total number of nodules per plant recorded without starter nitrogen and rhizobia HAMBI3570 (Table 4.36). This was due to when starter nitrogen is combined with rhizobia inoculation, it can influence TNNP by providing early growth support and stimulating nodulation. Starter nitrogen promotes vigorous vegetative growth, which can encourage root development and rhizobial colonization. In legume crops like haricot beans, the combined application of starter nitrogen and rhizobia has been shown to

enhance TNNP by facilitating early nodulation and promoting symbiotic interactions between the plant and rhizobia (Makoi & Ndakidemi, 2012).

Table 4. 37. Interaction effects of lime, starter nitrogen and rhizobia on total number of nodule per plant, effective number of nodule and percent of nodule effectiveness

Lime *Starter nitrogen*rhizobia			Biological nitrogen fixation		
Lime(L)	Starter nitrogen(Sn)	Rhizobia(R)	Total Number of nodule per plant (TNNP)	Effective number of nodule (ENNP)	Percent of nodule effectiveness(PNE)
0	0	0	27.17±5.29 ^l	12.68±1.87 ^o	47.29±4.96 ^k
0	0	1	60.88±7.81 ⁱ	55.33±7.83 ^j	90.75±1.46 ^f
0	0	2	68.37±8.10 ^h	62.77±7.91 ⁱ	91.75±1.23 ^f
0	1	0	43.85±8.43 ^k	33.48±6.82 ^m	76.21±1.25 ⁱ
0	1	1	75.25±7.44 ^g	71.08±7.64 ^{gh}	94.40±1.41 ^{de}
0	1	2	76.42±5.22 ^g	72.63±4.01 ^g	95.12±1.35 ^{cd}
0	2	0	49.15±3.51 ^j	39.78±3.74 ^l	80.84±2.09 ^h
0	2	1	82.47±7.98 ^f	79.22±7.90 ^f	96.03±.50 ^{bcd}
0	2	2	88.33±6.68 ^e	85.05±6.30 ^e	96.30±.66 ^{abcd}
1	0	0	39.70±2.69 ^k	22.82±4.70 ⁿ	57.18±2.61 ^j
1	0	1	69.15±8.01 ^h	63.57±8.28 ⁱ	91.79±1.55 ^f
1	0	2	72.10±8.95 ^{gh}	66.80±8.30 ^{hi}	92.65±.49 ^{ef}
1	1	0	51.72±4.47 ^j	42.90±5.38 ^l	82.71±3.52 ^h
1	1	1	96.50±13.56 ^d	93.15±12.74 ^d	96.57±.85 ^{abcd}
1	1	2	103.32±12.00 ^c	100.25±12.02 ^c	97.01±1.43 ^{abc}
1	2	0	58.33±6.98 ⁱ	49.65±6.93 ^k	84.94±2.06 ^g
1	2	1	140.88±11.84 ^b	137.33±12.14 ^b	97.45±.95 ^{ab}
1	2	2	152.45±8.68 ^a	149.93±8.44 ^a	98.35±.53 ^a
CV (%)			12.11	12.68	2.44
P-value			***	***	***

Where, LSD = Least Significant Difference at 5% level; CV = Coefficient of Variation. Interaction effect means in columns followed by the same letters are not significantly different at 5% level of significance from each other and means in columns followed by the different letters show significant differences between the means. From those *** = Very highly significant at probability value < 0.001 and L₀= without lime and L₁ = 2 t ha⁻¹; Sn₀ = without starter nitrogen, Sn₁ starter nitrogen = 10 kg ha⁻¹, Sn₂ starter nitrogen = 20 kg ha⁻¹; R₀ = without rhizobia, R₁ = Rhizobia HAMBI3562 and R₂ = Rhizobia HAMBI3570.

The nodule number per haricot bean plant exhibited a highly significant difference (p < 0.001) due to the interaction effects of lime, starter nitrogen, and rhizobium application, as depicted in Table 4.9.

The combined application lime, starter nitrogen, rhizobia over two years that the treatment combination of 2 t ha^{-1} of lime with 20 kg ha^{-1} starter nitrogen, and HAMBI3570 rhizobia strains resulted the highest nodule numbers per plant, reaching 152.45, and this was statistically significant compared to other treatments. Conversely, the lowest nodule number,(27.17), was recorded when haricot beans were sown without inoculation and lime application(Table 4.37). Notably, liming of the acidic soil of Koga irrigation scheme significantly improved nodule numbers over non-limed soil when the crop was grown symbiotically with Rhizobium. This enhancement can be attributed to lime creating a better soil environment by neutralizing acidic soil, thus facilitating indigenous rhizobia for nodulation. These findings align with the report of Workneh Bekere *et al.* (2013), who found that lime and Bradyrhizobium inoculation simultaneously produced the highest nodule numbers in soybeans in Southwestern Ethiopia. Abera Habete and Tadele Buraka (2016) similarly observed that the number of nodules per plant was significantly influenced by the interaction effect of rhizobium inoculation and nitrogen. Chalk *et al.* (2010), demonstrated that applying lime greatly increased nitrogen fixation in red clover and other experiments. Studies by Abera Habete and Tadele Buraka (2016) indicated that inoculation of common beans with the right Rhizobium strain significantly increased the number of nodules per plant compared to uninoculated beans, which is again consistent with various studies (Gibson *et al.*, 2012; Amsalu Habtamu *et al.*, 2017; Tolera Abera and Zerihun Abebe, 2018; Girma Wolde *et al.* (2017) demonstrated that the application of lime and Rhizobium inoculation on Nitosols in BenchMaji Zone, Southwestern Ethiopia, increased the number of nodules per haricot bean plant. Recent findings by Getenesh Genetu *et al.* (2021), Petros Ketema and Tsedeke Tefera (2022) also indicated a significant increase in the number of nodules per plant for faba beans in different parts of Ethiopia due to Rhizobia inoculation. Additionally, the number of nodules per plant was significantly influenced by the interaction effect of varieties with rhizobium inoculation and nitrogen application, leading to an increase in the number of nodules (Abera Habete and Tadele Buraka, 2016). Shumi Deresa (2018) reported that an increase in nitrogen fertilizer rate led to an increment in the total number of nodules per common bean plant.

4.3.2. Effective Number of Nodule Per Plant (ENNP)

The effective number of nodules per plant was impacted by the main effects of lime, starter nitrogen, and rhizobia ($p < 0.001$) in the combined analysis of variance across the two growing seasons (2021/2022) (Appendix Table 3). Furthermore, the two-way interaction between lime and starter nitrogen ($p < 0.001$), lime and rhizobia ($p < 0.001$), starter nitrogen and rhizobia ($p < 0.001$), and the three-way interaction among lime, starter nitrogen, and rhizobia exhibited a significant effect ($P < 0.01$) on the effective number of nodules per plant combined over the 2021 and 2022 growing seasons (Appendix Table 8).

In the main effect, the effective number of nodules per plant in the study area ranged from 33.55 to 90.16 (Table 4.33). Additionally, within the lime treatment, the highest effective number of nodules per plant (80.71) was observed with 2 t ha^{-1} of lime, while the lowest effective number of nodules per plant (56.89) was recorded without lime. Applying 2 t ha^{-1} of lime increased the effective number of nodules per plant by 41.9% compared to soil without lime. Lime application improves soil pH, which is often beneficial for legume growth and nodule formation. For haricot beans, lime can increase ENNP by neutralizing soil acidity, thereby enhancing root development and nodulation. In agreement with this study Sarkodie-Addo *et al.* (2006) has shown that lime application in tropical acid soil significantly improves nodule formation in legumes, including haricot beans

Similarly, within the starter nitrogen rate treatment, the peak and the nadir operational count of nodules per plant were witnessed in plots receiving 20 kg ha^{-1} starter nitrogen (90.16) and in plots without lime (47.33), respectively. Likewise, the application of starter nitrogen at a dosage of 20 kg ha^{-1} resulted in a 90.5% enhancement compared to soil without starter nitrogen. This finding aligns with the results of Muller *et al.* (1993), who reported that the application of nitrogen in the range of 22 to 33 kg N ha^{-1} enhanced both nodulation and seed yield of common bean varieties.

Regarding the diversity of rhizobia strains, the maximum effective count of nodules per plant (89.57) was observed in plots treated with the HAMBI3570 rhizobia strain, while the minimum operational count of nodules per plant (33.55) was noted in plots without any rhizobia strain. Introducing the HAMBI3570 strain of rhizobium into the soil led to a 166.9% increase in the effective count of nodules per plant compared to soil lacking rhizobium inoculation (Table 4.33). The results demonstrated by Samuel Adissie *et al.* (2021), who reported that inoculated plots had a higher

number of effective nodules, improved nitrogen fixation, and better plant growth metrics compared to non-inoculated plots. In similar vein previous studies effective rhizobia strains improve both the number and efficiency of nodules formed (Giller, 2001).

Within the interaction effect, the maximum effective number of nodule per plant (112.3) was observed in the treatment combining 2 t ha⁻¹ of lime with 20 kg ha⁻¹ of starter nitrogen, while the minimum effective number of nodule per plant (43.59) was recorded in the control plots. Application of 2 t ha⁻¹ lime with 20 kg ha⁻¹ starter nitrogen had increased the effective number of nodule per plant by 157.6% compared to effective number of nodule per plant recorded without lime and Starter nitrogen (Table 4.34). The combination of lime and starter nitrogen can synergistically improve nodulation by addressing both soil pH and initial nutrient needs. This combination has been shown to enhance ENNP more effectively than either treatment alone, by providing a more favorable environment for both plant growth and nodule formation (Vanlauwe *et al.*, 2019).

In the interaction effect, the peak effective count of nodules per plant (105.66) was observed in plots treated with 2 t ha⁻¹ of lime combined with rhizobia HAMBI3570, while the lowest effective count of nodules per plant (28.65) was recorded in the control plots. The application of 2 t ha⁻¹ of lime alongside rhizobia HAMBI3570 resulted in a 268.8% increase in the effective count of nodules per plant compared to plots without lime and rhizobia HAMBI3570 (Table 4.35). Combining lime with rhizobia inoculation can lead to significant improvements in nodule formation. Lime improves soil conditions for both the plant and the rhizobia, while inoculation ensures the presence of effective nitrogen-fixing bacteria. Studies indicate that this combination can substantially increase ENNP in haricot beans (Turco *et al.*, 2016).

Within the interaction effect, the maximum effective count of nodules per plant (117.49) was observed in plots treated with 2 t ha⁻¹ of lime combined with rhizobia HAMBI3570, while the minimum effective count of nodules per plant (17.75) was recorded in the control plots. Incorporating 20 kg ha⁻¹ of starter nitrogen with rhizobia HAMBI3570 resulted in a 569.9% increase in the effective count of nodules per plant compared to plots without starter nitrogen and rhizobia HAMBI3570 (Table 4.36). This result supported by Shibru Daba and Mitiku Haile. (2000) inoculation with mixed strains and starter N fertilizer gave a significantly higher grain yield and nodule number in the Hararghe highlands, Ethiopia.

The combined application lime, starter nitrogen, rhizobia over two years showed that the plot received a combined application of 2 t ha⁻¹ of lime, 20 kg ha⁻¹ of starter nitrogen, and Rhizobium biofertilizer (HAMBI3570 strains) recorded the highest number of effective nodules of 149.93 per plant followed by lime (2 t ha⁻¹), starter nitrogen (10 kg ha⁻¹), and the HAMBI3562 strain (140.88), whereas the control plot had the lowest count at 12.68 per plant (Table 4.37). The probable reason for the increase in the number of effective nodules may be attributed to the improved availability of nutrients such as phosphorus, where lime can facilitate the nodulation process. The integration of lime, starter nitrogen, and rhizobia inoculation can have the most pronounced effect on ENNP. This holistic approach addresses multiple limiting factors simultaneously, leading to optimal conditions for nodule formation and function. Research has consistently shown that this combination results in the highest ENNP values in legumes, including haricot beans (Bala *et al.*, 2011). Additionally, the application of starter nitrogen at planting reduces the risk of nitrogen deficiency during the early stages of haricot bean growth, which is crucial for effective nodulation. The suitability of the rhizobium strain for effective nodulation also plays a role in this observed phenomenon. The result inline with Abiyot Abeje *et al.* (2021) the maximum number of nodules per plant recorded from the addition of lime in combination with biofertilizers and inorganic fertilizer, which played a significant role in reducing acidity and therefore creating a favorable condition for survival of rhizobia and increasing the availability of nutrients. As a result, the available nutrients and the effective rhizobia in turn might hasten effective nodulation of soybean.

4.3.3. Percent of Nodule Effectiveness (PNE)

Percent of nodule effectiveness was influenced by the main effects of lime, stater nitrogen, and rhizobia ($p < 0.001$) in the combined analysis of variance over the two growing seasons (2021/2022) (Appendix Table 3). Moreover, the two way interaction of lime with rhizobia ($p < 0.001$), stater nitrogen with rhizobia ($p < 0.001$), and the three way interaction of lime, stater nitrogen and rhizobia showed that significantly ($P < 0.01$) effect on percent of nodule effectiveness combined over the year 2021 and 2022 growing season (Appendix Table 8).

In the main effect, the percentage of nodule effectiveness in the study area ranged from 71.52 to 95.19 (Table 4.33). Furthermore, within the lime treatment, the maximum percentage of nodule effectiveness (88.74) was observed from the application of 2 t ha⁻¹ of lime, while the minimum percentage of nodule effectiveness (85.41) was recorded in plots without lime. The addition of 2 t ha⁻¹

¹ of lime augmented the percentage of nodule effectiveness by 40.6% compared to soil without lime. Liming significantly increased nodule number, nodule volume, and nodule dry weight per plant as compared to the un-limed treatment in legume crops (Abubakari *et al.*,2016). Liming acidic soils enhance the activities of beneficial microbes in the rhizosphere and hence improve root growth.

In the same vein, within the starter nitrogen rate treatment, the highest and lowest percentages of nodule effectiveness were noted in plots receiving 20 kg ha⁻¹ starter nitrogen (92.32) and in plots without lime (78.57), respectively. Similarly, the application of starter nitrogen at a dosage of 20 kg ha⁻¹ resulted in a 103% improvement compared to soil without starter nitrogen.

With respect to rhizobia strains types the highest percent of nodule effectiveness (95.19) were observed with in HAMBI3570 rhizobia strain treatment where as the lowest percent of nodule effectiveness (71.52) was recorded without rhizobia strain. Inoculation of the soil with HAMBI3570 strain of rhizobium increased the percent of nodule effectiveness by 161.3% compared to the soil without rhizobium inoculation (Table 4.33). This study consistent with Dereje Geleta and Getachew Bekele. (2022) inoculation of rhizobium strain significantly increased the percentage of effective nodules per plant in contrast to noninoculated seeds.

Within the interaction effect, the highest percentage of nodule effectiveness (96) was observed in plots treated with 2 t ha⁻¹ of lime combined with 20 kg ha⁻¹ of starter nitrogen, while the lowest total number of nodules per plant (68.11) was recorded in the control plots. Application of 2 t ha⁻¹ of lime alongside rhizobia HAMBI3570 resulted in a 285% increase in the percentage of nodule effectiveness compared to plots without lime and rhizobia HAMBI3570 (Table 4.35).

In the interaction effect, the highest percentage of nodule effectiveness (97.33) was observed in plots treated with 20 kg ha⁻¹ of starter nitrogen combined with rhizobia HAMBI3570, while the lowest percentage of nodule effectiveness (52.24) was recorded in the control plots. Implementing 20 kg ha⁻¹ of starter nitrogen alongside rhizobia HAMBI3570 resulted in an 86.3% increase in the percentage of nodule effectiveness compared to plots without starter nitrogen and rhizobia HAMBI3570 (Table 4.36).

The combined application lime, starter nitrogen, rhizobia over two years showed that the plot received a combined application of 2 t ha⁻¹ of lime, 20 kg ha⁻¹of nitrogen, and HAMBI3570 rhizobia strains exhibited the highest percentage of effective nodules of 98.35%, while the control plot

recorded the lowest number of 47.29%. (Table 4.37). The combined application of lime, starter nitrogen, and rhizobia had synergistic effects on soil health, root development, and microbial activity, ultimately promoting more effective nodulation in haricot beans (Lemaire *et al.*, 2016)

4.4. Effect of Soil Ammendemnts on Yield and yield components

4.4.1. Number of pods per plant

The number of pods per plant was significantly affected by the main factors of lime, starter nitrogen, and rhizobia ($p < 0.001$) in the combined analysis of variance over the two growing seasons (2021/2022) (Appendix Table 5). Additionally, the two-way interaction of lime with rhizobia ($p < 0.001$) and the three-way interaction of lime, starter nitrogen, and rhizobia exhibited a significant effect ($P < 0.001$) on the number of pods per plant combined over the 2021 and 2022 growing seasons (Appendix Table 10).

Table 4. 38. Main effects of lime, starter nitrogen and Rhizobium biofertilizer on number of pods per plant, number of seeds per pod and hundred-seed weight

lime, starter nitrogen and Rhizobium	Crop phenology		
	Number of pods per plant (NPPP)	Number of seeds per pod	Hundred-seed weight (HSW) (g)
Lime			
Lime 2 t ha ⁻¹	66.75±20 ^a	1734.5±763.97 ^a	4.33±1.9 ^a
Lime 0 t ha ⁻¹	52.89±18.96 ^b	1231.3±629.67 ^b	3.08±1.57 ^b
LSD (5%)	1.68	40.5	0.101
CV (%)	3.83	2.98	4.68
P-value	***	***	***
Starter nitrogen			
Starter nitrogen 20 kg ha ⁻¹	70.3±20.23 ^a	1886±761.09 ^a	4.71±1.9 ^a
Starter nitrogen 10 kg ha ⁻¹	65±17.9 ^b	1634.7±655.61 ^b	4.08±1.64 ^b
Starter nitrogen 0 kg ha ⁻¹	44.14±13.29 ^c	927.9±403.4 ^c	2.32±1 ^c
LSD (5%)	2.06	49.61	0.12
P-value	***	***	***
Rhizobia strain			
HAMBI3570 Rhizobia strain	71.23±15.33 ^a	1944.4±596.83 ^a	4.86±1.49 ^a
HAMBI3562 Rhizobia strain	69.28±16.48 ^a	1757.79±619.23 ^b	4.39±1.55 ^b
O Rhizobia strain	38.94±10.93 ^b	746.51±292.16 ^c	1.86±.73 ^c
LSD (5%)	2.06	49.61	0.077
P-value	***	***	***

Where, LSD = Least Significant Difference at 5% level; CV = Coefficient of Variation. Interaction effect means in columns followed by the same letters are not significantly different at 5% level of

significance from each other and means in columns followed by the different letters show significant differences between the means. From those *** = Very highly significant at probability value < 0.001

In the main analysis, the number of pods per plant in the study area ranged from 38.94 to 71.23 (Table 4.38). Furthermore, among the lime treatments, the maximum number of pods per plant (66.75) was observed in plots treated with 2 t ha⁻¹ of lime, while the minimum number of pods per plant (52.89) was noted in plots without lime. Applying 2 t ha⁻¹ of lime resulted in a 26.2% increase in the number of pods per plant compared to plots without lime. Lime application improves soil pH, which can enhance nutrient availability and overall plant health. This improvement in soil conditions can lead to an increase in the number of pods per plant by promoting better root development and nutrient uptake. For haricot beans, lime application has been shown to increase the number of pods per plant by creating a more favorable growth environment (Fageria and Baligar, 2008).

In the same vein, among the plots treated with starter nitrogen rates, the highest number of pods per plant was observed in those receiving 20 kg ha⁻¹ of starter nitrogen (70.3), whereas the lowest count (44.14) was found in plots devoid of lime. Similarly, the application of starter nitrogen at a dosage of 20 kg ha⁻¹ led to a 59.3% elevation compared to plots lacking starter nitrogen. Starter nitrogen provides an early nutrient boost to plants, promoting vigorous growth and development. This initial growth spurt can lead to an increased number of pods per plant as the plant establishes a strong vegetative base for reproductive growth. However, excessive nitrogen can sometimes lead to luxuriant vegetative growth at the expense of pod formation. Moderate levels of starter nitrogen can positively affect the number of pods per plant in haricot beans (Awene Tadesse *et al.*, 2022)

In relation to the rhizobia strain varieties, the highest tally of pods per plant (71.23) was registered in plots subjected to the HAMBI3570 rhizobia strain treatment, while the minimum count (38.94) was observed in plots devoid of any rhizobia strain. The introduction of the HAMBI3570 rhizobium strain into the soil amplified the pods' count per plant by 82.9% compared to soil lacking rhizobium inoculation (Table 4.38).

Table 4. 39. Interaction effects of Lime and Starter nitrogen on number of pods per plant, number of seeds per pod and hundred-seed weight

Lime * Starter nitrogen		Yield and yield components		
Lime (L)	Starter nitrogen(Sn)	Number of pods per plant (NPPP)	Number of seeds per pod	Hundred-seed weight (HSW) (g)
1	2	44.53±7.37 ^a	6.33±1.13 ^a	45.88±6.51 ^a
1	1	43.17±7.34 ^b	6±1.05 ^b	42.71±4.41 ^b
0	2	39.49±11.93 ^c	4.41±.78 ^e	39.12±6.96 ^c
0	1	36.53±9.87 ^d	5.22±1.19 ^c	36.98±6.33 ^d
1	0	29.64±10.04 ^e	4.67±.85 ^d	33.89±8.69 ^e
0	0	23.61±7.77 ^f	3.72±.49 ^f	27.19±6.64 ^f
CV (%)		3.83	2.98	4.68
P-value		ns	***	ns

Where, CV = Coefficient of Variation. Interaction effect means in columns followed by the different letters show significant differences between the means. From those Non-significant probability value > 0.05, *** = Very highly significant at probability value < 0.001 and L₀= without lime and L₁ = 2 t ha⁻¹; Sn₀ = without starter nitrogen, Sn₁ starter nitrogen = 10 kg ha⁻¹, Sn₂ starter nitrogen = 20 kg ha⁻¹.

Table 4. 40. Interaction effects of Lime and rhizobia on number of pods per plant, number of seeds per pod and hundred-seed weight

Lime *rhizobia		Yield and yield components		
Lime (L)	Rhizobia(R)	Number of pods per plant (NPPP)	Number of seeds per pod	Hundred-seed weight (HSW) (g)
1	2	45.12±6.34 ^a	6.33±.99 ^a	45.59±4.39 ^a
1	1	44.32±5.93 ^b	6.17±.96 ^b	44.78±4.89 ^b
1	0	27.92±8.82 ^e	4.24±.67 ^e	32.11±7.41 ^e
0	2	40.44±8.16 ^c	5.26±.79 ^c	39.27±5.63 ^c
0	1	39.41±8.56 ^d	4.93±.95 ^d	38.46±5.6 ^d
0	0	19.78±4.96 ^f	3.43±.21 ^f	25.57±5.48 ^f
CV (%)		3.83	2.98	4.68
P-value		***	***	ns

Where, CV = Coefficient of Variation. Interaction effect means in columns followed by the different letters show significant differences between the means. From those Non-significant probability value > 0.05, *** = Very highly significant at probability value < 0.001 and L₀= without lime and L₁ = 2 t ha⁻¹; R₀ = without rhizobia, R₁ = Rhizobia HAMBI3562 and R₂ = Rhizobia HAMBI3570.

In the interaction effect, the maximum count of pods per plant (45.12) was observed in plots treated with 2 t ha⁻¹ of lime combined with the HAMBI3570 rhizobia strain, while the minimum count (19.78) was noted in the control plots. Implementing 2 t ha⁻¹ of lime alongside rhizobia HAMBI3570 led to a 128.1% increase in the pods' count per plant compared to plots without lime and rhizobia HAMBI3570 (Table 4.40). Studies conducted by Lemaire et al (2016) showed that combining lime with rhizobia inoculation has been reported to improve various growth parameters, including the number of pods per plant, in haricot bean. Similarly, Studies have shown that the combined application of lime and effective rhizobia strains can synergistically enhance the nodulation, growth, and yield of legumes, including haricot beans.

Table 4. 41. Interaction effects of Starter nitrogen and rhizobia on number of pods per plant, number of seeds per pod and hundred-seed weight

Trt	Starter nitrogen*rhizobia		Yield and yield components		
	Starter nitrogen(Sn)	Rhizobia(R)	Number of pods per plant (NPPP)	Number of seeds per pod	Hundred-seed weight (HSW) (g)
1	0	0	14.49±1.77 ⁱ	3.26±.13 ^h	20.17±2.55 ^h
2	0	1	32.27±4.45 ^t	4.28±.64 ^t	35.25±4.32 ^e
3	0	2	33.12±3.87 ^e	4.66±.37 ^e	36.21±4.46 ^d
4	1	0	28.15±5.35 ^h	4.05±.57 ^g	32.78±4.5 ^g
5	1	1	45.22±3.13 ^d	5.93±.76 ^d	42.92±2.83 ^c
6	1	2	46.19±2.61 ^c	6.03±.81 ^c	43.85±2.87 ^b
7	2	0	28.92±6.09 ^g	4.21±.63 ^t	33.58±3.99 ^t
8	2	1	48.10±1.57 ^b	6.43±.59 ^b	46.69±4.19 ^a
9	2	2	49.03±1.97 ^a	6.7±.56 ^a	47.23±3.72 ^a
CV (%)			3.83	2.98	4.68
P-value			ns	***	***

Where, CV = Coefficient of Variation. Interaction effect means in columns followed by the same letters are not significantly different at 5% level of significance from each other and means in columns followed by the different letters show significant differences between the means. From those Non-significant probability value > 0.05, *** = Very highly significant at probability value < 0.001 and Sn₀ = without starter nitrogen, Sn₁ starter nitrogen = 10 kg ha⁻¹, Sn₂ starter nitrogen = 20 kg ha⁻¹; R₀ = without rhizobia, R₁ = Rhizobia HAMBI3562 and R₂ = Rhizobia HAMBI3570.

Table 4. 42. effect of lime, starter nitrogen and Rhizobium bio fertilizer on number of pods per plant, number of seeds per pod and hundred-seed weight haricot bean

Lime *Starter nitrogen*rhizobia			Yield and yield components		
Lime(L)	Starter nitrogen(Sn)	Rhizobia(R)	Number of pods per plant (NPPP)	Number of seeds per pod	Hundred-seed weight (HSW) (g)
0	0	0	13.07±.96 ⁿ	3.17±.08 ^o	18.25±1.54 ^m
0	0	1	28.15±1.38 ^k	3.68±.08 ^l	31.23±1.31 ⁱ
0	0	2	29.60±1.31 ^j	4.32±.08 ^k	32.10±1.16 ⁱ
0	1	0	23.10±.92 ^l	3.52±.08 ^m	28.60±.94 ^k
0	1	1	42.50±1.42 ^f	5.22±.08 ^g	40.90±2.63 ^{ef}
0	1	2	44±1.51 ^e	5.28±.12 ^g	41.45±1.36 ^e
0	2	0	23.18±.89 ^l	3.62±.08 ^{lm}	29.87±1.19 ^j
0	2	1	47.57±1.25 ^d	5.88±.12 ^f	43.23±.99 ^d
0	2	2	47.72±1.61 ^{cd}	6.18±.19 ^e	44.25±2.75 ^{cd}
1	0	0	15.92±1.04 ^m	3.35±.10 ⁿ	22.08±1.77 ^l
1	0	1	36.38±.95 ^g	4.88±.15 ^{hi}	39.27±.73 ^g
1	0	2	36.63±1.28 ^g	5.00±.09 ^h	40.32±1.39 ^{fg}
1	1	0	33.20±.99 ⁱ	4.58±.12 ^j	36.95±1.36 ^h
1	1	1	47.93±1.36 ^{bcd}	6.63±.23 ^d	44.93±.96 ^c
1	1	2	48.38±1.08 ^{bc}	6.78±.26 ^c	46.25±1.57 ^b
1	2	0	34.65±1.33 ^h	4.80±.19 ⁱ	37.28±.80 ^h
1	2	1	48.63±1.77 ^b	6.98±.15 ^b	50.15±3.00 ^a
1	2	2	50.33±1.35 ^a	7.22±.08 ^a	50.20±1.27 ^a
CV (%)			3.83	2.98	4.68
P-value			***	***	***

Where, CV = Coefficient of Variation. Interaction effect means in columns followed by the same letters are not significantly different at 5% level of significance from each other and means in columns followed by the different letters show significant differences between the means. From those *** = Very highly significant at probability value < 0.001 and L₀= without lime and L₁ = 2 t ha⁻¹; Sn₀ = without starter nitrogen, Sn₁ starter nitrogen = 10 kg ha⁻¹, Sn₂ starter nitrogen = 20 kg ha⁻¹; R₀ = without rhizobia, R₁ = Rhizobia HAMBI3562 and R₂ = Rhizobia HAMBI3570.

The combined application lime, starter nitrogen, rhizobia over two years showed that the application of lime 2 ton ha⁻¹, starter nitrogen 20 kg ha⁻¹, and Rhizobia HAMBI3570 strain combination recorded the highest number of pods per plant under rain-fed growing conditions, followed by lime 2 t ha⁻¹, starter nitrogen 10 kg ha⁻¹, and Rhizobia HAMBI3562 strain, with counts of 50.33 and 48.63, respectively (Table 4.42). The observed increase in pod count with the combined application of lime,

nitrogen, and rhizobia suggests that lime improves soil conditions, while starter nitrogen aids haricot bean establishment, promotes node formation, canopy development, and pod setting. Additionally, the enzymatic activities influenced by these factors contribute to controlled flowering and pod formation, with lime neutralize acidic soil prov. The synergy of lime, nitrogen, and rhizobia not only enhances symbiotic nitrogen fixation but also improves soil fertility and physiological health, leading to a greater number of pods. This finding aligns with previous reports by Wondwosen and Tamado (2017) and Shumi Deresa (2018), indicating an increase in pod count with the application of fertilizer . Lime's significant contribution to the number of pods, particularly in conjunction with applied nitrogen, is consistent with the findings of Kisinyo *et al.* (2005), who suggested that lime's role in neutralizing acidic soil enhances phosphorus availability for plant uptake. Ali *et al.* (2003) reported that inoculation of seeds has an effect in increasing the number of pod per plant. Furthermore, the positive effects of lime reported by Negi *et al.* (2006) and Zaroug and Munns (1979) for symbiotically grown legumes reinforce the importance of lime in pod development. On the other hand, the lack of significance effects between lime and rhizobia concerning pod count in Southwestern Ethiopia, as reported by Girma Wolde *et al.* (2017), contrasts with the present findings.

Figure 4.Counting the number of pods per plant by farmers

4.4.3. Hundred Seed weight (g)

Hundred Seed weight was influenced by the main effects of lime, stater nitrogen, and rhizobia ($p < 0.001$) in the combined analysis of variance over the two growing seasons (2021/2022) (Appendix Table 5). Moreover, the two way interaction of Lime with Starter nitrogen ($p < 0.001$), lime with

rhizobia ($p < 0.001$), starter nitrogen with rhizobia ($p < 0.001$), and the three way interaction of lime, starter nitrogen rhizobia showed that significantly ($P < 0.001$) effect on hundred seed weight combined over the year 2021 and 2022 growing season (Appendix Table 10).

In the main effect, the hundred seed weight in the study area ranged from 1.86 to 4.86 (Table 4.38). Furthermore, under lime treatment, the greatest hundred seed weight (4.33) was observed with the application of 2 t ha^{-1} of lime, while the lowest weight (3.08) was noted in plots without lime. Implementing 2 t ha^{-1} of lime augmented the hundred seed weight by 40.6% compared to soil without lime. Lime application improves soil pH, which enhances nutrient availability and overall plant health. This can lead to increased seed size and weight by improving the conditions for nutrient uptake and growth. Studies have shown that liming acidic soils can lead to higher HSW in legumes such as haricot beans (Fageria & Baligar, 2008). Improved soil conditions lead to better plant health and more resources available for seed development.

In the same vein, within the starter nitrogen rate treatment, the maximum weight was observed in plots treated with 20 kg ha^{-1} starter nitrogen (4.71), while the lowest hundred seed weight (2.32) was noted in plots without treatment. Similarly, applying starter nitrogen at a rate of 20 kg ha^{-1} led to a 103% improvement compared to plots lacking starter nitrogen. This can result in larger, heavier seeds by ensuring that the plant has sufficient nitrogen during the critical stages of seed filling. However, excessive nitrogen can sometimes result in lush vegetative growth at the expense of seed development. Optimal levels of starter nitrogen can positively influence HSW in haricot beans (Ferguson *et al.*, 2002).

Regarding the types of rhizobia strains, the peak hundred seed weight (4.86) was observed in plots treated with the HAMBI3570 rhizobia strain, while the lowest weight (1.86) was recorded in plots without any rhizobia strain. Introducing the HAMBI3570 strain of rhizobium into the soil amplified the hundred seed weight by 161.3% compared to soil without rhizobium inoculation (Table 4.38). Inoculating haricot beans with effective rhizobia strains ensures efficient nitrogen fixation, enhancing plant growth and seed development. Effective nitrogen fixation by rhizobia can lead to an increase in HSW by providing a consistent nitrogen supply throughout the growing season (Giller, 2001). This improved nitrogen availability ensures that the seeds are well-nourished and can develop fully.

In the interaction effect, the maximum hundred seed weight (47.23) was observed in plots treated with 2 t ha^{-1} of lime combined with rhizobia HAMBI3570, while the minimum weight (20.17) was

recorded in the control plots. Implementing 20 kg ha⁻¹ of starter nitrogen alongside rhizobia HAMBI3570 increased the hundred seed weight by 134.2% compared to the weight recorded without starter nitrogen and rhizobia HAMBI3570 (Table 4.36). Combining starter nitrogen with rhizobia inoculation can also positively affect HSW. Starter nitrogen provides an initial boost, while rhizobia ensure continued nitrogen availability through biological fixation. This combination supports both early growth and sustained reproductive development, leading to heavier seeds in haricot beans (Miller *et al.*, 2012).

The combined application lime, starter nitrogen, rhizobia over two years showed that the treatment combining lime 2 t ha⁻¹, starter nitrogen 20 kg ha⁻¹, and Rhizobia HAMB3570 strain yielded the maximum hundred-seed weight of 50.2 g. In contrast, the control treatment resulted in the lowest hundred-seed weight at 18.25 gram (Table 4.42). According to Cobley and Steele (1976) classification, the lime 2 t ha⁻¹, starter nitrogen 20 kg ha⁻¹, and Rhizobia HAMB3570 treatment fell under the category of large seeds, while the control plot was classified as small seeds. The observed increase in hundred-seed weight can be attributed to enhanced nodulation, improved nitrogen bio-availability, and increased growth and nitrogen fixation. These factors contribute to higher grain filling by facilitating the translocation of assimilates later in the growth cycle, positively affecting seed weight. Additionally, inoculation with Rhizobium bacteria led to a substantial (199.7%) increase in the hundred-seed weight of haricot bean plants compared to the un-inoculated treatment, possibly due to the presence of indigenous haricot bean nodulating bacteria in the experimental soil.

Consistent with these findings, Tesfaye Dejene *et al* (2017), indicating an increase in hundred-seed weights of common bean with rising lime levels. Muhammad Shamim and Ali Naimat (1987) associated the increment in hundred-seed weight with factors such as cell division, phosphorus content in the seeds, and the formation of fat and albumin. Singh *et al.* (2007) reported a mean hundred-seed weight of dry bean ranging from 28g to 41g, consistent with results obtained by other authors.

4.4.4. Grain yield

Grain yield was influenced by the main effects of lime, starter nitrogen, and rhizobia ($p < 0.001$) in the combined analysis of variance over the two growing years (2021/2022) (Appendix Table 5). Moreover, the three ways interaction of lime, starter nitrogen, and rhizobia combined over the year 2021 and 2022 growing season also influenced ($p < 0.001$) the grain yield of haricot bean. However, the remain interactions of the factors had no significant effect on grain yield (Appendix Table 10).

Table 4. 43. Main effects of Lime, Starter nitrogen and Rhizobia on grain yield, biomass Yield, harvest index and straw yield haricot bean over two years

Lime, Starter nitrogen and Rhizobia	Yield and yield components			
	Grain yield (GY) kg ha ⁻¹	Biomass Yield (BY) kg ha ⁻¹	Harvest Index (HI) %	Straw yield (SY) kg ha ⁻¹
Lime				
Lime 2 t ha ⁻¹	3403.5±1115.16 ^a	5454.9±1587.15 ^a	61.11±6.8 ^a	2051.5±528.12 ^a
Lime 0 t ha ⁻¹	2445.3±1272.61 ^b	4143.8±1722.76 ^b	56.11±9 ^b	1698.5±490.8 ^b
LSD (5%)	127.53	174.05	1.46	94.81
CV (%)	11.37	9.45	6.5	13.18
P-value	***	***	***	***
Starter nitrogen				
Starter nitrogen 20 kg ha ⁻¹	3566.7±1182.05 ^a	5734±1709.12 ^a	61.3±5.73 ^a	2167.3±593.85 ^a
Starter nitrogen 10 kg ha ⁻¹	3261.6±1051.3 ^b	5208.8±1454.17 ^b	61.45±6.03 ^a	1947.2±452.68 ^b
Starter nitrogen 0 kg ha ⁻¹	1944.9±1012.27 ^c	3455.3±1292.39 ^c	53.07±9.8 ^b	1510.5±309.42 ^c
P-value	***	***	***	***
Rhizobia strain				
HAMBI3570 Rhizobia strain	3592.3±945.19 ^a	5700.7±1309.02 ^a	62.4±4.51 ^a	2108.4±417.25 ^a
HAMBI3562 Rhizobia strain	3481.3±974.47 ^b	5601.9±1424.32 ^a	61.55±4.42 ^a	2120.6±506.63 ^a
O Rhizobia strain	1699.6±944.25 ^c	3095.6±1186.93 ^b	51.86±10.1 2 ^b	1396±313.6 ^b
P-value	***	***	***	***

Where, LSD = Least Significant Difference at 5% level; CV = Coefficient of Variation. Interaction effect means in columns followed by the same letters are not significantly different at 5% level of significance from each other and means in columns followed by the different letters show significant differences between the means. From those *** = Very highly significant at probability value < 0.001

The results of the study shows the highest grain yield ($3403.5 \text{ kg ha}^{-1}$) were observed from 2 t ha^{-1} lime where as the lowest grain yield ($2445.3 \text{ kg ha}^{-1}$) recorded from without lime. This increased the grain yield by 39.2% compared to yield recorded without lime. This study inline with Getachew Alemu *et al* (2017) stated that application of lime on barely crop increase the grain yield by 274.0% compared to the control and Andric *et al* (2012) also reported increased soybean yield by 44% because of lime application in Croatia. Moreover, Nekesa *et al* (2011) in Western Kenya also found positive response of common bean grain yield to lime application. Notably, lime application to acid soils raises pH, improving nutrient availability, including phosphorus (P), calcium (Ca), magnesium (Mg), molybdenum (Mo), and subsequently enhancing crop yields (Opala *et al.*, 2009). Similarly, previous studies have shown that the application of lime increased the yield components of haricot beans grown in acidic soil in the Wolaita Zone (Mesfin kassa *et al.*, 2014) and in Nitosols in the Bench-Maji Zone, Southwestern Ethiopia (Girma Wolde *et al.*, 2017). The increased yield from lime could be lime, primarily composed of calcium carbonate (CaCO_3), neutralizes soil acidity by increasing soil pH. Haricot beans thrive best in soils with a pH between 6.0 and 7.5. Acidic soils can lead to poor nutrient availability and toxicity from elements like aluminum and manganese (Mesfin Kassa *et al.*, 2014). By raising the pH, application of lime could have been created a more favorable environment for haricot beans to absorb essential nutrients (Girma Wolde *et al.*, 2017). Moreover, adding lime improved soil structure, soil bulk density by reducing soil compaction and increasing soil aggregation. Thus better soil structure improves root penetration and water retention, leading to more robust plant growth and higher yields (Ball *et al.*, 2005 and Abdisa Mekonnen *et al.*, 2021).

Similarly, within the starter nitrogen rate treatment, the highest grain yield ($3566.7 \text{ kg ha}^{-1}$) was observed in the treatment that received 20 kg ha^{-1} of starter nitrogen, while the lowest grain yield ($1944.9 \text{ kg ha}^{-1}$) was observed in the treatment that received no any amendments. Starter nitrogen amendments increased yield by 83.4 % haricot bean yield compared with yield without starter nitrogen. This could be starter nitrogen provides an immediate source of nitrogen to young plants, which is crucial for early growth stages (Kife Tekulu *et al.*, 2020). This early nutrient boost helps establish a strong root system and vigorous vegetative growth, setting the foundation for higher yields. Enhanced nitrogen availability could also improve photosynthetic efficiency, leading to increased biomass production and, ultimately, higher grain yields (Leghar *et al.*, 2016).

With respect to rhizobia strains types the highest grain yield ($3592.3 \text{ kg ha}^{-1}$) were observed with in HAMBI3570 rhizobia strain treatment where as the lowest grain yield ($1699.6 \text{ kg ha}^{-1}$) was recorded without rhizobia strain. Inoculation of the soil with HAMBI3570 strain of rhizobium increased the grain yield of haricot bean by 111.4% compared to the soil without rhizobium inoculation (Table 4.43). The presence of Rhizobium could have improved the overall nutrient uptake efficiency of the plant. This symbiosis often enhances the absorption of other essential nutrients which further supports plant health and yield. Rhizobium bacteria form symbiotic relationships with leguminous plants like haricot beans, converting atmospheric nitrogen into a form the plants can use. This biological nitrogen fixation provides a significant and consistent nitrogen source, which is crucial for plant growth and development. It has been reported that N increased yield by 92.18% under direct soil incorporation, 87.55% under combined chemical and organic fertilizers application, and 72.86% under split application (Yokamo *et al.*, 2023). Similarly, Lagat, (2015) reported application of lime-treated soil, with a substantial improvement in maize and beans yield. The result inline with Ojiem, (2018) inoculation with the strain in Burundi resulted in a bean yield advantage of up to 59% .Studies using locally developed haricot bean varieties also indicated that inoculation with specific strains led to significant yield increases (Tolera Abera *et al.*, 2016). Similarly, Otieno *et al.* (2007) reported that inoculation of bacteria increases yield response of some food legumes. Rhizobium inoculation and nitrogen fertilization has previously also increased yield response of common bean in other studies (Abera Habete and Tadele Buraka, 2016). Additionally, rhizobium leguminosarum has shown to significantly increase yields in crops such as faba bean, field pea, lentil, and chickpea (Ruraduma, 2002; Asfaw Hailemariam *et al.*, 2006). Thus the study implies farmers can achieve significantly higher yields without relying heavily on expensive chemical fertilizers, improving their profitability and reducing input costs. Increased yields from Rhizobium inoculation can contribute to food security by producing more food per unit area, especially important in regions with limited access to fertilizers.

Table 4. 44. Interaction effects of Lime and Starter nitrogen on grain yield, biomass Yield, harvest index and straw yield haricot bean over two years

Lime * Starter nitrogen		Yield and yield components			
Lime (L)	Starter nitrogen(Sn)	Grain yield (GY) kg ha ⁻¹	Biomass Yield (BY) kg ha ⁻¹	Harvest Index (HI) %	Straw yield (SY) kg ha ⁻¹
1	2	4062.42±832.18 ^a	6472.80±1282.18 ^a	62.77±3.43 ^a	2410.39±531.67 ^a
1	1	3679.86±678.74 ^b	5779.32±1015.24 ^b	63.61±3.39 ^a	2099.46±398.29 ^b
0	2	3070.94±1289.85 ^c	4995.18±1792.79 ^c	59.84±7.16 ^b	1924.23±564.15 ^c
0	1	2843.43±1201.84 ^d	4638.31±1622.85 ^d	59.29±7.32 ^b	1794.88±462.75 ^{cd}
1	0	2468.13±1121.12 ^e	4112.65±1436.23 ^e	56.95±9.66 ^c	1644.52±337.75 ^d
0	0	1421.58±522.39 ^f	2798.03±679.04 ^f	49.18±8.54 ^d	1376.45±212.11 ^c
CV (%)		11.37	9.45	6.5	13.18
P-value		ns	ns	*	ns

Where, CV = Coefficient of Variation. Interaction effect means in columns followed by the same letters are not significantly different at 5% level of significance from each other and means in columns followed by the different letters show significant differences between the means. From those Non-significant probability value > 0.05, *= significant probability value between 0.01- 0.05 and L₀= without lime and L₁ = 2 t ha⁻¹; Sn₀ = without starter nitrogen, Sn₁ starter nitrogen = 10 kg ha⁻¹, Sn₂ starter nitrogen = 20 kg ha⁻¹.

Table 4. 45. Interaction effects of Lime and rhizobia on grain yield, biomass Yield , harvest index and straw yield haricot bean over two years

Lime *rhizobia		Yield and yield components			
Lime (L)	Rhizobia(R)	Grain yield (GY) kg ha ⁻¹	Biomass Yield (BY) kg ha ⁻¹	Harvest Index (HI) %	Straw yield (SY) kg ha ⁻¹
1	2	4014.30±675.15 ^a	6269.29±1002.18 ^a	63.99±2.58 ^a	2254.99±380.12 ^a
1	1	3908.17±650.21 ^b	6265.43±1072.71 ^a	62.49±2.91 ^{ab}	2357.26±489.22 ^a
1	0	2287.93±1008.00 ^c	3830.05±1226.88 ^d	56.83±9.94 ^c	1542.12±261.10 ^c
0	2	3170.25±1003.16 ^c	5132.14±1356.07 ^b	60.81±5.47 ^b	1961.89±410.46 ^b
0	1	3054.42±1070.69 ^d	4938.27±1446.91 ^c	60.61±5.46 ^b	1883.85±412.87 ^b
0	0	1111.28±294.32 ^f	2361.11±502.89 ^e	46.9±7.72 ^d	1249.83±298.47 ^d
CV (%)		11.37	9.45	6.5	13.18
P-value		ns	ns	***	ns

Where, LSD = Least Significant Difference at 5% level; CV = Coefficient of Variation. Interaction effect means in columns followed by the same letters are not significantly different at 5% level of significance from each other and means in columns followed by the different letters show significant

differences between the means. From those Non-significant probability value > 0.05, *** = Very highly significant at probability value < 0.001 and L₀= without lime and L₁ = 2 t ha⁻¹; R₀ = without rhizobia, R₁ = Rhizobia HAMBI3562 and R₂ = Rhizobia HAMBI3570.

Table 4. 46. Response of haricot bean to starter nitrogen with rhizobia combined over the 2021 and 2022 growing years

Starter nitrogen*rhizobia		Yield and yield components			
Starter nitrogen(Sn)	Rhizobia (R)	Grain yield (GY) kg ha ⁻¹	Biomass Yield (BY) kg ha ⁻¹	Harvest Index (HI) %	Straw yield (SY) kg ha ⁻¹
0	0	870.89±183.40 ^h	2096.35±296.12 ^f	41.23±3.71 ^c	1225.5±132.56 ^e
0	1	2400.25±830.36 ^e	4016.20±1076.86 ^d	58.64±5.38 ^b	1615.95±277.8 ^{cd}
0	2	2563.43±797.05 ^d	4253.47±1007.16 ^c	59.34±5.79 ^b	1690.04±271.93 ^c
1	0	2048.97±910.80 ^g	3502.60±1150.18 ^e	56.68±8.09 ^b	1453.63±332.26 ^d
1	1	3842.60±381.49 ^c	6027.20±518.45 ^b	63.73±2.36 ^a	2184.59±215.68 ^b
1	2	3893.36±365.74 ^c	6096.64±608.47 ^b	63.94±2.72 ^a	2203.28±310.35 ^b
2	0	2178.97±916.90 ^f	3687.79±1191.40 ^e	57.69±7.78 ^b	1508.82±368.42 ^{cd}
2	1	4201.04±451.62 ^b	6762.15±785.90 ^a	62.29±3.54 ^a	2561.11±446.12 ^a
2	2	4320.03±492.09 ^a	6752.03±637.09 ^a	63.93±2.89 ^a	2432±262.11 ^a
CV (%)		11.37	9.45	6.5	13.18
P-value		ns	***	***	***

Where, CV = Coefficient of Variation. Interaction effect means in columns followed by the same letters are not significantly different at 5% level of significance from each other and means in columns followed by the different letters show significant differences between the means. From those Non-significant probability value > 0.05, *** = Very highly significant at probability value < 0.001 and L₀= without lime and L₁ = 2 t ha⁻¹; Sn₀ = without starter nitrogen, Sn₁ starter nitrogen = 10 kg ha⁻¹, Sn₂ starter nitrogen = 20 kg ha⁻¹; R₀ = without rhizobia, R₁ = Rhizobia HAMBI3562 and R₂ = Rhizobia HAMBI3570

Table 4. 47. Interaction effect of lime, starter nitrogen and Rhizobium on grain yield and biomass of haricot bean with in two years

Lime *Starter nitrogen*rhizobia			Yield and yield components	
Lime(L)	Starter nitrogen(Sn)	Rhizobia (R)	Grain yield (GY) kg ha ⁻¹	Biomass Yield (BY) kg ha ⁻¹
0	0	0	766.74±140.04 ^m	1982.06±229.65 ^l
0	0	1	1632.05±43.30 ^j	3029.52±176.96 ⁱ
0	0	2	1865.97±318.78 ⁱ	3382.52±458.73 ^h
0	1	0	1230.13±158.80 ^k	2485.53±501.18 ^{jk}
0	1	1	3613.63±315.23 ^e	5662.61±388.43 ^d
0	1	2	3686.53±313.61 ^e	5766.78±451.44 ^d
0	2	0	1336.98±170.80 ^k	2615.74±535.86 ^j
0	2	1	3917.60±315.17 ^d	6122.68±500.85 ^c
0	2	2	3958.26±339.41 ^{cd}	6247.11±435.40 ^{bc}
1	0	0	975.03±168.40 ^l	2210.65±329.89 ^{kl}
1	0	1	3168.47±314.11 ^{fg}	5002.90±428.14 ^{ef}
1	0	2	3260.90±358.46 ^f	5124.42±447.96 ^e
1	1	0	2867.81±436.61 ^h	4519.68±420.22 ^g
1	1	1	4071.57±308.20 ^{cd}	6391.78±348.51 ^{bc}
1	1	2	4100.19±305.38 ^c	6426.50±591.24 ^b
1	2	0	3020.96±344.82 ^{gh}	4759.83±278.09 ^{fg}
1	2	1	4484.48±395.68 ^b	7401.62±355.74 ^a
1	2	2	4681.80±321.61 ^a	7256.94±302.50 ^a
CV (%)			11.37	9.45
P-value			***	***

Where, CV = Coefficient of Variation. Interaction effect means in columns followed by the same letters are not significantly different at 5% level of significance from each other and means in columns followed by the different letters show significant differences between the means. From those *** = Very highly significant at probability value < 0.001 and L₀= without lime and L₁ = 2 t ha⁻¹; Sn₀ = without starter nitrogen, Sn₁ starter nitrogen = 10 kg ha⁻¹, Sn₂ starter nitrogen = 20 kg ha⁻¹; R₀ = without rhizobia, R₁ = Rhizobia HAMBI3562 and R₂ = Rhizobia HAMBI3570

Combined application of lime at the rate of 2 t ha⁻¹, starter nitrogen at 20 kg per hectare, and HAMBI3570 rhizobia strains collectively produced the highest crop yield of 4681.8 kg ha⁻¹. Following closely, the treatment involving lime at the rate of 2 t ha⁻¹, starter nitrogen at 10 kg ha⁻¹, and HAMBI3562 rhizobia strains yielded 4484.48 kg ha⁻¹. In contrast, the control treatment, devoid of any amendments, resulted in the lowest crop yields at 766.74 kg ha⁻¹ (Table 4.47). Significant differences were observed among most of the treatments. The study highlights that application of

lime (2 t ha^{-1}) in combination of starter nitrogen (20 kg ha^{-1}) and inoculation of the soil with HAMBI3570 rhizobia remarkably increased the grain yield of haricot bean compared to the grain yield obtained from the soil without any amendments. The boost in haricot bean yield can be attributed to the combined effects of lime, rhizobium inoculation, and starter nitrogen, which enhance soil physical and chemical properties and provide ample available nitrogen (N) and other nutrients. The advantages observed in yield attributes are likely a result of greater availability and uptake of macro- and micronutrients, improved soil properties leading to heightened photosynthesis, tissue differentiation, assimilation, and translocation. This, in turn, results in improved vegetative growth and yield attributes. The study conducted by Haile Negash *et al.* (2020) showed that the combined use of lime, phosphorus application, and rhizobium inoculation resulted in a significantly recorded higher grain yield of haricot beans in southwestern Ethiopia.

Consistent with earlier studies, Sheleme Beyene *et al.* (2014), Tesfaye Dejene *et al.* (2016), and Mesfin Kassa *et al.* (2014) found that Rhizobium inoculation and liming increased yield of legume crops like chickpea, lentil, and common bean. Additionally, rhizobium leguminosarum has shown to significantly increase yields in crops such as faba bean, field pea, lentil, and chickpea (Bayou Bunkura *et al.*, 2021). Notably, Similarly, the combined application of organic and inorganic fertilizer satisfying the requirements of plants uptake and leading to higher yields (Gonda Abdou *et al.*, 2016). Studies conducted in southwestern Ethiopia indicate that lime and rhizobia bifertilizer contribute to increased haricot bean crop yield in specific regions (Haile Negash and Wondosen Wondimu., 2022). Recent study conducted by (Daba Etana and Amsalu Nebiyu., 2023) stated that the combined application of lime and TSP fertilizer of haricot bean (Variety deme) gave the highest grain yield (3.84 t ha^{-1}) in plots which received both lime and TSP fertilizer. Ultimately, the results of this study contribute to the enhancement of crop yield and optimum utilization of natural resources for sustainable food security and poverty reduction, especially in the face of uncertain climate change and limited land resources.

Figure 5. Evaluation of research and farmers demonstration site by the research advisors with stakeholder

Table 4. 48. Interaction effect of lime, starter nitrogen and Rhizobium on straw yield and harvest index of haricot bean with in two years

Lime *Starter nitrogen*rhizobia			Yield and yield components	
Lime(L)	Starter nitrogen(Sn)	Rhizobia (R)	Harvest Index (HI) %	Straw yield (SY) kg ha ⁻¹
0	0	0	38.46±2.94 ^c	1215.32±99.60 ^j
0	0	1	53.98±2.54 ^{bc}	1397.47±155.13 ^{hij}
0	0	2	55.12±4.98 ^b	1516.56±252.47 ^{ghi}
0	1	0	50.16±4.38 ^c	1255.40±354.60 ^{ij}
0	1	1	63.78±2.49 ^a	2048.98±168.92 ^{de}
0	1	2	63.94±2.55 ^a	2080.25±222.13 ^{cde}
0	2	0	52.09±6.67 ^{bc}	1278.76±405.91 ^{ij}
0	2	1	64.06±3.08 ^a	2205.09±294.18 ^{cd}
0	2	2	63.37±3.43 ^a	2288.85±276.85 ^{cd}
1	0	0	43.99±1.79 ^d	1235.62±168.80 ^j
1	0	1	63.30±2.24 ^a	1834.43±176.54 ^{ef}
1	0	2	63.56±2.53 ^a	1863.52±163.44 ^{ef}
1	1	0	63.20±4.77 ^a	1651.87±151.06 ^{fgh}
1	1	1	63.67±2.46 ^a	2320.21±172.24 ^{bcd}
1	1	2	63.95±3.13 ^a	2326.31±355.28 ^{bc}
1	2	0	63.30±3.67 ^a	1738.87±82.67 ^{fg}
1	2	1	60.52±3.26 ^a	2917.14±217.01 ^a
1	2	2	64.48±2.44 ^a	2575.14±159.12 ^b
CV (%)			6.5	13.18
P-value			***	ns

Where, CV = Coefficient of Variation. Interaction effect means in columns followed by the same letters are not significantly different at 5% level of significance from each other and means in columns followed by the different letters show significant differences between the means. From those

Non-significant probability value > 0.05 , *** = Very highly significant at probability value < 0.001 and L_0 = without lime and $L_1 = 2 \text{ t ha}^{-1}$; Sn_0 = without starter nitrogen, Sn_1 starter nitrogen = 10 kg ha^{-1} , Sn_2 starter nitrogen = 20 kg ha^{-1} ; R_0 = without rhizobia, R_1 = Rhizobia HAMBI3562 and R_2 = Rhizobia HAMBI3570.

4.4.5. Above ground biomass yield

Biomass yield was influenced by the main effects of lime, stater nitrogen, and rhizobia ($p < 0.001$) in the combined analysis of variance over the two growing seasons (2021/2022) (Appendix Table 5). Moreover, the two way interaction of Lime with Starter nitrogen ($p < 0.001$), lime with rhizobia ($p < 0.001$), stater nitrogen with rhizobia ($p < 0.001$), and the three way interaction of lime, stater nitrogen rhizobia showed that significantly ($P < 0.001$) effect on Aboveground biomass yield combined over the year 2021 and 2022 growing season (Appendix Table 10).

The main effect on aboveground biomass yield in the study area ranged from 3095.6 to 5734 kg per hectare (Table 4.43). Application of 2 t ha^{-1} of increased the grain yield by 31.6% ($5454.9 \text{ kg ha}^{-1}$) compared to the lowest aboveground biomass yield recorded without lime ($4143.8 \text{ kg ha}^{-1}$) (Table 4.43). This could be when lime is applied to acidic soils, it raises the soil pH towards a more neutral level, creating a more favorable environment for plant roots. Hirpa Legesse *et al.* 2013 reported higher total biomass was observed from treated by lime. This might be due to lime buffered acidity impacts which hinder macro and micro nutrients and adjusting soil pH enhances the availability of critical nutrients, including phosphorus, nitrogen, and potassium, which are vital for robust plant growth and increased dry biomass, leading to higher yields. As observed in this study lime amended soil shows lower bulk density and higher moisture content and these improvements could have contributed to a healthier root system, allowing plants to access water and nutrients more efficiently, leading to increased biomass and grain yield.

Similarly, application of starter nitrogen at the rate of 20 kg ha^{-1} has increased yield of biomass by 65.9 % (5734 kg ha^{-1}) as starter recorded the highest biomass yield of haricot bean compared with plants without starter nitrogen ($3455.3 \text{ kg ha}^{-1}$). It has been reported that without sufficient starter nitrogen, young plants can experience early stress, leading to stunted growth and reduced biomass. Providing starter nitrogen at the beginning of the growing season may reduces this risk, ensuring that plants can develop optimally from the start and yields greater biomass (Bhattacharya, 2022).

Moreover, the study shows inoculation of the soil with HAMBI3570 strain of rhizobium increased the aboveground biomass yield of haricot bean by 84.2% ($5700.7 \text{ kg ha}^{-1}$) compared to the soil without rhizobium inoculation ($3095.6 \text{ kg ha}^{-1}$) (Table 43). The significant increase in aboveground biomass yield of haricot bean by 84.2% with the inoculation of the soil using the HAMBI3570 strain of rhizobium can be attributed to the symbiotic relationship between rhizobia bacteria and leguminous plants like haricot beans. In support of this outcome, Getachew Yilma *et al.* (2021) showed that the application of three rhizobia strains, namely HB A-15, CB-NAK 91, and HB 429, in the Mandara district of northwestern Ethiopia, resulted in a 46.0% increase in biomass yield of the HB 429 strain during the 2017 cropping season compared to the control

With in the interaction effect the highest dry biomass yield ($6762.15 \text{ kg ha}^{-1}$) were observed from treatment received 2 t ha^{-1} lime combined with 10 kg ha^{-1} starter nitrogen where as the lowest dry biomass yield ($2096.35 \text{ kg ha}^{-1}$) was recorded from the untreated plots. In the absence of crop inoculation, the application of lime and nitrogen fertilizer, either individually or in combination, resulted in a markedly higher aboveground biomass per hectare. Application of 10 kg ha^{-1} Starter nitrogen with rhizobia HAMBI3562 had increased the dry biomass yield by 222% compared to dry biomass yield recorded without starter nitrogen and rhizobia HAMBI3562 (Table 4.46). This increment might be lime with starter nitrogen application can have synergistic effects on the growth and nodulation of haricot beans

The combined application of lime, starter nitrogen, and rhizobia over a two-year period demonstrated that using 2 t ha^{-1} lime, starter nitrogen 10 kg ha^{-1} , and Rhizobia HAMBI3562 strain treatment recorded the highest aboveground biomass at $7401.6 \text{ kg ha}^{-1}$, followed closely by 2 t ha^{-1} lime, starter nitrogen 20 kg ha^{-1} , and Rhizobia HAMBI3570 strain treatment at $7256.94 \text{ kg ha}^{-1}$ (Table 4.47). Conversely, the control treatment and the application of lime alone yielded the lowest aboveground biomass per hectare, registering $1982.06 \text{ kg ha}^{-1}$ under rain-fed growing conditions. Similarly, Aregu Amsalu *et al.* (2020) in 2015, under drought stress conditions at Halaba, the beans inoculated with HAMBI3562 achieved the highest biomass yield. The observed variability in the aboveground biomass of haricot beans can be attributed to improvements in soil nutrient status resulting from the integrated application of inoculation strain types and lime. In line with Hirpa Legesse *et al.* (2013) who noted that higher total biomass yield was observed from the lime-treated plots. Ricaurte *et al.* (2016) highlighted that an increase in leaf area enhances the assimilation rate of carbon and nutrients

in common bean varieties, contributing to the transition from biological yield. In agreement to this study the application of lime (Mesfin Kassa *et al.*, 2014; Hirpa Legesse *et al.*, 2013), starter nitrogen (Abera Habete and Tadele Buraka., 2016) and inocuation of the soil strain of rhizobium (Tarekegn Yoseph, 2011; Getachew Yilma *et al.*, 2021) has been shown increased haricot beans above ground biomass yield. Higher biomass yield may translates into increased crop production, providing farmers with greater yields per unit area of land and potentially improving food insecurity.

4.4.6. Harvest Index

The harvest index was significantly affected by the main effects of lime, starter nitrogen, and rhizobia ($p < 0.001$) according to the combined analysis of variance over the two growing seasons (2021/2022) (Appendix Table 5). Additionally, the two-way interactions between lime and starter nitrogen ($p < 0.05$), lime and rhizobia ($p < 0.001$), and starter nitrogen and rhizobia ($p < 0.001$), as well as the three-way interaction among lime, starter nitrogen, and rhizobia, showed a significant effect ($p < 0.001$) on the harvest index over the 2021 and 2022 growing seasons (Appendix Table 10).

In the main effect, the harvest index in the study area ranged from 51.86 to 62.4 (Table 4.43). Application of 2 t ha^{-1} of increased the harvest index by 8.9%, the highest harvest index (61.11). Similarly, applying starter nitrogen at a rate of 10 kg ha^{-1} enhanced the harvest index by 15.5%. This application resulted in the highest harvest index of (61.45) in haricot beans crop, compared to 53.07 in plants that did not receive starter nitrogen

Regarding rhizobia strain types, the highest harvest index (62.4) was observed with the HAMB13570 rhizobia strain treatment, while the lowest harvest index (51.86) was recorded without any rhizobia strain. Inoculating the soil with the HAMB13570 strain of rhizobium increased the harvest index of haricot beans by 20.3% compared to soil without rhizobium inoculation (Table 43). Soil amended with HAMB13570 strain of rhizobium likely increased the harvest index by improving soil fertility, enhancing nutrient uptake, optimizing photosynthesis, improving nutrient management, and enhancing plant physiology (Malik *et al.*, 2006; Haile Negash *et al.*, 2020). The findings are in agreement with previous studies who reported higher harvest index with lime, starter nitrogen and inoculation strain of rhizobium based soil amendments (Pirbalouti *et al.*, 2006; Malik *et al.*, 2006; Habete and Buraka, 2016).

In the interaction analysis, the greatest harvest index (62.77) was noted in plots treated with 2 t ha⁻¹ of lime combined with 10 kg ha⁻¹ of starter nitrogen. Conversely, the lowest harvest index (49.18) was observed in the control plots. The utilization of 2 tons per hectare of lime alongside 10 kg ha⁻¹ of starter nitrogen led to a remarkable 294% increase in harvest index compared to plots without lime and starter nitrogen application, as indicated in (Table 4.44). In the context of the interaction effect, the peak harvest index (63.99) was detected in treatments employing 2 tons per hectare of lime coupled with rhizobia strain HAMBI3570, while the least harvest index (46.9) was documented in the control plots.

The application of 2 t ha⁻¹ of lime alongside rhizobia strain HAMBI3570 resulted in a 36.4% increment in harvest index compared to the harvest index noted in the absence of lime and rhizobia strain HAMBI3570, as outlined in (Table 4.45).

Within the interaction paradigm, the highest harvest index (63.93) was observed in plots subjected to 20 kg ha⁻¹ of starter nitrogen combined with rhizobia strain HAMBI3570, while the lowest harvest index (41.23) was documented in the control plots. Application of 20 kg ha⁻¹ of starter nitrogen with rhizobia strain HAMBI3570 led to a 55% augmentation in the harvest index compared to instances where starter nitrogen and rhizobia strain HAMBI3570 were absent, as delineated in (Table 4.46).

The combined application lime, starter nitrogen, rhizobia over two seasons showed that the plot treated with 2 t ha⁻¹ lime, 20 kg ha⁻¹ starter nitrogen, and HAMBI3570 rhizobia strains recorded the highest percentage of harvest index at 64.48%, while the control plots without treatment yielded a harvest index of 38.46% (Table 4.48). There were significant differences observed among the various treatments. The harvest index, representing a crop plant's physiological ability to convert a proportion of dry matter into economic yield influenced by treatments. The results demonstrated that an adequate supply of nitrogen contributed to a favorable partitioning of dry matter toward grain, resulting in a higher harvest index. Lower harvest index were observed in control treatments. This aligns with the experiment conducted by Pirbalouti *et al.* (2006), where a highly significant difference in harvest index was noted among inoculants and nitrogen fertilizer. Similarly, Haile Negash *et al.* (2020) reported the highest harvest index recorded for lime, 23 kg P ha⁻¹, and inoculated seeds, attributing it to the higher grain yield obtained in relation to lower biomass yield.

Additionally, Malik *et al.* (2006) claimed a high harvest index value in soybean resulting from a combination of phosphorus fertilizer and inoculation.

4.4.7. Straw yield

Straw yield was influenced by the main effects of lime, starter nitrogen, and rhizobia ($p < 0.001$) in the combined analysis of variance over the two growing seasons (2021/2022) (Appendix Table 5). Moreover, the two way interaction of starter nitrogen with rhizobia ($p < 0.001$) effect on Straw yield combined over the year 2021 and 2022 growing season (Appendix Table 10).

Regarding the main effect, the straw yield within the research domain ranged from 1396 to 2167.3 kg ha⁻¹ (Table 4.43). Additionally, within the lime treatment regimen, the peak straw yield (2051.5 kg ha⁻¹) was witnessed with 2 t ha⁻¹ of lime, whereas the lowest straw yield (1698.5 kg ha⁻¹) occurred in plots without lime. The application of 2 t ha⁻¹ increased straw production by 39.2% in contrast to yields observed in plots without lime.

In a similar fashion, the highest straw yield (2167.3 kg ha⁻¹) was achieved in plots treated with 20 kg ha⁻¹ of starter nitrogen, whereas the lowest straw production (1510.5 kg ha⁻¹) was observed in plots without lime. Correspondingly, the application of starter nitrogen at a dosage of 20 kg ha⁻¹ led to 83.4% increase in straw output for haricot bean in comparison to plants lacking starter nitrogen. In relation to the different varieties of rhizobia strains, the highest straw yield (2108.4 kg ha⁻¹) was observed in plots treated with the HAMBI3570 rhizobia strain, whereas the lowest straw output (1396 kg ha⁻¹) was documented in plots lacking any rhizobia strain. The applications of HAMBI3570 strain of rhizobium to the soil led to a 111.4% increase in haricot bean straw yield compared to soil without rhizobium inoculation

Moreover, with in the interaction effect the highest Straw yield (2561.11 kg ha⁻¹) were observed from treatment received 2 t ha⁻¹ lime combined with 20 kg ha⁻¹ starter nitrogen whereas the lowest Straw yield (1225.5 kg ha⁻¹) was recorded from the control plots application of 20 kg ha⁻¹ starter nitrogen with rhizobia HAMBI3570 had increased the Straw yield by 98.5% compared to Straw yield recorded without Starter nitrogen and rhizobia HAMBI3570 (Table 4.46).

The combined application lime, starter nitrogen, rhizobia over two years the highest straw yield (2917.1 kg ha⁻¹) was observed in plants treated with 2 t ha⁻¹ lime, 10 kg ha⁻¹ starter nitrogen, and

HAMBI3562 rhizobia strains. Following closely, the treatment with 2 t ha⁻¹ lime, HAMBI3570 rhizobia strains, and 20 kg ha⁻¹ starter nitrogen yielded 2575.1 kg ha⁻¹. In contrast, the control plots, without any treatment, recorded a straw yield of 1215.32 kg ha⁻¹ (Table 4.46). Statistically significant differences among treatments were observed in most of the experiments. The study suggests that the application of lime (2 t ha⁻¹) combined with starter nitrogen (10 kg ha⁻¹) and HAMBI3562 strain, as well as lime (2 t ha⁻¹) with starter nitrogen (20 kg ha⁻¹) and HAMBI3570 strain, led to a remarkable increase in straw yield by 140% and 111.8%, respectively. These results align with the findings of Pirbalouti *et al.* (2006), who reported significant differences among four rhizobial strains nodulating haricot beans in terms of straw yield production at maturity.

4.5. Correlation among soil physico-chemical properties and crop growth parameters of haricot bean

4.5.1. Correlation coefficients among soil physico-chemical properties of study area

The study area grain yield has positive correlation with soil physico-chemical properties but negative correlation with bulk density ($r = -0.98^{***}$), exchangeable acidity ($r = -0.71^{***}$) and electrical conductivity ($r = -0.97^{***}$) (Table 4.49). This is because integrated soil fertility practices improve soil physical properties by improving soil organic matter and soil carbon. As a result, it improves soil aggregation. This is in line with Opela *et al* (2018) who found a maximum maize yield was obtained from application of combined application of lime with fertilizer as compared with the control. Similarly, Mulugeta Aytnew (2015) found that soil pH is positively correlated with CEC. Higher pH values increase the number of negative charges on colloids. Additionally, positive correlations were observed between soil CEC and soil organic content in the Dawja watershed, Enebe Sar Midir district, northwest Ethiopia.

Table 4. 49. Correlation coefficients among soil physico-chemical properties with grain yield of haricot bean

Variable	BD	TP	SM	pH	EA	OC	OM	TN	EC	CEC	SIN	Av.p	GY
BD	1	-1** *	-0.99* **	-0.79* **	0.73* **	-	-	-	0.97* **	-	-	-	-
TP		1	0.99* **	0.79* **	-0.73* **	0.99* **	0.99* **	0.99* **	-0.97* **	0.97* **	0.86* **	0.86* **	0.98* **
SM			1	0.79* **	-0.72* **	0.98* **	0.98* **	0.99* **	-0.96* **	0.97* **	0.85* **	0.85* **	0.98* **
pH				1	-0.94* **	0.77* **	0.77* **	0.77* **	-0.71* **	0.74* **	0.90* **	0.87* **	0.78* **
EA					1	-0.73* **	-0.73* **	-0.72* **	0.65* *	-0.66* *	-0.92* **	-0.87* **	-0.71* **
OC						1	1.00* **	0.99* **	-0.97* **	0.97* **	0.84* **	0.85* **	0.98* **
OM							1	0.99* **	-0.97* **	0.97* **	0.84* **	0.85* **	0.98* **
TN								1	-0.97* **	0.98* **	0.85* **	0.87* **	0.99* **
Ec									1	-0.97* **	-0.81* **	-0.84* **	-0.97* **
CEC										1	0.84* **	0.88* **	0.99* **
SIN											1	0.98* **	0.86* **
Av.p												1	0.89* **

Where, *** = very highly significant at $P < 0.001$, ** = highly significant at P between 0.001 - 0.01, * = significant at P between 0.01-0.05, $P > 0.05$, ns = non-significant. BD = bulk density, TP= total porosity, SM = Soil moisture, pH = Soil reaction , EA = Exchangeable acidity, Ec = Electrical conductivity, Oc = Organic carbon, Om = Organic matter, TN = Total nitrogen, CEC = cation exchange capacity, SIN = soil inorganic nitrogen, Av.P = Available phosphorus and GY= Grain yield

4.5.2. Correlation among selected growth parameters of haricot bean

The magnitude and direction of the association of agronomic and yield parameters as expressed by correlation coefficients (r) are indicated in Table 4.15. Most of the parameters are positive highly to very highly correlate to the grain yield. For instance, among the agronomic and yield components of haricot bean, grain yield was directly and very highly significantly correlated with the biomass yield ($r = 0.99^{***}$), number of pods per plant ($r = 0.98^{***}$), hundred seed weight ($r = 0.97^{***}$), number of seeds per pod ($r = 0.96^{***}$), leaf area per plant ($r = 0.95^{***}$), and leaf area index ($r = 0.95^{***}$). The experiment conducted by Desta Abayechawa and Ermias Ejamo (2019) reported that the number of primary branches per plant, plant height, number of seeds per pod, days to flowering, leaf area index, number of pods per plant, harvest index and above-ground dry biomass had a positive correlation with grain yield. The Pearson correlation analysis by Bayu Enchalew (2022) indicated that grain yield of chickpea was positively and significantly correlated with plant height, number of seeds per plant, hundred seed weight, biomass yield, and straw yield. Gebre-Egziabher Murut *et al.* (2014) report also showed that plant height, number of pods per plant, days to green maturity, average number of seeds per plant and thousand seed weight had highest positive correlation with common bean grain yield at Wukro and Shiket across two locations. Similarly, Bizunesh Abiye (2019) stated that the r value had positive and strong correlation or direct relationship between nodulation, yield and yield components chickpea. Notably, most of the agronomic parameters of soyabean in this study area were significantly and positively correlated with each other (Yifru Abera, 2019). Other studies in Ethiopia by different authors also revealed that strong correlations between nodule number and yield of soybean (Anteneh Argaw, 2014; Daniel Muleta *et al.*, 2017; Diriba Temesgen, 2017).

Table 4. 50. Correlation coefficients between growth and yield component of haricot bean

Variable	D	DM	PH	NPB	LAP	LAI	TNN	ENN	PEN	NPP	NSP	HS	GY	By	HI	SY
DF	1	0.99 ***	0.96 ***	0.95 ***	0.96 ***	0.96 ***	0.95 ***	0.96 ***	0.77 ***	0.90 ***	0.95 ***	0.91 ***	0.88 ***	0.91 ***	0.68 **	0.93 ***
DM		1	0.96 ***	0.96 ***	0.96 ***	0.96 ***	0.98 ***	0.98 ***	0.73 ***	0.87 ***	0.95 ***	0.89 ***	0.87 ***	0.90 ***	0.64 **	0.94 ***
PH			1	0.97 ***	0.99 ***	0.99 ***	0.93 ***	0.94 ***	0.75 ***	0.94 ***	0.99 ***	0.94 ***	0.94 ***	0.95 ***	0.73 ***	0.96 ***
NPB				1	0.96 ***	0.96 ***	0.92 ***	0.92 ***	0.64 ***	0.87 ***	0.95 ***	0.85 ***	0.86 ***	0.89 ***	0.58 ***	0.93 ***
LAP					1	1**	0.93 ***	0.94 ***	0.76 ***	0.95 ***	0.99 ***	0.94 ***	0.95 ***	0.97 ***	0.74 ***	0.98 ***
LAI						1	0.93 ***	0.94 ***	0.76 ***	0.95 ***	0.99 ***	0.94 ***	0.95 ***	0.97 ***	0.74 ***	0.98 ***
TNN							1	0.99 ***	0.72 ***	0.84 ***	0.92 ***	0.88 ***	0.85 ***	0.87 ***	0.62 **	0.92 ***
ENN								1	0.76 ***	0.87 ***	0.93 ***	0.90 ***	0.87 ***	0.89 ***	0.66 **	0.93 ***
PEN									1	0.88 ***	0.75 ***	0.89 ***	0.81 ***	0.80 ***	0.89 ***	0.73 ***
NPP										1	0.95 ***	0.97 ***	0.98 ***	0.97 ***	0.89 ***	0.93 ***
NSP											1	0.95 ***	0.96 ***	0.97 ***	0.76 ***	0.97 ***
HS												1	0.97 ***	0.97 ***	0.90 ***	0.94 ***
GY													1	0.99 ***	0.88 ***	0.95 ***
By														1	0.85 ***	0.97 ***
HI															1	0.73 ***
SY																1

Where, *** = very highly significant at $P < 0.001$, ** = highly significant at P between 0.001-0.01, * = significant at P between 0.01-0.05, $P > 0.05$, ns = non-significant. Ph = Plant height, NPB = Number of primary branches, TNNPP = Total number of nodules per plant, ENNPP = Effective number of nodules per plant, PEN = Percent of effective nodules, DF = Days to 50% flowering, DM = Days to 90% maturity, NPPP = Number of pods per plant, NSPP = Number of seeds per pod, HSW

= Hundred-seed weight, LAPP = Leaf area per plant, LAI = Leaf area index, GY = Grain yield, BY = Biomass yield, HI = Harvest index, and SY = Straw yield.

4.6. Economic Analysis

4.6.1. Partial budget analysis

The partial budget analysis of the 18 treatments is shown in (Table 4.16). Organizing experimental data and details regarding the costs and benefits of different alternative treatments were possible through the use of partial budget analysis. This method is useful for determining whether new technology will be profitable or not. It also offers a basis for assessing alternative treatments' relative profitability, determining how risky they are, and determining how profitable they would be in the event that input or product prices changed. In order to find the best net benefit with a reasonable marginal rate of return, cost-benefit analysis was done on various combined treatments under the assumption that the total variable cost was an expense resulting from the application of inputs. For each treatment, the gross field benefits were subtracted from the total variable cost to determine the net benefit. Because it was the same for all treatments, all costs were computed without taking into account the cost of other agronomic practices like land plowing, planting, weeding, protecting the farm, and harvesting.

The prices for fertilizers of TSP, urea, lime, HAMBI3570 Rhizobium strain, and HAMBI3562 Rhizobium strain (125 gram) were taken as 18.5 ETB kg⁻¹, 26.87 ETB kg⁻¹, 4.35 ETB kg⁻¹, 82.5 ETB/125 gram, and 80 ETB/125 gram of each nutrient, respectively. The cost of other production practices, like grain and weeding, was assumed to remain the same or insignificant among the treatments. To assess the costs and benefits associated with different treatments, partial budget analyses were carried out by taking the mean grain yield and prices of input and output of different amendements and haricot beans in the nearby northwestern Ethiopian market (Table 4.16). Marginal rates of return were calculated by adjusting the grain yield of haricot beans by 10% to narrow the yield gap between research and farmers' fields (CIMMYT, 1988). All costs and benefits were calculated on a hectare basis in Ethiopian Birr (ETB ha⁻¹). Accordingly, the current result revealed that the maximum net benefit (259,426.2 ETB ha⁻¹) was obtained from the application of lime 2 t ha⁻¹, starter nitrogen 20 kg ha⁻¹, and HAMBI3570 rhizobia strains, while the lowest net benefit (42,521.74 ETB ha⁻¹) was obtained from the control plots (Table 4.16). Therefore, the best alternative

return, the above mentioned fertilizer rate are recommended as best economically rewarding treatment rate for the study area (Table 4.16). In agreement with this result, Deresa Shumi *et al.*, 2018 (2018) obtained highest net benefit with the application of highest rate of fertilizer for common bean at Mid-land of Guji, Southern Ethiopia. Similarly, Muhammad Islam *et al.* (2011) reported that the combined application of fertilizer on chick pea resulted in higher value cost ratio. Notably, Dereje Shanka *et al.* (2015) and Fisseha Negash and Yayis Rezene. (2015) also reported that planting of the common bean Nasir produced the highest net benefit with acceptable marginal rate of return (30-40%) and 80% respectively

Table 4. 51. Partial budget analysis on haricot bean grain yield

Treatments			Grain yield(GY) (kg ha ⁻¹)	Adjusted Grain yield(AGY) (kg ha ⁻¹)	straw yield (SY) (kg ha ⁻¹)	Adjusted straw yield(ASY) (kg ha ⁻¹)	Gross field benefit (GFB) ETB	Total Variable Cost (TVC) ETB	NET benefit(NB) ETB
L	Sn	R							
0	0	0	766.74	690.066	1982.1	1783.89	44971.74	2450	42521.74
0	0	1	1632.05	1468.845	3029.5	2726.55	93583.8	3070	90513.8
0	0	2	1865.97	1679.373	3382.5	3044.25	106850.88	3080	103770.9
0	1	0	1230.13	1107.117	2485.5	2236.95	70900.92	3634.2	67266.72
0	1	1	3613.63	3252.267	5662.6	5096.34	205328.7	4254.2	201074.5
0	1	2	3686.53	3317.877	5766.8	5190.12	209452.86	4264.2	205188.7
0	2	0	1336.98	1203.282	2615.7	2354.13	76905.18	4818.4	72086.78
0	2	1	3917.6	3525.84	6122.7	5510.43	222571.26	5438.4	217132.9
0	2	2	3958.26	3562.434	6247.1	5622.39	224990.82	5448.4	219542.4
1	0	0	975.03	877.527	2210.6	1989.54	56630.7	3455	53175.7
1	0	1	3168.47	2851.623	5002.9	4502.61	180102.6	4075	176027.6
1	0	2	3260.9	2934.81	5124.4	4611.96	185312.52	4085	181227.5
1	1	0	2867.81	2581.029	4519.7	4067.73	162997.2	4639.2	158358
1	1	1	4071.57	3664.413	6391.8	5752.62	231370.02	5259.2	226110.8
1	1	2	4100.19	3690.171	6426.5	5783.85	232977.96	5269.2	227708.8
1	2	0	3020.96	2718.864	4759.8	4283.82	171699.48	5823.4	165876.1
1	2	1	4484.48	4036.032	7401.6	6661.44	255484.8	6443.4	249041.4
1	2	2	4681.8	4213.62	7256.9	6531.21	265879.62	6453.4	259426.2

Where; GY = Grain Yield, Adj.GY = Adjusted Grain Yield down to 10%, SY = straw yield, Adj.SY = Adjusted straw yield/kg GFB = Gross Field Benefit, TVC = Total Cost that Varies, NB = Net Benefit, ETB = Ethiopian Birr ,Lime(L), Starter nitrogen(Sn) , Rhizobia (R) and L₀= without lime and L₁ = 2 t ha⁻¹; Sn₀ = without starter nitrogen, Sn₁ starter nitrogen = 10 kg ha⁻¹, Sn₂ starter nitrogen = 20 kg ha⁻¹; R₀ = without rhizobia, R₁ = Rhizobia HAMBI3562 and R₂ = Rhizobia HAMBI3570

4.6.2. Marginal rate of return (MRR)

The percentage marginal rate of return between any pair of dominant treatments denotes the return per unit of investment in amendments expressed as a percentage. The best recommended treatments are not subjected to the highest marginal rate of return rather based on the minimum acceptable marginal rate of return, and the treatment with the highest net benefit together with an acceptable MRR becomes the tentative recommendation for the farmers (CIMMYT, 1988). The dominance analysis procedure, as detailed in CIMMYT (1988), was used to select potentially profitable treatments from the range that was tested. The dominant treatments were ranked from the lowest to the highest costs, which vary. This indicates that the net benefit decreased as the total cost that varied increased beyond undominated fertilizer application.

In this study, 100% was considered the minimum acceptable rate of return for the farmer's recommendation, and the maximum net benefit was taken. From the Table below, MRR values above 100% are accepted. If more than one treatment has a MRR of >100%, we take the treatment with the maximum net benefit. In our case, the acceptable marginal rate of return (25297.28%) with a maximum net benefit of 259,426.2 ETB ha⁻¹ for haricot bean production was obtained from the combined of lime 2 tons per hectare, starter nitrogen 20 kg ha⁻¹, and HAMB13570 rhizobia strains application, which had better haricot bean production and economic return (Table 4.17). This recommendation confirms with CYMMIT (1988), which reported that farmers should be willing to change from one treatment to another if the marginal rate of return of that change is greater than the minimum acceptable rate of return. The result is in line with Ermias Elka and Fanuel Laekemariam (2020) who reported that the highest net benefit with highest MRR of haricot bean crop was obtained from the treatment combination of organic nutrient source and fertilizer at Sodo Zuria district, Southern Ethiopia. Similarly, Eshetu Zenebu (2018) reported that the maximum marginal rate of return (MRR) was recorded at rhizobium-inoculated seed as compared to control at Gische District, North Shewa Zone, Ethiopia. Samuel Adissie *et al.* (2021) research also showed that the rhizobia-inoculated faba bean crop has the maximum net benefit per hectare while possessing an MRR of greater than 100%, thus making it economically feasible for Wereillu district. Notably, Muhammad Islam *et al.* (2011) reported that the combined application of fertilizer on chickpea result the best

economically rewarding treatment rate for the study. The result was inconformity with the findings of (Birhanu Messele and Lalit Mohan ., 2012)

Table 4. 52. Dominance analysis and marginal rate of return on haricot bean grain yield

treatments			TVC ETB ha ⁻¹	NET benefit ETB ha ⁻¹	Dominance	B: C ratio	MRR(%)
L	Sn	R					
0	0	0	2450	42521.74		17.35	
0	0	1	3070	90513.8		29.48	141.03
0	0	2	3080	103770.9		33.69	1325.7
1	0	0	3455	53175.7	Dominated		
0	1	0	3634.2	67266.72		18.50	
1	0	1	4075	176027.6		43.19	246.73
1	0	2	4085	181227.5		44.36	17714.25
0	1	1	4254.2	201074.5		47.26	1163.24
0	1	2	4264.2	205188.7		48.11	20092.45
1	1	0	4639.2	158358	Dominated		
0	2	0	4818.4	72086.78	Dominated		
1	1	1	5259.2	226110.8		42.99	501.02
1	1	2	5269.2	227708.8		43.21	22243.96
0	2	1	5438.4	217132.9	Dominated		
0	2	2	5448.4	219542.4		40.29	
1	2	0	5823.4	165876.1	Dominated		
1	2	1	6443.4	249041.4		38.65	243.81
1	2	2	6453.4	259426.2		40.19	25297.28

Where; TVC = Total Variable Cost, NB = Net Benefit, B: C = Benefit Cost ratio, Lime(L), Starter nitrogen(Sn) , Rhizobia (R) and L₀= without lime and L₁ = 2 t ha⁻¹; Sn₀ = without starter nitrogen, Sn₁ starter nitrogen = 10 kg ha⁻¹, Sn₂ starter nitrogen = 20 kg ha⁻¹; R₀ = without rhizobia, R₁ = Rhizobia HAMBI3562 and R₂ = Rhizobia HAMBI3570

$$MRR (\%) = \frac{NBSD - NBID}{TVCS - TVCI} * 100$$

Note: MRR = Marginal rate of return

NBSD = Net benefit from the superior dominant plot, NBID = Net benefit from the inferior plot, TVCS = Total variable cost from superior dominant plot, TVCI = Total variable cost from the superior dominant plot

CHAPTER 5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

5.1. CONCLUSION

Haricot bean (*Phaseolus vulgaris L.*) is a crucial food security crop in northwestern Ethiopia. However, its national average yield remains low due to various abiotic and biotic stresses. Major constraints limiting haricot bean yield in this region include low soil fertility and diminished biological nitrogen fixation, primarily caused by low soil pH and inadequate availability of essential nutrients like nitrogen (N), phosphorus (P), calcium (Ca), magnesium (Mg), and potassium (K). Continuous cultivation without nutrient replenishment, nutrient leaching, and high aluminum concentrations exacerbate soil fertility depletion, posing significant obstacles to achieving optimal harvests. Despite the continued cultivation of haricot beans in northwestern Ethiopia, average yields remain below the crop's potential. This study aimed to examine the effects of inoculation and soil amendments, including lime, starter nitrogen, and rhizobium inoculation, on soil properties and haricot bean yield.

The results of the study concluded that the application of starter nitrogen, lime, and rhizobia inoculation, individually and in combination, exerts significant positive effects on both soil physical and chemical properties and the yield and yield components of haricot beans. Starter nitrogen enhances early plant growth by providing an immediate nutrient boost, improving nitrogen content in the soil. Lime ameliorates soil acidity, enhances nutrient availability, and improves soil structure. Rhizobia inoculation promotes effective biological nitrogen fixation, enriching soil nitrogen levels and supporting plant growth. The combination of these treatments synergistically optimizes soil conditions, ensuring maximum nutrient availability and improved soil health. This results in enhanced plant growth, increased pod number, higher seed count per pod, and greater hundred seed weight, ultimately boosting haricot bean yield. The study concluded that integrating soil amendments with organic and inorganic fertilizers significantly increases bean yield in acidic soils. Specifically, the combined application of 2 t ha⁻¹ lime, 20 kg ha⁻¹ starter nitrogen, and HAMBI3570 Rhizobium strain was identified as the most effective strategy for maximizing productivity and profitability in haricot bean production.

5.2. RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the result found from the research conducted, the following recommendations are put to improve soil fertility at koga irrigation sites

- Based on two years of data collection, the combined application of 2 t ha⁻¹ lime, 20 kg ha⁻¹ starter nitrogen, and HAMB13570 strains is recommended for farmers to enhance productivity and achieve sustainable economic benefits.
- The government could facilitate the provision of calcite (CaCO₃) and biofertilizers to farmers to improve soil fertility and boost crop productivity.
- Before inoculating legume crops with biofertilizer, quantify the amount of viable bacteria is recommended
- Future research should focus on long-term effects as well as the economic feasibility and performance under various soil and climatic conditions.

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APPENDIX

Appendix Table 1. Main effects of mean square, F calculated results and probability value of three-way analysis of variance on selected soil physical properties under two lime level, three starter nitrogen rate, three rhizobia strain level within two years

Parameters	Lime			Starter nitrogen			rhizobia		
	Ms	F	P	Ms	F	P	Ms	F	P
Bulk density (g cm ⁻³)	0.07948981	78.76	<.0001***	0.09167315	90.83	<.0001***	0.15585648	154.43	<.0001***
Total Porosity (%)	113.1397370	78.76	<.0001***	130.5797694	90.90	<.0001***	221.9983694	154.53	<.0001***
Soil moisture (%)	103.8212231	57.28	<.0001***	142.3541148	78.54	<.0001***	200.0217065	110.36	<.0001***

Appendix Table 2. Main effects of mean square, F calculated results and probability value of three-way analysis of variance on selected soil chemical properties under two lime level, three starter nitrogen level, three rhizobia strain level within two years

Parameters	Lime			Starter nitrogen			rhizobia		
	Ms	F	P	Ms	F	P	Ms	F	P
Soil reaction (pH)	4.51004537	810.86	<.0001***	0.36977500	66.48	<.0001***	0.77126944	138.67	<.0001***
Exchangeable Acidity (EA) in cmol(+)kg ⁻¹	52.76611204	5676.04	<.0001***	1.96646204	211.53	<.0001***	4.97509259	535.17	<.0001***
% Organic carbon(OC)	1.19070000	103.69	<.0001***	1.15640833	100.70	<.0001***	2.52780833	220.13	<.0001***
Organic matter(OM)	3.53896996	103.69	<.0001***	3.43704909	100.70	<.0001***	7.51309126	220.13	<.0001***
% Total nitrogen(TN)	0.00317959	83.65	<.0001***	0.00352140	92.65	<.0001***	0.00653156	171.84	<.0001***
Electrical conductivity(EC) in dS/M	0.00022533	53.75	<.0001***	0.00046858	111.78	<.0001***	0.00079360	189.31	<.0001***

Available phosphorus in ppm	Soil Inorganic nitrogen (SIN) in mg kg-1	Cation Exchange Capacity (CEC) in cmol (+) kg-1)
2046.414948	139752.0833	205.013333
2052.23	4104.77	234.28
<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***
361.094095	19057.6944	308.100370
362.12	559.76	352.08
<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***
763.542006	43165.4444	590.983426
765.71	1267.85	675.34
<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***

Appendix Table 3. Main effects of mean square, F calculated results and probability value of three-way analysis of variance on crop phenology under two lime level, three starter nitrogen level, three rhizobia strain level within two years

Parameters	Lime			Starter nitrogen			rhizobia		
	Ms	F	P	Ms	F	P	Ms	F	P
Days to 50% Flowering (DF)	510.472593	103.37	<.0001***	417.951204	84.63	<.0001***	1032.810093	209.14	<.0001***
90% Days of maturity (DM)	1208.682315	125.18	<.0001***	1054.945648	109.25	<.0001***	2321.440093	240.42	<.0001***
Plant height PH (cm)	5777.24083	1499.19	<.0001***	7128.02600	1849.72	<.0001***	9819.13593	2548.07	<.0001***
Number of primary branches (NPB)	26.0092593	467.39	<.0001***	47.8002778	858.97	<.0001***	56.0577778	1007.36	<.0001***
Leaf area per plant (LAPP) in cm ²	6835071.37	613.19	<.0001***	8884346.11	797.04	<.0001***	14953795.40	1341.55	<.0001***
Leaf area index (LAI)	42.6889815	609.82	<.0001***	55.5456676	793.48	<.0001***	93.4286176	1334.64	<.0001***

Appendix Table 4. Main effects of mean square, F calculated results and probability value of three-way analysis of variance on Biological Nitrogen Fixation under two lime level, three starter nitrogen level, three rhizobia strain level within two years

Parameters	Lime			Starter nitrogen			rhizobia		
	Ms	F	P	Ms	F	P	Ms	F	P
Total Number of nodule per plant (TNNP)	15019.04593	180.48	<.0001 ^{***}	13736.72509	165.07	<.0001 ^{***}	25190.09565	302.70	<.0001 ^{***}
Effective number of nodule (ENNP)	15317.68926	201.27	<.0001 ^{***}	16512.60593	216.97	<.0001 ^{***}	33903.69065	445.49	<.0001 ^{***}
Perecent of nodule effectiveness(PNE)	299.66676	66.37	<.0001 ^{***}	1989.30455	440.60	<.0001 ^{***}	6530.10236	1446.31	<.0001 ^{***}

Appendix Table 5. Main effects of mean square, F calculated results and probability value of three-way analysis of variance on Yield and yield components under two lime level, three starter nitrogen level, three rhizobia strain level within two years

Parameters	Lime			Starter nitrogen			rhizobia		
	Ms	F	P	Ms	F	P	Ms	F	P
Number of pods per plant (NPPP)	942.822315	492.76	<.0001***	2498.774444	1305.98	<.0001***	4099.775833	2142.74	<.0001***
Number of seeds per pod	29.24481481	1283.92	<.0001***	28.47861111	1250.28	<.0001***	40.89583333	1795.43	<.0001***
Hundred-seed weight (HSW) (g)	1104.000833	356.33	<.0001***	1419.307037	458.10	<.0001***	2091.923426	675.20	<.0001***
Grain yield (GY) kg ha ⁻¹	24787311.76	224.32	<.0001***	26743628.37	242.03	<.0001***	40613507.54	367.55	<.0001***
Biomass Yield (BY) kg ha ⁻¹	46411524.0	225.50	<.0001***	51256171.2	249.04	<.0001***	78467183.5	381.25	<.0001***
Harvest Index (HI) %	675.500093	46.51	<.0001***	828.420737	57.03	<.0001***	1233.810179	84.94	<.0001***
Straw yield (SY) kg ha ⁻¹	3363232.32	55.07	<.0001***	4023463.68	65.88	<.0001***	6196620.38	101.47	<.0001***

Appendix Table 6. Interaction effects of mean square, F calculated results and probability value of three-way analysis of variance on selected soil physical properties under two lime rate, three starter nitrogen rate and three rhizobia strain types with in two years

Parameters	Soil Physical Properties											
	lime*Starter nitrogen			lime*RHhizobia			Starter nitrogen*Rhizobia			lime*Starter nitrogen*Rhizobia		
	Ms	F	P	Ms	F	P	Ms	F	P	Ms	F	P
Bulk density (g cm ⁻³)	0.00054537	0.54	0.5849 ^{ns}	0.00020648	0.20	0.8155 ^{ns}	0.00353426	3.50	0.0114*	0.00274537	2.72	0.0361*
Total Porosity (%)	0.7716954	0.54	0.5867 ^{ns}	0.2932565	0.20	0.8158 ^{ns}	5.0315972	3.50	0.0114*	3.9251815	2.73	0.0355*
Soil moisture (%)	2.1151815	1.17	0.317 ^{ns}	0.4008898	0.22	0.8021 ^{ns}	6.5685565	3.62	0.0095 ^{**}	4.7039815	2.60	0.0434*

Appendix Table 7. Interaction effects of mean square, F calculated results and probability value of three-way analysis of variance on selected soil chemical properties under two lime rate, three starter nitrogen rate and three rhizobia strain types with in two years

Parameters	Soil chemical Properties											
	lime*Starter nitrogen			lime*Rhizobia			Starter nitrogen*Rhizobia			lime*Starter nitrogen*Rhizobia		
	Ms	F	P	Ms	F	P	Ms	F	P	Ms	F	P
Soil reaction (pH)	0.00795093	1.43	0.2461ns	0.03133426	5.63	0.0053**	0.04742778	8.53	<.0001***	0.01441481	2.59	0.0436*
Exchangeable Acidity (EA) in cmol(+)kg ⁻¹	0.20289537	21.83	<.0001***	0.77862593	83.76	<.0001***	0.26216759	28.20	<.0001***	0.03698426	3.98	0.0057**
% Organic carbon(OC)	0.02522500	2.20	0.1186ns	0.02617500	2.28	0.1097ns	0.06898333	6.01	0.0003***	0.05650000	4.92	0.0015***
Organic matter(OM)	0.07497314	2.20	0.1186ns	0.07779671	2.28	0.1097ns	0.20503061	6.01	0.0003***	0.16792794	4.92	0.0015**
% Total nitrogen(TN)	0.00002868	0.75	0.4740ns	0.00000451	0.12	0.8883ns	0.00007273	1.91	0.1174 ^{ns}	0.00016234	4.27	0.0037**
Electrical conductivity(EC) in dS/M	0.00000451	1.08	0.3461ns	0.00000230	0.55	0.5800ns	0.00000369	0.88	0.4808 ^{ns}	0.00001068	2.55	0.0465*

Available phosphorus in ppm	Soil Inorganic nitrogen(SIN) in mg kg-1	Cation Exchange Capacity (CEC) in cmol (+) kg-1
1.247506	3858.0833	4.101111
1.25	113.32	4.69
0.2924 ^{ns}	<.0001***	0.0122*
5.021456	1953.4444	0.725833
5.04	57.38	0.83
0.0090**	<.0001***	0.4404ns
54.334404	1006.0972	2.284537
54.49	29.55	2.61
<.0001***	<.0001***	0.0424*
26.584973	851.7361	15.238611
26.66	25.02	17.41
<.0001***	<.0001***	<.0001***

Appendix Table 8. Interaction effects of mean square, F calculated results and probability value of three-way analysis of variance on Crop Phenology under two lime rate, three starter nitrogen rate and three rhizobia strain types with in two years

Parameters	Crop Phenology											
	lime*Starter nitrogen			lime*RHhizobia			Starter nitrogen*Rhizobia			lime*Starter nitrogen*Rhizobia		
	Ms	F	P	Ms	F	P	Ms	F	P	Ms	F	P
Days to 50% Flowering (DF)	50.579537	10.24	0.0001***	64.223981	13.01	<.0001***	20.750648	4.20	0.0041**	15.408426	3.12	0.0200*
90% Days of maturity (DM)	155.706204	16.13	<.0001***	163.862870	16.97	<.0001***	89.778148	9.30	<.0001***	40.590093	4.20	0.0041**
Plant height PH (cm)	170.64715	44.28	<.0001***	106.51083	27.64	<.0001***	424.77339	110.23	<.0001***	22.65184	5.88	0.0004**
Number of primary branches (NPB)	3.2739815	58.83	<.0001***	3.8414815	69.03	<.0001***	8.3447222	149.96	<.0001***	0.5412037	9.73	<.0001***
Leaf area per plant (LAPP) in cm ²	121779.10	10.93	<.0001***	196687.87	17.65	<.0001***	611846.07	54.89	<.0001***	46672.35	4.19	0.0042**
Leaf area index (LAI)	0.7595620	10.85	<.0001***	1.2255731	17.51	<.0001***	3.8308912	54.72	<.0001***	0.2930579	4.19	0.0042**

Appendix Table 9. Interaction effects of mean square, probability value and F calculated results of three-way analysis of variance on Biological Nitrogen Fixation under two lime rate, three starter nitrogen rate and three rhizobia strain types with in two years

Parameters	Biological Nitrogen Fixation											
	lime*Starter nitrogen			lime*RHrhizobia			Starter nitrogen*Rhizobia			lime*Starter nitrogen*Rhizobia		
	Ms	F	P	Ms	F	P	Ms	F	P	Ms	F	P
Total Number of nodule per plant (TNNP)	3034.99287	36.47	<.0001***	1282.98065	15.42	<.0001***	896.30204	10.77	<.0001***	899.40509	10.81	<.0001***
Effective number of nodule (ENNP)	3165.21593	41.59	<.0001***	1341.92120	17.63	<.0001***	724.60662	9.52	<.0001***	824.34162	10.83	<.0001***
Perecent of nodule effectiveness(PNE)	4.76642	1.06	0.3532 ^{ns}	82.89177	18.36	<.0001***	790.01684	175	<.0001***	11.35005	2.51	0.0489*

Appendix Table 10. Interaction effects of mean square, F calculated results and probability value of three-way analysis of variance on Yield and Yield components under two lime rate, three starter nitrogen rate and three rhizobia strain types with in two years

parameters	Yield and Yield components											
	lime*Starter nitrogen			lime*RHhizobia			Starter nitrogen*Rhizobia			lime*Starter nitrogen*Rhizobia		
	Ms	F	P	Ms	F	P	Ms	F	P	Ms	F	P
Number of pods per plant (NPPP)	5.793704	3.03	0.0546 ^{ns}	33.678426	17.60	<.0001 ^{****}	4.600278	2.40	0.0575 ^{ns}	56.252315	29.40	<.0001 ^{****}
Number of seeds per pod	0.94675926	41.57	<.0001 ^{****}	0.41842593	18.37	<.0001 ^{****}	1.39444444	61.22	<.0001 ^{****}	0.26620370	11.69	<.0001 ^{****}
Hundred -seed weight (HSW) (g)	3.010000	0.97	0.3834 ^{ns}	0.130278	0.04	0.9588 ^{ns}	24.832731	8.02	<.0001 ^{****}	17.946528	5.79	0.0004 ^{****}
Grain yield (GY) kg ha ⁻¹	106833.60	0.97	0.3852 ^{ns}	322481.35	2.92	0.0604 ^{ns}	232081.73	2.10	0.0896 ^{ns}	1908498.56	17.27	<.0001 ^{****}
Biomass Yield (BY) kg ha ⁻¹	255028.6	1.24	0.2957 ^{ns}	249438.0	1.21	0.3036 ^{ns}	1110468.9	5.40	0.0007 ^{****}	2648354.3	12.87	<.0001 ^{****}
Harvest Index (HI) %	55.966237	3.85	0.0257 [*]	167.651795	11.54	<.0001 ^{****}	180.249720	12.41	<.0001 ^{****}	93.082773	6.41	0.0002 ^{****}
Straw yield (SY) kg ha ⁻¹	122785.91	2.01	0.1414 ^{ns}	97971.01	1.60	0.2081 ^{ns}	348360.21	5.70	0.0005 ^{****}	101589.09	1.66	0.1679 ^{ns}

Appendix Table 11. Rating of soil physico-chemical properties

Soil parameter	Status	Critical level	References
Soil bulk density (g/ cm ⁻³)	Very low	< 1	Pam Hazelton and Brain Murphy (2007)
	Low	1 - 1.3	
	Medium	1.3 - 1.6	
	High	1.6 - 1.9	
	Very high	>1.9	
Soil moisture content (%)	very low	<8	Beernaert, Frank, and D. Bitondo (1992)
	Low	8 – 12	
	Medium	12 – 19	
	High	>19	
Soil pH(1:2.5 soil:water Suspension)	Very Strongly acidic	<4.5	Landon (2014)
	Strongly acidic	4.5-5.2	
	Moderately acidic	5.3-5.9	
	Slightly acidic	6-6.6	
	Neutral	6.7-7.3	
	Moderately alkalaine	7.4-7.3	
	Strongly alkaline	>8	
Total porosity	Sandy soils	35-50%	Hillel, D. (2003).
	Loamy soils	40-60%	
	Clay soils	50-70%	
Exchangeable acidity(cmolckg-1)	Very low	<0.5	Brady & Weil (2016).
	Low	0.5-1	
	Medium	1-2	
	High	2-4	
	Very high	>4	
Ec (dS/M)	Salt free	< 2	EthioSIS(2016)
	Very slightly saline	2-4	
	slightly saline	4-8	
	Moderately saline	8-16	
	Strongly saline	>16	
Organic carbon %	Very high	>3	Charman and Roper(2000)
	high	1.8-3	
	medium	1-1.8	
	low	0.6-1	
	Very low	0.4-0.6	
	Extremely low	<0.4	
Organic matter%	Very low	<0-2	Ethiosis (2016)
	Low	2-3	
	optimum	3-7	
	High	7-8	
	Very high	>8	
Cation exchange capacity (cmol(+)Kg ⁻¹)	Very low	<5	Landon (2014)
	Low	5-15	
	medium	15-25	
	High	25-40	
	Very high	>40	

Soil parameter	Status	Critical level	References
Total Nitrogen (%)	Very low	< 0.1	Landon (2014)
	Low	0.1 - 0.2	
	Optimum	0.2 - 0.5	
	High	0.5 - 1	
	Very high	> 1	
Available phosphorus (mg/kg)	Very low	0 - 5	Landon (2014)
	Low	5 - 10	
	Optimum	10 -15	
	High	15 - 20	
	Very high	> 20	
	Low	0.3-0.9	
	Medium	1-20	
	High	21-50	
	Very high	>50	
Soil inorganic nitrogen (mg/kg)	Very low	<5	Carter & Gregorich (2003), Keeney (1983) and Gunnarsson (2003).
	Low	5 - 20	
	Medium	20 - 50	
	High	50 - 100	
	Very high	>100	

Appendix Table 12. The USDA's soil texture triangle and soil texture identification software

Appendix Table 13. Monthly Rain falls (mm) for koga irrigation (2003 to 2022)

YEAR	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP	OCT	NOV	DEC
2003	0	15.82	10.55	0	21.09	126.56	295.31	305.86	142.38	0	0	21.09
2004	0	0	5.27	79.1	42.19	142.38	295.31	184.57	147.66	31.64	15.82	0
2005	0	0	10.55	63.28	121.29	147.66	332.23	237.3	147.66	15.82	0	0
2006	0	0	31.64	36.91	174.02	295.31	643.36	400.78	295.31	152.93	36.91	0
2007	5.27	5.27	21.09	58.01	195.12	216.21	485.16	384.96	158.2	42.19	5.27	0
2008	0	0	0	63.28	121.29	195.12	432.42	469.34	168.75	73.83	42.19	0
2009	10.55	0	5.27	36.91	26.37	168.75	485.16	363.87	137.11	116.02	5.27	0
2010	0	0	26.37	79.1	184.57	221.48	416.6	458.79	210.94	10.55	5.27	0
2011	0	0	26.37	5.27	179.3	179.3	237.3	200.39	121.29	0	42.19	0
2012	0	0	5.27	5.27	63.28	126.56	437.7	395.51	200.39	21.09	52.73	5.27
2013	0	0	5.27	21.09	237.3	237.3	522.07	448.24	189.84	158.2	21.09	0
2014	0	0	47.46	73.83	205.66	232.03	616.99	448.24	332.23	137.11	5.27	5.27
2015	0	0	15.82	0	73.83	226.76	179.3	421.88	121.29	63.28	36.91	31.64
2016	0	0	15.82	26.37	168.75	168.75	500.98	416.6	110.74	26.37	0	0
2017	0	21.09	21.09	84.38	158.2	121.29	326.95	295.31	137.11	21.09	0	0
2018	0	5.27	0	31.64	52.73	142.38	268.95	247.85	63.28	58.01	36.91	0
2019	0	5.27	15.82	31.64	21.09	126.56	179.3	274.22	247.85	47.46	15.82	10.55
2020	0	5.27	0	42.19	168.75	205.66	416.6	384.96	284.77	15.82	0	0
2021	5.27	5.27	0	71.31	151.06	114.41	796.8	338.09	212.67	24.14	15.36	39.79
2022	9.53	3.43	11.03	126.25	54.96	266.29	540.5	263.69	105.18	51.99	1.52	9.11
mean	1.53	3.33	13.73	46.79	121.04	183.04	420.45	347.02	176.73	53.38	16.93	6.14

Source: National Metrological Agency, Bahir Dar Branch, 2022.

Appendix Table 14. Monthly Maximum Temperature (°c) for koga irrigation (2003 to 2022)

YEAR	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP	OCT	NOV	DEC
2003	28.12	29.58	30.07	31.33	31.36	29.76	23.08	22.73	25.15	25.66	26.66	27.03
2004	27.53	29.14	30.46	30.23	31.23	29.1	24.44	24.12	25.35	25.75	27.17	26.51
2005	27.14	31	29.83	31.69	29.55	29.51	23.87	23.66	24.65	25.17	26.35	27.33
2006	28.76	29.36	29.62	29.33	30.56	27.8	23.68	22.91	24.78	24.65	24.18	25.41
2007	25.55	29.2	30.2	29.69	29.08	28.61	22.24	22.64	24.23	24.08	25.54	26.31
2008	27.62	28.12	29.97	29.71	29.87	27.95	24.76	23.67	24.67	24.02	24.73	25.25
2009	26.55	28.93	30.54	30.33	30.76	29.4	23.93	23.78	24.96	24.5	25.28	25.7
2010	27.56	28.99	29.94	29.54	30.02	27.48	24.51	22.84	23.87	24.8	25.37	25.17
2011	27.3	29.17	29.22	30.62	30.05	27.12	25.76	23.88	25.2	25.64	25.73	26.12
2012	27.57	28.8	30.76	30.4	30.4	29.82	23.92	22.48	24.38	25.37	26.19	25.67
2013	27.6	29.92	30.62	30.34	29.01	28.12	24.01	22.59	24.88	23.79	24.57	25.17
2014	27.73	28.83	29.48	29.71	27.96	28.33	25.89	23.41	24.07	23.96	24.41	25.25
2015	27.67	28.95	30.01	30.21	30.08	29.51	25.73	24.08	25.68	26.01	25.9	25.31
2016	26.33	30.52	31.18	30.5	28.01	28.82	23.37	23.39	24.9	25.08	26.4	27.23
2017	27.5	27.73	29.51	30.22	29.05	28.44	24.47	23.58	25.05	25.7	26.21	26.37
2018	26.51	29.14	29.34	28.68	30.56	28.16	25.73	23.12	24.83	25.17	25.86	26.37
2019	28.55	28.96	29.37	30.8	31.9	29.2	25.32	24.87	24.33	25.37	25.68	26.1
2020	26.98	29.42	30.38	31.01	29.71	28.23	25.26	23.08	24.44	24.25	25.48	26.48
2021	27.61	27.55	30.17	30	28.87	29.39	24.12	23.45	24.97	25.06	26.11	27.06
2022	26.1	28.63	30.44	30.59	30.22	29.62	22.78	23.52	24.83	25.06	25.55	25.47

Source: National Metrological Agency, Bahir Dar Branch 2022

Appendix Table 15. Monthly Minimum Temperature (°c) for koga irrigation (2003 to 2022)

YEAR	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP	OCT	NOV	DEC
2003	14.18	15.79	18.05	18.91	19.96	16.51	15.38	15.30	17.19	15.03	14.62	13.44
2004	14.94	15.27	17.16	17.94	17.93	16.68	15.58	15.73	17.19	13.94	14.82	14.95
2005	12.87	16.13	18.20	16.33	18.05	16.23	15.12	15.48	16.68	16.30	12.83	13.23
2006	14.29	17.01	17.28	17.48	17.87	17.16	15.26	15.76	16.01	14.36	14.04	13.92
2007	14.87	14.97	17.48	17.47	18.06	16.27	15.91	16.44	16.58	14.69	11.94	12.12
2008	14.46	14.33	15.18	16.6	16.73	17.20	15.6	16.09	16.23	15.24	12.55	14.26
2009	14.23	16.45	18.21	18.2	19.06	17.03	15.87	16.12	17.73	14.49	12.43	14.73
2010	14.38	15.40	15.87	19.08	19.15	16.09	15.56	15.71	17.38	16.44	14.53	14.38
2011	13.9	15.01	14.22	17.83	17.87	16.57	14.88	14.90	16.69	14.88	13.79	13.01
2012	12.67	14.65	17.30	17.97	17.8	16.80	15.73	16.62	16.90	13.65	16.23	14.22
2013	14.43	16.44	18.58	17.78	18.33	15.95	15.57	15.01	16.97	16.22	15.19	13.35
2014	14.08	14.93	16.88	17.76	17.67	17.89	15	16.23	15.95	15.33	14.09	13.76
2015	12.89	14.26	17.66	19.32	17.87	17.53	17.48	16.33	17.13	16.72	15.36	14.94
2016	14.54	16.54	18.55	18.94	18.01	16.98	15.83	15.20	16.72	15.73	12.10	12.28
2017	11.55	16.13	17.56	17.01	18.83	17.90	16.49	16.25	16.72	16.18	14.71	12.62
2018	13.48	15.67	15.53	18.83	17.82	16.42	15.46	15.57	16.85	15.64	14.01	15.00
2019	12.12	15.76	16.76	18.98	18.33	18.08	16.01	16.18	16.95	16.08	16.20	13.76
2020	14.23	15.68	17.30	17.4	17.94	17.89	15.39	14.46	17.77	15.73	13.52	14.14
2021	14.38	14.37	16.14	17.7	17.65	17.00	14.94	15.13	15.66	15.44	15.05	12.68
2022	14.31	15.74	18.18	18.27	18.27	16.91	14.94	15.54	16.37	15.92	15.28	14.51
mean	13.84	15.53	17.10	17.99	18.16	16.95	15.6	15.70	16.78	15.40	14.16	13.77

Source: National Metrological Agency, Bahir Dar Branch 2022

Appendix Table 16. Mean meteorological data of koga irrigation scheme from 2003 to 2022 cropping season

Month	Rainfall (mm)	Min. Temp (°C)	Max. Temp (°C)	Mean Temp (°C)
January	1.53	13.84	27.31	20.58
February	3.33	15.53	29.10	22.32
March	13.73	17.10	30.06	23.58
April	46.79	17.99	30.25	24.12
May	121.04	18.16	29.91	24.04
June	183.04	16.95	28.72	22.84
July	420.45	15.60	24.34	19.97
August	347.02	15.70	23.39	19.55
September	176.73	16.78	24.76	20.77
October	53.38	15.40	24.95	20.18
November	16.93	14.16	25.67	19.92
December	6.14	13.77	26.07	19.92
Mean	115.84	15.92	27.04	21.48

Source: National Metrological Agency, Bahir Dar Branch 2022

Appendix Table 17. Picture of Research field Activities

Health Food Africa project Banner

Professor Enyew Adgo and Dr. Mekamu Alemayehu

Farmer's field day

Farmer's field day Photo

Control plot

Treatment 18 (lime 2 ton ha⁻¹ + starter nitrogen 20 kg)

ha⁻¹ + HAMBI3570)

Appendix Table 18. Picture of farmers demonstration field Activities

Status of haricot bean Mr.Mekonen Tegege

Appendix Table 19. Farmer involvement in the research effectiveness

የጽ/ቤት

የመገምገሚያ መስፈርቶች

1. የሰጠው መረጃ ትክክል ነው
2. የሰጠው መረጃ ጥሩ ነው
3. ለሰጠው መረጃ ጥሩ ነው
4. ለሰጠው መረጃ ጥሩ ነው
5. የሰጠው መረጃ ጥሩ ነው
- 6.
- 7.

የተመረጠው መደብ ቁጥር

ከፍተኛ መደብ ----- 7

ዝቅተኛው መደብ ----- 16

የአርዕስደር ስም ዝርዝር

ተ.ቁ	ስም	ጎጥ	ተ.ቁ	ስም	ጎጥ
1	አብነት ገብረ	አዲስ	20	አብነት ገብረ	"
2	አብነት ገብረ	"	21	አብነት ገብረ	"
3	አብነት ገብረ	"	22	አብነት ገብረ	"
4	አብነት ገብረ	"	23	አብነት ገብረ	"
5	አብነት ገብረ	"	24	አብነት ገብረ	"
6	አብነት ገብረ	"	25	አብነት ገብረ	"
7	አብነት ገብረ	"	26	አብነት ገብረ	"
8	አብነት ገብረ	"	27	አብነት ገብረ	"
9	አብነት ገብረ	"	28	አብነት ገብረ	"
10	አብነት ገብረ	"	29	አብነት ገብረ	"
11	አብነት ገብረ	"	30	አብነት ገብረ	"
12	አብነት ገብረ	"	31	አብነት ገብረ	"
13	አብነት ገብረ	"	32	አብነት ገብረ	"
14	አብነት ገብረ	"	33	አብነት ገብረ	"
15	አብነት ገብረ	"	34	አብነት ገብረ	"
16	አብነት ገብረ	"	35	አብነት ገብረ	"
17	አብነት ገብረ	"	36	አብነት ገብረ	"
18	አብነት ገብረ	"	37	አብነት ገብረ	"
19	አብነት ገብረ	"	38	አብነት ገብረ	"
20	አብነት ገብረ	"	39	አብነት ገብረ	"
21	አብነት ገብረ	"	40	አብነት ገብረ	"
22	አብነት ገብረ	"	41	አብነት ገብረ	"
23	አብነት ገብረ	"			
24	አብነት ገብረ	"			
25	አብነት ገብረ	"			
26	አብነት ገብረ	"			
27	አብነት ገብረ	"			

Rep. 2

የመገምገሚያ መስፈርቶች

1. ያተኛነት ርዝመት / ቀመር
2. ያዘዘ ለዛን
3. ያፋፊ ርዝመት
4. ያፋፊ ከገጽ
5. ያፋፊ አፈርጃ ከሆነም ይዘትን ከለመደቀ
- 6.
- 7.

የተመረጠው መደብ ቁጥር

ከፍተኛ መደብ 25

ዝቅተኛው መደብ 23

የአርሳላደር ስም ዝርዝር

ተ.ቁ	ስም	ጎዮ	ተ.ቁ	ስም	ጎዮ
1	አዳኛው ሰጠ	ዳጊህ	28	ከሰው ያጌ-1	ሐጎጃጃን
2	ሐረርግ ከሰጠው	ላላዳዳ	29		
3	ሃይቲ ያጎ	>S	30		
4	ሐረርግ ስጦ	>S	31		
5	ዳረግሰጠ ለገጽ	>S	32		
6	አሰጠው ስጦ	>S	33		
7	ያገረው ከሰ	>S	34		
8	አሰጠው ከሰ	>S	35		
9	ሰጠው ገጽ	>S	36		
10	አሰጠው ሰጠው	ሐጎጃጃን	37		
11	አሰጠው ሰጠው	>S	38		
12	ገጽ ሰጠው	>S	39		
13	አሰጠው ሰጠው	>S	40		
14	አሰጠው ገጽ	>S	41		
15	ሰጠው ሰጠው	>S	42		
16	ተሰጠው ሰጠው	>S	43		
17	አሰጠው ከሰ	>S	44		
18	አሰጠው ከሰ	>S	45		
19	አሰጠው ሰጠው	ዳጊህ	46		
20	አሰጠው ሰጠው	>S	47		
21	አሰጠው ሰጠው	>S	48		
22	አሰጠው ሰጠው	>S	49		
23	አሰጠው ሰጠው	>S	50		
24	አሰጠው ሰጠው	>S	51		
25	አሰጠው ሰጠው	>S	52		
26	አሰጠው ከሰ	>S	53		
27	አሰጠው ሰጠው	ሐጎጃጃን	54		

የመገምገሚያ መስፈርቶች

1. በፍሬ እና በእያም የተሻሻለ መሆን
2. በዛገ የተሻሻለ መሆን
3. ቆይታ ማጠና ስራ
4. በምርት ማሳደግ የተሻሻለ መሆን
5. በተክለ ቁጥጥር የተሻሻለ መሆን
- 6.
- 7.

የተመረጠው መደብ ቁጥር

ከፍተኛ መደብ 53

ዝቅተኛው መደብ 50

የአርሶአደር ስም ዝርዝር

ተ.ቁ	ስም	ጎጥ	ተ.ቁ	ስም	ጎጥ
1	አጠናን ደሴ	66/መ	28	አሳፋ ገደ	>>
2	የቆየ ተሃገ	>>	29	የሥራው ተከላ	>>
3	አንተገኝ አየገጫ	>>	30	ደጃጫ ሰዓት	>>
4	ገገን አየራጫ	>>	31	ወንጌዎ አሳ	>>
5	ካላላ ምናል	>>	32	መንገድ መሰሪያ	66/መ
6	ሙሉ ተላሽ	>>	33	አጠቃ ደገጥ	>>
7	አላገራ አገን	>>	34	መሰሪያ ምንጭ	>>
8	ዘላቅ ገጭ	>>	35	ንግድ ዘላቅ	>>
9	ዘላቅ ገጭ	ደላጭ	36	በቀለ ገንጠ	>>
10	መንገድ አዳኝ	>>	37	መሰሪያ አላገኝ	>>
11	የአገራ አዳኝ ሰዓት	>>	38		
12	አላገን አዳኝ	ሳገገ	39		
13	ተሃገ ሰዓት	>>	40		
14	መንገድ ገንጠ	>>	41		
15	አንተገኝ ገንጠ	>>	42		
16	አንገራ ሰዓት	>>	43		
17	የተከላ ሰዓት	>>	44		
18	የሰዓት ሰዓት	>>	45		
19	አላገራ ሰዓት	>>	46		
20	ምናል አዳኝ	>>	47		
21	ደገ አሳ	>>	48		
22	አገራ አዳኝ	>>	49		
23	የተከላ አላገኝ	>>	50		
24	ደሴ አንገ	>>	51		
25	ዋለ አሳ	>>	52		
26	ደሴ አዳኝ	>>	53		
27	መሰሪያ ሰዓት	>>	54		

Appendix Table 20. Field layout, treatment and plot setup of the study sites

Where, p = plot and T= treatment

Appendix Table 21. Amount Soil sample collection for analysis

No-	parameters	unit	For two years			
			Before sowing		After harvest	
			Soil sample/g g	Total number	Soil samlpe	Total samlpe number
1	Texture(T)		2 kg		1	18
2	Bulk density	g cm ⁻³		24	1	18
3	Total Porosity	%			1	18
4	Soil moisture content	%			1	18
5	Soil reaction (pH)				1	18
6	Exchangeable Acidity (EA)	cmol(+)kg ⁻¹			1	18
7	Organic carbon(OC)	%			1	18
8	Organic matter(OM)				1	18
9	Total nitrogen(TN)	%			1	18
11	Eectrical conductivity	dS/M			1	18
12	Cataion Exchange Capacity (CEC)	cmol (+) kg ⁻¹			1	18
13	Soil inorganic nitrogen	mg kg ⁻¹			1	18
14	Available phosphorus	ppm			1	18

Soil laboratory results

The Federal Democratic Republic of Ethiopia Ministry of Education Bahir Dar University College of Agriculture and Environmental Science			Department Natural resources management Soil and pant analysis laboratory													
<p>Client Fekadu Tirunch</p>																
Code2	YR	L	Sn	R	BD g/cm ³	TP %	SM %	pH	cmol(+)/EA kg ⁻¹	SOC %	OM %	TN %	EC ds/m	CEC cmol(+)/kg	SIN mg kg ⁻¹	AV-P ppm
1	1	L0	S0	R0	1.20	54.72	23.62	5.18	2.71	1.64	2.83	0.187	0.052	24.00	65	9.84
2	1	L0	S0	R1	1.20	54.72	24.58	5.37	2.61	1.72	2.97	0.198	0.043	28.90	115	17.00
3	1	L0	S0	R2	1.18	55.47	25.13	5.50	2.51	1.83	3.15	0.203	0.044	30.20	116	19.88
4	1	L0	S1	R0	1.23	53.58	23.95	5.23	2.64	1.73	2.98	0.193	0.045	27.10	78	15.00
5	1	L0	S1	R1	1.10	58.49	29.19	5.50	2.52	2.30	3.97	0.218	0.037	35.50	118	20.10
6	1	L0	S1	R2	1.09	58.87	28.07	5.53	2.50	2.32	4.00	0.222	0.036	36.10	126	23.50
7	1	L0	S2	R0	1.20	54.72	24.14	5.26	2.65	1.74	3.00	0.194	0.043	28.40	91	16.50
8	1	L0	S2	R1	1.07	59.62	29.95	5.64	2.30	2.33	4.02	0.222	0.037	35.50	134	24.00
9	1	L0	S2	R2	1.06	60.00	29.68	5.69	1.70	2.46	4.24	0.226	0.036	36.00	145	24.40
10	1	L1	S0	R0	1.23	53.58	23.52	5.60	1.70	1.68	2.90	0.190	0.049	25.00	74	13.50
11	1	L1	S0	R1	1.13	57.36	27.08	5.75	1.15	2.26	3.90	0.212	0.039	33.00	176	30.40
12	1	L1	S0	R2	1.13	57.36	26.95	5.78	1.04	2.22	3.83	0.217	0.041	35.60	187	29.00
13	1	L1	S1	R0	1.16	56.23	26.00	5.70	1.55	1.98	3.41	0.207	0.044	31.20	155	25.00
14	1	L1	S1	R1	1.04	60.75	29.97	5.84	0.90	2.50	4.31	0.230	0.036	37.00	195	30.00
15	1	L1	S1	R2	1.03	61.13	30.14	5.89	0.70	2.57	4.43	0.228	0.034	36.40	215	31.20
16	1	L1	S2	R0	1.14	56.98	26.83	5.68	1.44	2.04	3.52	0.209	0.042	32.60	169	27.00
17	1	L1	S2	R1	1.01	61.89	31.52	5.90	0.50	2.52	4.34	0.234	0.034	41.20	216	31.00
18	1	L1	S2	R2	1.00	62.26	32.84	6.40	0.40	2.60	4.48	0.241	0.023	42.90	232	32.10

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Code3	YR	L	Sn	R	g/cm ³ BD	TP	SM	pH	cmol(EA +)/kg	SOC	OM	TN	EC	CEC	SIN	AV.P
						%	%		%	%	%	%	ds/m	cmol (+) / kg ⁻¹	mg kg ⁻¹	ppm
1	2	LO	S0	R0	1.27	52.08	22.58	5.20	2.64	1.63	2.81	0.187	0.049	24.90	61	9.10
2	2	LO	S0	R1	1.23	53.58	24.77	5.52	2.49	1.75	3.02	0.195	0.045	29.70	113	16.60
3	2	LO	S0	R2	1.22	53.96	24.55	5.45	2.37	1.80	3.10	0.197	0.042	30.50	112	18.72
4	2	LO	S1	R0	1.25	52.83	23.66	5.23	2.62	1.70	2.93	0.191	0.044	26.70	75	14.99
5	2	LO	S1	R1	1.13	57.36	27.75	5.45	2.32	2.21	3.81	0.218	0.036	35.80	114	19.61
6	2	LO	S1	R2	1.11	58.11	27.63	5.60	2.30	2.23	3.84	0.220	0.036	36.40	121	21.80
7	2	LO	S2	R0	1.24	53.21	23.89	5.28	2.60	1.68	2.90	0.193	0.048	28.40	85	15.79
8	2	LO	S2	R1	1.10	58.49	28.55	5.62	2.10	2.24	3.86	0.222	0.036	35.70	130	22.60
9	2	LO	S2	R2	1.09	58.87	28.75	5.66	1.90	2.30	3.97	0.224	0.036	35.90	144	23.40
10	2	L1	S0	R0	1.26	52.45	22.77	5.69	1.72	1.65	2.84	0.189	0.048	25.00	71	12.75
11	2	L1	S0	R1	1.16	56.23	26.34	5.75	1.22	2.15	3.71	0.215	0.038	33.60	172	28.24
12	2	L1	S0	R2	1.14	56.98	26.56	5.78	1.09	2.10	3.62	0.216	0.041	34.40	180	28.80
13	2	L1	S1	R0	1.18	55.47	25.83	5.71	1.67	1.85	3.19	0.200	0.041	31.00	152	24.97
14	2	L1	S1	R1	1.08	59.25	29.12	5.83	0.60	2.34	4.03	0.226	0.035	36.20	190	28.90
15	2	L1	S1	R2	1.05	60.38	29.13	5.83	0.50	2.41	4.15	0.228	0.034	35.90	213	30.00
16	2	L1	S2	R0	1.17	55.85	26.13	5.71	1.50	1.95	3.36	0.213	0.042	32.40	164	26.60
17	2	L1	S2	R1	1.05	60.38	32.85	5.94	0.30	2.45	4.22	0.230	0.034	38.00	224	30.40
18	2	L1	S2	R2	1.02	61.51	31.69	6.10	0.20	2.52	4.34	0.233	0.032	39.10	232	31.81

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Code1	YR	L	Soil	R	BD	TP	SM	pH	emol(+)-EA	SOC	OM	TN	EC	CEC	SIN	AV.P
					g/cm ³	%	%		cmol(+)-EA kg ⁻¹	%	%	%	ds/m	cmol (+) kg ⁻¹	mg kg ⁻¹	ppm
1	2	L0	S0	R0	1.31	50.57	21.56	5.10	2.62	1.60	2.76	0.183	0.048	24.50	58	9.10
2	2	L0	S0	R1	1.26	52.45	21.13	5.35	2.39	1.75	3.02	0.190	0.045	29.00	108	16.60
3	2	L0	S0	R2	1.23	53.58	23.65	5.40	2.30	1.78	3.07	0.191	0.042	30.00	108	18.72
4	2	L0	S1	R0	1.30	50.94	20.56	5.19	2.61	1.66	2.86	0.188	0.044	26.60	74	14.99
5	2	L0	S1	R1	1.16	56.23	26.83	5.36	2.20	2.11	3.64	0.215	0.036	35.50	112	19.21
6	2	L0	S1	R2	1.13	57.36	26.58	5.40	2.20	2.10	3.62	0.218	0.036	35.00	117	21.00
7	2	L0	S2	R0	1.29	51.32	20.89	5.28	2.58	1.64	2.83	0.189	0.047	28.20	83	15.79
8	2	L0	S2	R1	1.12	57.74	27.75	5.62	2.00	2.14	3.69	0.220	0.035	35.70	127	22.00
9	2	L0	S2	R2	1.12	57.74	27.34	5.64	2.00	2.10	3.62	0.221	0.035	36.90	136	23.00
10	2	L1	S0	R0	1.32	50.19	20.36	5.65	1.65	1.60	2.76	0.185	0.047	24.50	69	12.75
11	2	L1	S0	R1	1.19	55.09	25.64	5.70	1.20	2.10	3.62	0.213	0.037	33.10	167	27.44
12	2	L1	S0	R2	1.16	56.23	25.34	5.77	1.06	2.00	3.45	0.213	0.040	34.00	177	28.00
13	2	L1	S1	R0	1.20	54.72	24.77	5.71	1.60	1.80	3.10	0.180	0.042	31.60	147	23.97
14	2	L1	S1	R1	1.13	57.36	28.56	5.83	0.50	2.14	3.69	0.222	0.034	36.20	183	28.00
15	2	L1	S1	R2	1.08	59.25	27.13	5.82	0.40	2.31	3.98	0.221	0.031	35.90	208	29.00
16	2	L1	S2	R0	1.19	55.09	25.12	5.68	1.40	1.90	3.28	0.211	0.041	32.90	162	25.60
17	2	L1	S2	R1	1.07	59.62	28.44	5.92	0.20	2.25	3.88	0.227	0.033	38.20	219	30.00
18	2	L1	S2	R2	1.06	60.00	29.75	6.10	0.10	2.42	4.17	0.211	0.031	39.00	226	31.00

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Code3	YR	L	Sn	R	BD g/cm ³	TP %	SM %	pH	EA cmol(+) kg ⁻¹	SOC %	OM %	TN %	EC ds/m	CEC cmol (+) kg ⁻¹	SIN mg kg ⁻¹	AV.P ppm
1	1	L0	S0	R0	1.29	51.32	21.62	5.18	2.66	1.62	2.79	0.185	0.055	23.60	60	8.84
2	1	L0	S0	R1	1.22	53.96	23.56	5.37	2.51	1.72	2.97	0.194	0.044	28.60	95	17.00
3	1	L0	S0	R2	1.21	54.34	24.08	5.45	2.41	1.78	3.07	0.201	0.043	30.10	109	19.00
4	1	L0	S1	R0	1.25	52.83	22.77	5.21	2.62	1.69	2.91	0.190	0.045	27.20	76	15.00
5	1	L0	S1	R1	1.14	56.98	27.22	5.55	2.32	2.20	3.79	0.216	0.037	36.00	115	20.10
6	1	L0	S1	R2	1.12	57.74	27.77	5.53	2.30	2.22	3.83	0.219	0.036	35.20	114	21.50
7	1	L0	S2	R0	1.23	53.58	23.07	5.26	2.60	1.69	2.91	0.192	0.043	28.60	84	16.50
8	1	L0	S2	R1	1.11	58.11	28.44	5.63	2.10	2.23	3.84	0.221	0.037	35.50	131	22.00
9	1	L0	S2	R2	1.10	58.49	28.97	5.64	1.80	2.28	3.93	0.223	0.036	36.80	140	24.20
10	1	L1	S0	R0	1.26	52.45	22.22	5.74	1.60	1.64	2.83	0.187	0.048	24.70	70	12.50
11	1	L1	S0	R1	1.16	56.23	26.07	5.75	1.10	2.18	3.76	0.210	0.038	34.50	169	27.00
12	1	L1	S0	R2	1.15	56.60	26.44	5.78	1.00	2.11	3.64	0.215	0.041	33.80	183	28.50
13	1	L1	S1	R0	1.19	55.09	25.00	5.70	1.50	1.89	3.26	0.204	0.043	31.00	151	24.50
14	1	L1	S1	R1	1.09	58.87	28.62	5.81	0.80	2.30	3.97	0.225	0.035	36.50	194	29.00
15	1	L1	S1	R2	1.07	59.62	29.12	5.82	0.60	2.37	4.09	0.224	0.034	35.40	220	29.50
16	1	L1	S2	R0	1.18	55.47	25.52	5.72	1.40	1.92	3.31	0.207	0.041	32.10	166	26.00
17	1	L1	S2	R1	1.04	60.75	30.00	5.95	0.40	2.42	4.17	0.230	0.034	37.80	219	30.80
18	1	L1	S2	R2	1.04	60.75	31.39	6.00	0.30	2.50	4.31	0.231	0.033	38.80	230	32.50

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Code2	YR	L	Sn	R	BD	TP	SM	pH	emol(+)/EA	SOC	OM	TN	EC	CEC	SIN	AV.P
					g/cm ³	%	%		emol(+)/EA kg/y	%	%	%	ds/m	emol (+) kg)	mg kg-	ppm
1	2	L0	S0	R0	1.23	53.58	23.68	5.27	2.66	1.66	2.86	0.191	0.050	25.00	64	9.30
2	2	L0	S0	R1	1.19	55.09	24.96	5.40	2.59	1.75	3.02	0.200	0.045	29.90	117	17.10
3	2	L0	S0	R2	1.21	54.34	25.75	5.54	2.44	1.82	3.14	0.203	0.042	31.00	115	19.76
4	2	L0	S1	R0	1.24	53.21	24.75	5.28	2.63	1.74	3.00	0.194	0.044	26.80	80	15.49
5	2	L0	S1	R1	1.10	58.49	28.95	5.52	2.44	2.31	3.98	0.221	0.037	35.30	121	21.01
6	2	L0	S1	R2	1.09	58.87	28.83	5.65	2.40	2.36	4.07	0.222	0.036	35.80	127	23.60
7	2	L0	S2	R0	1.24	53.21	24.89	5.44	2.62	1.72	2.97	0.197	0.048	28.80	89	16.29
8	2	L0	S2	R1	1.08	59.25	29.95	5.65	2.20	2.34	4.03	0.224	0.037	36.20	138	23.70
9	2	L0	S2	R2	1.06	60.00	29.97	5.68	1.80	2.50	4.31	0.227	0.037	36.70	146	24.80
10	2	L1	S0	R0	1.22	53.96	23.97	5.73	1.79	1.70	2.93	0.193	0.049	25.20	75	13.25
11	2	L1	S0	R1	1.13	57.36	27.97	5.79	1.25	2.20	3.79	0.217	0.039	34.10	176	29.04
12	2	L1	S0	R2	1.12	57.74	27.77	5.81	1.10	2.20	3.79	0.219	0.041	35.80	191	29.90
13	2	L1	S1	R0	1.16	56.23	26.96	5.71	1.74	1.90	3.28	0.220	0.043	31.80	157	25.97
14	2	L1	S1	R1	1.03	61.13	29.58	5.94	0.70	2.54	4.38	0.230	0.036	37.70	200	29.80
15	2	L1	S1	R2	1.07	59.62	31.13	5.90	0.60	2.51	4.33	0.235	0.037	36.90	216	31.40
16	2	L1	S2	R0	1.15	56.60	27.77	5.76	1.60	2.00	3.45	0.215	0.043	33.50	172	27.60
17	2	L1	S2	R1	1.03	61.13	30.22	5.96	0.40	2.65	4.57	0.233	0.034	38.80	227	32.40
18	2	L1	S2	R2	1.01	61.89	33.55	6.60	0.30	2.62	4.52	0.255	0.033	39.60	238	33.60

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Code1	YR	L	Sn	R	BD g/cm ³	TP %	SM %	pH (1:2.5)	EA cmol(+)EA kg ⁻¹	SO C %	OM %	TN %	EC ds/m	CE cmol (+) kg ⁻¹ C	SIN mg kg ⁻¹	AV. ppm
1	1	L0	S0	R0	1.30	50.94	21.58	5.10	2.61	1.60	2.76	0.182	0.047	23.50	57	8.64
2	1	L0	S0	R1	1.24	53.21	22.17	5.30	2.41	1.72	2.97	0.190	0.044	28.40	90	15.50
3	1	L0	S0	R2	1.24	53.21	23.03	5.40	2.31	1.73	2.98	0.199	0.042	30.00	105	17.40
4	1	L0	S1	R0	1.28	51.70	21.66	5.19	2.60	1.65	2.84	0.187	0.044	27.00	71	14.50
5	1	L0	S1	R1	1.16	56.23	26.36	5.25	2.12	2.10	3.62	0.214	0.036	35.00	112	19.10
6	1	L0	S1	R2	1.14	56.98	26.19	5.50	2.10	2.12	3.65	0.216	0.036	35.00	120	21.00
7	1	L0	S2	R0	1.26	52.45	22.00	5.10	2.55	1.64	2.83	0.190	0.043	28.00	80	14.00
8	1	L0	S2	R1	1.13	57.36	27.77	5.59	1.90	2.13	3.67	0.220	0.035	35.00	125	22.00
9	1	L0	S2	R2	1.12	57.74	27.44	5.63	1.90	2.10	3.62	0.220	0.035	35.80	135	22.00
10	1	L1	S0	R0	1.30	50.94	21.12	5.67	1.50	1.60	2.76	0.184	0.047	24.30	66	12.00
11	1	L1	S0	R1	1.20	54.72	25.07	5.70	1.05	2.10	3.62	0.208	0.037	33.00	165	26.00
12	1	L1	S0	R2	1.15	56.60	25.22	5.78	0.96	2.00	3.45	0.213	0.041	34.00	170	28.00
13	1	L1	S1	R0	1.20	54.72	24.00	5.70	1.45	1.80	3.10	0.201	0.038	31.40	148	24.00
14	1	L1	S1	R1	1.13	57.36	27.95	5.80	0.70	2.10	3.62	0.220	0.034	36.50	181	28.00
15	1	L1	S1	R2	1.11	58.11	28.08	5.80	0.50	2.17	3.74	0.220	0.034	35.00	195	29.00
16	1	L1	S2	R0	1.20	54.72	24.90	5.70	1.36	1.80	3.10	0.205	0.040	32.00	160	25.00
17	1	L1	S2	R1	1.11	58.11	29.44	5.95	0.30	2.32	4.00	0.226	0.034	35.00	225	29.00
18	1	L1	S2	R2	1.06	60.00	30.59	6.20	0.20	2.40	4.14	0.221	0.043	35.60	228	31.00

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AUTHOR'S BIOGRAPHICAL SKETCH

Fekadu Tiruneh Kassa was born on May 24, 1986, in Dangila. He completed his elementary education at Menegsha Jemberie Primary and Junior Secondary School, and his secondary education at Dangila High School. In 2005, he enrolled at Bahir Dar University's College of Agriculture and Environmental Science, where he earned a B.Sc. degree in Natural Resource Management on June 30, 2015. Fekadu began his professional career as a soil and water conservation expert with the Office of Agriculture in Jawi District, where he served for approximately four years. Subsequently, he joined Injibara University as an academic staff member. Driven by a strong passion for education, he pursued postgraduate studies in Soil Sciences at Bahir Dar University. Throughout his academic journey, he encountered numerous challenges that ultimately fortified his resolve and determination. Despite self-funding his education, except for his research expenses, Fekadu balanced his responsibilities as an academic staff member at Injibara University, where he also coordinated the university's greenery initiatives.

